

**Investigating the impact of Digital Banking Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction
and Customer Loyalty: Empirical evidence from a Vietnam Commercial Bank**

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of
The University of the West of Scotland for the award
of Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

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DECLARATION

I certify that the thesis I have presented for the DBA degree examination of the University of the West of Scotland is solely my work other than where clearly indicated by references. I declare that the work in the thesis complies with the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland. I also declare that this thesis has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualifications.

I declare that my thesis consists of 76,922 words.

Signature:

DEDICATION

To my wonderful husband – my companion through many long nights of writing - Thank you for being my great compass along the way. I wish I had listened to you earlier. Thank you for bearing my mood swings and tantrums and still loving me the same. You are the best decision of my life!

To my precious children, Mason and Tiffany - thank you for being the biggest motivations for me. The dream of graduating in front of you and role-modelling the importance of lifelong learning to you keeps me up through the most difficult time of this academic journey.

To my beloved family - thank you for always believing in me and also for your unconditional love and support. I would like to dedicate this milestone to all of you because if not for you, this scholarly voyage would not have been possible. All my love, as always.

“You raise me up, to walk on stormy seas...

You raise me up to more than I can be...”

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of digital banking has fundamentally transformed the banking landscape globally, and emerging economies such as Vietnam is not an exception. Providing high-quality digital banking services is considered a basic strategy for attracting and retaining customers with digital banking platforms. To date, in Vietnam, where digital banking is still evolving and expanding, digital banking and customer relations is vastly under researched. The purpose of this research is to empirically investigate the impact of digital banking service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty from various perspectives in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Bank. The research employs Pragmatism Philosophy, Abduction Approach, Case Study Strategy, Mixed-Methods Design with customers survey and banking managers interviews, Spearman Correlation Coefficient and Template Analysis respectively, facilitating a comprehension of current implementations and effects of digital banking phenomenon in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks from various perspectives. Findings revealed ten distinct determinants of Digital Banking service quality with Digital- Emotional Connection and Trust exert strongest effect on Customer Satisfaction. There is also found a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The research offers valuable theoretical and managerial implications since it demonstrates which Digital Banking service quality determinants predict customer satisfaction which ultimately raises the Digital Banking loyalty of banking customers. This study concentrates on Vietnamese Commercial Banks, limiting its generalisability. Nevertheless, the fact that banks typically implement common standards in banking service quality management implies the potential robustness of the findings in the context of other banks globally. Replications of the research in other banking context will further add richness to this robustness.

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LISTS OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACB	Asia Commercial Bank
Agribank	Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANZ	Australia & New Zealand Banking Group Limited
ATM	Automated Teller Machine
ATMs	Automated Teller Machines
BankingPlus	Thoibaonghang BankingPlus Website
BCG	Boston Consulting Group
BCSI	Institute for Brand and Competitiveness Strategy
BIDV	Bank for Investment and Development of Viet Nam
BM	Banking managers in the Interview
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
CFs	Conceptual Framework (s)
COD	Cash On Delivery
DB	Digital Banking
DBA	Doctorate of Business Administration
DBSQ	Digital Banking Service Quality
DBSs	Digital Banking Service (s)
DT	Digital Technologies
e-banking	Electronic or Internet banking
EFA	Exploratory Factors Analysis
eKYC	Electronic Know Your Customer
Enternews	Enternews Vietnam Chamber of Commerce and Industry
F	Female
FBNC	Financial Business News Channels
FT Focus	Financial Times

GDP	Gross Domestic Product
H	Hypothesis
HSBC	The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation Limited
IDG	International Data Group
IMF	International Monetary Fund
J.P.Morgan	J.P. Morgan & Co.
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
KMPG	Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler International Limited
m-banking	Mobile Banking
McKinsey	McKinsey&Company
MIC	Ministry of Information and Communications.
MOF	The Ministry of Finance of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam
NAPAS	National Payment Corporation of Vietnam
NCSC	Vietnam National Cyber Security Monitoring Centre
NCSC	Vietnam National Cyber Security Monitoring Centre
OCB	Orient Commercial Joint Stock Bank
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OMNI	Omnichannel
OTT Alert	One-Time Token Alert
PLS-SEM	Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling
POS	Point – of – sale
PRQ	Principal Research Question
PwC	PricewaterhouseCoopers International Limited
QR codes	Quick Response codes
RQs	Research Questions
RQs	Research Question (s)
SBV	The State Bank of Vietnam
SCIV	The System of Credit Institutions of Vietnam
SEM	Structural Equation Modeling

SERVQUAL	Service Quality Gap Model
Smart OTP	Smart One-Time Password
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
t-banking	Telephone Banking
Techcombank	Vietnam Technological and Commercial Joint Stock Bank
TPBank	Tien Phong Commercial Joint Stock Bank
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
UTAUT2	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
VBS	Vietnamese banking sector
VECOM	Vietnam E-commerce Association
Vietcombank	Vietnam Technological and Commercial Joint Stock Bank
VietinBank	Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam
VIR	Vietnam Investment Review
VISA	Vietnam Information Security Association
VnEconomy	Vietnam Economy Website
VNG	VNG Corporation
VNISA	Vietnam Information Security Association
VTV	National Television Broadcaster of Vietnam
WB	World Bank
α	Cronbach's Coefficient
χ^2	Chi-Square Statistic
β	Standardised Regression Coefficient

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

The first chapter aims to give a brief introduction to the study and to the context in terms of the research site in Vietnam. It will also examine the problem situation, leading to a formulation of the research questions that the study attempts to address.

1.2. Research Background

Applying science and technology has become an integral part of business activities today (Filotto et al., 2021). Businesses tend to update and use the latest information technologies to move towards a digital economy that embraces all companies (Koroleva and Kudryavtseva, 2020). The activities of converting technology to information technology applications are collectively known as digital transformation (Hanelt et al., 2021). In recent times, the concept and activities of Digital Technologies have become popular and widely applied in organisations as well as published studies (Hanelt et al., 2021). When it comes to the Covid-19 pandemic, traditional (offline) activities are limited to the maximum extent in organisations. Therefore, activities applying digital transformation are of more interest to businesses as well as customers (e.g., McKinsey, 2020; Hanelt et al., 2021).

The adoption of technology benefits organisations and customers when they only need to make click-through transactions on applications or websites (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). Over time, the activities on the application have become routine in commerce, and it also becomes the daily preferences of customers (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019, Alkhowaiter, 2020). Therefore, the trend of transaction or shopping using technology is indispensable in people's work and daily lives. As reported by UNCTAD that 1.45 billion people, or one-quarter of the world's population with the age 15 and over, made online purchases in 2018. This figure is 9 per cent higher than the previous year 2017 (UNCTAD, 2020).

The application of digital transformation is widely applied in the retail industry (Narayanasamy et al., 2011; Yoon and Steege, 2013; Amin, 2016). In particular, the banking industry is an excellent example of using digital transformation to serve its customers (Aladwani, 2001; Alkhowaiter, 2020; Leong et al., 2020, Filotto et al., 2021). Therefore, banks actively implement digital transformation to improve their service quality to compete with other banks (Sundarraaj and Wu, 2005; Daniel, 1999; Mols, 2001; Mbama and Ezepue, 2018). In the applications of information technology or digital transformation, Vietnam banks have been transformed with two typical types: e-banking services and Digital Banking, in which e-banking service has become obsolete and is gradually being replaced by Digital Banking service when the development of the application becomes more and more popular with the integration of blockchain technology.

The concept of Digital Banking has been widely used over the past decade when referring to the digital services of banks. Meher et al. (2021) established Digital Banking is the evolution of physical banking (or traditional banking), in which customers must physically visit bank branches to conduct banking transactions such as checking account balances, transferring funds, and so on. The concept of Digital Banking has evolved from previous electronic services such as internet banking or i-banking (Yap et al., 2010; Ho & Lin, 2010; Harrison et al., 2014; Amin, 2016; Raza et al., 2020), e-banking (Hussien and El Aziz, 2013; Ayo et al., 2016; Hammoud et al., 2018; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019), online banking (Herington & Weaven, 2009; Aldás-Manzano et al., 2009; Yoon, 2010), mobile banking or m-banking (Jun & Palacios, 2016). However, Digital Banking is a technology developed after the era of e-banking when integrating new technologies such as blockchain to make transactions safer and more efficient (Sardana & Singhania, 2020). Digital Banking can be integrated on all platforms, such as mobile or internet-connected devices, and can operate on utility applications to make transactions more convenient and safer (Mbama and Ezepue, 2018).

This situation has led to many banks putting more effort into marketing strategies and improving their online banking technology with the aim to strengthen the relationships with their clients (Amin, 2016).

However, the change to Digital Banking applications in banking activities, access to new technology, or new applications can change customer perception or behaviour. Therefore, banks improve the convenience, safety, and efficiency of Digital Banking services and satisfy customer satisfaction and retention (Jayawardhena, 2004; Kandampully et al., 2015; Makanyeza and Chikazhe, 2017; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). As a result, it is crucial for online banking to reach or surpass customers' satisfaction standards as they increasingly have more demand regarding their expectations (Amin, 2016).

Nowadays, the application of online transaction technological system becomes more and more necessary (McKinsey & Company, 2021). Moreover, it seems like the working procedures are transforming from traditional to online. Hence, banks are proactively constructing their own online systems to assist clients with their demands in financial transactions (Hanelt et al., 2021). During the pandemic, new functions for making transactions need to be explored in order to raise the competition amongst banks. If a bank's online services fail to satisfy customer's wants and needs, it might deal with the fact that unsatisfied clients will switch to their rivals' services. Therefore, the COVID-19 presents both a problem and a possible opportunity for banks to innovate in order to satisfy their customers.

Due to the increased number of new international banks participating in the banking industry in Vietnam, the competitive environment for Vietnamese banks tends to be severer. Vietnamese banks not only have to compete with their domestic rivals but also have to deal with the market penetration of foreign banks. Banks' competition regulations with regards to service bundles can help them become more competitive in the market. However, service packages usually vary

little from bank to bank (mainly associated with interest rates controlled by the government). This is because of two reasons: tangible services are typically easy to replicate, and bank service packages are generally adjustable based on internal resources and future plans. As a result, to differentiate between themselves, banks are now seeking to innovate intangible services that are hard to duplicate. For instance, factors such as customer service, electronic transaction service, etc., might be deemed distinctive and difficult to imitate. This is because the values these elements deliver lie in service satisfaction.

Many banks have developed and employed the e-banking service to equip customers with the capability of making electronic transactions via the internet in recent years. However, due to the advancement of technology, customers are benefitting from the convenience of the use of apps. At the same time, customers' demands are fastly growing and the requirement for e-transactions is getting increasingly common (Sreejesh et al., 2016; Monferrer-Tirado et al., 2016; Heffernan, 2005). As a result, banks must provide better care service to customers and raise customers' satisfaction in order to achieve more revenues and grow. And the model of the Digital Banking services is designed to achieve those requirements. (Andaleeb et al., 2016; Mbama, 2018; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019). The growth of e-services would enhance customers' satisfaction, allowing banks to retain customers and hence facilitate customer loyalty. This will lead to an increase in the competitiveness for banks in the market (Amin, 2016).

Recently, the application of e-banking services has been replaced by a brand-new technological system called Digital Banking. The Digital Banking service accommodates users with a wider range of options and an increase in convenience compared to the traditional e-banking service. Many studies about the e-banking service and customers' satisfaction and loyalty have been conducted as e-banking service has been applied in banks for a long time, which means it is no

longer a new platform. On the other hand, the Digital Banking service was just created and implemented recently. It will need to reach customers differently via the app's interface, procedures, and functions. As a result, customers might have specific challenges while using this new banking service. Incurred problems that might impact customer satisfaction would incentivise banks to concentrate on enhancing the quality of their services to fulfil the requirements of customers more effectively.

1.3. Research Context – Vietnam

1.3.1. Overview of Vietnamese Economy

After the successful August Revolution in 1945, President Ho Chi Minh read the Declaration of Independence, giving birth to the Democratic Republic of Vietnam (SBV, 2020). During 75 years since the victory, Vietnam experienced ups and downs in national defense and socio-economic construction and development (Economy & Forecast Review, 2020). Although there are still limitations, Vietnam has achieved many great, comprehensive, and historically significant imprints on the economy, politics, culture, and society, fundamentally changing the face of the country (Economy & Forecast Review, 2020). From a country that mainly operated on the agricultural sector in the past, the high number of people living in remote areas, with low development level, Vietnam has transformed itself into a middle-income country in the world (Economy & Forecast Review, 2020). In terms of macroeconomic, Vietnam has experienced exceptional yearly GDP growth of 6% in the period 2014-2018 and 7% in 2019 (Austrade, 2021). In 2019, Vietnam's GDP ranked 8th worldwide and 2nd in the ASEAN region, making Vietnam one of the top 30 nations that experienced high growth in the level of import and export and the 22nd largest export economy in the world (Economy & Forecast Review, 2020). Due to expanded economic integration, Vietnam's socio-economy is mainly influenced by the event of the Covid-19 crisis in 2020. However, thanks to proactive countermeasures from the Government, the medical impact of the epidemic is not as severe as

in many other countries in the world. Macroeconomic and fiscal stability remained constant, with GDP growth predicted at approximately 1.81 per cent for the first two quarters of 2020. Vietnam weathered the Covid-19 pandemic better than most south-east Asian economies, with gross domestic product (GDP) growth above 2% in 2020/21 (The Banker, 2022). Regarding e-commerce, Vietnam has also experienced significant growth with gross merchandise value increased dramatically from US\$0.4 billion in 2015 to US\$4.6 billion in 2019 and is expected to reach US\$23 billion by 2025 (Austrade, 2021). In the meantime, it is anticipated that GDP per capita will increase from US\$2,516 in 2018 to US\$4,449 in 2025, leading to a potential sharp growth in the demand for consumer goods and services. In addition, Vietnam also has a favourable demographic profile for digital banking transformation with an expanding young population of 96.5 million as of 2019 with a median age of 30 and a population consisting 70% between the ages of 15 and 64 (Austrade, 2021).

Vietnam holds a promising position for the proliferation of digital banking. Its consumers, characterised by a high degree of digital literacy, young tech-savvy population are equipped and ready to navigate a wide variety of digital banking services (Deloitte, 2018). The widespread accessibility of the internet, with access rates rising from 48% in 2016 to 66% in 2019, along with a remarkable mobile subscriptions penetration rate of 130%, 51 million users of mobile phones and the internet, and 72% of adults own a smartphone is a significant factor (Austrade, 2021).

However, in terms of banking penetration, only 30% of adults in Vietnam now have an active bank account with only 2% of Vietnamese citizens owning credit cards, indicating that banking is still not very common in the country (Austrade, 2021). The scarce availability of actual financial infrastructure with the fewest bank branches (3.8 bank branches for every 100,000 people) and ATMs (24 ATMs for every 100,000 people) when compared to the other ASEAN nations further supports this low banking penetration (Google, Temasek and Bain, 2021). These

figures highlight the existing condition of banking in Vietnam and also point to opportunities for expanding the country's access to and utilisation of banking services (Austrade, 2021).

Thus, Vietnam is a country with low penetration of traditional banking, but digital infrastructure has developed quite strongly. This means that as the penetration level of banking services in general is promoted, Vietnam will have greater potential to promote the development of digital banking transactions in Vietnam in the medium term than Vietnam. other countries.

As forecasted by Google, Temasek, Bain & Company, Vietnam's digital economy will achieve the highest growth rate in Southeast Asia with an increase of 29-30per cent/year in the period 2022-2025; e-commerce increased by about 32per cent/year, 1.8 times higher than the regional average; the growth rate of value and number of electronic payment transactions reached 35-40 per cent/year thanks to the explosion of technology and the increasing demand of digital consumers (Google, Temasek and Bain, 2021). However, Vietnam also needs to overcome barriers in terms of institutions, infrastructure, quality of human resources, and innovation ecosystem to maximize the potential of the digital economy(Google, Temasek and Bain, 2021).

However, the effects of the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic are challenging to predict. The Covid-19 pandemic also suggests that more drastic reforms are necessary for the economy to recover in the near future; those reforms might include developing the business environment and facilitating the digital economy (Economy & Forecast Review, 2020). One of the most challenging barriers to the development of Vietnam's digital economy is that Vietnam is still considered a cash-based economy. In 2006, Prime Minister Nguyen Xuan Phuc put in use Decision No. 291/2006/QD-TTg, which approved the plan of non-cash payment for the period 2006-2010 and orientation to 2020, which is considered as the first legal corridor dealing with non-cash payment activities in Vietnam (Vietnam Investment Review, 2021). However, since then, the implementation of cashless payments has been facing various difficulties. Cash

payment is still prevalent in domestic transactions of people in Vietnam, particularly in rural and mountainous regions; non-cash payment in e-commerce is still low (Vietnam Investment Review, 2021). International Data Group (IDG) has reported that in 2019, although nearly 40 per cent of individuals in Vietnam have a bank account, there was still approximately 80 per cent of daily spending made by cash. More specifically, 98 per cent of cash payments were carried out for purchasing things under 100 thousand Vietnam dong and about 85 per cent of transactions at ATMs are cash withdrawals (IDG, 2019). The ratio of cash payment to other types of payment is still at the high rate relative to the target set out in Decision No. 2545/QD-TTg (IDG, 2019), which is 11.33 per cent as of December 31, 2019 (IDG, 2019). The main reason is that the habit of consuming cash is ingrained in people's subconscious, the hesitancy to adopt new payment methods, and their concerns about security, safety, and costs of e-payment methods.

1.3.2. Overview of Vietnamese Banking System

The System of Credit Institutions of Vietnam (hereinafter referred to SCIV as an abbreviation) serves as a vital instrument within the Vietnamese economy, fulfilling the pivotal functions of capital mobilisation, lending, and the provision of modern and convenient banking services to support economic activities (SBV, 2022). SCIV comprises various types of institutions with different ownership characteristics, including “Banks, Non- Bank Credit Institutions, Micro-Finance Institutions, Foreign Bank Branches, Representative Offices” (SBV, 2022). In terms of Banks, the majority of SCIV are Commercial Banks (four state-owned commercial banks, thirty-one private joint-stock commercial banks, nine wholly foreign-owned banks and joint-venture banks), followed by two Policy Banks and one Cooperative Banks (SBV, 2022). As for Non- Bank Credit Institutions, SCIV includes sixteen Finance Companies, ten Leasing Companies, and over 1200 people's credit funds as of 31 March 2023 (SBV, 2022).

Additionally, there are 4 Micro-Finance Institutions, fifty-two Foreign Bank Branches, and sixty-four Representative Offices as of 31 March 2023 (SBV, 2022).

Similar to the banking systems of many other nations, the apex of Vietnamese Banking System (VBS) is represented by the State Bank of Vietnam (SBV), which is a governmental agency operating at the ministerial level (SBV, 2022). It functions as the central bank of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam and is responsible for managing monetary, banking, and foreign exchange operations collectively referred to as monetary and banking operations (SBV, 2022). As a central bank, it is responsible for issuing currency, serving as the bank for credit institutions, providing monetary services to the government, and overseeing public services under its jurisdiction (SBV, 2022).

Among the prominent financial institutions in Vietnam, such as Agribank, BIDV, Vietin Bank, Vietcombank, and Techcombank, which hold a significant presence in the country's banking landscape, there are also notable foreign banks operating in Vietnam, including HSBC, ANZ, and Citibank. These foreign banks have established themselves as well-known entities, further enriching the banking sector in Vietnam and offering diverse options for customers in the country (Vietnam Investment Review, 2021).

In 2020, due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, businesses, households, and individuals faced many difficulties, the demand for credit is low, the growth of outstanding loans of credit institutions is challenging and lower than in previous years, the bad debt on the balance sheet increased. However, SCIV have accelerated restructuring, maintaining credit standards, promoting investment in Digital Banking technology, etc., continuing to develop sustainably (Tran and Pham, 2021). Despite the adverse effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, VBS had still experienced substantial growth in 2020 and achieved its set expectations. More specifically, the financial statements of 27 banks in the last quarter demonstrated a rise of 13.7 per cent from

2019 (Banking Review, 2019). One of the most significant highlights of the Vietnam banking industry in 2020 is that intense competition increased investment of financial and human resources for digital transformation (Tran and Pham, 2021).

Despite careful preparation from previous years, by 2020 with the pressure of the COVID-19 epidemic, digital transformation and digitisation of the banking industry have been promoted even more. A series of commercial banks have increased their investment of financial resources into digitisation combined with personnel training, and improved internal management processes. Many new Digital Banking services have been launched such as: the studied bank Digibank, Lienviet24h, Timoplus, SeAmobile... Stronger investment in digitalisation helps banks to rapidly increase the number of customers and increase revenue from services, cross-sell products, increase customer experience, reduce dependence on revenue from traditional credit activities, promote the development of cashless payment in the economy (Tran and Pham, 2021).

Banks in Vietnam have implemented a number of advanced technologies in their business administration to provide modern, friendly, and convenient products and services that provide customers with practical experiences and benefits, such as eKYC, QR codes, contactless payments, and have built a centralised, standardised, and integrated digital infrastructure to create a spreading digital ecosystem, which includes a mobile banking ecosystem connected with services. Finance, telecommunications, power, transportation, and healthcare are all examples of public-sector industries.

By the end of April 2021, it is recorded that over 79 payment service providers deploy payments through the internet while those of 44 other providers are implemented through mobile phones. As a whole, the market is now having more than 271,000 POS and more than 19,000 ATMs. Moreover, transactions through internet banking saw a rise of 65.9 per cent in quantity and 31.2

per cent in value, while at the same time, transactions through mobile phone banking grew by 86.3 per cent in quantity and 123.1 per cent in value. Furthermore, transactions by QR code expanded by 95.7 per cent in quantity and 181.5 per cent in value (Vietnam Investment Review, 2021).

1.3.3. Overview of Digital Banking in Vietnam

Digital Banking is currently developing and becoming more popular in Vietnam. Today, digital technology is a development trend. The banking industry is entering a new technology investment phase. The project "Modernisation of banks and payment systems" successfully implemented by the loans from World Bank for Vietnam has laid an important technological foundation for modernisation of Vietnam's banking industry. Until now, it is still promoting its effectiveness and is increasingly being upgraded and improved, improving technology better, effectively serving the activities of the banking industry in particular and the development of the economy in general (Banking Review, 2021b).

According to Austrade (2021), the majority of Vietnamese banks (60 per cent) had already adopted or were in the process of establishing digital transformation plans by the end of 2019.

The majority of banks in Vietnam have been through the stage of digitisation. Now they are in the phase of digital transformation, which comprises a variety range of communication channels and digital procedures to provide their customers with personalised experiences. At the same time, some other banks are now experiencing the first degree of transformation-digitalisation in the databases. A small number of commercial banks have taken the risk of redirecting their investment to digital technologies (Banking Review, 2021a). Typical is the case of OCB, TPBank. OCB's OMNI synchronously connects all communication channels with customers. All banking services are integrated on a single digital platform so that customers can use all services without going to the counter (Banking Review, 2021a).

Generally, Digital Banking is now rapidly evolving and gaining popularity in the Vietnamese banking industry. The widespread use of smartphones and tablets, along with most of the country's population getting access to the internet, has supported the expansion of Digital Banking in Vietnam. Especially as a result of a social distancing measure caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, from individuals to large organisations such as firms or the government have been obliged to adopt the digital means to preserve their everyday lives (FinnResearch 2020 Report). Digital Banking has been driven by changes in customers' behaviors, government support, and the consequences brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Clients and banks have always been interested in the way they can utilise a new service like Digital Banking (to check if clients are pleased or if they have any problems regarding the Digital Banking service) (Calisir and Gumussoy, 2008; Li-hua, 2012; Zhao et al., 2010). However, it will require a certain amount of time and customers' willingness to adjust their behaviors to adapt to a new working situation. Aside from the quality of the services offered by banks, this accounts for another challenge for customers to reach and make use of the Digital Banking service (Alsajjan and Dennis, 2010; Chemingui, 2013; Chen and Teng, 2013; Hanafizadeh et al., 2014; Khalil et al., 2010; Nor and Pearson, 2008). If the transformation and use are complicated and inconvenient, it is likely that clients would be uncomfortable and disappointed with this new service. (Karjaluoto et al., 2002). This is a topic that requires further investigation in order to provide the most accurate appraisal of the situation.

Furthermore, with the advancement of science and technology in Vietnam, which is seen as having some limits in comparison to industrialised nations, building a technological infrastructure base is seen as a challenge. As a result, the evolution of Digital Banking requires a progressive shift in response to user feedback on the interface, processing speed, and security. To enhance Digital Banking services at commercial banks in Vietnam in general, studies are required at each phase of technical development.

1.4. Research Rationale

The emergence of digital banking has fundamentally transformed the banking landscape globally, and emerging economies such as Vietnam is not an exception. Comprehending the importance of offering superior Digital Banking quality for customers is crucial for banks to maintain a competitive advantage in the banking environments (Amin, 2016). Therefore, it is critical to identify the significant aspects responsible for measuring the quality of integrated service in internet banking (Amin, 2016). Moreover, customers in the banking industry have become more receptive to competitive developments. Only an increase in the quality of internet service might not be sufficient to secure long-term relationships between banks and their clients (Brun et al., 2014). As a result, customers' satisfaction and loyalty have been highlighted as key contributions in creating and facilitating relationships between banks and customers to decrease the possible issues that might occur when using online banking (Dahlstrom et al., 2014). In this case, many banks have been incentivised to increase their marketing efforts and upgrade technology in their internet banking services to sustain the relations with their customers (Amin, 2016).

Even though the existing literature is quite comprehensive with the research of Digital Banking adoption, aspects of service quality, satisfaction, loyalty, previous research primarily have been addressed in the context of Western countries (Mbama & Ezepeue, 2018). However, it seems like the differences in the cultural background of customers would relatively affect its applicability in the context of developing countries (Amin, 2016). There is a lack of research inspecting this topic in the Vietnam Digital Banking context. There are still some limitations in terms of empirical research that have been generated to evaluate the relationships between Digital Banking service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in Vietnam. Of these limited sources, the predominant focus is on the adoption intention of online banking/internet

banking/mobile banking has been performed in Vietnam, but not the actual adoption or customer experience, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty.

Research Methodology employed in research is another gap which the researcher found in the Digital Banking literature in Vietnam context. Most of the recent studies focus on investigating the Digital Banking service quality dimensions only from customers' perspectives, using Survey Questionnaires as the main data collection methods and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) as the main data analysis technique to test hypotheses.

In short, little evidence is found in the current scientific knowledge on the effects of Digital Banking service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in Vietnam, revealing an important yet unanswered research gap. This gap provides the impetus for a deep investigation with a proper system of the effect of Digital Banking service quality factors on Digital Banking customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of developing countries (e.g., Vietnam) from major stakeholders' perspectives by using a mixed-method research design.

Therefore, this Doctoral thesis will accomplish this gap by examining the topic from different stakeholders' perceptions by employing a mixed-method study with a survey for customers, interviews for bank managers, and secondary data for other stakeholders' groups. These are the main reasons behind the selection of the chosen topic: "Investigating the impact of Digital Banking Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: Empirical evidence from a Vietnam Commercial Bank". Accordingly, the main objective of this study is to determine critical dimensions of Digital Banking service quality that hugely affect customers' satisfaction and loyalty in Vietnam, using one of the leading commercial banks in Vietnam as an example (hereinafter referred to "the studied bank" or "the case bank"). The study will also investigate different stakeholders' perceptions about current Digital Banking in Vietnam. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is no similar research being conducted in the

context of Vietnam. Therefore, the implications of this study are in the hope of making innovative contribution to theoretical and practical implications.

1.5. Research Problem

Digital banking revolution has been increasingly embraced by and offered significant advantages for Vietnamese banking users. Notwithstanding the promising position for the proliferation of digital banking that Vietnam holds thanks to its young tech-savvy population and a remarkable internet and mobile phone penetration along with huge investments made by Vietnamese banks into Digital Banking implementation, the usage of digital banking in Vietnam is still sparse compared to conventional banking adoption with only 30% of adults in Vietnam now have an active bank account with only 2% of Vietnamese citizens owning credit cards (Austrade, 2021). Vietnamese Commercial Banks have been struggling to keep up with their customers' constantly evolving demands and expectations in a changing digital banking landscape. Moreover, a stiff competition among financial institutions in Vietnam emerging digital banking market poses significant challenges for Vietnamese Commercial Banks in their Digital Transformation. Therefore, in order to stay competitive, Digital banking services offered by banks must be aligned with customer expectations to foster customer satisfaction and loyalty. Consequently, understanding the impact of different digital banking service quality determinants on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is significantly crucial. However, even though the extant literature is rich with research about Digital Banking, primarily researches are found in a Western context and not in emerging economies like Vietnam (Mbama and Ezepue, 2018). So far, in Vietnam, where digital banking is still evolving and expanding, existing research in this field is sparse. The impact of specific Digital Banking service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnam's emerging digital banking landscape, remains comparatively unexplored. This research is

therefore timely and relevant and will contribute invaluable theoretical and managerial implications.

1.6. Research Aim and Objectives

The research aims to examine the efficiency of Digital Banking and its relationship with Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty with regard to the main stakeholders (i.e., banking customers and banking managers), suggesting strategic recommendations for optimising digital banking service quality dimensions in enhancing customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks.

To accomplish the outlined aims, the thesis will pursue the fulfilment of the following specific objectives in details:

- Objective 1: To examine which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?”
- Objective 2: To evaluate the perceptions of the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) for the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks using the studied bank as a case in point.
- Objective 3: To investigate the challenges and constraints faced by Vietnamese Commercial Banks in their Digital Banking Implementation Process.
- Objective 4: To recommend strategies for Vietnam Commercial Banks in utilising Digital Banking as a means of enhancing Digital Banking Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty.

Table 1.1 presents where Research Questions are addressed

Research Questions	Research Objectives	Addressed in Chapter
RQ1	Objective 1	5,7
RQ2	Objective 2	5,6,7
RQ3	Objective 3	7

RQ4	Objective 4	8
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Table 1. 1 Research Questions (Source: Author)

1.7. Research Questions

The current research pursues to address these following Research Questions:

- RQ1: “Which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?”
- RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?"
- RQ3: “What are the key challenges to Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty?”
- RQ4: “What recommendations can be proposed to stakeholders regarding the utilisation of digital banking channels to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Banking Sector?”

Answers to these questions could provide essential insights for Vietnamese Commercial Banks to navigate their Digital Banking strategies, nurturing their Digital Banking customer satisfaction and loyalty, which is pivotal to the development and success of Vietnamese Banking Sector.

1.8. Research Methodology Summary

This present research involves primary data collection and applies a mixed-method design. Quantitative data is collected from 660 Digital Banking customers in Vietnam by using a

structured self-completed web-based survey (by Survey Monkey). Qualitative data is collected from interviews with five bank managers of the case bank. This Doctoral Thesis also make use of secondary data of Digital Banking to support the primary data collected and strengthen the results of the research, as in line with Saunders et al. (2019). Cronbach's alpha is used for Reliability Statistics, Spearman's Correlation Coefficient with Python is used for testing the hypotheses, while Template Analysis is employed for the qualitative data analysis. This research methodology is the most appropriate method for this particular empirical study, enabling the researcher to collect and analyse the necessary data from different sources to explore various stakeholders' perspectives of Digital Banking developments in Vietnam and investigate key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customers' satisfaction and loyalty.

1.9. Research Intention

I intended to make three forms of contribution with my Doctoral thesis:

- To acquire the set academic expectations and contribute to people who were in primary attention of this study.
- To make my conclusions available to all concerned stakeholders such as banking customers, the studied bank, other financial service institutions, and Vietnamese policymakers.
- To contribute to the knowledge regarding the relevance and appropriateness of Digital Banking in the banking industry related to the financial sector and the broader societal developments.

1.10. Researcher's Professional Background

In 2011, the researcher successfully completed her Bachelor's Degree (Distinction) in Finance and Banking at the Banking Academy in Hanoi, Vietnam, her country of origin. She then joined

the Asia Commercial Bank (ACB), worked for two years as a credit analyst, gaining valuable work experience and further enhancing her knowledge in the banking field.

Since then, she has developed further interest in financial services and joined the University of Sunderland at the London Campus to study a Master of Business Administration in Finance, which gives her a solid impetus to research the impacts of financial services on the broader socio-economic issues. As the researcher's interest and understanding of the effects of the financial industry developed, she has been drawn deeper into the sector and then wished to further her study to a greater extent of the Doctoral level. She then decided to continue researching a field that she is passionate about, i.e., contemporary bank marketing, and explore the determinants of banking service quality that could positively impact customer satisfaction. In 2018, the researcher then embarked on my Doctor of Business Administration journey at the University of West of Scotland. As part of her doctoral degree, the researcher has started to focus on contemporary business & financial practices. This also led to her passion for Customer Service and Digital Banking, where she can see her future profession. Hence, her decision is to explore the impact of Digital Banking service quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in the Vietnam Banking Sector, where she can genuinely contribute to the body of knowledge.

1.11. Research Process

Figure 1.1 describes the research process employed in this research at hand.

Figure 1. 1 Research Process (Source: Author)

Step 1: Determine the research objective.

The main aim of the thesis focuses on assessing the effects of Digital Banking on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty and comprehending the perceptions of different stakeholders about Digital Banking. The study also aims to investigate the challenges for developing Digital Banking, followed by recommendations.

Step 2: Literature review

After determining the research objective, the researcher conducts an extensive literature review on Digital Banking which presents a primary focus of the research to identify its gap.

Step 3: Research model and Research Methodology

Based on an extensive literature review about Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting Customer Satisfaction Loyalty, the researcher has selected the most appropriate dimensions for the research topic and context (Vietnam). Subsequently, the researcher proposed a research model and developed hypotheses.

Step 4: Data collection and data analysis

After determining research variables and building a research model, the researcher implements data collection with a customer survey and interviews for bank managers. The suitability of the questionnaires was checked and confirmed through the pilot test.

With the data collected from the preliminary survey, the researcher conducts a preliminary analysis to confirm the appropriateness of the questionnaire, the information, and especially the research variables. On that basis, the researcher conducts an official survey. From the data obtained from the official study, the researcher puts it into Python software for analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis techniques will reveal individual customer information. This research employs Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics to test the scale's reliability to assess the appropriateness of the observed variables and Spearman's Correlation Coefficients Model to figure out the Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customers' satisfaction and loyalty. Template Analysis also reveals the perceptions of various stakeholders about current developments of Digital Banking.

Step 5: Finalise the thesis report.

Based on the data analysis discussion, conclusions and solutions to improve customers' satisfaction and loyalty will be recommended. The research also points out the limitations of the topic and proposes further research directions related to the research topic.

1.12. Research Outcomes

This research is believed to contribute to the achievement of literature of bank marketing and academics by giving a complete description of how Digital Banking service quality aspects are

used as measures of customers' satisfaction with Digital Banking, which gives rise to an increase in Digital Banking customer loyalty. This study shows the major determinants that significantly affect Digital Banking customer satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, gaining a more profound knowledge of these potential interactions can allow the Digital Banking sector to see developments in formatting marketing strategies, promoting a long-term relationship with their clients and achieving competitive advantages to rank higher position in the global market.

1.13. Research Structure

In this research, eight chapters were presented for each stage in the research's process.

Chapter 1: The chapter provides detailed information on the research's subject, background, and importance in understanding critical components of Digital Banking Service Quality and its main effects on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. The research Problem is presented, leading to the formation of the research questions that are attempted to address. A summary of research methodology is also discussed, along with the thesis's research intention, process, and structure.

Chapter 2: This chapter conducts a comprehensive critical assessment of the relevant literature of Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in bank marketing research in the world and Vietnam, revealing an important yet unanswered research gap that needs to be studied.

Chapter 3: This chapter extensively and critically explores the critical attributes of the Digital Banking service quality predominantly evaluated in extant literature. The researcher develops a conceptual framework and hypotheses for obtaining outlined research objectives in chapter one based on the findings. The rationale from the theoretical foundation for choosing the

utilised conceptual framework is discussed, followed by the conceptual model and hypotheses development.

Chapter 4: This Chapter aims to explain and justify the chosen methodologies of the research. The justification of selected research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection, populations and sampling, data analysis is presented. Subsequently, this Chapter also discusses data management and ethical considerations, research validity, research reliability.

Chapter 5: This chapter mainly focuses on the quantitative data analysis, leading to a critical evaluation of the findings by relating the results to the previous studies. Quantitative obtained from a self-administered web survey (Survey Monkey) of 660 Vietnam Digital Banking customers was utilised to investigate the assumptions of the interactions amongst the research constructs using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Statistics and Spearman Correlation Coefficient with Python Software. After the hypotheses test, key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty were identified, answering Research Question 1. The researcher also conducted a descriptive analysis to investigate the customers' perceptions about current Digital Banking applications in the studied bank, answering Research Question 2.

Chapter 6: In this chapter, the qualitative data analysis results are presented by using Template Analysis. It explores bank managers' perceptions about Digital Banking regarding customers' satisfaction and loyalty and aims to answer Research Question 2.

Chapter 7: This chapter elaborates the implications of both quantitative and qualitative methods mentioned earlier in Chapter 5 and Chapter 6. As stated in Chapter 1, this research aims to determine the key dimensions of Digital Banking Service Quality that influence Digital Banking customers' satisfaction and loyalty in Vietnam. Studies about Digital Banking in

Vietnam are still limited. Thus, Digital Banking service quality factors contributing to Digital Banking customers' satisfaction and loyalty in Vietnam remain almost unknown. This Chapter answers the outlined research questions by discussing the main findings of the research.

Chapter 8: This chapter provides a conclusion for problems discussed in Chapter 7 and harmonises the crucial discoveries of the study. First, this chapter starts with a thesis chapters summary and the study's main findings. Subsequently, essential answers to the research questions and the contributions that were achieved in this research are then presented. This section then evaluates both theoretical and practical implication of the study, together with the acknowledgment of limitations and future research directions. Lastly, the chapter illustrates a summary of the whole thesis and an End-of-thesis Self Reflection of the researcher.

1.14. Summary

This first chapter provides background and an overview of the developments of Digital Banking in Vietnam. Then, this chapter discusses the problematic situation behind the rationale for the research, resulting in the generation of critical questions that the research attempt to explain. Subsequently, a brief summary of the chosen research methodology is discussed, followed by the research process and structure.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter provides an extensive critical review both worldwide and in Vietnam of the relevant literature on Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in bank marketing research, which served as the context for the study. Most recent high-quality journal articles have been utilised. The researcher emphasises the knowledge gap and justification for further research in each section reviewed. Finally, the researcher highlights a general research gap, and justifies the need for this present study to be conducted. This part will also highlight the areas where this study will provide fresh insights.

2.2. Digital Banking

The concept of Digital Banking has been widely used over the past decade when referring to banks' digital services. Meher et al. (2021) defined Digital Banking as the evolution of conventional banking in which banking clients must physically visit bank branches to conduct banking transactions. The concept of Digital Banking has evolved from previous electronic services such as i-banking, e-banking (Amin, 2016; Alkhowaiter, 2020). Recently, Sardana & Singhania (2020) and Mbama and Ezepeue (2018) defined Digital Banking as a new banking service developed by integrating new technologies such as blockchain to make more convenient and safer banking transactions. Building upon the perspective shared by Alkhowaiter (2020), this study encompasses various forms of Digital Banking services, including e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking, and online banking, which will be collectively referred to as Digital Banking (DB) henceforth.

Several authors had performed research examining the potential benefits of Digital Banking, especially e-banking (Daniel, 1999; Black, Lockett, Winklhofer & McKechnie, 2002). There exists a research debate in terms of the relationship between the impact of Digital Banking on

financial performance. Several authors, such as (Acharya et al., 2008; DeYoung et al., 2007; Sayar & Wolfe, 2007) confirmed online banking dramatically influences the financial performance of retail banking. Similarly, Mbama and Ezepue (2018) verified the importance of Digital Banking on the financial performance of UK banks. Conversely, researching the same topic but in a different context – Turkey banking sector, Kahveci and Wolfs (2018) argued that Digital Banking is only a strategic necessity yet a strategic advantage without providing banks any financial benefits. These findings imply that Digital Banking appears to have no impact on financial performance in the Turkey banking context. In terms of benefits for customers, there is evidence from several authors who confirmed that e-banking enhances customer services, retaining loyal customers for the banks (Martins, Oliveira and Popovič, 2014).

With regards to the importance of bank branches after the emergence of Digital Banking, Howcroft, Hamilton and Hower (2002) concluded that eventually, e-banking and t-banking will replace bank branches, while Stone & Laughlin (2016) argued bank branches would never be replaced although they acknowledged the significant challenge of Digital Banking on bank branches.

As pointed out by Aboobucker & Bao (2018), Internet banking acceptance has been well researched in a variety of contexts. Polatoglu & Ekin (2001) conducted research about the adoption of online banking in Turkey with a total of 150 banking customers' valid responses. The finding revealed “reliability, security, privacy, accessibility and perceived risk” are strong determinants affecting the adoption of online banking in Turkey. Though, the findings also showed that “saving of costs” appears not to have importance on the decision of accepting online banking by customers. Moreover, examining Internet Banking in Oman, Riffai et al. (2012) found out “trust”, “usability” and “perceived quality” are the key factors affecting Internet banking adoption, while Aboobucker & Bao (2018) proved that “Security/privacy

risk” is an obstruct preventing online banking acceptance in Sri Lanka. Wang et al. (2003) verified the importance of “trust” as a prominent determinant on customers’ intention to adopt internet banking in the context of Taiwan Banking Sector.

In terms of the effect of Digital Banking on customer satisfaction, Ahmed et al. (2017) conducted research in Pakistan banking with the support of a modified SERVQUAL model. The study obtained 830 customers responses and employed factor analysis, CFA, and bootstrapping methods for customers (Ahmed et al.,2017). The findings show that “online banking” significantly and positively affects customer satisfaction.

However, Aboobucker & Bao (2018) and Rotchanakitumnuai (2003) criticised that existing literature has been focusing predominantly on Digital Banking adoption rather than actual usage and customer experience. Sharing the same viewpoint, as criticised by Mbama and Ezepue (2018), research into different forms of Digital Banking services (mobile banking, internet banking, online banking, Digital Banking) has been conducted intensively globally. However, most of the research has been focusing on the adoption intention of Digital Banking services, and less attention has been put on users’ experience and satisfaction (Trinh et al., 2020; Boateng et al., 2016; Martins et al., 2014; Chong et al., 2010), which might not accomplish the current banking marketing needs.

Moreover, as Mbama & Ezepue (2018) criticised, existing research of Digital Banking is fragmented with authors investigating individual channels (e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking) or focusing attention on only a few variables, revealing that different factors need to be explored. This gap proves a necessity of conducting studies investigating the influence of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction with more factors employed in the research model.

This gap proves a need to conduct research exploring the importance of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction, especially in the context of emerging countries like Vietnam.

2.3. Digital Banking Service Quality

Comprehending the importance of offering superior Digital Banking Service Quality for clients is crucial for banks to sustain a competitive advantage in the market (Amin, 2016). Parasuraman et al.(1985) initially defined service quality as the kind of attitude that is unveiled as a result of the gap between the service expectation and actual presentation. The concept of service quality, in general, has been studied extensively in research history, with numerous researchers developing service quality concepts globally (Al-Jazzazi & Sultan, 2014; Caruana, 2002).

There has been a wide variety of researches exploring service quality management over the past four decades (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Zeithaml et al., 1996; Jun and Cai, 2001; Zeithaml et al., 2002; Caruana, 2002; Parasuraman et al., 2005). Parasuraman et al. (1988) verified there is a very “sturdy” and “durable” relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. Evidence from most of the existing literature confirms that providing high-quality services can be seen as a strategic weapon to gain competitive advantage in the marketplace, as pointed out by Caruana (2002) and also an essential strategy for the long-term success of organisations (Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Malhotra, 2002). Therefore, in order to improve customer service quality, it would be a crucial starting point to determine customer perceived salient service quality dimensions and evaluate the overall service quality as suggested by Jun & Palacios (2016).

However, Digital Banking Service Quality is an emerging research topic that recently received increasing interest from both marketing academics (Shankar & Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Mbama

& Ezepeue, 2018; Jun & Palacios, 2016; Jun & Cai, 2001; Herington & Weaven, 2009; Alkhowaiter, 2020) and practitioners such as (Boston Consulting Group, 2020; OECD, 2020). Digital Banking Service Quality refers to customers' overall assessment of the quality of the Digital Banking services (Zeithaml et al., 2002; Santos, 2003; Parasuraman et al., 2005; Bauer et al., 2006; Liao et al., 2011; Amin, 2016).

In the banking context, several authors have been undertaking research to recognise the main determinants of service quality. For example, a study by Jun & Palacios (2015) revealed 17 “mobile banking service quality” factors including “application quality (content, accuracy, ease of use, speed, aesthetics, security, diverse mobile application service features, and mobile convenience), and customer service quality (reliability, responsiveness, competence, courtesy, credibility, access, communication, understanding the customer, and continuous improvement”.

Moreover, after conducting an extensive literature review about Digital Banking and related themes, the researcher agreed with Amin (2016) that prior studies on banking service quality were primarily conducted in the context of Europe and North America using measurement scales mostly based on the SERVQUAL model developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) while little attention has been paid in developing countries such as Vietnam. Karatepe et al. (2005) proposed that cultural differences, such as the contrast between Collectivism in Vietnam and Individualism in Western contexts, could influence research outcomes when applied to other developing nations like Vietnam, which is the focus of the current study. This gap further emphasises the significance of conducting the present research.

2.4. Customer satisfaction

This research aims to understand to what extent the quality of Digital Banking services provided by the studied bank would affect its level of customer satisfaction. According to Geebren et al. (2021), there exists evidence that Satisfaction has been widely accepted as a

significant factor determining the continuous usage and accomplishment in the context of information systems and e-commerce contexts. There is no consensus in the extant literature with regards to the definition of customer satisfaction. As defined by Oliver (1981), satisfaction is “an emotional post consumption evaluative judgment concerning a product or service”. Similarly, customer satisfaction refers to “consumer response to the evaluation of the perceived difference between expectations and the final result after consumption” as proposed by Tse & Wilton (1988). Hammoud et al. (2018) defined customer satisfaction as “the comparison of post product/service performance with pre-formed expectations”.

In this present study, customer satisfaction will be regarded as the attitude of customers when using different types of general Digital Banking services (e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking, online banking, Digital Banking).

According to Ahmed et al. (2017), there are two undistinguishable notions of customer satisfaction in the extant literature: Cumulative satisfaction and Transaction-specific satisfaction. Cumulative satisfaction is regarded as the whole experience of clients with a service/product over a period of time (Olsen & Johnson, 2003; Ahmed et al. (2017) . Meanwhile, Transaction-specific is defined as “Transaction-specific satisfaction,” which measures the assessment of customers for the occurrence of a specific product/ service (Olsen and Johnson, 2003).

2.5. Digital Banking Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction.

There exists substantial evidence in the literature that by offering online transactions, financial institutions can significantly increase its customer satisfaction level (Olsen & Johnson, 2003; Raza et al., 2015).

There is significant academic debate on the relationship between banking service quality and customer satisfaction (Babakus and Boller, 1992; Mbama & Ezepue, 2018; Bahia and Nantel, 2000). Customer satisfaction can be seen as an antecedent of service quality (Parasuraman et

al., 1985; Carman, 1990; Bitner et al., 1990). In contrast, there are arguments that service quality is a predictor of customer satisfaction (Amin, 2016, Kassim & Abdullah, 2010, Ho & Lin, 2010; Bauer et al., 2006; Jun & Cai, 2001).

The relationship of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on customer satisfaction has been verified by numerous researchers globally (Filotto et al., 2021; Asiyani & Ishola, 2018; Hammoud et al., 2018); Mbama & Ezepue, 2018; Ahmed et al., 2017; Amin, 2016; Yoon, 2010; Kassim & Abdullah, 2010; Herington & Weaven, 2009; Bei and Chiao, 2006; Ranaweera & Neely, 2003).

For example, in a study about e-banking and customer satisfaction in the Australia banking sector using 200 banking customers survey responses and Factor Analysis for ascertaining factor structure and Regression Analysis for testing hypotheses, Herington & Weaven (2009) verified e-banking service quality has significant importance on customer satisfaction.

Geebren et al. (2021) performed a study about Mobile banking and customer satisfaction in Lybia with a focus on the mediating impact of trust. The study successfully collected 659 Lybian banking customers by an online survey that was mostly distributed on Facebook banking communities (Geebren et al., 2021). In terms of data analysis, the research employed structural equation modelling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM) (Geebren et al., 2021). The results revealed service quality has a major impact on customer satisfaction. Innovatively, the results pointed out trust has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction and also trust has a significant mediation effect between service quality and customer satisfaction (Geebren et al., 2021).

However, the findings of the extant literature are varied, with each findings indicated different Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions have different impact on Customer Satisfaction, which will be discussed in more details in the following Section 2.6.

2.6. Digital Banking Service Quality Dimensions and Customer Satisfaction

Various researchers have attempted to determine service quality dimensions affecting customer satisfaction in the Digital Banking context internet banking, mobile banking, e-banking such as Mbama and Ezepue (2018); Ahmed et al. (2017); Yoon (2010); Kassim and Abdullah (2010); Herington & Weaven (2009). These studies produced mixed results on how and to what extent different dimensions affect customer satisfaction.

Based on an extensive literature review on Digital Banking (Internet Banking, e-banking, mobile banking) or similar context like e-commerce, the researcher pointed out the most prominent dimensions determining Digital Banking Service Quality that frequently has been confirmed its impact on Customer Satisfaction in recent studies.

For example, in a study about e-banking and customer satisfaction in Australia banking sector using 200 banking customers survey responses, Factor Analysis for ascertaining factor structure and Regression Analysis for testing hypotheses, Herington & Weaven (2009) verified that three e-banking quality measures: "personal needs", "site organisation", "user-friendliness" significantly affected Customer satisfaction while "efficiency" appears to have no effect on Customer satisfaction (Herington and Weaven, 2009). Conversely, research conducted in the Lebanese e- banking sector by Hammoud et al. (2018) revealed a different result for the impact of "efficiency" on customer satisfaction. Hammoud et al. (2018) performed quantitative research by conducting a survey for Lebanese banking customers and employing structural equation modelling with SPSS and Amos (20) for data analysis. The findings indicated all the five E-banking service quality factors: "reliability, efficiency, and ease of use; responsiveness and communication; and security and privacy" positively influence customer satisfaction, in which "reliability" exerts the strongest effect on customer satisfaction (Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba, 2018). These findings of the most substantial impact of reliability on customer satisfaction confirm the results of the prior study by Zhou (2004).

Ahmed et al. (2017) conducted research in Pakistan banking with the support of a modified SERVQUAL model. The study obtained 830 customers responses and employed factor analysis, CFA, and bootstrapping methods for data analysis. The findings demonstrated that “responses” “empathy”, “competence”, “reliability”, and online service" have a substantial influence on overall customer satisfaction with “reliability” being the dimension with the strongest impact.

In contrast, previous research in m-banking in Oman using the SERVQUAL model presented that empathy (Al-Zadjali, Al-Jabri and Al-Balushi, 2015) does not have a significant effect on consumer satisfaction of Digital Banking.

Investigating UK Digital Banking customers, Mbama and Ezepue (2018) explained that banking clients are most satisfied with "service quality", "functional quality", "perceived value", "employee-customer engagement", "perceived usability" and "perceived risk". Besides, investigating digital payment and banking adoption in a different context of Gulf countries, Alkhwaiter (2020) accomplished a systematic review and verified that “trust” “perceived security” and “perceived usefulness” are the most robust antecedents for customer satisfaction. Kassim & Abdullah (2010) performed research in Malaysian and Qatari e-commerce settings using SEM analysis to confirm that “Perceived service quality” has a significant relationship with customer satisfaction.

Regarding research conducted in Asian countries, Yoon (2010) conducted an empirical research in China’s online banking context and collected 224 survey questionnaires, mostly from Chinese students. Using structural multi-group for hypotheses testing, the findings showed that “design, speed, security, information content, and customer support service” are all distinctive determinants for customer satisfaction while “ease of use” appears not relevant. Lately, Amin (2016) conducted research in Malaysian banking to examine the impact of internet banking service quality on e-customer satisfaction and e-customer loyalty. The

research collected 520 survey questionnaires from Malaysian banking customers and employed SEM for data analysis. The results confirmed that all four dimensions, “personal need, site organisation, user friendliness, and efficiency of website” have a significant impact on customer satisfaction (Amin, 2016).

Ling et al. (2016) conducted a study with 200 respondents in Malacca Malaysia verified that customers are more satisfied with “web design and content”, “convenience” and “speed” dimensions of internet banking service quality. Hence, they are the key drivers influencing Internet banking customer satisfaction in using Internet Banking.

Nevertheless, in general, limited attention has been paid to adopting different mediating and moderating variables such as “electronic word of mouth”, “brand loyalty” (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017), which proves a research gap that needs to be accomplished.

In short, numerous studies investigating different forms Digital Banking (online banking/internet banking/mobile banking) and its importance on customer satisfaction have been conducted globally. Existing literature documented key determinants for Digital Banking customer satisfaction are “reliability, security and privacy, ease of use, accuracy, customer service and support, responsiveness and web site design” (Rod *et al.*, 2009).

However, limited attention has been paid to the broader context of Digital Banking. Hence, the focus of future research should be shifted to Digital Banking.

2.7. Key measures discussed in the research

Table 2.1 illustrates key measures utilised in internet banking/e-banking/mobile banking/Digital Banking Research

Supporting literature	Main findings
Amin (2016)	Significant: “Personal need, site organisation, user friendliness, and efficiency of website”
Hammoud et al. (2018)	Significant: “Reliability, efficiency, and ease of use; Responsiveness and communication; and security and privacy”
Herington & Weaven (2009)	Significant: “personal needs, site organisation”, "user-friendliness" Not significant: “efficiency”

Hussien & El Aziz (2013)	Significant: “Usability, reliability, Responsiveness, privacy, incentives, fulfilment, efficiency, assurance, empathy”
Jun & Cai (2001)	Significant: “Reliability, privacy and security, website design and customer service and support”
Jun & Palacios (2015)	Significant: all 17 factors: “Content, accuracy, ease of use, speed, aesthetics, security, diverse mobile application service features, and mobile convenience), and customer service quality (reliability, responsiveness, competence, courtesy, credibility, access, communication, understanding the customer, and continuous improvement.”
Jun & Palacios (2016)	Significant: “Convenience, accuracy, service features, ease of use, and continuous improvement”
Larsson&Viitaoja (2017)	Significant: “Customisation, Contact interactivity, Cultivation, "Care", Community, Choice, Convenience, Character”
Ling et al. (2016)	Significant: “web design and content”, “convenience” and “speed”
Mbama and Ezepue (2018)	Significant: “service quality, functional quality, perceived value, employee-customer engagement, perceived usability and perceived risk” Not significant: “Convenience, Digital Banking innovation, trust”
Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019)	Significant: “reliability, privacy and security”
Yoon (2010)	Significant on customer satisfaction: “design, speed, security, information content, and customer support service” Not significant: “ease of use”

Table 2. 1 Key DBSQ dimensions (Source: Author)

2.8. Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

As Anderson and Srinivasan (2003) defined, e-customer loyalty refers to the propensity of users to “continue using the specific website, frequently visit it, and show high site adhesion with high detention time”. Hence, adapted and modified from Amin (2016) in a similar internet banking context, in this study, customer loyalty referred to customers’ intention to revisit Digital Banking channels in the future.

The existing literature of banking and e-commerce setting verifies the positive association between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty has been supported by empirical evidence

from various studies (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Mbama et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2017; Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017; Amin, 2016; Ramseook-Munhurrun and Naidoo, 2011; Kassim and Asiah Abdullah, 2010; Casalo' et al., 2008; Caruana, 2002; Zeithaml, Berry and Parasuraman, 1996). For example, investigating the e-commerce context of Malaysian and Qatari using SEM analysis, Kassim & Abdullah (2010) verified that both customer satisfaction and trust are strong predictors of customer loyalty. Besides, Amin (2016) performed research to scrutinise the service quality of internet banking and its importance on e-customer satisfaction and e-customer loyalty from customer perspectives and demonstrated the relationship between internet banking service quality and e-customer satisfaction and e-customer loyalty are significant. Innovatively, Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) also performed a study to link e-banking dimensions directly with customer loyalty but employed mediation and moderation variables. The research collected 1,028 survey responses from Indian e-banking users and utilised SEM to test the hypotheses (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019a). The findings showed that of the four proposed e-banking service quality dimensions, only “reliability” and “privacy and security” have a significant impact on customer loyalty. The results also showed that the initial trust in e-banking mediates the effects of e-banking factors on customer loyalty except for “website design” (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019a).

Simultaneously, besides customer satisfaction, there is a growing academic interest in researching the impact of trust on customer loyalty in the context of e-service quality and Digital Banking. Trust has been proved to significantly and positively affect customer loyalty (both in a direct relationship or indirect relationship via customer satisfaction) by numerous researchers (Ball et al., 2004; Geebren et al., 2021). For example, Geebren et al. (2021) performed a study about mobile banking and Customer Satisfaction in Lybia with the focus on the mediating impact of Trust. The study successfully collected 659 Lybian banking customers online survey mostly distributed on Facebook banking communities. In terms of data analysis,

the research employed using structural equation modelling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM). The results revealed Trust has a significant positive impact on Customer Satisfaction and also Trust also has significant mediation effect between service quality and Customer Satisfaction (Geebren, Jabbar and Luo, 2021).

2.9. Theories and models utilised.

Figure 2.1 SERVQUAL Model (Source: Parasuraman, 1988)

Figure 2.1 describe the SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman (1988), which measures the gap between customer expectations and experiences in order to reveal the perceived service quality (Parasuraman et al.,1988). In details, for each dimension “tangibles, reliability, responsibility, assurance, and empathy”, respondents will be asked about their expectations “Expected Service” of an ideal service and their perceptions of the service they actually received “Perceived Service” base on the perceptions of their experience (Parasuraman et al.,1988). The SERVQUAL model proposes difference between expectations and perceptions represents the level of “Perceived service quality” (Parasuraman et al.,1988). If perceptions fall short of expectations, the perceived quality is low. If perceptions meet or exceed expectations, the perceived quality is high (Parasuraman et al.,1988). The SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman

(1988) can be seen as the most classic in research service quality model that has been popular and frequently adopted in research about service quality and customer satisfaction. This model was developed on the initial foundation of 10 service quality dimensions also proposed by the same author Parasuraman et al. (1985). Until now, the SERVQUAL model developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) is evaluated as the most widely known service quality measurement instrument, which consists of 22 items assessing five key service quality dimensions: “tangibles, reliability, responsibility, assurance, and empathy” (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Jun & Palacios, 2015). Further stated in his research, Parasuraman et al. (1988) also pointed out that “reliability” is the most critical dimension, followed by “assurance”.

Numerous scholars have been conducted research based on SERVQUAL dimensions with some modifications. While these five dimensions are well accepted to explain service quality in general, however, it has been criticised by a number of researchers for its adaption in the e-service setting. For example, Cox and Dale (2001), Sahadev & Purani (2008) and Herington and Weaven (2009) claimed that conceptual framework developed by Parasuraman et al. (1985, 2005) were established to measure service quality in generic service delivery contexts or offline banking contexts and hence might not accomplish the same validity level in Digital Banking context. Herington and Weaven, 2009 pointed out that the SERVQUAL model still has limitations when there are no elements related to the interface or the risks associated with manipulation on the Internet. Therefore, the SERVQUAL model is only for reference and needs to add other factors to suit the specific research context.

Responding to the requirement of measuring service quality in the context of online businesses, Zeithaml et al. (2001) proposed E-SERVQUAL model, recognising twelve factors: “access; ease of navigation; efficiency; flexibility; reliability; customisation/personalisation; security/privacy; responsiveness; assurance/trust; site aesthetics; and price knowledge”.

Subsequently, Parasuraman et al. (2005) proposed two models E-S-QUAL and E-RecS-QUAL with the purpose of measuring electronic service quality on the websites. Firstly, E-S-QUAL consists of 22 items that assess four dimensions (instead of five as in the SERVQUAL model): “efficiency, fulfilment, system availability, and privacy”. E-RecS-QUAL only uses for examining when customers are experiencing recovery services and evaluates three service quality dimensions “responsiveness, compensation, and contact”. Moreover, Parasuraman et al. (2005) have acknowledged “efficiency” and “fulfilment” being the most critical factors of E-S-QUAL, which is different compared with two strongest drivers: “reliability” and “assurance” in the previous traditional SERVQUAL Parasuraman et al. (1988).

These two models ES-QUAL and E-RecS- QUAL models of Parasuraman et al. (2005) have been widely recognised and employed for research in the context of banking and online service industries by numerous scholars (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, although these models significantly contributed to providing knowledge about service quality dimensions in the e-commerce setting, their research approach is rather too general in scope and is mainly based on online service encounters, as criticised by Jun & Palacios (2015).

Additionally, also developing from SERVQUAL’s foundation of Parasuraman (1988), Bauer et al. (2006) established the eTransQual model, a transaction process-based scale for measuring service quality. This model consists of five dimensions “functionality/design”, “enjoyment”, “process” “reliability” and “responsiveness” (Bauer et al., 2006).

Furthermore, seeking to provide an understanding of the quality dimensions on satisfaction and the success of information systems, Delone & McLean (2003) developed an information system success model namely D&M IS Success Model consisting of 6 factors of “system quality”, “Information Quality”, “Use” “Use Satisfaction”, Individual Impact”, “Organisational Impact”. This model was initially established grounded on the mathematical

theory of communication by Shannon & Warren (1949) and the view on the effectiveness of information systems by Mason (1978). The model of DeLone & McLean (2003) has also been employed in studies investigating customer satisfaction and Digital Banking services. For example, numerous scholars such as Tam & Oliveira (2016) or Baabdullah et al. (2019) about Saudi Arabia banking sector and Geebren et al.(2021) about Lybia’s mobile banking context has employed DeLone & McLean (2003) model in exploring mobile banking service quality and customer satisfaction. It is also important to note that Baabdullah et al. (2019) combined two models, which are UTAUT2 and the D&M IS Success Model by DeLone & McLean (2003), to develop their conceptual framework conducted research to investigate the mobile banking customer satisfaction in Saudi Arabia.

Figure 2. 2 DeLone & McLean IS Success Model (DeLone & McLean, 2003)

However, even in the presence of vast criticism, the capability to measure service quality through the SERVQUAL model cannot be denied (Raza, Jawaid and Hassan, 2015). Numerous studies have used this model to strengthen the value to the SERVQUAL literature.

2.10. Data collection and analysis methods

Based on the extensive literature review, much of the previous research considered Digital Banking Service Quality related to customer satisfaction and customer loyalty from the customer perspective and adopted quantitative study (Amin, 2016). As for the quantitative analysis method, most studies used quantitative analysis techniques such as Reliability testing, convergence, and discriminant testing before going into Structural equation modeling (SEM) or regression to test the assumptions that statement theory associated with the research model. For example, Geebren et al. (2021) performed a study about mobile banking and customer satisfaction. Using structural equation modeling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM) to analyse data collected from 659 Lybian banking customers survey responses, the results revealed mobile banking service quality has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. There is less research examining perceptions of bank managerial roles with a qualitative approach, for example Larsson & Viitaoja (2017) to examine key challenges in using digital banking services as a means of enhancing customer loyalty in the context of Swedish banks. Fewer researches attempt to examine Digital Banking from different perspectives and adopt a mixed-method approach, such as investigating the association between Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction from UK banking customers and banking employees by Mbama and Ezepue (2018). This knowledge gap founded by the researcher proves a need to conduct this current study inspecting Digital Banking and its importance on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty from different perspectives with a mixed-method research design to provide a more comprehensive finding.

Table 2.2 shows examples of Data collection and analysis methods in extant literature:

Data collection	Data analysis	Participants	Supporting Literature
Online survey	PLS-SEM	659 Lybian banking customers	Geebren et al. (2021)
Survey	SEM	1,028 Indian e-banking users	Shankar & barajakirthy (2019)

Semi-structured interviews, survey questionnaire	“Shapley Value Regression Analysis”	Italian bank customers.	Filotto et al. (2021)
Semi-structured in-depth interviews, Open-ended questions	Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis	10 managers representing different Swedish banks	Larsson & Viitaoja (2017)
Customers Survey, Bank manager	SEM	206 usable questionnaires, 10 manager interviews	Mbama and Ezepe (2018)

Table 2. 2 Data collection and analysis methods (Source: Author)

2.11. Digital Banking Research in Vietnam context.

2.11.1. Digital Banking Adoption Research in Vietnam

The extensive literature review of Digital Banking in Vietnam revealed limited studies had been performed in Vietnam about Digital Banking in general, both adoption and actual usage experience, satisfaction, loyalty. However, of these limited sources, the research in Vietnam has predominantly been restricted to the issues of Digital Banking adoption intention/factors influencing the intention to adopt Digital Banking in Vietnam. Summaries of recent research conducted about Digital Banking adoption in Vietnam are presented below.

In terms of online banking, Chong et al. (2010) conducted a study investigating the antecedents of online banking adoption in Vietnam. By collecting 103 valid survey responses and using correlation and multiple regression for hypotheses testing, the author verified the key factors driving online banking adoption in Vietnam are "perceived usefulness", "trust", and "government support".

In contrast, "perceived ease of use" has no relationship with adoption intention. Conversely, Pham et al. (2013) revealed different findings regarding "ease of use". This study investigated factors influencing the adoption of e-banking and found that "perceived ease of use", "trust", and "perceived benefit" has a significant impact on e-banking adoption.

Besides, in terms of mobile banking adoption in Vietnam, a quantitative study of 220 Vietnamese participants and SEM analysis by Nguyen et al. (2019) indicated that “Ease of Use”, “Perceived Usefulness”, “Trust”, and “Perceived costs” are key factors driving mobile banking adoption in Vietnam.

Also using a quantitative study for the same research aims, however, Trinh, Le and Nguyen (2020) proposed a research model based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2) model and collected a more considerable number of responses (540 valid responses). The findings showed that "Security awareness", "Trust", "Hedonic motivation" and "Social Influence" exert the strongest influence on mobile banking adoption intention while "Facilitating condition" is not relevant.

In terms of internet banking adoption, Nguyen and Huynh (2021) conducted a mixed-method study by implementing a focus group with 12 customers and 475 survey interviews with Vietnam banking users to determine the key drivers of internet banking adoption. The study used Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis, CFA for testing the scale and SEM analysis for testing the hypotheses. The result showed crucial determinants of internet banking adoption in Vietnam are: "perceived usefulness", "attitude", "perceived risk", "innate innovativeness", "domain-specific innovativeness", and "internet experience". However, one of the limitations of this study is it exploited the sampling technique of direct and email interview methods. However, one of the limitations of this research is that it was conducted in a specific region (Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam), limiting the generalisability of the findings.

In terms of Digital Banking adoption, Thu Nguyen et al. (2020) conducted a study using the Modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2) and concluded that "performance expectancy", "effort expectancy", "hedonic motivation", "habit", and "trust" have a significant influence on the intention of using Digital Banking in Vietnam context. Nguyen (2020) conducted a study using multivariate data analysis techniques (Cronbach's

Alpha test, CFA, SEM) for a survey of 201 Digital Banking customers and concluded that "perceived usefulness" and "ease of use" are key drivers of Digital Banking adoption while "trust" is not.

2.11.2. Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction Research in Vietnam

In terms of the Vietnam banking context, few studies attempted to examine the relationship between Digital Banking and customer satisfaction.

For example, Duong (2015) conducted a quantitative study investigating the relationship between internet banking dimensions and customer satisfaction with 205 survey responses from Vietnamese internet banking users. Using Regression analysis to test the hypotheses, the study concluded that "service quality", "perceived value," and "Brand reputation" are all significant antecedents of customer satisfaction in the Vietnam Internet banking context.

Addressing the same research questions, Hsu and Nguyen (2016) performed a quantitative study and obtained 293 completed survey questionnaires by interviews through social media. Employing Regression analysis for data analysis and hypotheses test, the results indicated that "reliability", "fulfilment", "efficiency", and "website design" exert a strong impact on customer satisfaction, which, then, significantly affect customer loyalty (Hsu and Nguyen, 2016).

In the broader context- retail banking in Vietnam, Vu, Nguyen and Huu (2016) performed a quantitative research with 261 survey responses and used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the structural equation modelling technique (SME) to test hypotheses. The result showed that service quality and customer satisfaction are essential antecedents of customer loyalty and customer satisfaction mediates the effects of service quality on customer loyalty. However, one of the limitations of this study is the proposed conceptual model is too direct with three factors: "service quality", "satisfaction," and "loyalty" without specific dimensions used for service quality.

Apart from this research, the researcher can only find the same research topic but in a different research context. For example, Dam and Bui (2019) conducted an empirical study with 358 survey customers responses to examine the service quality and customer satisfaction in the context of the convenience stores in Vietnam. The study utilised the partial least squared structure equation modelling (PLS-SEM) for data analysis and hypotheses testing (Dam and Bui, 2019). The result showed that service quality has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction.

Addressing the same research questions but in a different context of life-insurance services in Vietnam, Nguyen et al. (2018) performed a study with 1476 survey responses and path analysis techniques and concluded that "corporate image", "service quality", and "perceived value" exert a substantial impact on customer satisfaction.

2.12. Emphasise the literature gap

2.12.1. Literature gap in worldwide research

After conducting an extensive literature review about Digital Banking in the broader context of worldwide research, the researcher finds out some literature gaps that call for the needs of future research.

Firstly, in terms of the research problem/research topic, Aboobucker & Bao (2018) and Rotchanakitumnuai (2003) criticised that existing literature focused predominantly on Digital Banking adoption rather than actual usage and customer experience. Sharing the same viewpoint, as criticised by Mbama and Ezepue (2018), research into different forms of Digital Banking services (mobile banking, internet banking, online banking, Digital Banking) has been conducted intensively globally. However, most of the research have been focusing on the adoption intention of Digital Banking services and less emphasises has been put on users' experience and satisfaction (Trinh et al., 2020; Boateng et al., 2016; Martins et al., 2014; Chong

et al., 2010), which might not accomplish the current banking marketing needs with increasingly emphasise on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Moreover, in terms of the Digital Banking types/forms, as criticised by Mbama and Ezepue (2018), existing research on Digital Banking is fragmented with authors investigating individual channels (e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking) or focusing attention on only a few variables, revealing that different factors need to be explored. Hence, the focus of future research should be shifted to Digital Banking. This gap also proves a necessity of conducting studies investigating the influence of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction with more factors employed in the research model.

Furthermore, in terms of research context, after conducting an extensive literature review about Digital Banking and related themes, the researcher agreed with Amin (2016) and Aboobucker & Bao (2018) that prior studies on banking service quality primarily conducted in the context of developed countries such as Europe and North America while little attention has been paid in developing countries such as Vietnam. As suggested by Karatepe et al. (2005), the difference in culture might alter these research findings when applied to other developing countries such as Vietnam– where this current research is conducted. Previous researchers emphasised the necessity of future research examining Digital Banking acceptance and its relationship with customer satisfaction in other context or different countries (Kassim & Abdullah, 2010; Martins et al., 2014; Aboobucker & Bao, 2018). According to Khan, Hameed, and Khan (2017), Digital banking services have been gaining significant popularity and developments in Asian countries recently. Customers in these countries are more likely to adopt Digital Banking. Meanwhile, current Digital Banking studies predominantly focus on investigating the context of developed countries, and limited attention has been paid to developing countries. Therefore, this gap calls for a necessity to conduct Digital Banking research for developing countries, such as Vietnam.

Nevertheless, in general, limited attention has been paid to adopting different mediating and moderating variables such as “electronic word of mouth”, “brand” loyalty” (Ahmed *et al.*, 2017), which proves a research gap that needs to be accomplished.

In short, there are few limitations of the extant literature in Digital Banking research in the global context: focusing on adoption rather than customer satisfaction, investigating different forms Digital Banking (online banking/internet banking/mobile banking) rather than a broader definition of Digital Banking, conducting in developed countries rather than developing countries. Again, these gaps support the importance of achieving this present research.

2.12.2. Literature gap in Vietnam research.

This gap proves a need to conduct research exploring the importance of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on Customer Satisfaction, especially in the context of emerging countries like Vietnam.

Firstly, in terms of the research problem/research topic, existing literature in Vietnam also suffered from the same limitations as in the global research, which focuses predominantly on Digital Banking adoption rather than actual usage and customer experience.

Research Methodology employed in research is another gap the researcher found in the Digital Banking literature in the Vietnam context. Based on the discussions above of Digital Banking literature in Vietnam, most of the recent studies focus on investigating the Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions only from customers' perspectives, using Survey Questionnaires as a main data collection method and Regression as the primary data analysis technique to test hypotheses. Therefore, this thesis will fill in this gap by examining the topic from different stakeholders' perceptions by employing a mixed-method study with a survey for customers, interviews for bank managers, and secondary data for other stakeholders' groups.

2.12.3. Emphasising the overall gap

Even though the extant literature is rich with research about Digital Banking adoption, quality dimensions, satisfaction, loyalty..., they primarily address it in a western context and not in Vietnam (Mbama & Ezepue, 2018). To the best of the researcher' knowledge, in spite of the intensifying debate in the current global literature, an inadequate effort has been made in exploring Digital Banking in Vietnam, especially in evaluating the association between Digital Banking Service Quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The predominant focus on the adoption intention of online banking/internet banking/mobile banking has been performed in Vietnam, but not the actual adoption or customer experience, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty. Research Methodology employed in research is another gap the researcher found in the Digital Banking literature in the Vietnam context, with most of the recent studies focusing on Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions only from customers' perspectives, using Survey Questionnaires as a main data collection method and Regression as the primary data analysis technique to test hypotheses. Therefore, this thesis will fill in this gap by examining the topic from different stakeholders' perceptions by employing a mixed-method study with a survey for customers, interviews for bank managers and secondary data for other stakeholders' groups.

In short, current scientific knowledge on the impact of Digital Banking Service Quality on customer experience, satisfaction, and loyalty in the Vietnam Digital Banking context is scarce. This gap provides the impetus for investigating the effects of Digital Banking Service Quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in emerging markets such as Vietnam from different stakeholders' perspectives by using a mixed-method research design. Accordingly, the main objectives of this research are to determine the critical Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the Vietnam context, using

a Vietnam commercial bank as an example. The study will also investigate different stakeholders' perceptions about current Digital Banking in Vietnam.

An extensive literature review on Digital Banking and related themes both worldwide and in Vietnam revealed a critical yet unstudied research gap that demands a comprehensive examination of the Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and their importance on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty from different perspectives, which again support the importance of conducting this present research. It is significant to identify which Digital Banking Service Quality factors have the most positive effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Vietnam Digital Banking context. To the researcher's knowledge, no similar research has been performed before in the Vietnam context. Therefore, the implications of this study are in the hope of developing a significant contribution to the new knowledge.

2.13. Summary

This chapter provided an extensive critical review of the relevant literature of Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in bank marketing research in the context of both worldwide and in Vietnam, which revealed an essential yet unanswered research gap that needs to fill in. To address this research gap, this research investigate the role and extent of Digital Banking on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in the Vietnam Banking Sector, using the studied bank as a case in point. The next chapter will continue the literature review on the selected Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions as the theoretical foundation for developing research model and hypotheses for this current research.

CHAPTER THREE: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Introduction

This Chapter extensively and critically explores the major attributes of the Digital Banking service quality predominantly evaluated in extant literature. Based on the findings, the researcher develops a conceptual framework and hypotheses in order to achieve the outlined research objectives in Chapter 1. The rationale for identifying the Independent and Dependent Variables, along with the development of the proposed hypotheses, has been thoroughly expounded upon. The theoretical underpinnings for the selection of the proposed conceptual framework have been articulated, along with the justifications for its development and the distinctions that set this framework apart.

3.2. Variables identification

Based on previous studies on Digital Banking, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty conducted in Chapter 2, this study selected 12 dimensions that are likely to be the most appropriate for Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting Customer Satisfaction, namely: Services portfolio/ Products, Ease of Use, Convenience, Usefulness, Privacy and Security, Speed, Reliability, Customer Service and Support, Digital-Emotional Connection, Trust, Covid-19 Risk Perception.

Accordingly, independent variables were set as Services portfolio/ Products, Ease of Use, Convenience, Usefulness, Privacy and Security, Speed, Reliability, Customer Service and Support, Digital-Emotional Connection, Trust, Covid-19 Risk Perceptions in relations with its dependent variable Customer Satisfaction. Whereas, Customer satisfaction and Trust were set

as independent variables in relations with its dependent variable customer loyalty. **Table 3. 1 presents the Independent/ Dependent Variables**

Variables	Type	Direct effect
Services portfolio/ Products	Independent	SPP → SAT
Ease of use	Independent	EOU → SAT
Convenience	Independent	CON → SAT
Usefulness	Independent	UFN → SAT
Reliability	Independent	REL → SAT
Privacy & Security	Independent	PRS → SAT
Speed	Independent	SPD → SAT
Design	Independent	DSG → SAT
Customer Service and Support	Independent	CSS → SAT
Digital-Emotional Connection	Independent	DEC → SAT
Trust	Independent	TRU → SAT
Covid-19 Risk Perception	Independent	COV → SAT
Customer Satisfaction	Independent/ Dependent	SAT → LOY
Trust	Independent	TRU → LOY
Customer Loyalty	Dependent	LOY ← SAT LOY ← TRU

Table 3. 2 Independent/ Dependent Variables (Source: Author)

Definitions and supporting literature evidence are presented in the following section, setting the foundation for the hypotheses.

3.2.1. Services portfolio/ Products

Services portfolio/ Products are adapted from the dimension “Banking service product quality” (refers to product variety/various features) gleaned from prior research of Jun and Cai (2001) investigating USA Internet banking. The findings confirmed that among a total of 17 dimensions utilised, Banking service product quality has a significant influence on Customer Satisfaction (Jun and Cai, 2001). Research outcomes from Ayo et al. (2016) investigating the Nigeria e-banking context also revealed “Service portfolio” as one of the most significant

predictors of e- banking service quality. For digital banking users, regarding the Services portfolio/ Products, they concern with the Digital Banking services range, its consistency overall Digital Banking channels (web/app), Digital Banking fees, and charges, which can have an impact on Customer Satisfaction of using Digital Banking.

3.2.2. Ease of Use

According to Davis (1989) in TAM model, “perceived ease of use is the degree to which the prospective adopter expects the new technology adopted to be a free effort regarding its transfer and utilisation”. The measure of Ease of Use consists of functionality, accessibility of flow of information, and the ease of ordering and navigating (Reibstein, 2002). The dimension of Ease of Use is a significantly crucial component of “customer usage of computer technologies” (Ribbink et al., 2004), and it is particularly important for new customers (Gefen and Straub, 2000). As adapted to banking context by Jun and Palacios (2015), Ease of Use refers to the extent to which a banking app is considered as easy to understand and operate by users. In digital banking context, Ease of Use refers to the ease of access and navigation in which the Digital Banking channels contains functions enabling banking users navigate what they need and allows them to perform the transactions easily and quickly across the channels as adapted from Hussien and El Aziz (2013), hence leading to Customer Satisfaction (Gummerus et al., 2004).

3.2.3. Convenience

Convenience is a crucial aspect because it is defined by the time and effort spent by consumers, (Laforet and Li, 2005). Garg et al. (2014) in India, Mbama and Ezepue (2018) in the UK, and Shin et al. (2020) in South Korea are a few research that found that convenience dictated Customer Experience in banking. In the digital banking context, convenience is the ability to

quickly access and use the banking services from any location at any time (Chen, Hsu, & Lin, 2010), easily manage my bank account and perform cashless payment (Amin,2016).

3.2.4. Usefulness

According to TAM model, Usefulness is “the potential user’s subjective probability that using a particular system will enhance job performance in an organisational context” (Davis et al., 1989). As adapted to online banking context Rao et al. (2003), banking users will accept the system if they trust the system will offer them benefits for example saving time and improving efficiency compared to conventional banking (Rao et al., 2003). In the context of digital banking, Usefulness refers to the extent to which the digital banking users believe that digital banking offer them more benefits when compared to conventional banking such as allowing them to access to a wide range of financial services, saving time and cost.

3.2.5. Reliability

As defined by Parasuraman et al. (2005), reliability refers to “the ability of the service provider to perform the promised services accurately and consistently”. The banks are renowned for their dependability and consistency in completing banking duties, according to Singh and Kaur (2013). In the digital banking context, a common concern is that whether digital banking transactions offered by the banks are timely and accurate (Kim et al., 2009). The bank’s digital banking platforms must be dependable, trustworthy, and secure because digital banking necessitates the interchange of private and personal data, according to Cheng and Chan (2009). Existing literature suggest a positive and significant relationship between reliability and Digital Banking Customer Satisfaction (Raza et al., 2020; Hammoud et al., 2018; Shankar & Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Liao & Cheung, 2002). Therefore, Reliability is perceived as a significant factor in this study to analyse the impact of Digital banking service quality on customer satisfaction.

3.2.6. Privacy and Security

“Privacy and Security” can be defined as “the degree to which customers believe that the site is safe from intrusion and that personal information shared over the platform is protected” (Hussien and El Aziz, 2013). This dimension relates to security of online transactions, customers’ beliefs in online system, and privacy of personal information (Ribbink et al., 2004). Privacy and Security are major concerns for the settings of e-commerce (Wang et al., 2003) and e-banking services (Shankar and Kumari, 2016). In the context of digital banking, Customers will be more likely to be satisfied and loyal with the services if the banks guarantee the security of all digital banking channels for finalising financial transactions and ensure the privacy of customers' personal information communicated via the platform (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019).

3.2.7. Speed

Speed (often referred to transaction speed or response time) has received attention in the context of information systems and e-commerce due to an increase in focus on the efficiency of operational resources. Due to the increased emphasis on optimising operational resources, the effectiveness of transaction processing time, also known as “Speed” or “Transaction Speed” or “Response time”, has become a crucial factor in the worlds of information technology and e-commerce. Speed is considered as a time-saving feature and an crucial predictor for customer satisfaction with self-service technologies (Liao and Cheung, 2002; Yoon (2010). Speed is concerned with how fast a mobile application is loaded, updated, and processed, as well as with the availability of timely and up-to-date information displayed on the application. In this study, Speed is referred to the connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...); the page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels; the transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels.

3.2.8. Design

In the general banking context, Design can be regarded as site organisation as in an internet banking study by Raza et al. (2020) and Amin (2016), or website design in internet banking study by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019), which all confirmed that website design has a positive influence on customers' satisfaction. This study examines Digital Banking channels, including (website/app). Therefore, it adapted "website design" from the literature review and modified it to "design" to suit the context of Digital Banking channels (website/app).

3.2.9. Customer Service and Support

Blut et al. (2015) defined Customer Service and Support as services offered to customers to satisfy their wants and needs and bring about responses to their complaints. This dimension evaluates a company's capability and willingness to supply immediate customer support when clients encounter difficulties (Zeithaml et al., 2002). If a company can understand its customers' requirements and develop its service based on customers' feedback, it can improve Customer Satisfaction and Trust (Gummerus et al., 2004). In the digital banking context, Customer Service and Support refers to the empathy of the digital banking customer care team, ease of access to the support services and the bank's commitment to resolve customer issues, (Shankar & Jebarajakirthy, 2019). Similarly, Customer Service and Support dimension as in this study (or can be regarded as Responsiveness in other studies such as Yoon (2010) intends to focus on the professional care and prompt support from banking advisors given to customers when they encounter any Digital Banking services problems.

3.2.10. Digital-Emotional Connection

Digital – Emotional Connection is adapted from KPMG International (2020) and Deloitte (2018). As defined by KPMG International (2020) and Deloitte (2018), Digital – Emotional Connection measures the ability of a digital banking service providers to appeal to clients' emotions, provide a pleasurable and delightful banking experience, and hence raise customer

satisfaction. Customers develop an emotional bond with a brand when they associate it with their core beliefs, objectives, and motivations (The Financial Brand, 2017). Customers are complicated people with high expectations. Relationships with brands and service providers are changing as never before as a result of this complexity (Deloitte Digital, 2019). One of the biggest, most significant opportunities for banks moving forward is the capacity to use emotionally intelligent platforms to recognise and use emotional data at scale (Deloitte Digital, 2019).

3.2.11. Trust

As defined by Garbarino and Johnson (1999), Trust refers to “customer confidence in the quality and reliability of the services offered” . Rousseau et al. (1998) defined Trust as “a psychological state composing the intention to accept vulnerability based on expectations of the intentions or behaviour of another”. As pointed out by Wu et al. (2018), Trust refers to “a belief, confidence, sentiment, or expectation about buyer intention”. In the service industry context, trust relates to customers’ expectations and beliefs that their service provider will carry out actions as promised (Marinkovic and Obradovic,2015). In the case of Digital Banking, consumers are primarily concerned about the confidentiality and Security of their data stored on their respective devices (Yoon, 2010).

In the banking context, it has been shown that if customers have the feeling of trust in the banks in general and the digital banking services offered, they are more likely to be satisfied with the bank (Marinkovic and Obradovic,2015; Levy and Hino, 2016).

3.2.12. Covid-19 Risk Perceptions

This research is an initial attempt to incorporate Covid-19 Risk Perceptions as a dimension of Digital Banking Service Quality and as an independent variable in the conceptual framework with potential impact on dependant variable Customer Satisfaction. The study attempts to

explore the impacts of the Covid-19 Risk Perceptions on the Digital Banking Customer Satisfaction in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks. The justification for this inclusion is that Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the Digital Banking adoption globally, and Vietnam is not an exception (KPMG International, 2020). During the national lockdown from the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic in January 2020 when no alternate modes of payment were available, customers' Risk Perceptions of the pandemic had the potential to affect their Digital Banking adoption, usage, then they may have had different experiences with Digital Banking affecting their level of satisfaction. This decision also aligns with the existing literature, which suggests that service quality is a dimensional construct.

3.2.13. Customer Satisfaction

This research aims to understand to what extent the quality of Digital Banking services provided by the studied bank would affect its level of customer satisfaction. According to Geebren et al. (2021), there exists evidence that Satisfaction has been widely accepted as a significant factor determining the continuous usage and accomplishment in the context of information systems and e-commerce contexts. There is no consensus in the extant literature with regards to the definition of customer satisfaction. As defined by Oliver (1981), satisfaction is “an emotional post consumption evaluative judgment concerning a product or service”. Similarly, customer satisfaction refers to “consumer response to the evaluation of the perceived difference between expectations and the final result after consumption” as proposed by Tse & Wilton (1988). Hammoud et al. (2018) defined customer satisfaction as “the comparison of post product/service performance with pre-formed expectations”. In this present study, customer satisfaction will be regarded as the level of satisfaction of customers when using different types of general Digital Banking services (e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking, online banking, Digital Banking).

3.2.14. Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty occurs when a customer acquires a favourable attitude towards a bank over some time (Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017). E-customers' loyalty refers to the intentions of users to stick with existing particular websites, regularly access to it, and demonstrate "high site adhesion with high detention time" (Anderson and Srinivasan, 2003). Customer loyalty is the consequence of Customer Experience in online banking in India (Khan et al., 2016). Hence, in this Digital Banking research, adapted as well as modified from Amin (2016) and (Caruana, 2002) in a similar internet banking context, customer loyalty refers to customers' tendency to "reassess the Digital Banking channels and contemplate a repurchase of a favoured product and service constantly in the future".

3.3. Hypotheses

Continuing from Chapter 2, this part aims to present the rationale for the hypotheses development by extensively and critically reviewing the extant literature on the dimensions of Digital Banking service quality that might significantly present a positive correlation with customers' satisfaction and loyalty. Subsequently, the research presents the selected dimensions and proposed hypotheses.

3.3.1. Services portfolio/ Products - Customer Satisfaction

Services portfolio/ Products are adapted from the dimension "Banking service product quality" (refers to product variety/various features) gleaned from prior research of Jun and Cai (2001) investigating USA Internet banking. The findings confirmed that among a total of 17 dimensions utilised, Banking service product quality has a significant influence on Customer Satisfaction (Jun and Cai, 2001). In the Digital Banking context of this study, Services portfolio/ Products concerned with the Digital Banking services range, its consistency overall Digital Banking channels (web/app), Digital Banking fees, and charges can have an impact on

Customer Satisfaction of using Digital Banking. However, there is barely any attention to this factor in the extant literature. Especially, based on the researcher's knowledge and observations, attention has not been paid to it in the Vietnamese Digital Banking context. Therefore, the research comes up with the following exploratory hypothesis linking Services portfolio/ Products and customers' satisfaction:

“H1: There is a positive relationship between “Services portfolio/ Products” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.2. Ease of use - Customer Satisfaction

Ease of use regarding customer's cognizance of a specific system is effortless, simple and easy to use (Davis, 1989; Taylor and Todd, 1995). As Jun and Palacios (2015) defined, Ease of use refers to the extent to which a banking app is considered as easy to understand and operate by consumers. The measure of Ease of Use consists of functionality, accessibility of flow of information, and the ease of ordering and navigating (Reibstein, 2002). The dimension of Ease of Use is a significantly crucial component of “customer usage of computer technologies” (Ribbink et al., 2004), and it is particularly important for new customers (Gefen and Straub, 2000). In this study, we refer to Ease of use as the ease of access to Digital Banking applications and transactions. Ease of Use also displays the service provider's capability and hence lead to Trust (Gummerus et al., 2004).

In a prior research by Yoon (2010) investigating China online banking in 2010, the author argued that Ease of Use does not present a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction (Yoon, 2010). However, existing literature on Digital Banking predominantly demonstrates that Ease of use is a strong predictor of customers' satisfaction. There is a positive correlation between Ease of use and customer satisfaction, for example, in the e-commerce setting (Devaraj et al.,

2002; Castaneda et al. 2007; Kassim and Abdullah, 2010) or in the banking sector: Pakistan internet banking (Raza *et al.*, 2020), Lebanese banking industry (Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba, 2018) or USA mobile banking (Jun and Palacios, 2016). Thus, this contradiction proves a need to examine the relation between Ease of use and customers' satisfaction in Vietnamese Digital Banking context, leading to the formation of the following exploratory hypothesis:

“H2: There is a positive relationship between “Ease of Use” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.3. Convenience - Customer Satisfaction

The existing literature indicates that there is a positive relationship between Convenience and Customer Satisfaction such as Arbore & Busacca (2009) and Jun & Palacios (2016). . An example could be observed in the US mobile banking sector (Jun and Palacios, 2016). However, Keisidou et al. (2013) investigated the Greek banking sector and came to the conclusion that Convenience has no influence on customer satisfaction, which contradicts the findings of Arbore & Busacca (2009) and Jun & Palacios (2016).

The research, therefore, frames the following “exploratory hypothesis” associating Convenience with customers' satisfaction:

“H3: There is a positive relationship between “Convenience” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.4. Usefulness - Customer Satisfaction

According to TAM model, Usefulness is “the potential user’s subjective probability that using a particular system will enhance job performance in an organisational context” (Davis et al.,

1989). Numerous research projects indicate that perceived usefulness has a decisive influence on customers' satisfaction (Zhou and Lu, 2011; Wu, 2013). This statement is then investigated by applying it to the Digital Banking experience; hence, it is hypothesised that:

“H4: There is a positive relationship between “Usefulness” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam”

3.3.5. Reliability - Customer Satisfaction

The existing literature indicates that there is a positive relationship between Reliability and customers' satisfaction; examples could be observed in the case of Pakistan internet banking sector (Raza *et al.*, 2020), Lebanese banking industry (Hammoud *et al.*, 2018) and e-banking (Shankar & Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Liao & Cheung, 2002). Particularly, Liao & Cheung (2002) considered “Reliability” as of the highest importance in terms of features that users look for to evaluate the quality of E-Banking service. Similarly, investigating Lebanese banking industry study, Hammoud *et al.* (2018) indicated six strong determinants of customers' satisfaction: “Reliability”, “Efficiency”, “Ease Of Use”, “Responsiveness”, “Communication” and “Security And Privacy”, in which “reliability” is the dimension that provides the most significant effect.

However, there is barely any studies carried out regarding Reliability as a measure of Digital Banking Service Quality in the Vietnamese Banking Sector, which sets up the following hypothesis:

“H5: There is a positive relationship between “Reliability” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.6. Privacy and Security - Customer Satisfaction

As pointed out by Wang et al. (2003) in a research about Internet Banking, Customers' perceptions of "Security and Privacy" can affect the adoption intention of online services but do not influence customers' satisfaction and loyalty. However, the existing literature indicates that there is a positive relationship between "Security" and Customer Satisfaction, for example, in China online banking sector (Yoon, 2010), in the USA mobile banking industry (Jun and Palacios, 2016), or other research such as Rita et al. (2019). Similarly, "Perceived Risk" is confirmed to influence customer satisfaction significantly, as stated in further research related to banking (Mbama et al., 2018; Hussien & El Aziz, 2013; Mssartins, Oliveira and Popovič, 2014).

Thus, the following hypothesis is formed:

"H6: There is a positive relationship between "Privacy and Security" and Digital Banking "Customer Satisfaction" in Vietnam."

3.3.7. Speed- Customer Satisfaction

The existing literature revealed that "Speed" has a positive influence on users' satisfaction in utilising information systems (DeLone and McLean, 1992; Srinivasan, 1985); commercial website appraisals (Aladwani & Palvia, 2002), or in online banking context (Yoon, 2010), Jun & Palacios (2016). In developed societies, customers are inclined to be very sensitive when it comes to Speed of service delivery (Liao and Cheung, 2002). Thus, "Speed" may be an important determinant of customers' satisfaction in the case of Digital Banking. On the basis of the preceding evaluation, the following hypothesis is explored:

"H7: There is a positive relationship between "Speed" and Digital Banking "Customer Satisfaction" in Vietnam."

3.3.8. Design - Customer Satisfaction

In the general banking context, “Design” can be regarded as site organisation as in an internet banking study by Raza et al. (2020) and Amin (2016), or website design in internet banking study by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019), which all confirmed that website design has a positive influence on customers’ satisfaction. This study examines Digital Banking channels, including (website/app). Therefore, it adapted “Website Design” from the literature review and modified it to “design” to suit the context of Digital Banking channels (website/app). Hence, the “Design” of the Digital Banking channels (website/app) may also have a positive influence on users’ satisfaction, resulting in the formation of the hypothesis below:

“H8: There is a positive relationship between “Design” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.9. Customer Service and Support - Customer Satisfaction

Existing literature in the banking sector indicated a positive relationship between “Customer Service and Support” with “Customer Satisfaction” (Ahmed et al., 2017; Hsu and Nguyen, 2016; Jun and Palacios, 2015; Jun and Cai, 2001).

Thereby, “Customer Service and Support” may ring impacts to “Customer Satisfaction” in Digital Banking in the context of Vietnam digital banking, leading to the formation of the following hypothesis:

“H9: There is a positive relationship between “Customer Service and Support” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.10. Digital-Emotional Connection -Customer Satisfaction

In the banking context, empirical research of Levy and Hino (2016) was one of the few attempts specifically investigating the impact of “Emotional brand attachment” on “Customer Satisfaction”. Their findings show a significant, direct and positive relationship between the “Emotional brand attachment” and “Customer Satisfaction”. In the digital banking context, as defined by KPMG International (2020) and Deloitte (2018), Digital – Emotional Connection measures the ability of a digital banking service providers to appeal to clients' emotions, provide a pleasurable and delightful banking experience, and hence raise customer satisfaction. However, to the best of the researcher’s knowledge, there is no empirical study in the extant literature examining the direct relationship between Digital Emotional connection and Customer Satisfaction in the context of Vietnam digital banking. In this context, an emotionally satisfying bond between customers and banks may lead to the greater level of customer satisfaction, predicting that that the digital banking service providers’ emphasis on “Digital-Emotional Connection” with their customers can enhance the level of “Customer Satisfaction”. Accordingly, adapted from KPMG International (2020) and Deloitte (2018), the research proposes the formation of the following hypothesis:

“H10: There is a positive relationship between “Digital-Emotional Connection” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.11. Trust - Customer Satisfaction

The existing literature indicates a positive relationship between Trust and customers’ satisfaction (Jadil, Rana and Dwivedi, 2021; Alkhowaiter, 2020; Sharma and Sharma, 2019; Kassim and Abdullah, 2010; Ahmed et al., 2017). In the case of Digital Banking, consumers are primarily concerned about the confidentiality and Security of their data stored on their respective devices (Yoon, 2010). Therefore, it is predictable that Trust can be an essential

dimension affecting customers' satisfaction, which causes the formation of the following hypothesis:

“H11: There is a positive relationship between “Trust” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Digital Banking in Vietnam.”

3.3.12. Covid-19 Risk Perceptions- Customer Satisfaction

Based on the researcher's knowledge, Covid-19 Risk Perceptions has not been incorporated in any conceptual framework in the context of Digital Banking. This research is an initial attempt to incorporate Covid-19 Risk Perceptions as a dimension of Digital Banking Service Quality and as an independent variable in the conceptual framework with potential impact on dependant variable Customer Satisfaction. The study attempts to explore the impacts of the Covid-19 Risk Perceptions on the Digital Banking Customer Satisfaction in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks. The justification for this inclusion is that during the national lockdown from the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic in January 2020 when no alternate modes of payment were available, Covid-19 Risk Perceptions of banking customers had the potential to affect their Digital Banking adoption, usage, then they may be inclined to have different experiences with Digital Banking affecting their level of satisfaction. This decision also aligns with the existing literature, which suggests that service quality is a dimensional construct.

In essence, Covid -19 is likely to have impact on Customer Satisfaction when they have to use Digital Banking Service due to the Covid -19 restriction and their risk perceptions. As a result, in the hope of achieving innovative research outcomes, the following hypothesis can be regarded as a primary hypothesis newly developed by the researcher.

The following hypothesis is created:

“H12. There is a positive relationship between “Covid-19 risk perceptions” and Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” in Vietnam.”

3.3.13. Customer Satisfaction - Customer Loyalty

In the case of banking and e-commerce setting, the substantial positive relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty has been proved by empirical evidence from various research (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Mbama et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2017; Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017; Amin, 2016; Ramseook-Munhurrin and Naidoo, 2011; Kassim and Asiah Abdullah, 2010; Casalo' et al., 2008; Caruana, 2002; Zeithaml, Berry and Parasuraman, 1996). For example, investigating e-commerce context of Malaysian and Qatari using SEM analysis, Kassim & Abdullah (2010) verified that Customer Satisfaction along with Trust are strong predictors of Customer Loyalty. Besides, Amin (2016) performed a research to evaluate the quality of the internet banking service and its potential effects on customers' satisfaction and loyalty from customers' perspectives and demonstrated that the correlations between internet banking service quality, e-customer satisfaction and e-customer loyalty are outstanding.

Innovatively, Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) also performed a study to link e-banking dimensions directly with customer loyalty but employed mediation and moderation variables. The research collected 1,028 survey responses from Indian e-banking users and utilised SEM to test the hypotheses (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019a). The findings indicate that amongst the four proposed e-banking service quality dimensions, only “Reliability” and “Privacy and Security” have significantly influenced Customer Loyalty. The results also showed that the “initial trust in e-banking” is a bridge connecting the impacts of e-banking factors and Customer Loyalty, excluding “website design” (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019a).

The existing literature, which is quite equivalent to the case of the current research indicates that there is a positive relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty, for example, in Pakistan internet banking sector (Raza *et al.*, 2020), UK Digital Banking (Mbama *et al.* (2018), Malaysia e-banking industry (Amin, 2016), Greek banking sector (Keisidou *et al.*, 2013), Vietnam Internet banking (Hsu and Nguyen, 2016). These researches mentioned above all conclude that Customer Satisfaction can lead to Customer Loyalty. The shortage of customer loyalty studies in the case of Digital Banking as criticised by Mbama *et al.*, (2018) proves a necessity to test the relationship between “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty” in Digital Banking. Therefore, the research proposed the following hypothesis:

“H13. There is a positive relationship between Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” and Digital Banking “Customer Loyalty” in Digital Banking in Vietnam.”

3.3.14. Trust - Customer Loyalty

The extant literature which is relatively equivalent to the existing study indicates that “Trust” has a significant influence on “Customer Loyalty”. Grembler and Brown (1996) considered “Trust” as a driver of “Customer Loyalty”, which is consistent with the findings of Kassim & Abdullah (2010) in their research in online banking and (Levy and Hino, 2016) in banking context. Results from that study suggest that “Trust” can be accounted as a strong-driven factor of “Customer Loyalty”. In order to develop a long-term relationship between clients and service providers, trust is seen as a critical prerequisite of customer loyalty to e-banking (Hong and Cho, 2011).

Thus, in this study, Trust is tested on the direct effect on Customer Loyalty via the following hypothesis:

“H14. There is a positive relationship between “Trust” and Digital Banking “Customer Loyalty” in Digital Banking in Vietnam.”

3.4. Hypotheses Formation

Deriving from the discussions mentioned above and the context of Vietnam, this study proposed the following fourteen hypotheses to test the relationship between the important dimensions of the quality of Digital Banking service and “Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty” in the Vietnamese Banking Sector.

Table 3.1 presents proposed hypotheses

H1: “There is a positive relationship between Services portfolio/ Products and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H2: “There is a positive relationship between Ease of Use and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H3: “There is a positive relationship between Convenience and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H4: “There is a positive relationship between Usefulness and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H5: “There is a positive relationship between Reliability and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H6: “There is a positive relationship between Privacy and Security and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H7: “There is a positive relationship between Speed and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H8: There is a positive relationship between Design and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.
H9: “There is a positive relationship between Customer Service and Support and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H10: “There is a positive relationship between Digital-Emotional Connection and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H11: “There is a positive relationship between Digital Banking trust and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H12. “There is a positive relationship between Covid-19 risk perceptions and Digital Banking customer satisfaction in Vietnam.”
H13. “There is a positive relationship between Digital Banking Customer satisfaction and Digital Banking customer Loyalty in Vietnam.”

H14. “There is a positive relationship between Digital Banking trust and Digital Banking customer loyalty in Vietnam.”

Table 3. 3 Hypotheses (Source: Author)

3.4. Conceptual Framework

The main aim of the research is to empirically investigate the Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and its impact on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. In terms of theoretical foundations, since Digital Banking not only has service-oriented underpinnings but also technological foundations, hence, it is crucial to consolidate technology adoption theories (Lin and Lee, 2005) and service marketing theories (Van Looy et al., 1998) in its conceptualisation . Among the acceptance of technology theories, The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), is one of the acceptance of technology models that is frequently used to examine people's adoption of technology (See Figure 3.1).

Figure 3. 1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Source: Davis,1989)

According to Davis (1989) in TAM model, “perceived ease of use is the degree to which the prospective adopter expects the new technology adopted to be a free effort regarding its transfer

and utilisation” Usefulness is “the potential user’s subjective probability that using a particular system will enhance job performance in an organisational context”, directly affecting their “Attitude towards Usage” and “Behavioural Intention to Use”, ultimately affecting their “Actual System Use” in their technology adoption (Davis, 1989). This research at hand incorporates the “Usefulness” and “Ease of Use” from the TAM model but to investigate its relationship with customer satisfaction.

On the other hand, the SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman (1988), which measures the gap between customer expectations and experiences in order to reveal the perceived service quality (Parasuraman et al.,1988). In details, for each dimension “tangibles, reliability, responsibility, assurance, and empathy”, respondents will be asked about their expectations “Expected Service” of an ideal service and their perceptions of the service they actually received “Perceived Service” base on the perceptions of their experience (Parasuraman et al.,1988).

Figure 3. 2 SERVQUAL Model (Source: Parasuraman, 1988)

This study incorporates the “Reliability” and modifies “Responsiveness” to its similar constructs “Customer Service and Support” from the the SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman (1988).

Moreover, The construction of Services Portfolio/Products and Convenience as two independent variables (with Customer Satisfaction is dependant variable) was unified into the research model owing to the absence of essential empirical evidence in the extant literature.

Based on the extensive literature review presented in Chapter 2, along with the aforementioned theoretical foundation, this study incorporates two variables (Ease of Use and Usefulness) from TAM model of Davis (1989), two variables (Reliability and Responsiveness) SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman (1988) with several variables from validated modified models of e-banking, internet banking, mobile banking, digital banking, e-service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty such as (Shankar & Jebarajakirthy,2019;Jayawardhena, 2004; Hussien & El Aziz , 2013; Hammoud et al., 2018; Jun & Palacios, 2016; Amin, 2016; Yoon,2010). Variables were adopted or modified from previously validated scales in Digital Banking extant literature. Adjustments have been made to the measures by replacing questionnaires items to make them suitable for the research topic (Digital Banking) and appropriate for the research context (Vietnam). The remaining two dimensions, Digital-Emotional Connection and Covid-19 Risk perception, newly emerged in this study as Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customers' satisfaction and loyalty.

A conceptual framework is the logical conceptualisation of the entire research project. The research proposes the following conceptual framework for the apprehensibility of the impact of Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions on “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty” in the Vietnamese banking industry. The model is constructed by linking each of the 12 independent variables - Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions: Services portfolio/Products, Ease of Use, Reliability, Convenience, Usefulness, Privacy and Security, Speed, Customer Service and Support, Digital-Emotional Connection, Trust, Covid-19 risk perceptions with its corresponding dependant variable Customer Satisfaction; linking

independent variable Customer Satisfaction with dependant variable Customer Loyalty; linking independent variable Trust with dependant variable Customer Loyalty.

Even though the conceptual model proposed in this research (see Figure 3.1) shares the variables of other conceptual frameworks investing of banking service quality in general and digital banking service quality in particular and its relationships with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the extant literature, this one differs from the current literature for several points. Firstly, although most of the selected Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions have been well-researched in the extant literature, they have never been incorporated in a unified conceptual model before to test their effects on customers' satisfaction and loyalty. Based on an extensive and in-depth literature review, this current research proposed a newly developed conceptual framework adapted and modified from previous studies. In addition, the construction of Services Portfolio/Products and Convenience as two independent variables (with Customer Satisfaction is dependant variable) was unified into the research model owing to the absence of essential empirical evidence in the extant literature. Moreover, the two dimensions, Digital-Emotional Connection and Covid-19 Risk perception, newly emerged in this study as Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customers' satisfaction is an innovative approach in building conceptual framework. Based on the author's knowledge and observations, this is the first-time research with regards to Vietnamese Banking has been carried out in which customers' satisfaction and loyalty are examined to such a high degree via the employment of numerous components.

Figure 3.3 depicts the proposed conceptual framework.

Figure 3. 3 Research Model (Source: Author)

Figure 3.3 illustrates that the research model incorporates 14 different elements predominantly gathered from the extant literature and 14 respective testable hypotheses. In detail, 12 independent variables are associated with “Customer Satisfaction” via 12 exploratory hypotheses from H1-H12, while H13 and H14 are applied to the investigation of the direct effects of “Customer Satisfaction” and “Trust” on “Customer Loyalty”.

In essence, the proposed conceptual framework emphasises Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and its contribution to Digital Banking “Customer Satisfaction” and Digital Banking “Customer Loyalty” in the Vietnam Banking Sector. Based on the author’s knowledge and observations, this is the first-time research with regards to Vietnamese Banking has been carried out in which customers’ satisfaction and loyalty are examined to such a high degree via the employment of numerous components.

3.5. Digital Banking Service Quality factors and Items

Factors	Items	Supporting Literature
1. Services portfolio/ Products	1. The studied bank Digital Banking offers a full range of Digital Banking services.	Jun & Cai (2001) Bahia & Nantel, (2000)
	2. The studied bank Digital Banking provides a consistent experience across all of its Digital Banking channels (website/app)	
	3. The fees of the studied bank Digital Banking are reasonable.	
2. Ease of Use	4. I find it easy to register and log in to the studied bank Digital Banking channels.	Yoon (2010) Jun & Palacios (2016)
	5. I find it easy to navigate on the studied bank Digital Banking channels (website/app).	
	6. I find it easy to process transactions on the studied bank Digital Banking channels.	
3. Convenience	7. I can access the studied bank Digital Banking anytime anywhere I want.	Amin (2016)
	8. Using the studied bank Digital Banking, I can easily manage my bank account.	
	9. The studied bank Digital Banking gives me the ability to go cashless, which is a long-term convenience.	
4. Usefulness	10. The studied bank Digital Banking gives me access to a wide range of financial services.	Yoon (2010)
	11. The studied bank Digital Banking helps me to save my time.	
	12. The studied bank Digital Banking helps me to save my cost.	
	13. In general, I find it useful to use the studied bank Digital Banking.	
5. Reliability	14. The studied bank Digital Banking always provides the services exactly as promised.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) Jayawardhena (2004) Hussien & El Aziz (2013) Hammoud et al. (2018) Jun & Palacios (2016) Parasuraman et al., (2005)
	15. The studied bank Digital Banking always provides the services at the promised time.	
	16. The information provided over the studied bank Digital Banking channels is accurate, timely and complete.	

	17. The studied bank Digital Banking terms and fees are transparent.	
	18. The studied bank Digital Banking channels rarely makes mistakes with my account.	
6. Privacy and Security	19. The studied bank Digital Banking allows me to use biometric authentication to log in (fingerprint/voiceprint/facial recognition).	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy(2019) Hammoud et al., (2018)
	20. The studied bank Digital Banking channels ask me for additional verification if it spots a login from an unknown device.	
	21. My account information is protected on the studied bank Digital Banking platform.	
	22. The transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels are safe and secured.	
7. Speed	23. The connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...) is fast.	Yoon (2010) Aladwani &Palvia (2002) Yoon and Kim (2009) Jun & Palacios (2016)
	24. The page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is fast.	
	25. The transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is fast	
8. Design	26. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (website/app) is user friendly.	Amin (2016) (site organisation) Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) (website design)
	27. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is consistent across all of its channels (website/app).	
	28. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (Website/app) is well organised.	
	29. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (Website/app) is professional.	
9. Customer Service and Support	30. The studied bank Digital Banking channels offer easy access to customer service representatives.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) Parasuraman et al., (2005)

	31. The studied bank Digital Banking channels inform me what to do if my transaction is not processed.	
	32. Banking advisors is prompt in replying to queries or requests.	
	33. Banking advisors are knowledgeable of Digital Banking services.	
	34. Banking advisors has customers' best interests at heart.	
10. The Digital-Emotional Connection	35. The studied bank Digital Banking knows me and what I need.	KPMG International, (2020) Deloitte (2018)
	36. The studied bank Digital Banking offers me the most value compared to the same types of products.	
	37. The studied bank Digital Banking often launches new Digital Banking features to enhance my experience.	
	38. The studied bank Digital Banking provides me with customised services according to my preferences and habits.	
11. Customer trust in Digital Banking	39. The studied bank Digital Banking cares about the current and future interests of users.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019)
	40. This Digital Banking service provider (the studied bank) has necessary experience to provide Digital Banking services.	
	41. This Digital Banking service provider (the studied bank) is a leading brand in the market.	
	42. I completely trust the studied bank Digital Banking.	
12. Digital Banking Customer satisfaction	43. I am satisfied with the services provided by the studied bank Digital Banking.	Sikdar et al. (2015) Amin (2016)
	44. I am satisfied with the transactions processing in the studied bank Digital Banking.	
	45. I am satisfied with the experience that I had with the studied bank Digital Banking.	

13. Digital Banking Customer Loyalty	46. I would like to say positive things about the studied bank Digital Banking to other people.	Amin (2016) Shankar& Jebarajakirthy (2019) Parasuraman et al., (2005)
	47. I would like to recommend the studied bank Digital Banking to someone who seeks my advice.	
	48. I would encourage friends and family to use the studied bank Digital Banking.	
	49. I consider the studied bank Digital Banking to be my first choice for future transactions.	
	50. I intend to continue using the studied bank Digital Banking.	
14. COVID-19 risk perception	51. I feel COVID-19 has a high fatality rate.	KPMG International, (2020) Deloitte (2018)
	52. I am worried about myself, my family or my colleagues who may be affected by COVID-19.	
	53. I believe that there is an outbreak of COVID-19 in the area where I live and work.	
	54. In general, I know that COVID-19 is highly dangerous.	

Table 3. 4 Digital Banking Service Quality factors and Items (Source: Author)

3.6. Summary

This Chapter conducted a critical literature review of the most important dimensions of Digital Banking Service Quality that can affect “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty” to develop a conceptual framework and hypotheses developments to address the outlined questions in the study in Chapter 1 in which Digital Banking Service Quality factors along with their items are presented. The following Chapter - Chapter 4, will elaborate on the Research Methodology employed by this study.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to explain and justify the chosen methodology of the study. Justification of the selected research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection, populations and sampling, data analysis is presented. Subsequently, this chapter also discusses data management and ethical considerations, research validity, research reliability.

This study adopts a mixed-method research design with the quantitative and qualitative research established from survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. It is the most appropriate method for this particular empirical study, enabling the researcher to collect the necessary data from different sources to explore various stakeholders' perspectives of Digital Banking developments in Vietnam and investigate key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customer satisfaction and loyalty.

4.2. Research Philosophy

4.2.1. Possible Research Philosophies

Research philosophies as the systems of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge that will shape all aspects of a research project Saunders et al. (2019). Guided by the outline research questions and the nature of the phenomenon under investigation - Digital Banking, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty, this current research takes into consideration the four main research philosophies: positivism, interpretivism, critical realism and pragmatism. Firstly, regarding positivism which was developed by the French philosopher Auguste Comte in the early 19th century, the foundation of this philosophy is the belief that reality is objective and exists apart from our senses. Positivism researches generally use

quantitative techniques for the data collection and hypothesis testing to decipher the links between variables, supporting the objective explanation of reality. In contrast, Interpretivism philosophy was deeply rooted in the work of German sociologist Max Weber, a key figure in early 20th century – who is considered as one of the originators of Interpretivism and its central viewpoint is the belief that reality is socially constructed and subjective. Hence, in order to investigate the social phenomena, interpretivist researches significantly underscore the necessity to grasp people's experiences and perceptions, and, accordingly often employ qualitative methods such as interviews, observations, and document analysis. Combining Positivism and Interpretivism, Critical Realism is a research philosophy related to philosopher Roy Bhaskar (1944-2014), distinguishing an external reality which is similar to positivism while simultaneously emphasising the crucial role of human perception and interpretation which is similar to interpretivism.

Moreover, pragmatism philosophy is a school of thought originating in the United States in the late 19th century and is believed to be rooted in the work of American philosopher John Dewey (1859-1952) who is widely recognised as one of the originators of Pragmatism. Pragmatism according to John Dewey (1859-1952) is less concerned with philosophical debates about truth and reality, and more focused on practical applications and results. The core idea of pragmatism is beliefs are guides to actions and should be judged against the outcomes rather than abstract principles. Researchers adopting pragmatism frequently entails utilising whichever philosophical or methodological techniques are regarded most effective for answering a specific research question, rather than following entirely to one philosophical methodology. Henceforth, Pragmatism often supports the conduction of mixed-methods research approach with both quantitative method (frequently related to Positivism) and qualitative method (frequently related to Interpretivism) can be conducted (Creswell and Poth, 2017).

4.2.2. Research philosophy adopted for the current study

Based on the aforementioned discussions about the main research philosophical approaches, the researcher decided to adopt Pragmatism in guiding this research. The choice of Pragmatism research philosophy in this current research is influenced by the specific objectives of this research, the context of Vietnam Digital Banking, and the specific research questions outlined that this current research seeks to answer.

First and foremost, Pragmatism supports the conduction of mixed-methods research approach with both quantitative method (frequently related to Positivism) and qualitative method (frequently related to Interpretivism) can be conducted. This adaptability can be advantageous in researching the influence of digital banking service quality with regards to various stakeholders because it allows the researcher to acquire a diversity of the data form different perspectives. For example, quantifiable data gathered from customer surveys may reveal a relationship between DB service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction, permitting the investigator to seek the answer for RQ1: “Which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?” by developing and testing the hypotheses proposed in Chapter 3. The main aim of hypotheses testing is to evaluate how Digital Banking Service Quality can affect customer satisfaction and customer loyalty and identify which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions have the most significant impact on Customer satisfaction.

Additionally, quantitative data collected from banking customer survey and qualitative data collected from banking managers interviews could provide insights into the current implications of Digital Banking in Vietnam, allowing the researcher to reveal how Digital Banking is perceived by different stakeholders in Vietnam, addressing RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation

of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?". This is also reasonable with Pragmatism philosophy 's inherent openness to Multiple Perspectives which proves to be invaluable in researching different stakeholders' perspectives.

Last but not least, Pragmatism according to John Dewey (1859-1952) is less concerned with philosophical debates about truth and reality, and more focused on practical applications and results, which aligns well with the real-world importance of improving banking service quality to increase satisfaction and loyalty. A pragmatic approach enables researcher to disseminate actionable insights for improving banking services. Using Pragmatism philosophy, the researcher was able to comprehend the possible challenges which Vietnam Banking Sector has to face in the Digital Banking development journey, addressing the RQ3: "What are the key challenges to Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty?" as well as formulating recommendations for Vietnam Banking Sector's Digital Banking strategy, responding the RQ4: "What recommendations can be proposed to stakeholders regarding the utilisation of digital banking channels to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Banking Sector?".

In summary, a pragmatic approach has been chosen for the current research due to the fact that it can offer several advantages when researching the phenomenon digital banking, enabling enables the researcher to review and analyse the complex nature of Vietnam Digital Banking developments and their impact on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty.

4.3. Research Approach

4.3.1. Possible Research Approaches

4.3.1.1. Deductive approach

According to Saunders et al. (2019), there are three main approaches to theory development:

deduction, induction and abduction. According to Bell & Bryman (2015), the deductive method is most concerned with a scientific investigation in which the current theory development is subjected to a rigorous test. In other words, as pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019), with deductive approach, the research will develop a theory and hypotheses and then design a research strategy in order to test the hypotheses. One of the disadvantages of deductive approach is that it might end up with low clarity due to the fact that the generation of hypotheses determines the theory selection (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

4.3.1.2. Inductive approach

Conversely, the inductive approach focuses on investigating the research phenomenon through different methods (e.g., data analysis, interview) to attain a deep comprehension of the research topic, leading to theories being generated at the end of this process Saunders et al. (2019). Furthermore, Saunders et al. (2019) also point out that researchers should take careful actions in investigating or observing the research's subjects and pay attention to potential causal links. Therefore, the effectiveness of an inductive research is secured, resulting in a reliable interpretation for a specific situation. However, as criticised by Bell & Bryman (2015), the inductive approach fails in theory development since empirical evidence are not sufficient enough to create theories.

4.3.1.3. Abductive approach

Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914), an American “philosopher, logician, mathematician, and scientist” widely regarded as “ the first modern logician to explicitly formulate a theory of abduction (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce , 1992-98) - a model of discovery that works as a problem-solving heuristic encoded in a computer program” which made outstanding contributions to scientific methodology (Mabsout, 2015) and considered to “play a unique role in the history of modern American philosophy” (Niiniluoto, 2018).

Peirce's "pragmatist principle", as a rule for interpretations of concepts and hypotheses which guide scientific investigations (Peirce, 1931-58; Hookway, 2018), is intimately connected with his views on the abduction approach.

As defined by Peirce (1992-98) in "The Essential Peirce, Selected Philosophical Writing": "Pragmatism is the principle that every theoretical judgment expressible in a sentence in the indicative mood is a confused form of thought whose only meaning, if it has any, lies in its tendency to enforce a corresponding practical maxim expressible as a conditional sentence having its apodosis in the imperative mood." Abduction approach, according to Peirce, "consists in studying facts and devising a theory to explain them" (Peirce, 1931-58). Peirce claimed abduction as "the only kind of reasoning by means of which new ideas can be introduced", which is an "invaluable tool for scientific examination because it forces investigators to prioritise empirical facts over abstract concepts" (Peirce, 1931-58; Beckwith et al., 2018). This alignment with pragmatic philosophy enables abduction approach to lead to enhanced comprehension, verification or refutation of theories based on practical effects (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce , 1992-98; Psillos, 2007).

With abduction approach, the researcher will collect data to explore a phenomenon, identify key themes and explain patterns, generate a new or modify an existing theory, then collect additional data to test the new theory (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This means abductive approach combines both deductive and inductive approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Hence, the abductive approach can address the potential limitations of inductive and deductive methods by putting forward a pragmatist perspective (Creswell, 2009).

As also suggested by Saunders et al. (2019), abductive approach combines deductive approach and inductive approach and therefore, it is often used for researching a topic with a wealth of

information in one context but far less in the particular researching context, allowing the researcher to make theory generation or modification for an existing theory.

4.3.2. Evaluation of Possible Research Approaches

Table 4.1 below compares the three types of research approach mentioned above in terms of logic, generalisability, data collection usage and theory construction.

	Deductive approach	Inductive approach	Abductive approach
Logic	The precisely accurate hypotheses cause appropriate conclusions	Assumptions result in the formation of untested theories	Assumptions generate testable theories
Generalisability	General to specific generalisation	Specific to general generalisation	Generalisation from interactions between the general and the specific
Data collection usage	The collected data is used for evaluating hypotheses related to the existing theories	Collecting data for exploring a phenomenon, categorising themes, explaining patterns and generating a conceptual framework	Collecting data for exploring a phenomenon, categorising themes, explaining patterns. Data collection is used to generate a new or modify an existing theory, which is subsequently tested through additional data collection.
Theory	Theory verification	Theory Generalisation	Theory Generation or modification

Table 4. 1 Evaluation of deduction, induction and abduction research approaches

(Source: Adapted from Saunders et al., 2019)

4.3.3. Research approach adopted for the current study

Given the aforementioned discussions about three main research approaches, the researcher has chosen to adopt the abduction approach to conduct this research at hand. The choice of Abduction approach in this current research is influenced by the specific objectives of this

research, the context of Vietnam Digital Banking, and the specific research questions outlined that this current research seeks to answer.

Firstly, in line with Charles Sanders Peirce's abduction reasoning (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98), abductive approach is predominantly advantageous when conducting research about complex and unexplored phenomena because it is considered as an invaluable tool for generating plausible explanations for unexpected research findings (Mabsout, 2015; Hookway, 2018). As articulated in Chapter 2, there is a wealth of information about Digital Banking – research topic in the global context, but the extant literature in Vietnam – where the research is conducted, is still limited due to the fact that digital banking is a developing phenomenon in the context of Vietnam Commercial Banks. Additionally, the complexity and dynamism of the Vietnamese digital banking landscape can probably create such surprises.

It is in this context that the flexibility of abduction approach, inspired by Peirce's ideas (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98), proves to be invaluable, with the possibility that abduction approach might disclose innovative findings, for instance, a counterintuitive relationship between certain digital banking dimensions and customer satisfaction.

In details, in line with Peirce's ideas of abduction reasoning (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98), is particularly suitable for this research, as it allows for the exploration and explanation of the digital banking – a complex and evolving phenomenon, its impacts on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty (answering RQ1: “Which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?”), its current developments and challenges from the perspective of different stakeholders (answering RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial

Banks?" as well as RQ3: "What are the key challenges to Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty?"), suggesting strategic recommendations (answering RQ4: "What recommendations can be proposed to stakeholders regarding the utilisation of digital banking channels to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Banking Sector?") in the unique context of Vietnam. In order to answer these RQs, the research proposes a conceptual framework based on an extensive literature review based on the extant literature. It uses the collected data from different sources (customer survey, bank managers interview, secondary source) to test hypotheses to answer the outlined research questions and modify existing theory if needed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

In addition, stimulated by Peirce's ideas (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98), abduction approach is an excellent fit for interpreting the diversity of human experiences with different perspectives, given its inherent recognition of the variety of viewpoints and experiences. Therefore, this approach can be crucial in comprehending various perceptions of different stakeholders in order to seek the answer for the RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?".

In essence, the researcher has explicitly grounded the current study in Peirce's abduction reasoning (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98) and justified the choice of abduction approach. With its flexibility, creativity, and respect for diversity, abduction could be considered as an invaluable tool for this research because allows the researcher to comprehend the multilayered phenomenon digital banking and its impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnam Commercial Banks, proving to be the most appropriate approach to theory for this research, enabling the researcher to modify existing theory (Peirce, 1931-58; Peirce, 1992-98; Mabsout, 2015; Hookway, 2018; Saunders et al., 2019; Niiniluoto, 2018).

4.4. Research Strategy

This research aims to comprehend the role and extent of Digital Banking on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. It involves discovering what is happening in the Vietnam Banking Sector and gaining insights about Digital Banking in Vietnam by implementing five interviews for bank managers – who can be considered as experts in this field. These reasons make this research an exploratory study, as suggested by Saunders et al. (2019).

On the other hand, in order to achieve Research Question 1, this study intends to collect quantitative data from banking customers in Vietnam by a self-completed web-based survey, then use the Spearman's Correlation Coefficient Analysis to test the hypotheses to establish the casual relationships between Digital Banking Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction. Hence, these reasons make this research an explanatory study, as suggested by Saunders et al. (2019). Therefore, this research can be designed to fulfill a combination of exploratory and explanatory study as suggested by Saunders et al. (2019).

Saunders et al. (2019) defined a research strategy as the methodological link between the research philosophy and subsequent data collection and data analysis methods. Different research strategies have been taken into account for this present research, including Experimental research, survey, archival and documentary research, case study, ethnography, action research and grounded research. These research strategies will be discussed below.

4.4.1. Possible research strategies

The first possible research strategy being considered for this current research is experimental research. According to Saunders et al. (2019), experimental strategy is often employed in natural sciences related to research investigating the link between two variables. Experimental strategy only focuses on testing the hypotheses. Therefore, it may not be appropriate for business and management studies because this research emphasises the implications of these

relationships between variables, not just the hypotheses testing (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Secondly, survey is often related to the deduction approach (Collis & Hussey, 2014). In contrast with Experimental research, Survey can be considered as a popular research strategy in business and management research for its benefits of economically achieving a large number of respondents (Saunders et al., 2019). On the other hand, one of its drawbacks is the time-consuming process involved in designing and piloting the questionnaires and the dependence on others for the data (Bryan, 2012). Besides, due to limitations in the number of questions in a Survey questionnaire, data collected from Survey is unlikely to be as wide-ranging compared to data compiled by other research strategies (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Another research strategy is Archival and documentary research. Archival or documentary research allows researchers to access a wide range of secondary data sources, which can be considerable foundations for conducting a research project (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Using Archival or documentary research can also save time and cost for the researchers (Bryan, 2012). Moreover, documentary research enables researchers to conduct research projects related to changes during a specific period (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). However, the efficiency and effectiveness of archival research strategy immensely depend on the appropriateness and reliability of the data obtained, which requires excellent care taken during the research process by researchers (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Researchers often combine documentary research with other strategies such as Case study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Moreover, Ethnography is also taken into account as a research strategy for this research at hand. The main reason for considering Ethnography for this present research is that this strategy is relevant and valuable in the field of marketing (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Ethnography strategy is applied in studies examining a group's culture or social world (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Therefore, this strategy is considered a beneficial research strategy in market research for companies wishing to comprehend the

market and customer experience (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). On the one hand, by using the ethnography strategy, the researcher can gain an in-depth knowledge of different social groups; however, the time-consuming process and difficulty in presenting findings on journal articles are the main drawbacks of ethnography (Bryan, 2012, Saunders et al., 2019). Furthermore, Saunders et al. (2019) pointed out that Action Research focused on promoting organisational learning and addressing practical purposes. It is important to note that the process of Action Research requires collaboration participation and the facilitator role of the researcher (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). It will be an appropriate research strategy for part-time students who conduct research in the context of their organisations (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Therefore, it might not be appropriate for an external researcher like the researcher of this current study. Furthermore, Grounded theory is often used to build derived theories about a research phenomenon which has not existed previously or considered to be inadequate in a specific situation (Saunders et al., 2019). It requires researchers to be skilful in order to manage effectively large amounts of data (Creswell and Clark, 2017). Moghaddam (2006) pointed out that grounded theory is primarily applied in the inductive approach, while Saunders et al. (2019) argued that it might be more appropriate to relate Grounded Theory to the abductive approach.

Apart from the aforementioned research strategies, this current research significantly places a greater emphasis on the consideration of employing case study research strategy to facilitate the research. According to Yin (2018), a case study research is defined as “an empirical inquiry that investigate a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident” (Yin, 2018).

Regarding the usage, by dint of a deep engagement with the rich context of the specific case, researchers can gain an in-depth understanding of the research topic “in its complexity and particularity and discover pivotal insights, significantly contributing to the wider body of

knowledge of the field” (Stake, 1995). Case study has a prolonged and widespread use by researchers worldwide primarily due to their capacity of generating rich insights from intensive research of reality and fostering the development of theories (Yin, 2018).

Regarding the process of conducting case study research, Stake (1995) underscores the importance of specific context, triangulation (multiple sources of data from various perspectives) and the role of researchers in interpreting the case study data. According to Stake, case study research are not entirely objective endeavours, but also include interpretive aspects in which the researcher actively participates in the construction of meaning and knowledge (Stake, 1995).

Regarding the use of single case studies, in his article "Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research", Flyvbjerg (2006) discusses several common misconceptions about case study research, protecting this strategy and its usage in generating in-depth knowledge. In line with Flyvbjerg (2006), the first misconception is that broad, theoretical (context-independent) knowledge is more beneficial than specific, practical (context-dependent) knowledge. Second misunderstanding, according to Flyvbjerg (2006), is case study research cannot develop contribution to scientific development because discoveries from a single case study research cannot be generalised (Flyvbjerg, 2006). Additionally, another misconception is that case study research is only beneficial for generating hypotheses which belongs to the initial stage of a total research process, whereas other research strategies are more useful for later stages such as hypotheses testing and theory building (Flyvbjerg, 2006). As stated by Flyvbjerg (2006), case study research is an invaluable tool “for both generating and testing of hypotheses but is not limited to these research activities alone”. Regarding bias, as also criticised by Flyvbjerg (2006), the fourth misapprehension about case study is this research strategy encompasses a propensity to validate researchers’ pre-existing beliefs, leading to a potential bias toward verification. Consistent with his perspectives, last misconception for case study, according to

Flyvbjerg (2006) is that researchers might encounter various challenges in summarising and developing general propositions and theories from the insights generated from a specific case study research.

In essence, as both agreed by Flyvbjerg (2006) and (Yin, 2018), single case studies have been considered as an advantageous strategy for researchers who pursue to investigate typical cases because this approach are believed to allow researchers to generate unexpected and enlightening perspectives which could be applicable beyond the unique case being researched. As also further supported by Saunders et al. (2019), case study is applied for researchers undertaking empirical research into a topic or phenomenon and wishing to generate in-depth empirical findings. Case study research may be used for both exploratory or explanatory research along with both quantitative and qualitative data in order to achieve fruitful insights (Creswell and Clark, 2017). By using case study strategy, the researcher achieves comprehensive knowledge on a phenomenon through the use of different evidence sources (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007).

4.4.1. Evaluation of Possible Research Strategy

Research strategy	Usage	Advantages	Disadvantages
Experimental research	Create causal relationship between two variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A straight-forward way for testing causal • Can check and verify results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artificial situations may not reflect reality • Human errors can affect the research validity
Survey	Achieve information or describe the characteristics of a phenomenon from a large sample of a specific population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost effective • Achieve a large number of respondents • Convenient data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inflexible design • Inappropriate questions • Not suitable for controversial issues
Archival research	Obtain background information to come up with practical solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access a wide range of secondary data • Save time and cost • Usage for longitudinal studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collected data might not be relevant to research questions. • Concerns with the reliability of the data

Case study	Emphasise the analysis of the context in detail on events, their relationships, and conditions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate rich insights from an intensive study of a unit • Achieves comprehensive knowledge on a phenomenon • Compare various facts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited sampling, leading to generalisation problems • Subjectivity can lead to biases
Ethnography	Examine a group's culture, researchers observe society from viewpoint of the research topic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow an in-depth understanding of complex group behaviours • Disclose relationships among different dimensions of group interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-consuming • Difficulties presenting findings on journal articles
Action research	Solve problems and provide guidelines for effective practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of practical relevance • Applicable for both quantitative and qualitative data • Obtain in-depth knowledge of a research phenomenon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in distinguishing between research and action time-consuming • Lack of repeatability and rigour
Grounded theory	Develop an understanding of a social phenomenon not formulated or developed previously	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present the situated nature of knowledge and contingent nature of the practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult data management • Require skilful researchers • No standard rule for determination of categories

Table 4. 2 Evaluation of Research Strategies (Saunders et al., 2019)

4.4.2. Research Strategy adopted in the current research

Based on the aforementioned discussions, Case Study Research Strategy was selected for this current research for its appropriateness in addressing the specific research questions and objectives outlined in this current research, based on the core works of notable case study researchers such as Stake (1995), Yin (2018) and (Flyvbjerg,2006). These researchers have made major contributions to research methodology, who shared a common view regarding the usage of case study research: by dint of a deep engagement with the rich context of the specific case, researchers can gain an in-depth understanding of the research topic “in its complexity

and particularity and discover pivotal insights, significantly contributing to the wider body of knowledge of the field” (Stake, 1995, Yin, 2018, Flyvbjerg, 2006). The purpose of the current study is to investigate the key dimensions of Digital Banking and its impact on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the context of Vietnam. Digital banking in Vietnam is a complex phenomenon that involves multiple stakeholders, including banks, customers, regulators, and technology provider. Hence, in this context, there may be a lack of distinct separation or delineation between the Digital Banking and its surrounding context. Therefore, in line with Yin (2018), employing case study method for this current research will enable the researcher to conduct “an empirical inquiry that investigate a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident” (Yin, 2018). Moreover, the decision to focus on a single commercial bank in Vietnam for this research aligns with the Flyvberg's perspectives on the single case study approach, allowing the researcher to delve into the intricacies and complexities of the interactions between digital banking service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty within a specific banking context (Flyvbjerg, 2006). This allows the researcher to take into account the unique circumstances and dynamics of the specific organisational context, achieving a rich understanding of the research phenomenon,

Furthermore, the case study approach allows for a holistic examination of the research phenomenon by considering multiple perspectives (Stake, 1995), often by integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to enhance the richness and depth of the research findings.

In summary, the case study approach was chosen for its ability to provide a thorough and contextualised understanding of the research phenomenon, its relevance to the Vietnam banking sector, its holistic perspective, theoretical development potential, and practical consequences. By investigating a real-world case within the Vietnam Commercial Banks,

research findings can offer valuable insights and recommendations for practitioners, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. Various research also indicates that the case study approach is beneficial when there is a need to deeply appreciate an issue, event, or phenomenon of interest in its natural, real-life context. This, in turn, also helped to answer the research questions and accomplish the ultimate objective of this research as pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019). These justifications support the choice of the single case study approach as the most appropriate research strategy for this research at hand.

4.5. Research designs

According to Saunders et al.(2019), research designs is defined as a framework and guidelines including specific activities for research data generation. Research design allows researchers to identify the procedures for conducting the data collection and data analysis method for the research (Creswell, 2014). Research designs have seen significant developments over the years due to the technology advancements which bring new methods of analysing complicated research models (Creswell, 2014). As pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019), there are three common research methods: quantitative, qualitative and mixed-method, which will be discussed in more detail in the following section.

4.5.1. Quantitative research

In quantitative research method, researchers generate numerical data or employ a statistical approach to conduct the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Quantitative research aims to develop, test, confirm or validate relationships among variables for the purpose of developing generalisations to a theory (Creswell, 2009). In a quantitative research, researchers often follow deduction research approach for theory testing by generating numerical data through positivist model and an objective viewpoint about the research phenomenon (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Quantitative data can be utilised for objective assessment of reality or meaning generation through the objectivity exposed from the data obtained (Blaxter, Hughes

and Tight, 2010). Thus, by using quantitative methods for research design, researchers can gain confirmative, explanatory or predictive outcomes (Creswell, 2009).

4.5.2. Qualitative research

Qualitative method is often applied for research using observation or interviews for data collection process and non-numerical data-analysis procedures (Creswell and Poth 2017; Saunders et al. 2019). Qualitative research aims to investigate a research phenomenon from participants' viewpoints (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2010). Qualitative research is appropriate for social science research embracing subjective perspectives and feeling (Collis and Hussey, 2014). This contradicts the aims of quantitative research to examine the causal relationships among variables (Gill and Johnson, 2010). In contrast with quantitative research, in qualitative methods, researchers often apply inductive research approach for theory generations (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). According to Bell & Bryman (2015), in qualitative research, researchers often apply interpretivist model to inspect different viewpoints and develop knowledge rather than only testing the theory in "reality".

4.5.3. Mixed method design

Mixed method is the combination or integration of quantitative and qualitative research to enhance the strengths and reduce the weaknesses of each design alone (Creswell, 2014). Mixed method can be regarded as multiple method because it involves collecting various forms of data (Creswell, 2014). According to Saunders et al.(2019), researchers can apply inductive, deductive, and abductive approaches to theory development in mixed methods research. Mixed method designs allow researchers to explore the complex nature of the research phenomenon from participants' perspectives and investigate the relationships among variables in order to comprehend the research phenomenon (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In mixed methods, researchers can build research design based on combined data collection and data

analysis for both theory generation and hypotheses testing simultaneously (Thomas, 2009).

Mixed methods research can be divided into two main types of variation based on how and to what extent the combination of qualitative and quantitative methods occurs in the study: concurrent mixed methods and sequential mixed method (including three main types: sequential exploratory, sequential explanatory, sequential multi-phase) (Creswell & Clark, 2017, Saunders et al., 2019). In concurrent mixed methods, researchers conduct a separate use of quantitative and qualitative methods with a single-phase research design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Interpretation and analysis of these two sets of qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously enable researchers to use both types of data to support the other and generate a more comprehensive research finding than the use of mono method design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Meanwhile, sequential mixed methods involve more than one phase of data collection and analysis (See Figure 4.1.), which is time-consuming and less practical to undertake than concurrent mixed methods (Creswell & Clark, 2017).

4.5.4. Evaluation of possible Research Designs

The distinguishment of quantitative method and qualitative research can be based on the difference in data treatment of each research method (Gill and Johnson, 2010). In the quantitative method, researchers define and isolate variables to form a conceptual framework and hypotheses based on the identified variables, followed by the data collection and hypotheses testing (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In contrast, in qualitative research, researchers begin with the definition of a general concept and this definition is transformed during the research development (Maxwell, 2013). Thus, using quantitative method, researchers perform a narrow investigation for an identified set of variables, while in qualitative method, researchers conduct broader research for unspecified sets of concepts (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Quantitative method is often applied in studies that comprise surveys, questionnaires for data collection, and statistics/graphs for data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Conversely, the qualitative method is used for research involving interviews or observations in the data collection process and non-numerical data-analysis procedures.

The logic of quantitative research is based on generalisation, which means how the research findings can be generalised (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In contrast, qualitative designs focus on replicating research findings on other cases or set of situations for the research generalisation (Maxwell, 2013).

In quantitative method, researchers employ pre-identified instruments and use statistical data analysis techniques to test the research model, resulting in less flexible, reflective and imaginative outcomes (Creswell, 2009). Conversely, in qualitative method, researchers evaluate the research phenomenon from its participants' perspectives, aiming to achieve imaginative insights from their viewpoints, which results in reflective and flexible findings, yet maintains some levels of distance (Maxwell, 2013).

As defined by Creswell (2009), mixed-method design is the combination or integration of both quantitative and qualitative methods to neutralises the limitations and improve the benefits of each individual method. It is the main advantage of mixed method designs as it enables researchers to reach efficiency and balance in data collection and analysis (Creswell & Clark, 2017). By using mixed-method designs, researchers can collect a wealth of data to achieve more insightful and comprehensive findings (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Nonetheless, the high cost involved in data collection and possible data repetitions can be seen as the main disadvantages of research using mixed methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

In concurrent mixed- methods, researchers conduct both quantitative and qualitative methods with a single-phase research design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The single-phase

allows researchers to perform data interpretation and analysis of both sets of qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously, which enables researchers to use both types of data concurrently to support the other in order to generate a more comprehensive research finding (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

4.5.5. Research Design adopted for the current study

This present research adopted mixed-method designs (customer survey and bank managers interviews) because the research's nature required information-rich respondents to provide answers to the research questions to achieve the research objectives. Based on the evaluation mentioned above of the pros and cons of each research method and the emphasis of the research phenomenon – determining Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and its impact on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in Vietnam commercial banks, the researcher adopted concurrent mixed-method for this study. The researcher then considered concurrent and sequential mixed methods and decided to choose concurrent mixed methods because it is more practical and less time-consuming than sequential mixed methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). By using this concurrent mixed-method research design, the current research can simultaneously conduct quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). This allows the researcher to use both types of data concurrently to support the other, hence generating more comprehensive answers to the research questions about Digital Banking and its impact on customer relations, as Saunders et al. (2019) suggested. The requirement to triangulate results and improve the overall validity of the research motivated the choice to use a mixed methods methodology. The study sought to get over the drawbacks of using just one method by mixing various data sources, research procedures, and data collection strategies in order to produce a more thorough and robust examination of the investigated topic (Creswell & Poth, 2017).

4.6. Population for the current study

4.6.1. Population and sampling

As defined by Gill & Johnson (2010), sampling is the process of extracting data from a population. As lately confirmed by Saunders et al. (2019), sampling is the process of collecting a group of relatively small number of people to represent the entire population for conducting the research. The people selected in the sampling group are regarded as participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Saunders et al. (2019) also clarified that sampling techniques allow researchers to save time and cost for data collection because it only collects a group representing the whole population. There are two types of sampling techniques: probability sampling and non-probability sampling (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

(See Figure 4.1. for more details of types of sampling techniques)

Figure 4. 1 Sampling techniques (Saunders et al., 2019)

Probability sampling is applied for research with the chance that each element chosen from the population has been identified and equal to the elements (Blaxter, Hughes and Tight, 2010). Meanwhile, non-probability sampling is employed for research in which the probability of each

component is unknown when selected from the entire population (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Hence, in non-probability sampling, the selected sample may not characterise the whole population (Gill and Johnson, 2010).

Even though probability sampling requires a great deal of effort, including huge cost and time, this technique also effectively reduces systematic errors and minimizes biases (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In contrast, Collis & Hussey (2014) pointed out that conducting non-probability sampling is less complicated with less time and effort than the probability sampling technique requires. However, its main disadvantage is the high possibility of systematic errors and biases that can occur during the research process (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Due to the time constraints of the DBA program, the present research applied non-probability sampling because it is more practical and less effort than probability sampling. As suggested by Saunders et al. (2019), despite the limitations of non-probability sampling, this technique still enables the researcher to answer research questions and achieve research objectives effectively.

4.6.2. Types of Non-Probability Sampling Techniques

Techniques	Description
Quota Sampling	Quota sampling is a non-random selection of elements in the research population and is frequently used for interviews(Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The sample is used to represent the research population since the sample’s variability for different quota variables will be similar to that of the total research population (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).
Purposive Sampling	Purposive sampling is often applied for small-scale samples(e.g., case-study research) or when researchers want to select rich-information respondents (Bryan, 2012)

	Purposive sampling allows researchers to select participants based on their assessment to guarantee that chosen respondents can effectively answer the research questions and meet research objectives.
Snowball Sampling	Snowball sampling is often used when there exist difficulties in determining the number of research population (Collis and Hussey, 2014).
Self-selection Sampling	In self-selection sampling, researchers display each case to decide whether to contribute to the research. Researchers show the research information on appropriate social media or ask for participation. Interested participants can respond and agree to participate in the study(Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).
Convenience Sampling	Convenience sampling is the selection of the easiest-to-obtain cases for the sample.

Table 4. 3 Types of Non-Probability Sampling Techniques

(Adapted from Saunders et al.,2019)

4.6.3 Evaluation of Non-Probability Sampling Techniques

In order to choose the most appropriate type of non-probability sampling technique for the current research, the research carried out a critical evaluation of possible sampling techniques that can be used and their impact on the research process and outcomes, followed by the selection of sampling techniques for the current study in the next section. The following table presents the evaluation adapted from Saunders et al. (2019):

Sampling Techniques	Usage	Advantage	Disadvantage
Quota Sampling	Select a sample closely matches the population ratio on a set of characteristics of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a highly representative sample without using probability sampling. • Cost-effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible difficulties in identifying sampling errors, biases, and generalisation due to Non-random sampling
Purposive Sampling	Concentrate on particular	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to information-rich respondents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection biases • Researcher Bias • Lack of Generalisability

	characteristics of a population		
Snowball Sampling	Access to specific populations which share the same kind of social characteristic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility to hard to access. populations • New participants are recruited by existing respondents, increasing response rate. • Cost-effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Generalisability • Selection bias • Lack of Researcher Control • Sampling errors may be hard to identify.
Self-selection sampling	Allow participants to decide to participate in a volunteer manner.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time saving in finding appropriate participants. • Engaged Participants, Increase Participants' commitments to the research • Ease of Recruitment • Cost-effective 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-selection bias • Lack of Generalisability • Validity Threats
Convenience	Enable the most accessible approach to the participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most economical method in non-probability sampling that allows researchers to gain the right sample size quickly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unknown sampling frame and non-random selection of sample can lead to inherent bias • Lack of Generalisability

Table 4. 4 Evaluation of Non-Probability Sampling Techniques

(Adapted from Saunders et al.,2019)

4.6.4. Sampling Techniques adopted for survey questionnaires

Given that it is impossible to obtain a complete list of Digital Banking customers in Vietnam, a non-probability convenience sampling technique was adopted to draw the study sample as suggested by Geebren et al. (2021). Dillon, Madden, & Firtle (1993) pointed out that the non-probability convenience sampling technique allows researchers to obtain an adequate sample size. The researcher did consider other sampling approaches, such as snowball sampling was not used as the sample was large (Soloff, Lawrence, & Johnstone, 2005). Hence, the researcher

used the convenience sampling technique to gather the quantitative data as it allowed the most accessible approach to the research participants. The survey instrument was created online through Survey Monkey. It was shared on different social media channels (e.g., Facebook, Zalo, Telegram) with the web link or email sent to prospective respondents. Saunders et al. (2019) pointed out that this convenience sampling technique allowed the researcher to quickly gain the right sample size, access a “diverse pool of respondents” and increase the participation rate.

4.6.5. Sampling Techniques adopted for Interviews

The researcher set out the selection criteria for the participants of the interview, including four requirements: they need to work in the studied bank for a long time, at least ten years, currently have a managerial role in the studied bank, have an in-depth understanding and knowledge about Digital Banking practice and has significant interaction either directly or indirectly with banking customers as suggested by Larsson & Viitaoja (2017).

The researcher was a student of Banking Academy in Vietnam and also had previous working experience as a credit analyst in Asia Commercial Bank so the researcher could secure network connections with these banking managers in the studied bank. Therefore, as suggested by Saunders et al. (2019), the researcher followed purposive sampling to choose the participants for the interview. By using purposive sampling, the researcher could select the participants who adequately meet the selection criteria of the research and hence, can provide insightful perceptions for the current study.

However, it is essential to note that the research can only get access to five bank managers' interviews due to time constraints. This sampling did not represent the Digital Banking population. However, according to the researcher's opinion, it is the most appropriate in this current study because it enables the research to select the information-rich respondents to get

an insightful understanding of the practice. To avoid biases, the researcher used a survey questionnaire and secondary data as a complement to support the collected interview data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

However, since purposive sampling is adopted to select these five individuals, selection bias, small sample size and the potential for selection bias is a limitation. While the insights gained from these five individuals can provide valuable qualitative data and in-depth understanding, generalisability of the findings should be done with cautions.

4.7. Data collection

To achieve the research objectives, the researcher used different sources of data. In this current study, the researcher considers two possible types of data sources that can be used to the research phenomenon in detail and find possible solutions: primary data and secondary data, as suggested by Saunders et al. (2019).

4.7.1. Primary data

As defined by Creswell & Clark (2017), primary data is the kind of data collected via interviews, questionnaires, focus groups or observation, etc., to serve the research objectives. The main advantage of primary data is its originality and direct relationships with the research topic (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Since researchers collect primary data from reliable participants, the collected primary data might be of high reliability, enabling the researcher to achieve an original and insightful data analysis and interpretation (Collis and Hussey, 2014). However, the main disadvantage of primary data is that primary data collection might be costly and time-consuming (Bryan, 2012). In addition, the quality of the primary data obtained significantly depends on the participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Respondents may not wish to reveal the sensitive information, or they may provide outdated information or socially-accepted answers instead of honest ones (Gill and Johnson, 2010). In

terms of the amount of data collection, researchers may not have control over the amount of data collected because respondents can misapprehend the questions and leave the survey questionnaire unfinished.

4.7.2 Secondary data

Secondary data is defined as the data that were collected originally for other purposes and subsequently utilised in research to be further analysed and aid different research aims and objectives (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). According to Saunders et al. (2019), three broad types of secondary data are survey, document, and multiple sources, as presented in Figure 4.2. Saunders et al. (2019) recommended that secondary data are primarily used for literature reviews and easier to access than the primary data because they were located at the tertiary domains.

Figure 4. 2 Types of secondary data (Saunders et al.,2019)

Saunders et al. (2019) emphasised the effectiveness and convenience of accessibility of secondary data. Using secondary data can save researchers a significant amount of time and effort than collecting primary data themselves (Vartanian, 2011). Besides, researchers can access high-quality data sources funded by agencies on a larger sample size, allowing them to better understand the targeted population, achieve higher research validity and produce more prosperous research outcomes (Smith et al., 2011). Hence, secondary data provides opportunities for researchers who have time constraints on conducting longitudinal studies or comparative research (Saunders et al., 2019). Furthermore, by using secondary data, researchers have quicker access to sensitive topics without sophisticated consultations, which is defined as an “unobtrusive measure” (Saunders et al., 2019). Researchers can reinterpret

and reanalyse secondary data in existing empirical research to extend research, leading to the possibility of achieving unforeseen insights for their research (Gill & Johnson, 2010; Saunders et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, the use of secondary data also has some disadvantages. First, the secondary data can be unrelated to the research phenomenon and thus cannot answer the research questions (Saunders et al., 2019). The secondary data may be initially collected in a different geographic area or research population, which can be inappropriate for another research (Vartanian, 2011). In addition, the researcher may encounter difficulties accessing some secondary data sources which are not available online (Saunders et al., 2019). Copyright is also a prominent drawback of utilising secondary data (Vartanian, 2011).

Moreover, since researchers do not directly take part in the secondary data collection, they do not have control over the reliability of the data. At the same time, there exists concern about the quality of “distorted” secondary data, which requires excellent care taken in evaluating the data (Saunders et al., 2019).

4.8. Data collection for this current study

This present study employed both primary and secondary data. By using secondary data, the researcher found the information related to the research phenomenon and themes by reviewing the extant literature from high-quality journal articles and other publications. These data were accessed via publicly available databases on the key research areas, which include digital economy, Digital Banking, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, The studied bank, and other relevant key themes. Furthermore, the researcher focused on determining dimensions of Digital Banking Service Quality affecting customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. By conducting an extensive literature review on the research topic, the researcher had an idea of

the key themes which can be used for the primary data collection through survey questionnaires and interviews.

The potential data sources determined in this case study are focused on semi-structured interviews and large-scale online surveys. The interviews have been conducted with the boundaries only to determine the research questions' answers and objectives. On the other hand, the survey triangulated the collected data via the interview that ensures the views of other main stakeholders' groups – in this case, the customers and this, in turn, helps to tell a trustworthy story. However, due to the Coronavirus Pandemic, the researcher could not visit Vietnam, so further interviews could not be conducted with other groups, e.g., policymakers and government officials. This, therefore, is replaced by searching for additional secondary data in terms of annual reports, industry reports, etc.

In short, this research-based thesis used interviews and surveys and reviewed diverse documents from reputable secondary sources, including policy documents and business reports from the government and financial institutions. The interviews revealed bank managers' perceptions, and the survey gathered customers' opinions while the reviewed secondary source collected other stakeholders' perceptions. Results from the qualitative data (semi-structure interviews) and quantitative data collection (surveys) along with secondary data provided an in-depth understanding of the research phenomena.

4.8.1. Primary Data – Survey

According to Creswell (2013) the survey approach is the combination of experimental and ethnography researches. This approach tests the logic of a lab experiment in reality to investigate and evaluate the causal links among variables. A survey's format should consider its connection to deductive enquiry's logic and its intermediate position achieved by the reliable data collection and statistical control of variables instead of data collection in the lab.

In business and management studies, survey methods are employed to accurately represent the research phenomena via descriptive surveys and to identify the relationship among variables via analytical survey. King and Horrocks (2010) noted the limitation of survey method is that the researcher might not know exactly what his or her targets are. Moreover, the validity level may be low; and the use of biased samples could lead to poor external validity. include: Surveys completed by respondents (such as questionnaires sent via emails or traditional mails, interviews via telephone or face-to-face interviews).

Table 4.5 describes the different survey methods:

	Pros	Cons
Physical questionnaire distribution and collection after completion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal interaction • Opportunity for clarifications • Control over the sample • Higher response rates compared to online surveys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited reach to wide respondents • Incomplete or missing responses • Manual data entry • Time and resource-intensive • Expenses implications
Face-to-face surveys (interviewing)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity for clarifications • Flexibility and adaptability to responses • Non-verbal cues and context • Higher response rate • Personal interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time and resource-intensive • Interviewer bias • Social desirability bias • Limited anonymity
Telephone surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide reach to different geographical locations (rural areas, no internet areas) • Efficient data collection • Real-time interaction • Random sampling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited participant control • Potential non-response bias • Telephone screening challenges • Limited visual cues • Possible limited coverage of target population due to landline usage decrease
Traditional Mail Surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide reach to different geographical locations (rural areas, no internet areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for low response rates • Time-consuming • Slow process • Incomplete or missing responses

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical presence of questionnaires compared to online surveys • Familiarity and trust with traditional mail. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited opportunity for clarification • Cost considerations
Online surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide reach to target individuals worldwide. • Cost-effective compared to traditional survey methods. • Quick data collection • Skip patterns options • No field staff involvement. • No manual data entry • Data accuracy and consistency • Ease of data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential bias from certain demographics exclusion (lack of internet/technology) • Non-response bias • Limited control over participants • Data security and privacy concerns • Lack of personal interaction • Potential for low response rates
Mixed-Mode Surveys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide reach to a broader range of respondents. • Potential high response rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time and resource-intensive • Expenses implications

Table 4. 5 Comparison of different survey methods

(Adapted from Saunders et al.,2019)

4.8.2. Survey method selected for the current study

Based on the discussions above, an online survey created through Survey Monkey was applied for this evidence-based research by dint of its abundant advantages. The main aim of this is to understand the customer perceptions about Digital banking service quality dimensions and further explore their satisfaction as this will ultimately lead to maintaining and gaining customer loyalty. For this study, the survey method was selected considering the population of the sample and its characteristics, type of questions, topics of questions, cost, time, and the response rate (Saunders et al., 2019). The web-based survey was supported by an e-mail reminding respondent about visiting the website to fill in the questionnaire. This helped the research benefit from both methods while minimising limitations.

The researcher only choose individual banking customers for the customers survey, not the corporate customers, because there exists evidence in the extant literature shows that “individual customers are always in the best position to explain their perceptions of service and channel quality as well as the reasons for their choices, attitudes, and intentions towards the services they receive” (Harrison, Onyia and Tagg, 2014).

4.8.3. Primary Data – Interview

Research interview is a powerful technique to collect narrative data, enabling researchers to comprehend participants’ perceptions to a greater extent (Bell and Bryman, 2015). Interviews are defined as a “purposeful conversation” between interviewee and interviewer to gain in-depth information on a topic and understand a research phenomenon to gather valid and reliable data to answer research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In the same way, interviews allow researchers to examine constructive and negotiable meanings of definitions and topics in a natural way (Roepstorff, Petersen and Berthelsen, 2016).

There are different types of research interviews; however, in this present research, the author only considers possible types of research interviews, namely structured, semi-structured and in-depth interviews (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Structured interviews: Saunders et al. (2019) emphasises that in structured interviews, researchers use researcher-completed questionnaires with an identical set of questions on a standard schedule with pre-coded answers were used, which leads to a low level of freedom and flexibility on the interviewing topics. Using structured interviews, researchers need to read out pre-written questions precisely in the same tone of voice to ensure that they do not cause any bias (Saunders et al., 2019). Moreover, structured interviews are often used in quantitative research through the use of a pre-determined questionnaire to collect quantifiable data (Maxwell, 2013). Researchers can use pre-coded answers to produce straightforward answers

for statistical results. However, Collis & Hussey (2014) emphasised that the obtained data will be invalid if interviewees misunderstand the questions.

Semi-structured interviews: Compared to structured interviews, the flexibility of semi-structured interviews is higher, which allows researchers to expand and probe the interviewees' answers (Whiting, 2008). Semi-structured interviews are beneficial if researchers expect to gain in-depth responses and preserve the constraints of the research objectives (Whiting, 2008). Nonetheless, if researchers adopt semi-structured interviews, they can make modifications in terms of the wording or the order of questions depending on the actual context of each interviewee and combine both closed and open-ended questions (Bazeley, 2013).

In-depth interviews: In-depth interviews can be regarded as “unstructured interviews” or “informal interviews” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In in-depth interviews, the interviewer and interviewee naturally discuss the research topic with no pre-determined questions to collect qualitative data (Sharlene, 2010). By using in-depth interviews, researchers can achieve the highest level of freedom and flexibility for both the interviewer and interviewee in terms of planning, organising content, and conducting interviews (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). However, researchers should avoid going too far from the research topic being studied in an unstructured interview (Bazeley, 2013).

4.8.4. The interview selected for the current study

Based on the discussions above, in this present research, the researcher decided to adopt semi-structured interview technique for conducting interviews with bank managers in The studied bank. The interviews aim to capture bank managers' perceptions of Digital Banking's current developments, challenges, opportunities, and their impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty. After conducting an extensive literature review, the author prepared the interview questions based on the key themes founded and research objectives. Using semi-structured interviews,

the researcher can obtain in-depth answers of the research phenomenon based on pre-coded themes with the opportunity to probe respondents' explanations where necessary (Maxwell, 2013). Semi-structured interviews can increase the level of understanding between the interviewer and interviewees due to the ability to clarify the questions if the participants do not understand (Kaplowitz, 2000). Kaplowitz (2000) also emphasised that Semi-structured interviews can allow the researcher to attain both the natural flow of information and the required amount of data, resulting in a richer understanding of the research phenomenon.

The researcher can gain more in-depth responses than other structured interviews or survey questionnaires by employing semi-structured interviews, leading to more profound data collection results and more insightful research outcomes (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

4.9. Survey Data Collection Process

4.9.1. Development of survey questionnaire measures

The survey questionnaire consists of scales to evaluate various measures from the conceptual framework proposed in Chapter 3. In line with Amin (2016) and Shankar and Jebarajakirthy (2019), the items used to measure study constructs were adapted and modified from previously validated scales in Digital Banking extant literature. Adjustments have been made to the measures by replacing questionnaires items to make them suitable for the research topic (Digital Banking) and appropriate for the research context (Vietnam). The questionnaire consists of 54 items developed from 14 major factors.

Table 4.6 presents these adapted constructs which consists of 14 factors including 54 items along with their reference sources.

Factors	Items	Supporting Literature
	1. The studied bank Digital Banking offers a full range of Digital Banking services.	Jun & Cai (2001)

1. Services portfolio/ Products	2. The studied bank Digital Banking provides a consistent experience across all of its Digital Banking channels (website/app)	Bahia & Nantel, (2000)
	3. The fees of the studied bank Digital Banking are reasonable.	
2. Ease of Use	4. I find it easy to register and log in to the studied bank Digital Banking channels.	Yoon (2010) Jun & Palacios (2016)
	5. I find it easy to navigate on the studied bank Digital Banking channels (website/app).	
	6. I find it easy to process transactions on the studied bank Digital Banking channels.	
3. Convenience	7. I can access the studied bank Digital Banking anytime anywhere I want.	Amin (2016)
	8. Using the studied bank Digital Banking, I can easily manage my bank account.	
	9. The studied bank Digital Banking gives me the ability to go cashless, which is a long-term convenience.	
4. Usefulness	10. The studied bank Digital Banking gives me access to a wide range of financial services.	Yoon (2010)
	11. The studied bank Digital Banking helps me to save my time.	
	12. The studied bank Digital Banking helps me to save my cost.	
	13. In general, I find it useful to use the studied bank Digital Banking.	
5. Reliability	14. The studied bank Digital Banking always provides the services exactly as promised.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) Jayawardhena (2004) Hussien & El Aziz (2013) Hammoud et al. (2018) Jun & Palacios (2016) Parasuraman et al., (2005)
	15. The studied bank Digital Banking always provides the services at the promised time.	
	16. The information provided over the studied bank Digital Banking channels is accurate, timely and complete.	
	17. The studied bank Digital Banking terms and fees are transparent.	
	18. The studied bank Digital Banking channels rarely makes mistakes with my account.	
6. Privacy and Security	19. The studied bank Digital Banking allows me to use biometric authentication to log in (fingerprint/voiceprint/facial recognition).	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy(2019)

	20. The studied bank Digital Banking channels ask me for additional verification if it spots a login from an unknown device.	Hammoud et al., (2018)
	21. My account information is protected on the studied bank Digital Banking platform.	
	22. The transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels are safe and secured.	
7. Speed	23. The connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...) is fast.	Yoon (2010) Aladwani &Palvia (2002) Yoon and Kim (2009) Jun & Palacios (2016)
	24. The page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is fast.	
	25. The transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is fast	
8. Design	26. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (website/app) is user friendly.	Amin (2016) (site organisation) Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) (website design)
	27. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is consistent across all of its channels (website/app).	
	28. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (Website/app) is well organised.	
	29. The design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels (Website/app) is professional.	
9. Customer Service and Support	30. The studied bank Digital Banking channels offer easy access to customer service representatives.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) Parasuraman et al., (2005)
	31. The studied bank Digital Banking channels inform me what to do if my transaction is not processed.	
	32. Banking advisors is prompt in replying to queries or requests.	
	33. Banking advisors are knowledgeable of Digital Banking services.	
	34. Banking advisors has customers' best interests at heart.	
10. The Digital-Emotional Connection	35. The studied bank Digital Banking knows me and what I need.	KPMG International, (2020) Deloitte (2018)
	36. The studied bank Digital Banking offers me the most value compared to the same types of products.	

	37. The studied bank Digital Banking often launches new Digital Banking features to enhance my experience.	
	38. The studied bank Digital Banking provides me with customised services according to my preferences and habits.	
11. Trust	39. The studied bank Digital Banking cares about the current and future interests of users.	Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019)
	40. This Digital Banking service provider (the studied bank) has necessary experience to provide Digital Banking services.	
	41. This Digital Banking service provider (the studied bank) is a leading brand in the market.	
	42. I completely trust the studied bank Digital Banking.	
12. Digital Banking Customer satisfaction	43. I am satisfied with the services provided by the studied bank Digital Banking.	Sikdar et al. (2015) Amin (2016)
	44. I am satisfied with the transactions processing in the studied bank Digital Banking.	
	45. I am satisfied with the experience that I had with the studied bank Digital Banking.	
13. Digital Banking Customer Loyalty	46. I would like to say positive things about the studied bank Digital Banking to other people.	Amin (2016) Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) Parasuraman et al., (2005)
	47. I would like to recommend the studied bank Digital Banking to someone who seeks my advice.	
	48. I would encourage friends and family to use the studied bank Digital Banking.	
	49. I consider the studied bank Digital Banking to be my first choice for future transactions.	
	50. I intend to continue using the studied bank Digital Banking.	
14. COVID-19 Risk Perceptions	51. I feel COVID-19 has a high fatality rate.	KPMG International (2020) Deloitte (2018)
	52. I am worried about myself, my family or my colleagues who may be affected by COVID-19.	
	53. I believe that there is an outbreak of COVID-19 in the area where I live and work.	
	54. In general, I know that COVID-19 is highly dangerous.	

Table 4. 6 Description of Digital Banking Service Quality (14 factors, 54 items)

(Source: Author)

4.9.2. Survey Questionnaire design

The survey questionnaire consists of five parts with three main parts (See Appendix A: Final Customers Survey English version and Appendix B Final Customers Survey Vietnamese version). The researcher allows respondents to choose either English or Vietnamese version Survey based on their language proficiency; however, all of the returned responses were in Vietnamese – the primary language used in the research context.

- ✓ Part 1: Welcome
- ✓ Part 2: (5 questions from Question 1 to Question 5) General information pertaining to respondents' Digital Banking usage, including questions about Length of the banking relationship, Number of banking relationships, Primary bank, Frequency of using The studied bank Digital Banking Channels, Financial transactions made by Digital Banking channels.
- ✓ Part 3: (14 questions from Question 6 to Question 19) Evaluation on Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions. This part pertains to respondents' evaluation on Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions, satisfaction, loyalty, including Services Portfolio/Products (Q6), Ease of Use (Q7); Convenience (Q8); Usefulness (Q9); Reliability (Q10); Privacy and Security (Q11); Speed (Q12), Design (Q13); Customer Service and Support (Q14); Digital-Emotional Connection (Q15); Trust (Q16); Customer Satisfaction (Q17), Customer Loyalty (Q18), Covid-19 risk perceptions(Q19).

Table 4.6 mentioned above presents the measures and items and its source where the researcher adapted the measures. The items are measured with a five-point Likert-scale: strongly disagree, disagree, neither disagree nor agree, agree, strongly agree.

✓ Part 4 (8 questions from Question 20 to Question 27) pertaining respondents' Demographic information. As an approach utilised in developing the understanding of the research perspective, demographic analysis of this study pertains to this information of the respondents: Age Group, Education Level, Occupation, Monthly Income, Current Relationship Status, Experience of Using Digital Banking Services, Internet Usage Literacy. Because of the privacy and personal nature of these questions, the researcher decided to place these questions near the end of the questionnaire after the evaluation questions to reduce bias from customers' responses. The reason for putting demographic characteristics of respondents into the survey is because there exists evidence that these demographic characteristics influence Digital Banking satisfaction and loyalty (Oliveira et al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2017).

Table 4.7 presents the demographic measures used in the current research

Construct	Classification
Age (in years)	18-24
	25-34
	35-44
	45-54
	55 and above
Gender	Male
	Female
	Think of yourself in another way
	Prefer not to say
Education level	Under graduate
	Graduate

	Post graduate
Occupation	Student
	Public servant/Office staff
	Businessman
	Self-employed
	Worker
	Retired
	Housewife
Monthly income	Under 500\$/month
	500\$- under 800\$/month
	800\$- under 1000\$/month
	>=1000\$/month
Current relationship status	Single
	Married
	Separated
	Divorced
	Widowed
Experience of using Digital Banking Services	Less than 6 months
	6 months to a year
	1 - 2 years
	2 or more years
Internet usage literacy	Beginner
	Intermediate
	Advanced

Table 4. 7 Demographic measures (Source: Author)

- ✓ Part 5: Open-ended questions for recommendations and thank you

4.9.3. Survey Questionnaire content validity

For the demonstration of content validity, the questionnaire for the survey was examined by a board of experts, including two banking managers and two professors of Foreign Trade University in Vietnam. The two bank managers have expertise in Banking practice. The two professors have expertise in marketing research, particularly bank marketing and e-commerce; therefore, they will be the best person to check the content of the survey questionnaires as suggested by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019).

Following the suggestion by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) and Hammoud et al. (2018) from similar research, the questionnaire was initially written in English and then translated into Vietnamese. Subsequently, that interpreted Vietnamese version of the survey was retranslated back into English and was cross-examined by two other bilingual researchers and two Vietnamese banking managers. This technique was used in order to ensure the intended meaning of the questions was precisely and adequately conveyed. Finally, the two English and Vietnamese versions of the survey were double-checked to ensure its clarity, reliability and validity (wording and meaning), reaching the final questions for the pilot study.

4.9.4. Pilot study for survey

The research conducted a pilot test to enhance questionnaire structure and content. Fifty questionnaires were distributed to banking customers who have experienced using Digital Banking in the studied bank. The researcher ensured that the respondents taking part in the pilot test were not used in the actual data collection and analysis as suggested by (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Modifications of the survey content and format were incorporated into two final survey versions in English and Vietnamese based on the pilot test results and final recommendations of the two banking senior executives and two bilingual researchers.

4.9.5. Survey distribution

Convenience sampling technique was used to collect the survey quantitative data as it allowed the most accessible approach to the survey respondents (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The survey instrument was created online through Survey Monkey and was shared on different social media channels (e.g., Facebook, Zalo, Telegram) with the URL link or by emails sent to prospective respondents. As pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019), this convenience sampling technique allowed the researcher to gain the right sample size quickly, access a “diverse pool of respondents”, and improve the response rate.

4.9.6. Potential non-response bias

Non - response bias happens when a surveyor does not respond to your survey or survey question because they are unable or do not want to complete it. While the reasoning for not completing or responding to the survey can vary, non- response bias can make your survey data less accurate. The researcher was aware of the possibility of non-response bias in the current research, in which the opinions and behaviours of individuals who chose to participate to the survey may differ consistently from those who did not.

Several measures were implemented to mitigate the potential impact of non-response bias.

Firstly, the researcher purposely chose not to give incentives for participation in order to avoid attracting participants who would just take part in the research for the incentive, which could have an impact on the authenticity of their comments (Resnik, 2015). Instead, the researcher underlined the significance and relevance of the study to encourage participation.

Additionally, in order to address the non-response bias, the researcher followed up regularly with the participants or sent them with friendly reminder. Since the survey was created online by Survey Monkey platform, this allowed the researcher to set up the “Schedule Reminder” automatically to gently encourage the participations.

Since the survey was created online by Survey Monkey platform, the researcher could be able to craft the survey to be accessible and user-friendly across multiple devices (mobile phone, Iphone, Ipad) to enhance the survey's accessibility, this allowed the researcher to meet the digital habits of our survey target – digital banking users, which again motivated participants.

It is worth noting that although the researcher has made significant efforts to mitigate non-response bias, it is crucial to acknowledge the fact that no methodology can completely eliminate this risk. However, by proactively taking this into account and addressing it in the research methodology, the researcher has made a conscious effort in enhancing the validity and reliability of the research findings.

4.10. Interview Data Collection Process

4.10.1. Participants' Profile

By dint of previous working experience in the Vietnam banking sector, to choose participants for the interview, the researcher initially requested former colleagues to establish connections and secure contacts with the bank managers. The interviewee selection was purposive to answer the research questions from the bank managers who have good knowledge and understanding regarding the bank's innovations, digital technologies, and the service they render to their customers via Digital Banking. It was also ensured that the relevant bank managers understood innovations with their objectives, implementation purposes, and challenges of implementing digital innovations in banks.

The researcher had successfully had five interview acceptance from five bank managers of the studied bank. They all have important roles in the studied bank with a deep understanding of Digital Banking developments and the customer service of the studied bank. They have been working in the studied bank for 10-16 years.

Table 4.8 presents the demographic information of the interviewees in this study.

BM	Gender	Age	Title/Position	Department	Number of years in bank
1	F	32	Deputy of Department Customer Service Centre	Head office	10 years.
2	F	42	Deputy of Department- Senior customer advisor	Head office	13 years
3	F	39	Bank branch manager	Branch	12 years.
4	F	45	Supervisor	Head office	16 years
5	F	38	Deputy of Department	Customer Service Centre	10 years

Table 4. 8 Demographic information of the interviewees (Source: Author)

4.10.2. Interview Questionnaire Design

As mentioned earlier, this current research adopted semi-structured interviews. The interview questions were extrapolated from the factors used in the conceptual framework. The semi-structured interview questions were focussed on the and topic were mainly focussed on the following key issues, which is captured from the five key executives:

The interview allowed the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of Digital Banking’s current developments and its impact on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty from bank managers’ perspectives. The interview supports the findings of the quantitative approach – customer survey to gain a richer picture about the topic.

The interview questionnaire consists of three main parts (See Appendix I: Interview Schedule in English and Appendix K Interview Schedule in Vietnamese).

Part 1: Personal Demographics Pertaining Participants’ Job Title, Department, Length of Working in the studied bank

Part 2: Current Digital Banking Developments pertaining Bank Managers' Perception about Positive Results, Overall Quality, Competitors, Overall Customer Satisfaction, Digital Banking Staffs, Information Security, Major Investments and Partnerships.

Part 3: Challenges and opportunities pertaining to Bank Managers' Perception challenges and opportunities of Digital Banking developments in the studied bank.

4.10.3. Interview Questionnaire content validity

For the demonstration of content validity, the questionnaire for the survey interview was examined by a board of experts, including two banking managers and two professors of Foreign Trade University in Vietnam. The two bank managers have expertise in Banking practice and the two professors have expertise in marketing research, particularly bank marketing and e-commerce, so they will be the best people to check the content of the survey questionnaires as suggested by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019).

As suggested by Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) and Hammoud et al. (2018), the questionnaire was initially written in English and then translated into Vietnamese. Subsequently, that interpreted Vietnamese version of the survey was retranslated back into English and was cross-examined by two other bilingual researchers and two Vietnamese banking managers in order to ensure the intended meaning was precisely and adequately conveyed. Finally, the two English and Vietnamese versions of the interview were double-checked to ensure its clarity, reliability and validity (wording and meaning).

4.10.4. Pilot study for interview

Before conducting any interview, the first piloted interview was conducted with an interviewee whom the researcher has known for many years as a friend but who is also a bank senior executive in the studied bank with more than 10 years of banking experience and is also unaffiliated to the study. The interview covered all the questions in the primary interview

questionnaire. It was also used to test the online platform to record and conduct the interview. The consent form was signed by the interviewee before commencing the piloted interview. The interviewee was also informed about the recording of the interview along with other requirements that are mentioned in the consent form. The whole interview was conducted in the same manner that the main interviews followed. The time of the discussion was maintained. After finishing the interview, the recorded interview was transcribed and sent to the interviewee for confirmation of the correctness. Once the interviewee confirmed the correctness of the data, then the transcribed interview was sent to the supervisor. The aim of the pilot interview is to ensure the clarity of the interview questions as well as to estimate the length of the interview. A few corrections were needed to make in the primary questionnaire following a slight change advised by the lead supervisor for better fitness of the required data. Once the lead supervisor was happy, the main interviews were conducted.

4.11. Secondary Data

4.11.1. Justifications for the need for secondary data

This Doctoral Thesis research involves primary data collection (survey and interviews), so collecting and analysing secondary data in the study can support the primary data and strengthen the research results as in line with (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Also, one of the research questions is to determine the challenges and opportunities of digital transformation in Vietnam, so the collected secondary data may prove helpful in allowing the researcher to answer, or partially answer, that research questions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

The main types of secondary data used in this research were documents, followed by multiple sources. This is reasonable because this research uses a case study and collects primary data, which goes in line with suggestions from Saunders et al. (2019): “a case study of a particular organisation or research that collects primary data will often use documentary secondary data”.

4.11.2.Types of secondary data used

According to Saunders et al. (2019), three broad types of secondary data are survey, document, and multiple sources. Adapting these classifications to this research, the author used main secondary data types, which were presented along with examples of sources in Table 4.9 below:

Types of Secondary Data used in current research		
Survey	Documents	Multiple Source
Organisations' survey: McKinsey, PwC, FT Focus, OECD, BCG...	Reports: WB, McKinsey, KMPG, IMF, Austrade, J.P.Morgan, AsiaMoney, IntellAsia, PwC, FT Focus, General Statistics Office, Bank Annual Reports	Vietnam Government Publications: Economy, Banking Sector, Digital Transformation...
Governments' surveys	Interview Transcript: Interview banking professors, SBV, Governments...	Books: Retail and Digital Banking (Henderson, 2018)
	News Report: VIR, VietnamNews, , Banking Plus, Banking Review, The Banker, Enternews, VnExpress, VnEconomy	Banking Industry Reports
	Magazines/Articles: Banking Review, BankingPlus	Banking and DB Journal Articles: Banking Review
	Organisations' websites: MOF, SBV, BCSI, Banks	
	Visual document: VTV/ FBNC about DB	

Table 4. 9 Types of secondary data used in current research (Source: Author)

4.11.3. The secondary data collection process

The researcher used a wide variety of procedures to collect the secondary data. Firstly, based on high-quality journal articles and books that the researcher has read when conducting the literature review, the researcher have an idea of what types of secondary data are possible for her research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Then the researcher read the journal articles' bibliography to find out the original source of data, then search the appropriate online database, find and download the data if possible (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The researcher tried to find the official PDF file, downloaded it into a separate folder, and saved it in Mendeley for later referencing.

Browsing and reading quality national newspapers about the main themes of the research (e.g., Vietnam Investment Review, Banking Plus...) regularly throughout her DBA journey is also beneficial in helping the researcher to navigate secondary data because these newspapers frequently report summary results of recent reports (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). It was actually a time-consuming process from establishing the likely availability of secondary data, locating secondary data to evaluating secondary sources using Checkbox in Saunders et al.(2019), but eventually it totally worth it because the researcher have successfully gained a wealth of valuable and suitable secondary data for her research.

In this research, the document review technique is used as much as practically possible and have been the source of the literature review and an in-depth internal investigation within the chosen institution. This also has been a invaluable resource to complement and identify appropriate semi-structured interview questions and to further design the questions for the survey for triangulation purposes.

4.12. Qualitative Data Analysis

There are two methods used for data analysis, namely quantitative and qualitative data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Quantitative data analysis allows the researcher to convert and analyse numerical data into meaningful information by employing critical and rational thinking (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Quantitative data analysis examines the difference and frequencies of variables (Creswell and Clark, 2017). Moreover, in quantitative data analysis, researchers often analyse the collected data in searching for evidence to support or reject the proposed hypotheses(Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Qualitative data analysis allows the development of theories of the research to from the data collected (Saunders et al., 2012) to come up with generalizable statements from the comparison

of different texts, cases and materials (Bazeley & Patricia, 2013). Conversely, qualitative data analysis is the “classification and interpretation of linguistic (or visual) material to make statements about implicit and explicit dimensions and structures of meaning-making in the material and what is represented in it” (Bazeley & Patricia, 2013). However, the generation of meaning from qualitative interpretations can be subjective to the social meanings of the research.

Based on the data collection methods, this present research adopted qualitative data analysis method for analysing bank manager’s perceptions while also adopting quantitative data analysis techniques for analysing survey data from customers. Using both these data analysis techniques allowed the researcher to maintain coherence with the research design outlined earlier and achieve a more comprehensive research outcome.

4.12.1. Approaches to Qualitative analysis of data

There are different approaches for qualitative data analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). In this present research, the researcher only considers two qualitative data analysis, namely Thematic Analysis and Template Analysis which will be discussed in more detail below:

Thematic Analysis

Thematic Analysis starts with coding all data items prior to the research of themes, which is called a coding template (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). Thematic analysis is a systematic method of finding, categorising and proposing insight into a pattern of themes through a dataset. This analysis is an increasingly prevalent qualitative data analysis method that is also flexible and accessible (Brown & Clarke, 2012). Moreover, the thematic analysis method is becoming a widely accepted, unique and valuable method besides other established approaches (e.g., narrative, discourse analysis and grounded theory) (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). As mentioned earlier, accessibility and flexibility are the two key reasons for using this qualitative data analysis. For

the new researchers who conduct qualitative research, the thematic analysis provides access to the research that would otherwise be seen as imprecise, confusing, over-complex and conceptually challenging (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). Brown and Clarke (2012) also state that the thematic analysis approach offers an entrance into qualitative research that provides a coding mechanism and a systematic analysis of qualitative data. This can be linked to wider conceptual and theoretical issues. The broader debates of thematic analysis help qualitative research that it was the most appropriate for wider audiences.

The thematic map is either visual (Brown and Clarke (2012)) or textual (Frith and Gleeson, 2004). These elements help to derive analysis and recognising theme, sub-themes and interconnections between both. There will be six phases to the approach of thematic analysis briefly discussed below.

- Familiarising with qualitative data: in this phase, the researcher will be immersed in the collected data by 'reading and re-reading' and then re-reading text-based data. For example, interview transcripts, case studies, surveys, observations).
- Generating primary code: this phase will develop codes from the primary data generating initial codes.
- Looking for themes: This phase will search for themes from initially generated codes.
- Re-examining potential themes: Re-examining potential themes involves recursion where the derived themes are re-examined concerning the data coded and the whole dataset collected. In essence, it is all about the quality checking of the themes.
- Naming and defining themes: This phase should clearly identify the themes regarding their uniqueness and specification by naming the themes.
- Creating the report: This phase finally should create a clear and convincing report. Many authors say that a thematic analysis report should go beyond explaining the research questions and creating valid arguments.

Template Analysis

As pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019), Template Analysis starts with the coding process of only part of the data before establishing codes and themes. In Template Analysis, the main analytical tool is the coding template, which consists of a hierarchical list of codes and themes (Sharlene, 2010; Brooks et al., 2015). In studies conducting qualitative analysis by Template Analysis, researchers will start by coding a percentage of data only (e.g., the first interview transcript), but not the whole set of data in order to develop an initial coding template (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). Subsequently, the codes are arranged until a satisfactory initial template is established. Afterward, the remaining collected data (e.g., interview transcripts) will be coded based on the initial template. Modifications will be made with the new data being used, which, lastly results in the formation of a final coding template (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). Both Thematic Analysis and Template Analysis relate to the coding of data items. However, the difference between these two qualitative analysis approaches is that Thematic Analysis starts with the coding of all data items prior to the research of themes, while template analysis starts with the coding process of only part of the data before establishing codes and themes (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

4.12.2. The selected Qualitative Analysis Approach

Based on the discussion above, the research adopted Template Analysis because it allowed the researcher to perform coding from the research-related factor questions and the collected data. Hence, the analytical codes were based on the key empirical themes of the research, which are Digital Banking, the development of Digital Banking Vietnam, Digital Banking Service Quality affecting customer satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in Vietnam, challenges for Digital Banking developments in Vietnam.

The researcher established the themes from the research's literature review and from the major terms emphasised during the interviews. The researcher did not develop its themes based on the representation or opinion of the researcher's personal experience. Therefore, the themes were strong and aimed at addressing validity and reliability factors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The researcher applied the Template Analysis method to summarise responses of the participants based on the key themes of the literature in order to generate a clear understanding of the interviewees' perceptions.

4.12.3. Issues in Template Analysis and the Overcoming Approach

One of the main disadvantages of template analysis is that the coding process can remove some texts from the research themes, which leads to the loss of meaning of the responses (Bryan, 2012). Secondly, as Brooks et al. (2015) criticised, the template analysis's flexibility may lead to the lack of coherence or inconsistency because the themes are established based on both literature review and the research data. Furthermore, the lack of meaningful literature on the technique compared to other methods such as grounded theory can have a negative impact on the quality of the data analysis (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). If the coding uses simple language, researchers may not accurately state the opinions of the respondents (Brooks *et al.*, 2015).

To overcome the above limitation, the researcher constructed the themes based on an extensive literature review of high-quality journal articles to establish the key themes that appear to be significant for the research topic (Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions). The researcher then compares theoretical terms in the literature and the terms used by the interviewees to achieve the research objectives. This allows the researcher to investigate different aspects of the interviewees, obtain unanticipated insights and emphasise both similarities and differences (Brooks *et al.*, 2015). The researcher also found that the template analysis could be quickly followed, thanks to its prescriptions and procedures (Braun & Clarke, 2006), enabling the researcher to overcome the difficulties and conduct a rigorous analysis.

4.13. Quantitative Data Analysis

4.13.1. Approaches to the Quantitative Data Analysis

Univariate analysis

Univariate is the simplest data-analysis method which primarily used for description, data collection, data summary and data-pattern searching (Sanchez, 2006).

In univariate analysis, each variable is measured and examined separately, which means univariate analysis do not examine the relationships or causes like bivariate analysis or multivariate analysis (Sanchez, 2006).

In univariate analysis, the description of data pattern can be implemented by using different techniques such as dispersion (variance, range, maximum, minimum and quartiles (including interquartile range), standard deviation, or central tendency (including mean, mode and median) (Sanchez, 2006).

As pointed out by Sanchez (2006), the options for description of univariate data are Histograms, Frequency Distribution Tables, Pie Charts, Frequency Polygons and Bar Charts.

Bivariate analysis

Bivariate analysis is the analysis of two variables at the same time to investigate the relationship between them (Denis, 2020). Bivariate analysis is applied to perform the investigation of relationship among variables to a greater extent than simple frequencies for individual ones (Denis, 2020).

Bivariate analysis consists of three main types of analysis method, namely: scatter plots, regression analysis and correlation coefficients (Denis, 2021). Bivariate analysis only provide a description for the relationship between the two variables without an explanation because it causally does not factor in how a variable could influence the other (Denis, 2021). Therefore,

Explanatory analysis is often used together with bivariate analysis to provide a richer findings (Denis, 2021).

Multivariate analysis

Tenny & Abdelgawad (2021) point out that multivariate analysis is applied in to studying and analysing data sets which are more complicated than the data which can be handled by univariate analysis methods. In order to use multivariate analysis, researchers needs to employs software such as SPSS or Python to analyse data due to the fact that manual data analysis is cumbersome even for the smallest data sets (Denis, 2021). While Bivariate analysis methods only examine the relationship between two variables, multivariate analysis methods are often used to evaluate whether a third variable has impact on the others (Denis, 2021).

Statistical significance

Statistical significance is regarded as a measuring method to evaluate whether the research outcomes are meaningful and how close the statistics of the research matches the expected value that researchers wish to find in an entire research population (Tenny and Abdelgawad, 2021). Statistical significance has been gaining significant popularity recently because more and more companies currently rely on data to make critical decisions (Tenny and Abdelgawad, 2021).

4.13.2. The selected Quantitative Analysis Approach

This present study adopted univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis for quantitative data analysis in order to determine which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions exert the strongest impact on Customer Satisfaction. Univariate analysis method is also used with bar charts automatically generated on Survey Monkey in order to represent descriptive analysis for the quantitative data. This study is also used bivariate and multivariate analysis because it

employs Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient with Python software based on the suggestion and guidance of Mukaka (2012) and (Denis (2021).

Bivariate analysis using Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient is applied for determination of the relationship between two variables: Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and Customer Satisfaction. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is a non-parametric statistic widely used in machine learning to examine whether the monotonic relationships between variables exist and how strong they are (Mukaka, 2012). Multivariate analysis was employed by using Python Software for implementing Spearman's rank correlation coefficient for assessment of the relationship between the independent variables (Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions) and the dependent variables (Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty); between Customer Satisfaction and Trust (independent variables) with Customer Loyalty (dependent variable).

4.14. Triangulation method

Several frameworks have been established to evaluate the qualitative data's accuracy and trustworthiness (Guba and Lincoln, 1985). Moreover, numerous strategies have been written for finding transferability, confirmability, credibility and dependability of qualitative data (Pamela and Susan, 2008). This research has ensured that enough details are provided so that the readers can have access to the research's validity and reliability. In addition, triangulation of the data sources and data types has been viewed and discovered from different facets.

As stated earlier, this research is aimed at exploring the role & extent of digital technology on banking services with empirical evidence being sought from the banks that determine the impacts of digital services in terms of meeting customers' expectations that will ultimately improve customer retention banks growth and sustainability. Thus, this is to find that the semi-structured interview and the survey can be connected effectively to an integrated framework

provided. Furthermore, the data collection and the comparison made from reputable secondary sources can enhance the quality, credibility, validity, reliability and trustworthiness of the data based on the philosophies of the case study of the research, idea convergence and findings (Knafl and Breitmayer, 1989).

4.15. Data management

Data management is defined as the principles and practices used to help researchers effectively use, manage and preserve research data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Blaxter et al. (2010) pointed out that the risk of facing errors in research data is diverse and inestimable and emphasised the importance of accurate data collection and management because good data will result in insightful and reliable research findings.

During the interviews, discussion can be complex and the researcher could miss or overlook information, which can negatively affect the data quality and, therefore, the results of the data collection (Bazeley, 2013). To manage the consistency and accuracy of the collected data from the interview, the researcher seeks permission from the participants (five bank managers) to record the interviews and use note-taking when necessary to reduce the risk of relying on the recording as suggested by Bazeley (2013). The audio records and documents collected from the interviews were stored securely and protected by passwords on the researcher's computer. Paper notes were also destroyed after the data was entered into the computer.

4.16. Ethical considerations

Saunders et al. (2019) defines ethics as the appropriateness of the researcher in protecting the rights of the participants or of the people who are impacted by the research. (Rizza, Büscher and Watson, 2017) proposed the concept of ethics as the behaviour criteria including the instructions and guidance for the researcher on how to behave and form relationships with others during the research process.

In other ways, research ethics is concerned with every step in the research process: developing and clarifying the research topic and design; gaining access, collecting and storing, analysing data and preparing the research report without leaving any negative impact on the researcher and people who are involved in the research (Saunders et al., 2019; Israel & Hay, 2006). This researcher guarantees that this present study was strictly governed by UWS Ethics Committee Guidance. Moreover, data collection only proceeded after the UWS Ethical Approval was granted for my research proposal. The approval from the university showed that this research meets the ethical standard and shall not have any negative impact on the researcher and its participants and shall not produce any disadvantage or unethical results (Israel and Hay, 2006). Moreover, Saunders et al. (2019) and Braun & Clarke (2006) pointed out several issues in research implementation, namely access, informed consent, vulnerable groups of people, and respect for anonymity and confidentiality, which requires the compliance with ethical standards in order to protect both the researcher and participants avoiding any harmful or embarrassing situations. Ethical considerations in this research in terms of different issues is discussed below:

- ✓ Access Consideration: This research would make use of primary and secondary data and needed access to obtain all the empirical evidence required. A clear written and oral brief about the resolution of this study, the researcher's contact details, and the collected data used in this research were provided to the contributors before giving their approval. To obtain the primary data by way of performing semi structured interviews, securing access to the organisation was mandatory. A formal email with CONSENT FORM and PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET summarising the purpose of the study and how the collected data would be used was sent to bank managers and they kindly offered their permission. The researcher has also informed the participants on the voluntary participation in the research and the withdrawal is possible at any moment if they do not wish to continue.

Please see

- Appendix E: Information Sheet for Participants in English
 - Appendix F: Information Sheet for Participants in Vietnamese
 - Appendix G: Participant Consent Form in English
 - Appendix H: Participant Consent Form in Vietnamese
- ✓ Confidentiality and Anonymity: The participants' anonymity was highly deliberated. Bank names and persons' names were encoded during the interview transcription. Also, confidentiality awareness as a declaration was given to the participants before conducting the interview. The researcher avoids asking questions about participants' private lives, as Walker (2012) suggested. The researcher seeks permission from the participants (five bank managers) to record the interviews and use note-taking when necessary to reduce the risk of relying on the recording, as suggested by Bazeley (2013). The audio records and documents obtained from the interview and survey results from Survey Monkey were stored securely and protected by passwords on the researcher's computer. Note taking for the interviews were destroyed after finishing the transcript and translation of interview result while all the records will be deleted when the research concludes. Only the researcher and the supervisor had access to research data. The information, notes and recordings of the participants were used only for research purpose. Moreover, the name of the bank will be anonymously presented as "the studied bank" and the viewpoints of the participants were anonymously presented for data analysis and presentation.
- ✓ Vulnerable groups of People: Dillman (2007) defined vulnerable groups of people as people who could not protect their rights and welfare who cannot provide their informed consent and need protection from studies of sensitive topics. Researchers cannot force this group of people to do the research. However, this group of people is not applicable to this

current research as this research was conducted with Digital Banking customers and bank managers in Vietnam on the basis of voluntarily.

4.17. Research Validity

Research validity is defined as the degree to which the research accurately reflects the actual concepts it intended to investigate Donlevy et al. (2002). There are two types of research validity: content validity and construct validity as suggested by Donlevy et al. (2002). Content validity refers to the level to which the researcher or research instrument adequately covers the required content of the research with respect to the required variable and whether the research instrument addresses the whole domain related to the variable (Devellis and Thorpe, 2022). Construct validity, on the other hand refers to whether the research can develop implications that are related to the concepts under study Donlevy et al. (2002).

In this present thesis, the researcher performs the content validity by investigating whether the research addresses the required subjects related to the concept of Digital Banking, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty. In the meantime, construct validity will scrutinise whether the research can develop interpretations relating to Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction concepts.

From a different perspective, Hardesty & Bearden (2004) classified two kinds of validity: internal and external validity. Internal validity examines whether the research measures what it intended to measure while external validity evaluates the generalisation of research outcomes.

In this present thesis, the researcher sustained a neutral attitude during the interview to diminish the propensity of interpreting the participants' perceptions by her own preconceived notions(Sharlene, 2010). In terms of the participants, the researcher also tried to diminish the

likelihood of bias by lowering the tendency of providing answers which would support pre-conceived notions by the participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The researcher also probed and confirmed participants' responses to guarantee that the actual viewpoints were provided, which enabled the researcher to avoid misconceptions and misunderstandings.

4.18. Research Reliability

Research reliability is the level at which consistent results can be generated from the research analysis or data collection methods. As pointed out by Saunders et al. (2019), research reliability examines whether the same results can be attained if the research is conducted by another party in a similar context. Bryman (2012) argued that using interviews can result in low-reliability research findings due to various types of bias arising in the discussions, especially when researchers tend to compare different views of participants. Sharing the same opinion, Creswell & Clark (2017) also pointed out that using interviews can lead to low reliability in research findings and admitted that no research could be completely reliable.

Therefore, to overcome the issues related to interview bias, to maintain reliability, this research applied the techniques recommended by Saunders et al., (2019) for conducting the interviews. Researchers used audio recordings along with note-taking during the interview in order to reduce dependence on recordings only. Besides, after the completed transcripts were sent back to the participants for them to check whether their opinion was adequately conveyed and also for them to make clarifications if needed (Sharlene, 2010).

4.19. Summary

This Chapter described the research approach single case study that is believed to be most appropriate in understanding the wider Digital Banking utilisation issues and to explore the ways in which Digital Banking was utilised to support customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in an emerging economy like Vietnam. It presented a discussion of case study research

in terms of its theoretical underpinnings. The research design was then described in terms of how the conceptual model was operationalised in this particular study. It indicated how and where the study was staged, who the participants were, and the methods of data collection and analysis employed.

CHAPTER FIVE: QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

5.1. Introduction

This Chapter puts forward the quantitative data analysis, followed by a critical evaluation of the findings by relating the findings to the previous studies. Quantitative obtained from a self-administered web survey (Survey Monkey) of 660 Vietnam Digital Banking customers was utilised to investigate the hypotheses related to the correlations between the research constructs using Spearman Correlation Coefficient with Python software. After the hypotheses test, key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty” were identified, answering Research Question 1. The researcher also conducted a descriptive analysis to investigate the customers’ perceptions about current Digital Banking applications in the studied bank, answering Research Question 2.

5.2. Summary of Actual Data Collection

By dint of previous working in the bank before the researchers, the research secured network connections with banking staff and banking managers. Firstly, the URL survey link was sent to banking professors of the studied bank in several branches residing in major cities of Vietnam: Hanoi Hochiminh City, Haiduong, Haiphong, Danang, requesting them to take part and forward the e-mails or survey link to their contacts (family members, friends, colleagues) and, especially to the customers of the studied bank. By leveraging the researcher's past relationships within the banking industry, the researcher was able to circulate the survey amongst a diverse lists of customers who routinely use digital banking services of the studied bank, which is consistent with the study's objectives. Although the survey was initially distributed in the main cities of Vietnam, by leveraging the power of the internet and digital platforms, the survey was distributed online, this allowed the researcher to to gather an array of responses from different regions of Vietnam, which added a rich depth to the data. By online

survey, the research was able to collect a total of 715 questionnaires, among which 660 usable questionnaires were usable, 55 questionnaires are invalid due to the fact that respondents failed to complete the questionnaire or were not the studied bank customers, giving a completion rate of 92.3per cent, which is relatively high and successful compared to another similar research stated in Chapter 2. Table 5.1 illustrates an outline of survey responses:

Survey Summary Data	
Method	Survey Monkey, online distribution
Start date	16/11/2021
End date	16/12/2021
Total responses	715
Completed responses	660
Incomplete/invalid responses (deleted)	55
Completion rate	92.3per cent

Table 5. 1 Summary of Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.3. Participants' Profile

Of a total of 715 questionnaires distributed, 660 respondents responded, yielding a response rate of 92.3% percent. Out of 660 total respondents, the majority 67.73 per cent are banking customers of the studied bank for three or more years and 14.24 per cent are for 1 to 2 years. Almost half of all the total 660 respondents (48.94 per cent) use Digital Banking services several times per week. The sample comprised 48.03 per cent (317 respondents) within the aged range of 25 to 34, followed by 23.79 per cent per cent (157 respondents) were within the age range of 35 to 44, then 15.76 per cent (104 respondents) were from 18-24 years old. The least percentages fall into the age group 55 and more (59 respondents with 8.94per cent per cent) and the age group 45 to 54 (23 respondents with 3.48per cent per cent). A gender distribution of mainly 62.58 per cent (413) were females and 35.76 per cent (236) were males,

followed by 0.91 per cent (6) preferred not to say and then 0.76 (5) per cent think of themselves in another way were seen in the total. Regarding Education Level, 81.81 percent of respondents have Graduate and Postgraduate Education Level. Regarding Occupation, a majority of 56.52 per cent are Public servant/Office staff, 10.91 per cent are Business people, 10.76 per cent are Student, followed by the rest: Retired (6.97 per cent), Self-employed (6.52 per cent), Worker (6.52 per cent- same percentage as Self- employed) and lastly Housewife (1.82 per cent).

5.4. Limitations encountered

In order to gather quantitative data, a convenience sampling method was adopted with the support of online survey for digital banking users of the studied bank. The survey was crafted online by Survey Monkey as a practical response to the Covid-19 pandemic restrictions, when face-to-face data collecting was impractical due to social distance regulations and health concerns. Although the online survey approach proved especially beneficial, it did, however, inevitably have certain drawbacks. The use of convenience sampling might mean that our sample is not fully representative of the broader population of digital banking customers, restraining the generalisability of the findings. In addition, even though we were successful in gathering response from 92.3% of participants who was targeted, the self-reported nature of the survey might introduce response bias, with participants potentially providing socially desirable responses.

5.5.Descriptive analysis- General Information Analysis

The main aim of conducting a descriptive analysis of the collected survey data is to understand customers' overall perceptions about the Digital Banking services they are currently using, answering a part of Research Question 2 outlined in Chapter 1- perceptions of banking customer:

RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?"

The first section of the questionnaires asks respondents for general information about their Digital Banking usage. Descriptive analysis of general information is presented below.

5.5.1. Length of banking relationship

This question asks respondents how long they have been the studied bank customers, including four options: less than 6 months, 6 months - 1 year, 1 – 2 years, 3 or more years. (Note: The answer choice “I have not been a customer of the studied bank yet” is only used to ensure the respondents are the studied bank customers).

Table 5.2 indicates the Length of business relationships between customers and the studied bank.

The analysis shows that out of 660 total respondents, the majority are the studied bank customers for three or more years (67.73 per cent/447 respondents), followed by the studied bank for 1 to 2 years (14.24 per cent /94 respondents), the studied bank customers for less than six months (10.30 per cent/68 respondents) and the studied bank for six months to a year (7.73 per cent/51 respondents). This finding implies that most respondents have three years or more of business relationships with the studied bank, which means they have enough experience and understanding to answer the studied bank services/products questions. This also enhanced the reliability of their responses obtained.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Less than 6 months	10.30%	68
Six months to a year	7.73%	51
1 - 2 years	14.24%	94
3 or more years	67.73%	447
I have not been a customer of Vietcombank yet.	0.00%	0
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 2 Length of banking relationship (Source: Author)

5.5.2. Number of banking relationships

This question asks respondents about how many banks they currently have business relationships. The result is presented in Table 5.3 below.

In terms of number of banking relationships, the analysis shows that most of the 660 respondents are currently having business relationships with more than two banks (52.58 per cent with 347 responses), followed by 30.76 per cent with 203 respondents have two banks, and 16.67 per cent with 110 respondents are having business relationships with only one bank (in this case, it is the studied bank). In short, a majority of respondents (83.34 per cent of the total 660 respondents) are currently having business relationships with at least two banks. This implies the increasingly significant competition in Vietnam Banking Industry, and the need to foster the relationship between the case bank and its clients to enhance their satisfaction and loyalty.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
One	16.67%	110
Two	30.76%	203
More than two	52.58%	347
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 3 Number of banking relationships (Source: Author)

5.5.3. Primary bank

The result of the question asking respondents whether they consider the studied bank as their primary bank or not is presented in Table 5.4 below.

The table indicates that most of the 660 respondents currently consider the studied bank as their primary bank with 441 respondents (66.82 per cent) while the rest 219 respondents (33.18 per cent) do not consider the studied bank as their primary bank. This implies that most respondents have enough experience and understanding to answer the studied bank services/products questions. This will enhance the reliability of their responses in the data obtained. This result also implies the customer preferences and increasing competition in Vietnam Banking Industry.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	66.82%	441
No	33.18%	219
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 4 Primary bank (Source: Author)

5.5.4. Frequency of using the studied bank Digital Banking Channels

Table 5.5 below presents the analysis of the Frequency of using the studied bank Digital Banking Channels of respondents.

The result shows a mix in the Frequency of using the studied bank Digital Banking Channels. As presented in Table 5.5, almost half of all the total 660 respondents (48.94 per cent/323 respondents) use Digital Banking services several times per week, followed by 17.88 per cent use Digital Banking several times a month. However, the results also reflected 19.70 per cent (130 respondents) rarely use Digital Banking services, although they are the studied bank customers.

For most respondents who are currently using the Digital Banking channels quite frequently, there is a need to foster their bank - customers relationships via Digital Banking to improve the bank's business growth. On the other hand, the significant number of respondents who have not adopted Digital Banking presented in the results implies a need to identify the reasons to increase Digital Banking adoption and usage.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Several times a week	48.94%	323
About once a week	5.45%	36
Several times a month	17.88%	118
About once a month	4.70%	31
Less than once a month	3.33%	22
Rarely	19.70%	130
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 5 Frequency of using the studied bank Digital Banking Channels

(Source: Author)

5.5.5. Financial transactions made by Digital Banking channels

Customers were asked to choose which financial transactions they often make by Digital Banking channels (participants can choose more than one option). The analysis of the financial transactions made by Digital Banking channels is presented in Table 5.6 below.

As presented in Table 5.6, respondents using Digital Banking channels to carry out a wide range of financial transactions with the order of prevalence is: transferring funds (91.67 per cent), managing account (63.03 per cent), QR code payments (55.00 per cent). Paying bills and topping up has quite a similar percentage, about 51 per cent each, followed by the other three Savings, Shopping and Bank Card Services with more or less than 40 per cent each. Significantly, a minor percentage (16.21 percent) falls into the respondents using Digital Banking channels for Insurance and Investment. The result implies that most respondents only use Digital Banking channels for simple transactions such as transferring funds and managing accounts. Insurance and Investment transactions via Digital Banking channels have not been a popular choice of customers. Hence, there is a need to diversify the financial transactions made by Digital Banking channels.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Managing account	63.03%	416
Transferring funds	91.67%	605
QR code payments	55.00%	363
Paying bills	51.67%	341
Topping up	51.36%	339
Savings	42.88%	283
Shopping	36.97%	244
Bank card services	43.33%	286
Insurance and investments	16.21%	107
Total Respondents: 660		

Table 5. 6 Financial transactions made by Digital Banking channels (Source: Author)

5.6. Descriptive analysis - Demographic Data Analysis

Demographic information was asked from Question 20 to Question 27 in the Survey Questionnaire and its analyses are presented in the item-by-item form. As an approach utilized in developing the understanding of the research perspective, demographic analysis of this study pertains to such information of the respondents namely Age Group, Education Level, Occupation, Monthly Income, Current Relationship Status, Experience of Using Digital Banking Services, Internet Usage Literacy.

Table 5.7 below shows comprehensive descriptive statistics of the respondents' characteristics data collected. It presents the findings of customer profile queries as Frequency (number of respondents) and percentage (per cent) of the data distribution.

Construct	Classification	Frequency (units)	Percentage (per cent)
Age (in years)	18-24	104	15.76per cent
	25-34	317	48.03per cent
	35-44	157	23.79per cent
	45-54	23	3.48per cent
	55 and above	59	8.94per cent
Gender	Male	236	35.76per cent
	Female	413	62.58per cent
	Think of yourself in another way	5	0.76per cent
	Prefer not to say	6	0.91per cent
Education level	Under graduate	120	18.18per cent
	Graduate	385	58.33per cent
	Post graduate	155	23.48per cent
Occupation	Student	71	10.76per cent
	Public servant/Office staff	373	56.52per cent
	Businessman	72	10.91per cent
	Self-employed	43	6.52per cent
	Worker	43	6.52per cent

	Retired	46	6.97per cent
	Housewife	12	1.82per cent
Monthly income	Under 500\$/month	199	30.15per cent
	500\$- under 800\$/month	176	26.67per cent
	800\$- under 1000\$/month	92	13.94per cent
	>=1000\$/month	193	29.24per cent
Current relationship status	Single	209	31.67per cent
	Married	429	65.00per cent
	Separated	5	0.76per cent
	Divorced	14	2.12per cent
	Widowed	3	0.45per cent
Experience of using Digital Banking Services	Less than 6 months	99	15.00per cent
	6 months to a year	68	10.30per cent
	1 - 2 years	68	10.30per cent
	2 or more years	425	64.39per cent
Internet usage literacy	Beginner	216	32.73per cent
	Intermediate	351	53.18per cent
	Advanced	93	14.09per cent
Note: Total completed responses for each construct		660	100per cent

Table 5. 7 Descriptive statistics of Survey respondents’ characteristics (Source: Author)

5.6.1. Age

Table 5.8 indicates the age group of the respondents.

The total sample of 660 respondents who are customers of the studied bank was categorised into five age categories. The order of prevalence is 48.03 per cent (317 respondents) were within the aged range of 25 to 34, followed by 23.79 per cent (157 respondents) were within the age range of 35 to 44, then 15.76 per cent (104 respondents) were from 18-24 years old. The least percentages fall into the age group 55 and more (59 respondents with 8.94per

cent per cent) and the age group 45 to 54 (23 respondents with 3.48per cent per cent). In short, the sample respondents were predominantly in the age group from 25 to 34 with 48.03 per cent (317 respondents), while the least is people in the 45-54 age group and more than 55. This implies that the studied bank gains more patronage from Vietnamese people aged 25 to 34. These are the very productive age who are very familiar with Digital Banking & related technologies that can contribute to further Digital Banking services sustainability. These are the age groups in which technology acceptance and utilisation are mostly appreciated, encouraging the studied bank to explore technology adoption to enhance customer relationship management in the study area. It assists the studied bank to relate to the main stakeholders – in this case, the bank customers. Since these are the active and productive age groups, they are relevant to the studied bank market exploration, retention, and gaining market advantage.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
18-24 year old	15.76%	104
25-34 year old	48.03%	317
35-44 year old	23.79%	157
45-54 year old	3.48%	23
55 and above	8.94%	59
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 8 Age group of the Survey Respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.2. Gender of respondents

Table 5.9 presents a descriptive analysis of the gender distribution of the respondents.

The results show a gender distribution of mainly 62.58 per cent (413) were females and 35.76 per cent (236) were males, followed by 0.91 per cent (6) preferred not to say and then 0.76 (5) per cent think of themselves in another way. This classification enables the data obtained for the research to accommodate opinions from various perspectives in terms of the Gender of

respondents. This data result shows that the studied bank Digital Banking captures every individual in society.

The results show that a more substantial percentage of respondents are females, and they are more involved in obtaining Digital Banking services business than their male counterparts. Thus, the impact of Digital Banking is observed to be more on females than males in this study area. Hence, the studied bank has the opportunity to concentrate on boosting the males' Gender of its customer base to improve the percentage of involvement towards expanding Digital Banking services.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Male	35.76%	236
Female	62.58%	413
Think of yourself in another way	0.76%	5
Prefer not to say	0.91%	6
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 9 Gender of the Survey respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.3. Education level

Table 5.10 presents a descriptive analysis of the Education Level of the respondents.

In terms of Education Level of respondents, the order of prevalence is Graduate Group (58.33 per cent/385 respondents), followed by Postgraduate Group (23.48 per cent/155 respondents) and Undergraduate Group (18.18 per cent /120). Hence, in total, 81.81 percent of respondents (540 out of 660) have Graduate and Postgraduate Education Level, which enables them to be literate to a certain extent to adopt and use Digital Banking services productively and efficiently, as in accordance with Mbama et al. (2018). This result will also enhance the quality and reliability of the data obtained for the research.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Under graduate	18.18%	120
Graduate	58.33%	385
Post graduate	23.48%	155
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 10 Education level of the Survey Respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.4. Occupation

The observation from the analysis of the demographic occupation information presented in Table 5.11 also further indicates different customers who patronise the studied bank Digital Banking services as its customers in Vietnam. These individuals included Student, Public servant/Office staff, Business People, Self-employed, Retired and Housewife.

This data presentation shows that the studied bank captures every individual in society.

Overall, with a total sample of 660 respondents as categorised into seven diverse groups, the sample customers had a majority of Public servant/Office staff (373 customers with 56.52 per cent), followed by Business people (72 respondents with 10.91 per cent), Student (71 respondents with 10.76 per cent), Retired (46 customers with 6.97 per cent), Self-employed (43 respondents with 6.52 per cent), Worker (43 respondents with 6.52 per cent- same percentage as Self- employed) and then lastly Housewife (12 customers with 1.82 per cent).

The result of the respondents' Occupation shows that the majority of the studied bank's customers are drawn from the Public Servant/Office staff group, followed by Business People and Student. This group of customers possesses a certain annual family income to seek more financial services from the studied bank Digital Banking. Thus, this group of customers would make the digital business highly relevant and excel because they are full of potential and productivity.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Student	10.76%	71
Public servant/Office staff	56.52%	373
Business people	10.91%	72
Self-employed	6.52%	43
Worker	6.52%	43
Retired	6.97%	46
Housewife	1.82%	12
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 11 Occupation of the Survey Respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.5. Monthly Income

The analysis of the monthly income information as presented in Table 5.12 indicates different income statuses of the respondents who are the studied bank customers.

As demonstrated in Table 5.12, most of the respondents have monthly income are under 500\$ (30.15 per cent/199 respondents), followed by those with monthly income above \$1000 (29.24 per cent/193 respondents), then monthly income from \$500 to under \$800 (26.67 per cent/176 respondents) and monthly income from \$800 to under \$1000 (13.94 per cent/92 respondents).

The analysis shows that 56.82 percent of respondents have a monthly income under \$800. This result is also consistent and reasonable, with the highest percentage of 56.52 per cent of respondents who were public servant/office staff. This, again, affirms the reliability of the data obtained.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Under 500\$/month	30.15%	199
500\$- under 800\$/month	26.67%	176
800\$- under 1000\$/month	13.94%	92
>=1000\$/month	29.24%	193
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 12 Monthly Income of the Survey Respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.6. Current Relationship Status

The analysis of the Current Relationship Status information as presented in Table 5.13 indicates different Current Relationship statuses of the respondents.

As demonstrated in Table 5.13, concerning Current Relationship Status, the largest population of respondents fall within married Group with 65 per cent (429 respondents), followed by Single Group with 31.67 per cent (209 respondents), then Divorced Group with 2.12 per cent (14 respondents), Separated Group with 0.76 per cent (5 respondents), and Widowed Group with 0.45 per cent (3 respondents). The result shows that the data obtained cover opinions from different people in terms of relationship status.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Single	31.67%	209
Married	65.00%	429
Separated	0.76%	5
Divorced	2.12%	14
Widowed	0.45%	3
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 13 Current Relationship Status of the Survey respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.7. Digital Banking Experience

The analysis of the Digital Banking Experience information as presented in Table 5.14 indicates different groups of Digital Banking Experience of the respondents: less than 6 months, 6 months - a year, 1-2 years, 2 or more years.

From Table 5.14, the sample consumers mainly had two or more years of experience using Digital Banking (64.39 per cent/425 respondents), followed by respondents who have less than six months of experience in Digital Banking (15 per cent/99 respondents). Interestingly, the other two groups, six months to a year and one-to-two-year experience in Digital Banking share the same percentage of 10.30 per cent (68 respondents) for each group.

The results cover opinions from all various Digital Banking experience groups. Most respondents have two or more years of Digital Banking Experience, which allowed them to have enough experience to answer the research questions.

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Less than 6 months	15.00%	99
6 months to a year	10.30%	68
1 - 2 years	10.30%	68
2 or more years	64.39%	425
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 14 Digital Banking Experience of the Survey Respondents (Source: Author)

5.6.8. Internet Usage Literacy

The analysis of the Internet usage literacy information as presented in Table 5.15 indicates different groups of Internet Usage Literacy of the respondents: Beginner, Intermediate and Advanced.

As in Table 5.15, most respondents describe themselves as having Intermediate Internet Usage Literacy with 53.18 per cent (351 respondents), followed by Beginner Group with 32.73 per cent (216 respondents), then Advanced Group with 14.09 per cent (93 respondents).

The results show that most respondents have at least Intermediate Internet Usage Literacy or more, with a total of 67.27 per cent (444 respondents). This implies that the respondents had high Internet literacy levels, which allowed them to use Digital Banking effectively and provide real experience for the Survey questionnaires, according to Mbama et al.(2018).

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Beginner	32.73%	216
Intermediate	53.18%	351
Advanced	14.09%	93
TOTAL		660

Table 5. 15 Internet usage literacy of the Survey respondents (Source: Author)

5.7. Descriptive analysis- Evaluations of Digital Banking service quality dimensions

To understand what customers appreciate and/or value about the Digital Banking services which they have been using in the studied bank, a number of questions were raised in the Survey to gain customers' evaluations of Digital Banking service quality dimensions, including Services Portfolio/Products (Q6), Ease of Use (Q7); Convenience (Q8); Usefulness (Q9); Reliability (Q10); Privacy and Security (Q11); Speed (Q12), Design (Q13); Customer Service and Support (Q14); Digital -Emotional Connection (Q15); Trust (Q16); Customer Satisfaction (Q17), Customer Loyalty (Q18), Covid-19 risk perceptions(Q19).

Table 5.16 to Table 5.29 and Descriptive Analysis of the results presented below demonstrate customers' perceptions of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank.

5.7.1. Services Portfolio/Products

Table 5.16 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Services Portfolio/Products offered by the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking offers a full range of Digital Banking services, a majority of 61.81 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 23.48 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 15.91 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Besides, when customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking provides them consistent experience across all of its Digital Banking channels, a majority of 55.30 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 25.46 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

However, regarding the fees of the studied bank Digital Banking, there is a mix of opinions with the order of prevalence: 41.06 per cent did not find the studied bank Digital Banking fees reasonable, followed by 39.69 per cent agree and 19.24 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

This implies a need for the studied bank to look into the Digital Banking fees.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking offers a full range of digital banking services.	15.00% 99	8.48% 56	15.91% 105	39.85% 263	20.76% 137	660	3.43
VCB Digital Banking provides consistent experience across all of its digital	13.79% 91	11.67% 77	19.24% 127	40.30% 266	15.00% 99	660	3.31
The fees and charges of VCB Digital Banking are reasonable.	20.91% 138	20.15% 133	19.24% 127	26.36% 174	13.33% 88	660	2.91

Table 5. 16 Services portfolio/ Products (Source: Author)

5.7.2. Ease of Use

Table 5.17 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Ease of Use.

The analysis indicates that most of the respondents (58.18 per cent) agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) found it is easy to register and log in to the studied bank Digital Banking channels. Besides, 59.09 per cent of respondents (both strongly agree and agree combined) also found it easy to navigate Digital Banking channels. Additionally, 59.70 per cent of respondents (both strongly agree and agree combined) also found it easy to process transactions on Digital Banking channels.

Overall, the finding indicates that the majority of respondents (about nearly 60 per cent) found it is easy to use Digital Banking channels, followed by about 20 per cent disagreed and 17 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
I find it easy to register and log in to VCB Digital Banking channels.	12.73% 84	11.21% 74	17.88% 118	38.48% 254	19.70% 130	660	3.41
I find it easy to navigate on VCB Digital Banking channels (website/app).	12.42% 82	10.15% 67	18.33% 121	40.91% 270	18.18% 120	660	3.42
I find it easy to process transactions on VCB Digital Banking channels.	12.73% 84	9.85% 65	17.73% 117	41.06% 271	18.64% 123	660	3.43

Table 5. 17 Ease of Use Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.3. Convenience

Table 5.18 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Convenience.

The survey result demonstrates that most respondents felt they could use Digital Banking anytime, anywhere they wanted (63.33 per cent). Besides, 63.33 per cent said the Digital Banking services make it easy for them to manage their bank account, and 65.3 per cent felt Digital Banking services gave them a long-term convenience which is the ability to go cashless.

Overall, the finding indicates that most respondents (63–65 per cent) found Digital Banking convenient, followed by about 20 per cent disagreed and 15 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
I can access VCB Digital Banking anytime anywhere I want.	12.42%	9.39%	14.85%	43.48%	19.85%		
	82	62	98	287	131	660	3.37
Using VCB Digital Banking, I can easily manage my bank account.	12.88%	8.33%	15.15%	43.18%	20.45%		
	85	55	100	285	135	660	3.37
VCB Digital Banking gives me the ability to go cashless	12.72%	8.33%	13.64%	43.33%	21.97%		
	84	55	90	286	145	660	3.41

Table 5. 18 Convenience Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.4. Usefulness

Table 5.19 presents respondents’ evaluations of Digital Banking Usefulness.

Taking a closer look into the “Usefulness” of Digital Banking services, the survey results reflected that 61.81 per cent of respondents stated that Digital Banking offered them access to a wide range of financial services. Further, 63.94 per cent indicated that Digital Banking helps them save time and 52.43 per cent indicated Digital Banking allows them to save cost.

In general, the survey results showed that most respondents find Digital Banking useful (60 per cent) while 20.91 per cent disagree and 19.09 percent neither agree nor disagree. This implies the need to raise customers’ awareness about the Usefulness of Digital Banking services.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking gives me access to a wide range of financial services.	12.73% 84	8.64% 57	16.82% 111	42.27% 279	19.54% 129	660	3.48
VCB Digital Banking help me to save my time.	12.42% 82	8.79% 58	14.85% 98	42.42% 280	21.52% 142	660	3.52
VCB Digital Banking help me to save my cost.	13.64% 90	11.97% 79	21.97% 145	35.91% 237	16.52% 109	660	3.30
In general, I find it useful to use VCB Digital Banking.	12.58% 83	8.33% 55	19.09% 126	39.70% 262	20.30% 134	660	3.47

Table 5. 19 Usefulness Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.5. Reliability

Table 5.20 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Reliability.

Regarding customers' views on the Reliability of Digital Banking they have been using at the studied bank, 62.58 per cent of respondents stated that the studied bank' Digital Banking system always provides them the services exactly as promised. Besides, 49.09 per cent of respondents further said Digital Banking provides them the services at the promised time. Additionally, 59.54 per cent stated that the Digital Banking channels are accurate, timely, and complete. Moreover, 62.27 per cent of respondents noted the fees are transparent.

However, with the statement "the studied bank Digital Banking channels rarely make mistakes", there is an opposite trend of the order of prevalence with 39.09 disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 38.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking always provides the services exactly as promised.	13.03% 86	9.70% 64	14.70% 97	40.91% 270	21.67% 143	660	3.49
VCB Digital Banking always provides the services at the promised time.	13.18% 87	13.79% 91	18.94% 125	37.27% 246	16.82% 111	660	3.31
The information provided over VCB Digital Banking channels is accurate, timely and complete.	13.33% 88	8.94% 59	18.18% 120	41.51% 274	18.03% 119	660	3.42
VCB Digital Banking terms and fees is transparent.	12.57% 83	9.70% 64	15.45% 102	42.42% 280	19.85% 131	660	3.47
VCB Digital Banking channels rarely makes mistakes.	18.79% 124	20.30% 134	22.42% 148	26.51% 175	11.97% 79	660	2.93

Table 5. 20 Reliability Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.6. Privacy and Security

Table 5.21 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Privacy and Security.

It is evident from the table that respondents' view about the Privacy and Security of the Digital Banking services that they have been using at the studied bank is very mixed.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels ask them for additional verification if it spots a login from an unknown device, 61.21 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.28 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree) combined and 16.51 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

However, when customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking allows them to use biometric authentication to log in (fingerprint/voiceprint/facial recognition), 48.63 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.43 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 13.94 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Besides, concerning the protection of customers' account information, finding from the statistical analysis indicates that 51.51 per cent disagree that their account information is protected on the studied bank Digital Banking platform (both strongly disagree and disagree

combined). In comparison, 32.58 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 15.91 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Moreover, in terms of the safety of transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels, 49.51 per cent disagree that the transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels are safe and secured (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) while 33.52 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 16.97 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Overall, the finding analysis implies customers have concerns with the privacy and security of Digital Banking services, which is reasonable with the current situation of Digital Banking in Vietnam.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking allows me to use biometric authentication to log in (fingerprint/voiceprint/facial recognition).	23.33% 154	25.30% 167	13.94% 92	24.39% 161	13.04% 86	660	3.38
VCB Digital Banking channels ask me for additional verification if it spots a login from an unknown device.	12.88% 85	9.40% 62	16.51% 109	40.15% 265	21.06% 139	660	3.48
My account information is protected on VCB digital banking platform.	22.57% 149	28.94% 191	15.91% 105	18.94% 125	13.64% 90	660	3.53
The transactions over VCB Digital Banking channels are safe and secured.	23.48% 155	26.03% 172	16.97% 112	21.55% 142	11.97% 79	660	3.49

Table 5. 21 Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.7. Speed

Table 5.22 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Speed.

Regarding the connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...), a majority of respondents (52.73 per cent) think it is fast

(both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.42 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.85 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Regarding the page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding also indicates that a majority of respondents (51.21 per cent) think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.17 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 20.61 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Regarding the transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding indicates that 51.06 per cent of respondents think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.03 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 20.91 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Overall, the finding indicates that about 50 per cent of respondents are happy with the Design of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank, followed by nearly 28 per cent disagree and 20 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
The connection speed of VCB Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...) is fast.	14.24% 94	13.18% 87	19.85% 131	35.76% 236	16.97% 112	660	3.28
The page loading speed of VCB Digital Banking channels is fast.	13.93% 92	14.24% 94	20.61% 136	35.91% 237	15.30% 101	660	3.25
The transaction processing speed of VCB Digital Banking channels is fast.	14.09% 93	13.94% 92	20.91% 138	34.39% 227	16.67% 110	660	3.26

Table 5. 22 Speed Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.8. Design

Table 5.23 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Design.

When customers were asked about their views of the Design of the Digital Banking channels(web/app) that they have been using at the studied bank, 60 per cent of respondents stated that the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is friendly. Besides, 61.52 per cent of respondents further noted the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is consistent across all channels (web/app). Moreover, 60.31 per cent stated the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is well-organised. Additionally, 60.91 per cent indicated the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is professional.

Overall, the finding indicates that about 60 per cent of respondents are happy with the Design of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank, followed by about 20 per cent disagree and 20 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
The design of VCB Digital Banking channels (website/app) is user friendly.	12.12% 80	7.88% 52	20.00% 132	42.58% 281	17.42% 115	660	3.45
The design of VCB Digital Banking channels is consistent across all of its channels (website/app)	11.06% 73	9.39% 62	18.03% 119	44.85% 296	16.67% 110	660	3.47
The design of VCB digital banking channels (Website/app) is well organised.	11.97% 79	7.73% 51	20.00% 132	44.70% 295	15.61% 103	660	3.44
The design of VCB digital banking channels (Website/app) is professional.	11.36% 75	8.33% 55	19.39% 128	45.30% 299	15.61% 103	660	3.45

Table 5. 23 Design Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.9. Customer Service and Support

Table 5.24 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking Customer Service and Support.

This analysis shows a mix of messages in terms of Customer Service and Support that customer have received when using Digital Banking at the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels offer them easy access to Customer Service representatives, 43.79 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 33.94 agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 22.27 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels inform them what to do if their transaction is not processed, 45.31 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 35.30 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 19.39 per cent neither disagree nor agree. The finding implies there seems to be a problem with error notifications of Digital Banking provided by the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether Banking advisors is prompt in replying to their queries or requests, 42.42 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 33.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 24.09 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

When customers were asked whether their banking advisors has customers' best interests at heart, 42.73 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 35.60 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 21.67 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

However, most respondents believe that the studied bank banking advisors are knowledgeable in Digital Banking services with 60.61 per cent (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.15 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking channels offer easy access to Customer Service representatives.	16.97% 112	26.82% 177	22.27% 147	22.27% 147	11.67% 77	660	3.05
VCB Digital Banking channels inform me what to do if my transaction is not processed.	16.67% 110	28.64% 189	19.39% 128	23.33% 154	11.97% 79	660	3.05
Banking advisors is prompt in replying to queries or requests.	16.21% 107	26.21% 107	24.09% 159	21.36% 207	12.12% 80	660	3.07
Banking advisors are knowledgeable of digital banking services.	12.12% 80	8.03% 53	19.24% 127	43.64% 288	16.97% 112	660	3.45
Banking advisors has customers' best interests at heart.	15.15% 100	27.58% 182	21.67% 143	20.45% 135	15.15% 100	660	3.41

Table 5. 24 Customer Service and Support Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.10. Digital-Emotional Connection

Table 5.25 presents respondents' evaluations of Digital Banking "Digital - Emotional Connection". This analysis shows a mix of messages in terms of Digital - Emotional Connection between customers and the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether they think the studied bank understands them, 48.18 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.73 percent neither disagree nor agree and 24.09 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

When customers were asked whether they think the studied bank Digital Banking offers them the most value compared to the same types of products, 48.33 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.12 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 24.54 percent neither disagree nor agree.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking often launches new Digital Banking features to enhance their experience, the majority of respondents with 55 per

cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.88 percent neither disagree nor agree and 22.12 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking provides them with customised services according to their preferences, 48.64 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.33 percent neither disagree nor agree and 23.02 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

Overall, the finding indicates that about a half of respondents could have a feeling of Digital - Emotional Connection with the studied bank.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
VCB Digital Banking knows me and what I need.	13.03% 86	11.06% 72	27.73% 183	34.24% 226	13.94% 92	660	3.25
VCB Digital Banking offers me the most value compared to the same types of products.	14.09% 92	13.03% 86	24.54% 162	34.09% 225	14.24% 94	660	3.22
VCB Digital Banking often launches new digital banking features to enhance my experience.	12.73% 84	9.39% 62	22.88% 151	38.64% 255	16.36% 108	660	3.37
VCB Digital Banking provides me with customised services according to my preferences	12.57% 83	10.45% 69	28.33% 187	35.91% 237	12.73% 84	660	3.26

Table 5. 25 The Digital-Emotional Connection Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.11. Trust

Table 5.26 represents respondents’ evaluations of Digital Banking “Trust”.

This analysis shows a mix of messages regarding Digital Banking Trust of customers for the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking cares about users' current and future interests, 40.91 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 36.82 percent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.27 percent neither disagree nor agree.

When customers were asked whether they completely trust the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding indicates 40.60 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.27 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.12 percent neither disagree nor agree.

However, most of respondents believe that the studied bank has essential experience to introduce the Digital Banking service with the majority of 61.36 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.45 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 18.18 per cent neither disagree nor agree. Besides, the majority of respondents think the studied bank is a leading brand in the market with 60.76 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.00 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL
VCB Digital Banking cares about the current and future interests of users.	12.12% 80	28.79% 190	22.27% 147	20.30% 134	16.52% 109	660
This Digital Banking service provider (VCB) has necessary experience to provide digital banking services.	11.21% 74	9.24% 61	18.18% 120	41.06% 271	20.30% 134	660
This Digital Banking service provider (VCB) is a leading brand in the market.	11.21% 74	8.79% 58	19.24% 127	39.85% 263	20.91% 138	660
I completely trust VCB Digital Banking.	11.36% 75	29.24% 193	22.12% 146	18.18% 120	19.09% 126	660

Table 5. 26 Trust Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.12. Covid-19 Risk Perceptions

Table 5.27 presents respondents' evaluations of their Satisfaction with the studied bank Digital Banking.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
I feel COVID-19 has a high fatality rate.	3.64% 24	5.00% 33	22.88% 151	52.58% 347	15.91% 105	660	3.72
I am worried about myself, my family or my colleagues who may be affected by COVID-19.	2.88% 19	3.94% 26	17.42% 115	57.42% 379	18.33% 121	660	3.84
I believe that there is an outbreak of COVID-19 in the area where I live and work.	3.48% 23	9.70% 64	25.30% 167	48.48% 320	13.03% 86	660	3.58
In general, I know that COVID-19 is highly dangerous.	3.03% 20	3.18% 21	16.21% 107	53.33% 352	24.24% 160	660	3.93

Table 5. 27 Covid-19 Risk Perceptions Survey Responses (Source: Author)

As shown from Table 5.27, in terms of Covid-19 Risk Perceptions, about half of respondents agree that Covid-19 has a high fatality rate and stated a health concern for their family and themselves.

5.7.13. Satisfaction

Table 5.28 presents respondents' evaluations of their Satisfaction with the studied bank Digital Banking. It is evident from the finding that respondents' view of Customer Satisfaction proves a consistent pattern.

Regarding satisfaction with Digital Banking services introduced by the studied bank, the order of prevalence is 39.85per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 37.87per cent are not satisfied (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.27per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Concerning satisfaction with the transactions process via Digital Banking channels by the studied bank, the Survey reflected that 40.85per cent of respondents are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 36.67per cent are not happy (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42per cent neither disagree nor agree.

In terms of satisfaction with the experience with the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding showed that 39.70 per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 37.88 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Overall, the findings shows that about 40 per cent of sample customers are satisfied with the studied bank Digital Banking while about 37 per cent of respondents are not satisfied and about 23 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL
I am satisfied with the services provided by VCB Digital Banking.	12.72% 84	25.15% 166	22.27% 147	27.73% 183	12.12% 80	660
I am satisfied with the transactions processing in VCB Digital Banking.	14.85% 98	21.82% 144	22.42% 148	30.15% 199	10.70% 71	660
I am satisfied with the experience that I had with VCB Digital Banking.	15.76% 104	22.12% 146	22.42% 148	29.09% 192	10.61% 70	660

Table 5. 28 Satisfaction Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.7.14. Loyalty

Table 5.29 presents respondents' evaluations of their Loyalty to the studied bank Digital Banking.

Regarding Loyalty, there is a mix of opinions from sample Digital Banking users.

In terms of Intentions to say Positive things about the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding indicates 40.15 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 36.52 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), and 23.33 per cent are neither disagree nor agree.

In terms of Intentions to recommend Digital Banking to someone who seeks their advice, the order of prevalence is 39.39 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.64 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 2.88 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

When customers were asked whether they would encourage their friends and family to use the studied bank Digital Banking, the Survey reflected 41.09 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.09 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and then 21.82 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

However, when customers were asked whether they would consider the studied bank Digital Banking as their first choice for future transactions, 39.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed 38.40 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.12 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Besides, about their Intentions to continue using the studied bank Digital Banking, the results show a nearly a half (49.39 per cent) of respondents agree to continue using Digital Banking (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 31.67 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 18.94 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	NORMAL	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL
I would like to say Positive things about VCB Digital banking to other people.	15.91% 105	24.24% 160	23.33% 154	25.61% 169	10.91% 72	660
I would like to recommend VCB Digital banking to someone who seeks my advice.	17.27% 114	22.12% 146	22.88% 151	26.97% 178	10.67% 71	660
I would encourage friends and family to use VCB Digital banking.	18.82% 125	22.27% 146	21.82% 144	26.82% 177	10.27% 68	660
I consider VCB Digital banking to be my first choice for future transactions.	15.82% 104	22.58% 149	22.12% 146	25.61% 169	13.87% 92	660
I intend to continue using VCB Digital banking.	11.52% 76	20.15% 133	18.94% 125	28.48% 188	20.91% 138	660

Table 5. 29 Loyalty Survey Responses (Source: Author)

5.8. Reliability Statistics

This research employed Cronbach’s Coefficient Cronbach's Alpha (α) with Python Software to demonstrate the reliability statistics. There are two main reasons for choosing this method. Firstly, as pointed out Statistics (2021), Cronbach's alpha (α) is the most popular and reliable measure of internal consistency of the variables. Secondly, Cronbach's alpha is most frequently employed in researches with multiple Likert questions in a survey which develop a scale and the researcher wish to determine the reliability of the scale. Therefore, it is reasonable to conduct Cronbach's alpha because this research used Survey Questionnaires with five-point Likert Scale and developed a research model with the constructs are Digital Banking service quality dimensions, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

The Cronbach's Alpha (α) result of each construct is presented in the Table 5.30 (See Appendix N for Python Presentation of Cronbach's Alpha (α) test).

As shown in Table 5.30, the highest (α) is 0.904 and the lowest (α) is 0.781. Therefore, the values of Cronbach's Alpha (α) of each construct all surpass the minimum of 0.7 as documented in Nunnally (1978) and 0.6 as documented in Garg et al. (2014). Thus, it can be concluded that

the constructs and data in this present research were reliable and valid for further analysis as suggested by Garg et al. (2014).

Construct	Items	Cronbach's alpha
Services Portfolio/Products	3	0.899
Ease of Use	3	0.872
Convenience	3	0.874
Usefulness	4	0.876
Reliability	5	0.860
Privacy and Security	4	0.876
Speed	3	0.781
Design	4	0.877
Customer Service and Support	5	0.857
Digital -Emotional Connection	4	0.773
Trust	4	0.879
Customer Satisfaction	3	0.883
Customer Loyalty	5	0.886
Covid-19 Risk Perception	4	0.904

Table 5. 30 Reliability Statistics (Source: Author)

5.9. Spearman Correlation Coefficient Analysis

5.9.1. Variables utilised in Research Model

No	Variables	Abbreviations
1	Services portfolio/ Products	SPP
2	Ease of use	EOU
3	Convenience	CON
4	Usefulness	UFN
5	Reliability	REL
6	Privacy and Security	PRS
7	Speed	SPD
8	Design	DSG
9	Customer Service and Support	CSS
10	Digital-Emotional Connection	DEC
11	Trust	TRU
12	Covid-19 Risk Perception	COV
13	Customer Satisfaction	SAT
14	Customer Loyalty	LOY

Table 5. 31 Variables utilised in Research Model (Source: Author)

5.9.2. Data analysis techniques

The proposed research model is tested using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient with Python software based on the suggestion and guidance of Mukaka (2012). Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is a non-parametric statistic widely utilized in machine learning to examine whether the monotonic relationships between variables exist and how strong they are (Mukaka, 2012). Since the assumption of Spearman is held that a majority of the data in the Survey is ordinal/rank data type); therefore, Spearman's correlation is applied to the dataset to determine the relationship between elements (Mukaka, 2012).

5.9.3. Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Testing the proposed research model by using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient with Python software was carried out through 3 main stages based on the suggestions of Mukaka (2012).

Stage 1: Export Summary Data Survey of 660 responses from Survey Monkey to file Excel

Stage 2: Import Summary Data Survey to Python Software.

Stage 3: Data Analysis by Python Software (Please see Appendix O for Python Result PDF File).

- Remove irrelevant variables
- Rename columns and remove first row
- Transform text values to numerical values
- Replace missing numerical values with most popular value of corresponding variable
- Function to find all relevant variable names
- Function to calculate a total score of all selected variables

- Function to create spearman values: Spearman correlation and spearman p-value

Step 4: Compare results and conclude hypotheses testing based on the Rule of Interpretation suggested by Hinkle et al. (2003).

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
.90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00)	“Very high positive (negative) correlation”
.70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90)	“High positive (negative) correlation”
.50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70)	“Moderate positive (negative) correlation”
0.30 to .50(-.30 to -.50)	“Low positive (negative) correlation”
.00 to .30 (.00 to -.30)	“Negligible correlation”

**Table 5. 32 “Rule of Thumb for Interpreting the Size of a Correlation Coefficient”
(Source: Hinkle et al., 2003)**

The research aims to test the conceptual framework established in Chapter 3 on the relationships between Digital Banking Service Quality and “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty” in the Vietnamese Banking Sector. After completing statistical analysis utilising Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient with Python, the author obtained the following summary results as presented in Table 5.32 “Rule of Thumb for Interpreting the Size of a Correlation Coefficient”.

The Spearman Analysis is presented in Table 5.33, in which the hypothesis, correlations, P-value, findings and hypotheses conclusion are illustrated. The correlation displays the extent to which independent variables affect dependent variables while the p-value determines the hypotheses.

Using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient with Python, the author obtained the following summary results as presented in Figure 5.1.

No	Proposed Hypothesis	Spearman Correlation	Spearman P-value	Findings	Hypotheses Conclusion
H1	SPP → SAT	0.261	1.957e – 11	Negligible correlation	Accept
H2	EOU → SAT	0.805	2.344e – 146	High Positive correlation	Accept
H3	CON → SAT	0.824	5.734e – 159	High Positive correlation	Accept
H4	UFN → SAT	0.836	9.245e – 168	High Positive correlation	Accept
H5	REL → SAT	0.864	2.435e – 192	High Positive correlation	Accept
H6	PRS → SAT	0.868	1.806e – 195	High Positive correlation	Accept
H7	SPD → SAT	0.864	7.535e – 192	High Positive correlation	Accept
H8	DSG → SAT	0.806	4.354e – 147	High Positive correlation	Accept
H9	CSS → SAT	0.873	1.930e – 200	High Positive correlation	Accept
H10	DEC → SAT	0.900	1.154e – 231	Very High Positive correlation	Accept
H11	TRU → SAT	0.924	1.863e – 268	Very High Positive correlation	Accept
H12	COV → SAT	0.335	3.289e – 18	Low Positive correlation	Accept
H13	SAT → LOY	0.927	1.923e – 273	Very High Positive correlation	Accept
H14	TRUST → LOY	0.908	1.368e – 242	Very High Positive correlation	Accept

Table 5. 33 Hypothesis Testing Result (Source: Author)

Figure 5. 1 Pictorial results of hypothesis test by correlation analysis (Source: Author)

In summary, of the twelve Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions, the correlation analysis results also present high correlation coefficients between most of the variables. As shown from Table 5.33, there is strong evidence that most relationships between pairs of two variables exist and are positive. Spearman p-values in all tests are significant and close to 0, which means that all the proposed hypotheses can be accepted, and strong associations between pairs of variables are indicated (Mukaka, 2012). Besides, except for the test in H1 and H12, Spearman coefficient values are over 0.8, which can be considered as evidence of the high positive or very high correlations (Mukaka, 2012).

General speaking, apart from H1 and H12, in each pair of two variables, the value of one variable goes up; there is an extremely high possibility that the other value increases as well. In the case of H1 and H12, the association between two variables in a pair can be seen as negligible and low positive correlation, respectively.

Services portfolio/ Products and Customer Satisfaction

The association of “Services portfolio/ Products” and “Customer Satisfaction”, shown by H1 (correlation = 0.261, p-value = $1.957e - 11$), is a negligible correlation, indicating that the role of Digital Banking Services portfolio/ Products on customer satisfaction is not significant.

Ease of Use and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship of “Ease of Use” and “Customer Satisfaction” shown by H2 (correlation = 0.805, p-value = $2.344e - 146$) is a positive correlation, so the hypothesis is accepted.

Convenience and Customer Satisfaction

The association of “Convenience” and “Customer Satisfaction” showed by H3 (correlation = 0.805, p-value = $5.734e - 159$) is high positive and significant, meaning that the hypothesis is accepted.

Usefulness and Customer Satisfaction

H4 (correlation = 0.836, p-value = $9.245e - 168$) shows the high positive correlation between “Usefulness” and “Customer Satisfaction”, hence, accepting the hypothesis.

Reliability and Customer Satisfaction

The association of “Reliability” and “Customer Satisfaction”, shown by H5 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = $2.435e - 192$), is a high positive correlation; hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Privacy and Security & Customer Satisfaction

The association of “Privacy and Security” and “Customer Satisfaction”, shown by H6 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = $1.806e - 195$), is a high positive correlation; hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Speed and Customer Satisfaction

The link of “Speed” and “Customer Satisfaction”, exhibited by H7 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = $7.535e - 192$), is a high positive correlation, thus accepting the hypothesis H5.

Design and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship of “Design” with “Customer Satisfaction”, represented by H8 (correlation = 0.806, p-value = $4.354e - 147$), is a high positive correlation, the hypothesis is accepted.

Customer Service and Support & Customer Satisfaction

The relationship of “Customer Service and Support” and “Customer Satisfaction”, represented by H9 (correlation = 0.873, p-value = $1.930e - 200$), is a high positive correlation, the hypothesis is accepted.

Digital-Emotional Connection and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship of “Digital-Emotional Connection” and “Customer Satisfaction”, represented by H10 (correlation = 0.900, p-value = $1.154e - 231$), is a high positive correlation, the hypothesis is accepted.

Trust and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship of “Trust” and “Customer Satisfaction”, represented by H11 (correlation = 0.924, p-value = $1.863e - 268$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted.

Covid-19 Risk Perceptions and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship between “Covid-19 Risk Perception” and “Customer Satisfaction”, represented by H12 (correlation = 0.335, p-value = $3.289e - 18$), is a low positive correlation. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that “Covid-19 Risk Perception” has a low impact on “Customer Satisfaction”.

Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

The relationship between “Customer Satisfaction” and “Customer Loyalty”, represented by H13 (correlation = 0.927, p-value = $1.923e - 273$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that “Customer Satisfaction” significantly impacts “Customer Loyalty”.

Trust and Customer Loyalty

The relationship between “Trust” and “Customer Loyalty”, represented by H14 (correlation = 0.873, p-value = $1.368e - 242$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that “Trust” significantly impacts “Customer Loyalty”.

5.5.3. Correlation Coefficient Analysis Summary

In short, ultimately, the total 14 hypotheses proposed in Chapter 3 were tested using collected data from Customer Survey using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient with Python

software. The results indicated that 14 out of 14 hypotheses were accepted. It was found that Customer Satisfaction and Trust significantly contribute to Customer Loyalty. In terms of the effects of Digital Banking service quality on Customer Satisfaction, based on Spearman's rank correlation coefficient results, 12 factors of Digital Banking service quality can be divided into four groups based on the strength of its relationship with Customer Satisfaction, in decreasing order:

- Group 1: Trust (correlation = 0.924), followed by Digital Emotional Connection (correlation = 0.900), has the most substantial impact on customer satisfaction (very high positive correlation).
- Group 2: Customer Service and Support, followed by Privacy and Security, then Reliability and Speed (same correlation = 0.864), Usefulness (correlation = 0.836), Convenience (correlation = 0.824), Design (correlation = 0.806), lastly is Ease of Use (correlation = 0.805). These Digital Banking service quality dimensions all have highly correlated with Customer Satisfaction.
- Group 3: Covid-19 Risk Perceptions (correlation = 0.335) presents a low positive relationship with Customer Satisfaction.
- Group 4: The last being Services Portfolio/Products (correlation = 0.261). the relationship between Services Portfolio/Products and Customer Satisfaction has a negligible correlation.

5.10. Summary

In Summary, Chapter 5 presented a descriptive analysis of the data to understand customers' overall perceptions about the Digital Banking services they are currently using. Besides, Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient analysis indicated that 14 out of 14 proposed hypotheses were accepted. Discussions and implications of these findings will be illustrated in Chapter 7.

CHAPTER 6: QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

6.1. Introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the qualitative data obtained through in-depth interviews conducted with five esteemed bank managers. The primary objective is to explore and gain a profound understanding of their perceptions regarding the implications of Digital Banking on customer satisfaction and loyalty within the context of Vietnam Banking System. To begin, a detailed description of the data collection process and analysis techniques employed is provided, ensuring transparency and rigor in the research process. Furthermore, the chapter includes an introduction to the participating bank managers, shedding light on their professional backgrounds and expertise. Moving forward, the chapter delves into the key themes that emerged from the managers' perspectives on various aspects of Digital Banking. This thorough qualitative analysis, encompassing key themes and sub-themes, significantly addresses the research question by providing valuable insights into the impact of Digital Banking on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Vietnamese banking landscape.

6.2. Participants' Profile

Qualitative data were collected through a series of semi-structured in-depth interviews with five banking managers with profound insight in the digital banking and customer relations in the Vietnamese Banking Sector. Purposive sampling was employed to select the five interviews from digital banking population. All the respondents have been working in the studied banks for a long period from ten to sixteen years and currently holding the post of managers/senior executives. Being banking managers, they are in charge of supervising and directing a wide variety of banking operations, which encompasses both conventional banking services as well

as digital banking activities. Their pivotal roles are vital in supervising banking technology integration, developing digital strategies and services, guiding their customers' experiences, and recognising areas for improvement. Moreover, their dual role as digital banking providers and users offers a unique and comprehensive insight into digital banking, enabling them to have the knowledge and firsthand experience required to answer the research questions, enhancing the richness and relevance of the research findings.

Table 6.1 presents the demographic information of the interviewees in this study.

BM	Gender	Age	Title/Position	Department	Number of years in the bank
BM 1	F	32	Deputy of Department Customer Service Centre	Head office	10 years.
BM 2	F	42	Deputy of Department-senior customer advisor	Head office	13 years
BM 3	F	39	Bank branch manager	Branch	12 years.
BM 4	F	45	Supervisor	Head office	16 years
BM 5	F	38	Deputy of Department	Customer Service Centre	10 years

Table 6. 1 Demographic information of the interviewees (Source: Author)

6.3. Interview Conduction

The researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with five chosen Senior Executives/bank managers. The previous plan for the data collection was face-to-face case study interviews. However, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, the researcher could not return to the research site and consequently had to change the plan to online interviews through Facebook/Skype. After gaining consent from every interviewee, interviews were conducted over Facebook/Skype between the period of 17 November 2021 to 30 November 2021. The organiser of the

interviews was the researcher herself, who asked, examined and followed the interviews' questions. The interviewees were asked to provide their views of current Digital Banking developments, challenges, and opportunities in the studied bank and its impact on customer relations.

The length of each interview is between 45-60 minutes, which makes a total of approximately five hours. All interviews were asked for their permission to be recorded. All the interviews agreed. Apart from the recording, the researcher took additional field notes during the interviews if needed. Records and note-taking were used for transcribing purposes. This was to ensure all information was captured correctly and accurately. The documented evidence was then transcribed at the end of the interview or shortly after. The transcribed information was also sent back to the interview participants to ensure that the information was accurate. As a result, the final transcribed information was concise and made ready for qualitative data analysis.

The researcher used a semi-structured interview for the bank managers/senior executives. As an interviewer, the researcher familiarised herself with emphasising the research aims and objectives and talked about the interview's key themes at the commencement of all interviews. The interviews were conducted in a friendly and balanced style. During the interview, the researcher used a loose collection of themes to be answered by participants, as suggested by (Creswell and Poth 2017; Saunders et al. (2019)). The researcher also used planned themes but departed if an interesting theme comes from participants in order to capture their opinion from those events. The researcher asked supplement questions when it was necessary to gain a more profound testimony (Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017). These interviews were conducted to capture the bank managers' perceptions in how they experienced Digital Banking services that their bank offered to customers and how do perceive its impact on customer relationships from their managerial perspective. This was then captured, ascertained, analysed, and presented in

storytelling to showcase the views and perceptions towards Digital Banking Service Quality and its link to customer satisfaction and loyalty.

6.4. Limitations encountered

Even though semi-structured interviews bring many benefits for this current research, on the other hand, the researcher acknowledged several challenges of conducting interviews in the context of this research.

Inevitably, being forced to conduct the interviews remotely as a practical response to Covid-19 pandemic travel restrictions at the time, probably meant that the information collected lacked some of the richness of in-person interviews due to the lack of social presence between the researcher and the interviewees and the inability to observe the surroundings or the interviewee's full body language. Nevertheless, thankfully by utilising technology advancements, the researcher was able to navigate the transition to online interviews and conduct the qualitative data collection with minimal disruption. The social platforms and video interfaces not only allowed for flexible scheduling and the convenience of the interviewees but also primarily provided the same output as physical interactions. However, of the five interviews, two were held when the interviewees were at home (interviewees were relaxed and focused on the interactions). So, the surrounding environments were different from the environment of the offices. The remaining three interviewees were at banks. While conducting interviews, phones were ringing during interviews, and the interviewees needed to break off to talk to colleagues and so on. These barriers, along with some technical glitches happened during the interviews, to some extent, diverted the interviewee's attention while answering the questions, leading to interruptions of the conversation flow. Moreover, it also changed their body language. Nevertheless, based on the data collected, it was felt that relatively little was lost due to the absence of traditional face-to-face interaction, proving online interviews were

not only a practical response but also beneficial method for gathering data from banking managers while at the time, in-person interviews were out of the question due to the Covid-19 pandemic travel restrictions. Although in-depth insights were gathered from the interviews, the generalisability of these findings to all banking executives is restricted due to the small number of interviewees.

In addition, another challenge of conducting interviews for this current research is that the participants' responses could be shaped or limited by their willingness to reveal sensitive information (Whiting, 2008). Conducting an interview also faces an inherent risk of "social desirability bias", meaning the participants may over-report "positive behaviour" though under-reporting "negative behaviour". To reduce this risk, the researcher ensured the presented questions were as neutrally worded as possible and gave complete anonymity for all participants (Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017).

Moreover, unquestionably, as suggested by Kopec and Esdaile (1990) and Martin (2005), interviews always incur a risk of "recall bias". Interviewees' perceptions could change over time due to the complexity of the Vietnam Banking Sector or concerns with ideas, data protection, and prosperity right. Therefore, responses collected from the interviewees may not be relevant to reality (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). To reduce this risk, the researcher used a clear description and articulation of the interview questions while applying a standardised data collection mode throughout the interview (Hassan, 2012). Furthermore, the researcher gave each participant ample time before responding to the questions to reflect on the experience based on their perceptions (Hassan, 2012).

Another disadvantage of conducting a semi-structured interview is the time involved in data collection and data analysis (Maxwell, 2013). Because the research context is Vietnam, the language used in the interviews is Vietnamese; therefore, the researcher had to spend a

tremendous amount of time and effort in recording, coding, and having the transcript translated by professional translators to ensure the meanings of all the responses' discussions were fully conveyed.

Notwithstanding the aforementioned constraints, the integration of in-depth qualitative data from banking managers and broad quantitative data from banking customers offered a holistic examination of customer satisfaction and loyalty within the Vietnamese digital banking sector.

6.5. Data Analysis Techniques

This present research adopted Template Analysis for the qualitative analysis of interviews data collected from bank managers. The researcher established the themes from the research's literature review and from the major terms emphasised during the interviews. The researcher did not develop its themes based on the representation or opinion of the researcher's personal experience. Therefore, the themes were strong and aimed at addressing validity and reliability factors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The researcher applied Template Analysis method to summarise responses of the participants based on the key themes of the literature in order to generate a clear understanding of the interviewees' perceptions. Template Analysis allowed the researcher to perform coding from the research-related factor questions and the collected data.

Hence, the analytical codes were based on the key empirical themes of the research, which are Digital Banking, the development of Digital Banking Vietnam, Digital Banking Service Quality affecting customer satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in Vietnam, challenges for Digital Banking developments in Vietnam.

6.6. Coding process

Coding is a process that determines different data aspects related to the research question. The Coding process included collection and categorization of data; the search was for evidence for

the code from various databases and code labelling (Creswell, 2012). The researcher adopted the complete-coding approach for this present research (Braun & Clarke, 2013). The printed transcript was highlighted with annotations based on the template coding of data, then thoroughly read the transcripts in order to understand the data to a greater extent (Braun & Clarke, 2013). To establish themes, the author read the printed-out interview transcripts carefully, then looked for the similarities and differences in the interview content of the five bank managers. The researchers then categorised the codes into key themes and sub-themes, as Braun and Clarke (2006) suggested. The twelve key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions were identified during the interview process. Each main factor was considered as the main theme, which includes sub-themes. The following section is dedicated to a comprehensive investigation of the research's main themes and sub-themes, delving into their meanings and implications.

6.7. Qualitative Data Results Analysis

6.7.1. Bank managers' perceptions about Digital Banking services

The interviewees – banking managers were asked for their perceptions about how customers evaluate the overall quality of the studied bank Digital Banking based on the dimensions of the conceptual framework proposed in Chapter 3: Services portfolio/products, Ease of use, Convenience, Usefulness, Reliability, Privacy and Security, Speed, Design, Customer Service and Support, Digital - Emotional connection. The results from the five interviews were summarised and highlighted below.

Services portfolio/products

Based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers generally agreed that the studied bank provides a diversify of Digital Banking services/products and also a wide range of features on its Digital Banking channels (web/app). The managers think their Digital Banking

service is suitable for different customer segmentation. However, it is essential to note that most of the managers stated that the current fee of its Digital Banking is currently high compared to other banks, which could not be a competitive advantage for the studied bank. However, they also noted that customers would receive no free transfer transactions if they register for account packages. The managers also pointed out some services/products that customers are interested.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: “(...) provides diverse Digital Banking services which suit different needs of different customer segmentations.”

“Diverse products/ services which catches up with the market trends (opening online account/ opening accounts using the electronic Know Your Customers (eKYC) system, transferring money by QR code, Withdrawal by QR code, investments, Stock trading, open a securities account, Deposit for security account, Deposit money into e-wallets...) which suit the different needs of all customer segments”

Manager 2: “the fee to implement the Digital Banking service for the first time is still at a high rate, there are many types of fees”

Manager 3: “The service is suitable for every individual's needs.” However, “The services fee are relatively high compared to competitors in the banking sector.”

Manager 4: “...the transaction limit is high, and customers can even make a transaction when they are overseas.”

Manager 4: customers are interested in “collecting loyalty points to exchange for gifts, saving the costs when using Digital Banking services (for example, if customers register Account Packages, they will be offered free of charge when making transferring transactions)

Manager 5: “the services provided by (the studied bank) is diverse...”

Ease of Use

Based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers agreed that in general, Digital Banking products offered by the studied bank is easy to use for customer with the consolidations of web/app design by 01 username and password. However, some managers are concerned that the Smart OTP activation is too complex, which might be difficult for middle-aged customers. Most managers agreed that the studied bank had not comprehensively developed communications and guidance for customers in using Digital Banking services. The bank has not regularly uploaded video guidance to instruct/educate customers to perform all the features of the Digital Banking app/websites. Communications on each new feature launching have not been reached broadly (widely and deeply) to customers”.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: "(the studied bank) has changed the log-in interface design which is very similar both on app/website, so it will be easy for users. (...) has also unified login details with only 01 username and 01 passwords for all its Digital Banking channels, which again makes it very easy for customers to use"

Manager 2: “easy to remember (log in)” however “the separation of the Smart OTP application when customers use it on the web or in the app is often more confusing for customers.”

Manager 3:

“Customers faces difficulties in increasing money transfer limit, activating Smart OTP transaction authentication method.”

Manager 4: “Smart OTP activation is too complicated with many steps which are difficult for customers, especially middle-aged customers.”

Manager 5: “Smart OTP Settings has too many steps”

Convenience

Based on the analysis of the interviews, all of the managers agreed that Digital Banking brings many conveniences for customers: saving time, saving cost, access service any time anywhere. All managers highly evaluated the convenience of 01 username and 01 password on both Digital Banking channels web/app. They also stated that the transaction limit for both Digital Banking channels is the same, which is easy for customers to remember.

Key theme: access, anywhere, anytime, save cost, save time

Excerpts:

Manager 1: "Customers can access anywhere anytime with Digital Banking channels". "The feature of receiving notice of balance change via OTT message (OTT Alert) is integrated right on THE STUDIED BANK Digibank's Mobile application, replacing SMS notification, helping customers save costs.". "With Smart OTP, customers can actively receive the OTP code to complete the transaction without having to wait for the OTP code via traditional SMS by the bank."

Manager 2: "There are homogenous productions on all platforms (app/web), make it easy and convenient for customer to use". "Our digital banking app represents a significant enhancement in convenience for our customers, for example, the integration of critical features such as card activation, card lock/unlock, card registration/unsubscribe on the Internet, change card transaction limit".

Manager 3: "(...) Booking is a new feature that allows customers to book an advanced appointment with the bank to save waiting time and transaction time by booking an appointment, stating what services customers want to use on the website before going to the bank."

Manager 4 “Customers can open bank account online by e-KYC anytime anywhere by THE STUDIED BANK app, no need to go to the branch/transaction office/ counter, saving time and costs, high transaction limit.” “Especially, (the name of Digital Banking app of the studied bank) username is the phone number registered with ... (the studied bank) by the customers.” “The feature of receiving notice of balance change via OTT message (OTT Alert) is integrated right on Digital Banking mobile application, replacing SMS notification, allowing users to reduce costs.”

Manager 5: “the services provided by (the studied bank) is convenient...” “only 1 username and 1 password for both Digital Banking channels app/website”. “Banking consumers are not constrained to specific working hours or locations (as with traditional banking services). They could utilise the digital banking services around the clock, from anywhere in the world, as long as they had an internet connection”

Usefulness

Based on the analysis of the interviews, all the five managers highly evaluated the Usefulness of Digital Banking for customers. All of them stated that Digital Banking had brought many benefits to customers with diverse features allowing customers to perform financial transactions. However, most managers think the studied banks can do better.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Diverse features on (the studied bank Digital Banking) (app/website) allows customers to perform financial transactions, payments and shopping easily and conveniently.”

Manager 2: “the Digital Banking service has been continuously upgraded, amended and completed, but I think we can do better.”

Manager 3: “The service is suitable for every individual's needs. However, it needs to improve to be more useful for middle-aged customers.”

Manager 4: “All the features are beneficial for customers.”

Manager 5: “the services provided by (the studied bank) brings many benefits to customers..., but I believe we will have more benefits offered to customers in the future”

Reliability

Based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers are generally concerned with the Reliability of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank. Most managers are concerned with the errors that sometimes happen when customers use the instant money transfer 24/7 service from the studied bank to other banks but do not receive money instantly.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Instant money transfer 24/7 outside (the studied bank) often occurs errors so beneficiaries could not receive money instantly.”

Manager 4: “errors in top up a transaction: mobile phone top-up transactions were not successful, but the bank account still got debited, mobile phone top-up transactions were not successful, but the bank account still got debited.”

Manager 3: “The feature of Instant Money transfer 24/7 outside the studied bank usually faces a timeout error, making beneficiaries unable to receive their money immediately”. Manager 3 shared the same opinions with Manager 1.

Manager 3: “difficulty in activating Smart OTP transaction authentication method”

Manager 4: “sometimes errors occurred in connections. The transactions were not successful, but the notification received is unclear which customers did not know and tried to make the transactions again many times.”

Privacy and Security

Based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers generally evaluated the Privacy and Security of Digital Banking channels as “relatively good”. They all agreed that the studied bank currently integrate many advanced security technologies to ensure the privacy and security for customer information and transaction on the Digital Banking channels web/app. However, they also stated that problems such as unauthorised banking transactions sometimes come from customers’ side when they accidentally disclose their information to scammers.

Key theme: security, authentication, notification, leaking, password

Excerpts:

Manager 1: "Integrate many advanced security technologies, especially (...) also added new login authentication technology - Push Authentication. With this technology, when customers log in on the web browser, the system will automatically send a notification to the mobile application to request the customer to confirm before allowing successful login."

Manager 3: “Banks in general and our bank in particular are currently using a variety of communication methods, warning of fraudulent tricks on the bank's website system, via email, by text messages and communication campaigns. Banking clients should pay attention to constantly update, remember and recognise new cyber hackers’ tricks”

Manager 4: “Phone password, app password, random keyboard display, Smart OTP, fingerprint, face recognition...”

Manager 5: “trustworthy, high security” “new login authentication technology - Push Authentication”

However, manager 3 pointed out that although the studied bank utilises various Security and Privacy authentication technologies and promotes Risk Prevention regularly, the problems sometimes come from customers’ lack of digital understanding and knowledge.

Manager 1: “On the bank's side, we have been continuously invested in human resources including technology officers, cybersecurity experts to offer the best technology solutions to our banking users, especially anti-impersonation technology. However, of course, while we are constantly increasing their security, scammers also find ways to get around. Therefore, the problem of impersonation fraud always exists, but never goes away. Therefore, customers must always be vigilant”

Manager 2: “Some customers often have the habit of sharing personal information and data such as citizen identification images, phone numbers, payment account numbers, etc. on social media, that in turn they could be targets of banking technology crime”

Manager 3: “Customers due to negligence accidentally leak the security login information for Digital Banking channels (username, password, OTP) for scammers and after that, noticed unauthorised banking transactions from their bank account.”

Speed

Based on the analysis of the interviews, there is a mixed messages from the bank managers regarding the Speed of Digital Banking channels. On one hand, most of the managers agreed that in general, the Speed of Digital Banking channels have improved significantly. The studied banks offer smooth transactions on their Digital Banking channels, only sometimes a bit slow at the end of the day because this is when the banks run end-of-day data. On the other hand, some managers are concerned that the system is often overloaded, making customers unable to access their accounts.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Mostly smooth experiences, sometimes the loading speed of the app/websites is a bit slow at the end of the day because this is the time the banks run end-of-day data.”

Manager 2: “The Digital Banking channels (app/web) can run smoothly with few errors.”

Manager 3: “the system is often overloaded, leading to the customers could not be able to access their accounts.”

Manager 4: “Fast connection”

Manager 5: “... the speed of the service has improved significantly; the software runs smoothly, and there are few errors.”

Design

Based on the results of the five interviews, most of the managers agreed that in general, the Design of Digital Banking channels is simple, modern, and easy to use with the new style “dark mode”. They stated customers have good feedback with the Design and colour of the Digital Banking web/app. However, in terms of the features of the web/app, they also noted the features displayed on the screen are not concise and logical. There is an overuse of icons, requiring many manipulations with the toolbar from customers to choose. Moreover, they concerned that putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers.

Excepts:

Manager 1: “Interface Design is simple, easy to use and professional. Interface designed in the style of "dark mode" - dark background mode, has positive benefits to user's health, optimises mobile phone battery life, and increases the durability of the device.”

Manager 2: “Customer shows interest in the colour dark green of the design.”

Manager 3: “The features displayed on the screen are not concise. There is an overuse of icons, requiring many manipulations with the toolbar from customers to choose. Moreover, putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers.”

Manager 4: “Interface designed in the style of "dark mode" - dark background mode, has positive benefits to user’s health.”

Manager 5: “Some details of the interface design are currently not reasonable. For example, in order to see the current using version, customers need to go in Setting- Contact, so it’s not logical...”

Customer Service and Support

Based on the results of the interviews, all of the managers highly evaluated the quality of the bank staff in terms of Digital Banking knowledge and capability of supporting customers. They are concerned that customers have difficulties reaching Hotline 24/7 Customer Service due to extremely high-volume calls. In contrast, all of the managers stated that the Digital Banking app/website of the studied bank has not yet allowed customers to contact online with customer service. All of the managers highly evaluated the quality of the bank staff in terms of Digital Banking knowledge and capability of supporting customers.

Excerpts:

Manager 1: “I always have a high evaluation for (the studied bank) human resources for Digital Banking.

Manager 2: “The staff (...) high quality, enthusiastic in their work”

Manager 5: “I highly evaluated the human resources involved in (the studied bank) Digital operations. They always update themselves to be knowledgeable and adaptive... bring new experience for customers”.

However, most of the managers stated that the Digital Banking app/website of the studied bank has not yet allowed customers to contact online with customer service. In contrast, customers have difficulties reaching Hotline 24/7 Customer Service due to extremely high-volume calls.

Excerpts:

Manager 1:

“Sometimes customers have difficulties in contacting with Hotline 24/7 due to extremely high-volume calls to the hotline. Digital Banking (app/web) has not yet allowed customers to quickly contact online with customer service”

Manager 2: “long waiting time ... the line is too busy...”

Manager 3: “... the hotline is often overloaded”

Manager 4: “... should allow customers contact online with customer service staff”

Manager 5: “Digital Banking (app/web) has not yet allowed customers to quickly contact online with customer service”

Digital – Emotional connection**Excerpts:**

Manager 1: “From both our bank’s customer and manager perspective, I feel emotionally connected with (the studied bank), I felt satisfied as well as proud in every touch and every experience on the Digital Banking app which is developed by the bank itself”

Manager 2: “Forming an emotional connection with customers is one of the key factors in ensuring a bank's success, and always at the heart of our bank’s strategy”

Manager 3: “In our digital banking implementation, our mindset has been shifting from a rational aspect such as various performance measures to an emotional aspect such as customer and employee satisfaction, with an emphasis on building a long-term relationship between the bank and our customers”

Manager 4: “We have been trying our best to navigate what customers love about our digital banking services and think about how to integrate them to create a more emotionally engaging experience”

Manager 5: “Well, in my opinion, despite financial products are created by technology, the end users are real people, not robots, and humans can feel emotions and empathy, therefore, our bank has placed a significant a significant emphasis on building strategies to generate positive emotions to create an emotional bond between our bank and our customers”

6.7.2. Perceptions of advantages and disadvantages of DB services of the studied bank

Based on the results of the interviews, all of the bank managers pointed out some advantages and disadvantages of the studied bank Digital Banking services compared to other banks. The advantages that they highly evaluated are: the interface design, account packages and ease of use of only 01 username and 01 password.

Advantage

Manager 1: “Interface design in the style of dark mode.”

Manager 2: “The paying and transferring features (...) is by far the most used features and they also bring the highest fee revenue for (...)”

Manager 3: “(customers value the most) is Account Packages. Customers who register for account packages will have a free transferring fee.”

Manager 4: “Currently, the feature that customers value the most is Smart OTP authentication methods. This login authentication technology and Smart OTP are additional layers of protection, helping to create a solid “wall” of security to ensure customers' safety in each transaction. Besides, the transaction limit is high, and customers can even make transactions when they are overseas”

“...username and password are identical: 01 username and 01 passwords (for all channels). Therefore, customers will no longer have difficulties in remembering 02 separate login names and passwords...”

Manager 5:

“... the speed of the service has improved significantly; the software runs smoothly, and there are few errors.”

“By March 2021, the service fee package has brought many incentives fees for customers.”

Disadvantage

Manager 1:

"Current service fee is not competitive if customers do not register for Account Packages. Only customers who register for Account Packages can have free money transfer."

"Communications and guidance for customers in using Digital Banking services has not been comprehensively developed"

Manager 2:

"The features displayed on the screen are not concise. There is an overuse of icons, requiring many manipulations with the toolbar from customers to choose. Moreover, putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers."

"The dark screen is an obstacle, but now there is a light mode / dark mode option to solve this problem."

"The fee to implement the service for the first time is still at a high rate and there are many types of fees. This is the main obstacle when it comes to using (the studied bank) Digital Banking services. However, by March 2021, the service fee package has brought many discounts to customers.

Manager 3:

“Customers faces difficulties in increasing money transfer limit, activating Smart OTP transaction authentication method.”

“Errors in 24/7 money transfer”

Manager 4:

“The languages used (in Digital Banking channels) is not diverse”

“Smart OTP Settings has too many steps”

“The notifications of errors are sometimes not clear”

Manager 5: “The features displayed on the screen are not concise, the icons are many and to use, users have to pull and push the toolbar down a lot to choose; Putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers.”

“The dark screen is an obstacle; however now there is a light mode / dark mode option to improve this problem.”

“The fee for the first time of service implementation is still high, many types of fees.”

Manager 5: “Some details of the interface design are currently not reasonable, for example, in order to see the current using version, customers need to go in Setting- Contact, so it’s not logical...”

6.7.3. Overall customer satisfaction

Based on the findings of the interviews, all of the managers are reasonably satisfied with the level of Digital Banking services that their bank currently offers. In terms of customer satisfaction, from their perspectives, most of the managers think their customers are moderately happy with the Digital Banking services. However, they acknowledged there is still a lot of room for enhancing their customer satisfaction. All of the managers stated the most complaints/problems/issues that customers often encounter when using Digital Banking

Services, from then recommended how the studied bank can achieve better accomplishments in its journey of attaining customer satisfaction via Digital Banking applications.

Excerpts as below:

Manager 1: “In my opinion, most of the customers are satisfied with their Digital Banking services experience with us. With customers only using the neither disagree nor agree features (account management, internal money transfer within (the studied bank), opening an online savings account), Digital Banking services always have good performance. With customers using other features which are related to our partnerships, sometimes errors can occur during the process”

Manager 2:

“The level of customer satisfaction when using (...) Digital Banking service has been proven by the award "Best Mobile Banking Application in Vietnam year (...)" but we can still need to improve it...”

Manager 3:

"Uhm, well, basically, I think our Digital Banking is at average level, (the studied bank) has met the quality of the service, but the system is often overloaded, leading to the problem that customers sometimes could not be able to access to their accounts. Moreover, the feature of Instant money transfer 24/7 outside (the studied bank) usually faces a timeout error, making beneficiaries unable to receive their money immediately."

Manager 4:

“Most customers are satisfied with (...) 01 username password for both its app and website channels. easy for customers to remember the log in details and avoid confusions. Besides, customers are pleased with the new interface design because it is modern and trendy”.

Manager 5:

"Well, I actually have never seen a result of any official survey about Customer Satisfaction when using Digital Banking services of (...). However, in my managerial experience of working in (...) for about 10 years until now, I can see that most customers, especially long-lasting customers of (...) believe in the studied bank products, the number of new customers using Digital Banking has increased every year, fee income from Digital Banking services has also increased every year, so I am sure that the Digital Banking services of (...) has bring a lot of nice experience for customers"

However, the bank managers also point out some major customer complaints that they often receive in their managerial practice:

Excerpts:

Manager 1: "Customers face difficulties in contacting Hotline 24/7 due to the fact that the hotline is always busy/overloading"

"Instant money transfer 24/7 outside (the studied bank) service often occurs errors so beneficiaries could not receive money instantly."

Manager 2: "Many customers have not been aware of the feature of Online Investigation for banking transactions, so they wasted their time coming to the branches or contacting many times to Hotline 24/7 to receive support."

"Instant money transfer 24/7 outside (the studied bank) service often occurs errors so beneficiaries could not receive money instantly."

Manager 3: "Customers due to negligence accidentally leak log in the security information for Digital Banking channels (name, password, OTP) for scammers and after that, noticed unauthorised banking transactions from their bank account"

Manager 4: “The barriers and difficulties customers often encounter when using The studied bank Digital Banking are: activating Smart OTP, errors in top up a transaction: mobile phone top-up transactions were not successful but the bank account still got debited, interruptions in connections ...”

Manager 5: “The number of major customer complaints is related to the request to check payment transactions on (...) due to connection errors and errors in accounting processing of the system. This error is a barrier of the service, but I think this is not the fault of (the studied bank), but much depends on the infrastructure connection of both the Vietnamese banking system and the Napas supplier in general.”

6.7.4. Challenges

Legal framework

Based on the interview results, 5 out of 5 interviewees shared their concerns with the current legal framework for Digital Banking operations and development. They all stated that although the SBV has issued general guiding documents for digital banking implementation, however, along with the development of the market, many new relationships and products have arisen, but legal documents to regulate them have not been issued in time, which prevents the development of Digital Banking of the studied bank in particular and the Vietnam banking sector in general.

Key themes: legal framework, lacking, domestic legal regulations, difficult

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Need to create and launch eKYC policy and electronic authentication.”

Manager 2: “The legal framework for Digital Banking is still slow compared to the speed of technological developments.”

Manager 3: “The introduction of the general legal framework is still slow. For example, the law on electronic transactions, promulgated since 2005, has many shortcomings. However, it has not been modified and updated with new technology advancements.”

Manager 4: “The speed of technology development is fast, while the promulgation of legal regulations requires a lot of time, (...) so it has affected the development of some Digital Banking services in Vietnam banks.”

Manager 5: “In fact, currently, there is no legal framework for completely new digitised product ideas, leading to banks' reticence in launching new products, which will be outside the permitted scope and subject to legal adjustments”

Information Security System

Based on the interview results, 5 out of 5 interviewees shared their concerns with the current legal framework for Digital Banking operations and development. Regarding Information Security System, all interviewed banking managers shared their concerns that fraud cases related to high-tech crimes are increasingly dangerous, sophisticated and complex. Although the ability to prevent and combat fraud in digital banking transactions has always been of interest to the studied bank, it has not yet created complete peace of mind for customers.

Key themes: scammers/cyber-attacks, safety, security, fraud, high-tech crimes, sophisticated

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Challenges related to information safety and security, especially customer information: Financial information of customers is very sensitive and is the target of scammers/cyber-attacks.”

Manager 2: “Specifically, the situation is that a customer is attacked by phishing, transferring money from his account to the fraudster's account at another bank. The first reaction of

customers when they find out that their money has been lost is to call the bank but sometimes, they couldn't call through the official channel. Even if temporarily processed, it is very difficult to investigate to get the money back”.

Manager 3: “The most common online scams today are scam calls via social networks, thereby taking over accounts or sending messages impersonating a bank”

Manager 4: “However, the problem of attack, fraud, impersonation of financial institutions, banks will not be able to completely handle 100%, we will always have to face it”

Manager 2: “In fact, there are many cases of customers misusing the service and being tricked into fake bank pages, allowing fraudsters to take advantage of and extract money from customer accounts.”

Manager 3: "Moreover, the fact that scammers/hackers take advantage of customers' lack of digital understanding and knowledge to steal the money in customers' bank account is a widespread problem, despite many warnings for risk prevention and transaction security regularly sent by (the studied bank) through many media means such as social networks, texts, email, media communications."

“The recent cases of fraud related to digital payment activities are becoming more and more sophisticated and complex.”

Manager 4: “In addition to the many conveniences brought to customers, Digital Banking development is facing the problem of personal information security, when the banking industry is always the number one target of technology criminals. Many cases happen because customers misuse the service and get tricked into fake bank pages, causing fraudsters to take advantage of appropriate money in customer accounts”

Manager 5 “...it is still a challenge for the bank to have a team of cybersecurity experts with knowledge of business operations.”

“(cybercriminals) asking customers to provide passwords and OTP codes.”

“... Send messages containing fake links.”

“...Stealing information through fake websites...”

“... on social networks, banking scam sites can run ads, run viral campaigns online and a lot of people are fooled by clicking on such pages”

“Fraud and risk of fraud from e-commerce are on the rise, in which fraudsters have approached users and introduced programs to support loan interest rates, support for withdrawing balances in credit cards, close or activate credit cards... thereby appropriating users' credit card information to shop on e-commerce platforms”

Capital requirements

Regarding Capital requirements, as specified by all the interviewed banking managers, another prominent challenge for Vietnam Banks in the process of digital banking implementation is that the transformation requires continuous upgrading and updating, leading to substantial technology investments, both in terms of finances and human resources to ensure the successful digitisation of digital banking services.

Key themes: Investment costs, technology systems, maintenance, security solutions

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Investment costs for technology systems and development of new digital banking services are intensive” “Banks must allocate extensive resources in training employees and customers on new technologies and how to use them safely”

Manager 2: “High technology costs, frequent improvements, maintenance, system upgrades, and new technology changes to meet competition have undeniably put a lot of pressure on banks.”

Manager 3: “In digital banking, banks must make substantial investments are required in security solutions to ensure that customer information and payment transactions are not exposed”

Manager 4: “Huge capital required for digital reinvention projects; this is the challenge for the technology investment for banks' digital transformation.”

Manager 5: “Large-scale investments in cybersecurity measures are crucial to protect sensitive customer data”. “The larger the size of the bank, the more challenging the budget requires investment.”

Human resources

Regarding Human resources, as specified by all the interviewed banking managers, Banks are focusing on digital transformation and automation, which is increasing demand for positions in IT, technology, and data analytics... These vacancies particularly require high-quality human resources, which poses a significant challenge for banks in recruitment and investment owing to market competition. With existing human resource, Digital transformation requires a change in culture and processes within the bank. This can face the difficulty of changing traditional thinking and working habits.

Key themes:

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: As banks are focusing on digital transformation and automation, the demand for such positions like IT, technology, and data analytics are significantly increasing... These vacancies are predominantly focused on high-quality human resources, which is tough to recruit and keep them stay loyal”.

Manager 2: “The source of candidates in the field of digital transformation of the banking industry is very limited in both quantity and quality” “Challenge is about getting new talent

into making the transformational changes.” “Recruitment for DB human resources requires a significant investment owing to market competition”

Manager 3: “Digital Banking is a new field with a lot of new knowledge that not every employee is fully equipped with, both banks and banking officials have to invest in training and acquiring new technologies, knowledge and skills” “the difficulty of changing traditional thinking and working habits”

Manager 4: “In the market, there are also banks that choose to hire external consultants, and at the same time recruit technology staff who do not have banking experience to train them”.

Manager 5: “Digital transformation requires employees with digital knowledge and skills. Banks need to invest in training and developing employees so that they can understand and effectively use new technology”

Competitions

Regarding Competitions, as concerned by all the interviewed banking managers, the Vietnamese digital banking landscape has been rapidly expanding, leading to an infusion of both domestic and foreign institutions into the market who are in constant race in investing cybersecurity measures and meeting customers’ expectations. This can be seen as a substantial challenge for the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general in their digital transformation journey.

Key themes: Increasing competition, competitors, domestic, foreign institutions

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: “Increasing competition with other competitors and Fintech companies”.

Manager 5: “Well, in my opinion, I think the biggest challenge (...) has to face in its Digital Banking development journey is the competition with other competitors. All of the other banks in the Vietnam banking sector are competing in the race of Digital Banking. Even some private

banks with smaller scales and smaller total assets but more dynamic in technology application can still be seen as big competitors for the studied bank's journey toward digital reinvention”.

Manager 4: “If the studied bank acts slower than the competitors or does not have high determination in the journey, does not evaluate the importance of the journey properly, we will lose track, lose current customers, and cannot attract more new customers”.

Manager 5: “The digital banking business in Vietnam is rapidly expanding, resulting in an infusion of both domestic and foreign institutions into the market who are in constant race in investing cybersecurity measures and meeting customers’ expectations”.

Cashless payments challenges

As concerned by all the interviewed banking managers, Cashless payments challenges is another challenge for the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general in their digital transformation journey. The main reason for cashless payments challenges is due to the habit of using cash ingrained in people's subconscious, the fear of accessing new payment technology, as well as concerns about security and safety when making online purchases using digital banking services. Therefore, changing people's consumption habit of using cash also poses many challenges to the digital transformation process of the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general.

Key themes: cash, subconscious, cash on delivery, fear, cash payment

Example of Excerpts:

Manager 1: “difficult in promoting Digital Banking” “Customers prefer using cash.”

Manager 2: “The main reason is due to the habit of using cash ingrained in people's subconscious, the fear of accessing new payment technology, as well as concerns about security and safety when making online purchases using digital banking services”

Manager 3: “Most customers make purchases in the form of cash on delivery - COD, accounting for about 85-90% of total transactions”

Manager 4: “The habit of using cash is still quite common. Therefore, changing people's consumption habit of using cash also poses many challenges to the digital transformation process of Vietnamese banks”.

Manager 5: “Vietnam is still a cash economy. The high rate of cash payment is a challenge, a big obstacle not only of the banking system, but of the whole Vietnamese economy”

Overall, the qualitative analysis of the banking managers' interview transcripts revealed that from all five bank managers' perspectives, there is a wide variety of challenges that the studied bank in particular and Vietnam commercial banks, in general, have encountered in their Digital Banking developments.

First and foremost, regarding the legal framework, all interviewees shared their concerns with the lack of legal frameworks for Digital Banking operations and development, which prevents the development of Digital Banking in Vietnam in general.

Secondly, regarding Information Security System, all interviewed banking managers shared their concerns that fraud cases related to high-tech crimes are increasingly dangerous, sophisticated and complex. Although the ability to prevent and combat fraud in digital banking transactions has always been of interest to the studied bank, it has not yet created complete peace of mind for customers.

In additions, a common concern shared by most the managers is that the implementation of digital banking requires a substantial Capital requirements, including investments in technology, infrastructure and human resource training, which is one of the prominent challenges for banks in Vietnam.

Moreover, in the digital banking journey, the studied bank in particular and Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general Vietnamese banks has been facing a substantial obstacle regarding Human resources, as specified by all the interviewed banking managers. Vietnamese banks are focusing on digital transformation and automation, which is increasing demand for positions in IT, technology, and data analytics... These vacancies particularly require high-quality human resources, which poses a significant challenge for banks in recruitment and investment owing to market competition. With existing human resource, Digital transformation requires a change in culture and processes within the bank. This can face the difficulty of changing traditional thinking and working habits.

Last but not least, as concerned by all the interviewed banking managers, Cashless payments challenges is another challenge for the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general in their digital transformation journey. The main reason for cashless payments challenges is due to the habit of using cash ingrained in people's subconscious, the fear of accessing new payment technology, as well as concerns about security and safety when making online purchases using digital banking services. Therefore, changing people's consumption habit of using cash also poses many challenges to the digital transformation process of the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general.

6.8. Summary

In summary, this chapter provides the analysis results of the interviews conducted with five banking managers of the studied banks. The findings result from the practical experience of the interviews, show insightful perceptions from banking managerial perspective on current developments of Digital Banking of the studied bank and its impact on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. These findings will be discussed in the following Chapter along with

the data analysis obtained from Survey for customers. The consolidation and discussion of the quantitative and qualitative data, as well as primary and secondary findings from the research enables a thorough and holistic investigation of the research findings, which will then pave the path for a comprehensive conclusion.

CHAPTER SEVEN: DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

7.1. Introduction

This chapter outlines the implications of the quantitative and qualitative evaluations discussed in Chapters 5 and 6, respectively. As stated at the outset of this study, the primary goal of this academic investigation is to identify the critical Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions that exert a strong influence on digital banking customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese commercial banks. This chapter discusses the research findings presented in the chapter five and chapter six along with the literatures discussed in the literature review in order to answer the research questions.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of digital banking service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty and proffer relevant recommendations for related stakeholders to promote digital banking uptake and satisfaction and loyalty. To pursue the research aim, four research objectives have been made in line with four research questions, to be achieved at the end of this study. In order to achieve the research aim, the following research questions were expected to answer in this chapter:

RQ1: “Which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?”

RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?"

RQ3: What are the key challenges to Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty?

RQ4: What recommendations can be proposed to stakeholders regarding the utilisation of digital banking channels to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Banking Sector?

In order to answer the above research questions, both primary and secondary data are being used in quantitative and qualitative aspects. Primary data were collected through survey strategy from customers and interviews from banking managers of the studied bank. Secondary data is also used to compare the findings of primary research to provide strong discussion to this study. The research findings presented in chapter five and chapter 6 will be consolidated and discussed in this chapter in order to answer above research questions and finally, to achieve research objectives.

7.2. Key DBSQ dimensions and its impact on DB customer satisfaction and customer loyalty

7.2.1. Summary of the findings.

The present research is designed to examine Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions and their relation with Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty in the context of Vietnam Banking Sector. The research aim is to enhance prior understanding and comprehending the most crucial factors of Digital Banking Service Quality and how Digital Banking Service Quality affects customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Figure depicts the pictorial results of the proposed hypotheses test of the research:

Figure 7. 1 Pictorial results of hypothesis test by correlation analysis

The following section discusses in detail the relationship of each Digital Banking Service Quality dimension with customer satisfaction.

7.2.1. Services portfolio/ Products

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the association of Services portfolio/ Products and Customer Satisfaction, shown by H1 (correlation = 0.261) is a negligible correlation, indicating the role of Digital Banking Services Portfolio/ Products on customer satisfaction is not significant. These findings imply that Services portfolio/ Products appear to have little impact on Customer Satisfaction and hence, Services Portfolio/Products appear irrelevant for Digital Banking customers. This result contradicts prior research of Jun and Cai (2001), indicating that “Banking service product quality” exerts a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction when investigating Internet Banking in the USA. Possible explanations for these contradictories may be due to the research site. Since Digital Banking is a new emerging

service/product in Vietnam, the range of Digital Banking services offered by different Vietnam banks is currently quite similar.

Additionally, the thorough analysis provided in Chapter 5 shows that the majority of Vietnamese banking clients now use digital banking systems largely for simple operations like cash transfers and account management. Vietnamese banking consumers currently do not frequently perform complicated financial services such as insurance and investment transactions through digital banking channels. This implies that consumer satisfaction in the context of Vietnamese digital banking is not significantly influenced by the portfolio, diversity, and breadth of digital banking services currently provided by the studied bank. The findings suggest that Vietnamese digital banking users may not completely appreciate the uniqueness and novelty of these goods and services, adding fresh perspectives to the existing body of literature. Hence, it is beneficial for Vietnamese commercial banks to study and integrate digital banking service portfolios or products from developed countries, leading to a potential decrease in resource allocation for Digital Banking research and development.

Based on the survey descriptive analysis, when customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking offers a full range of Digital Banking services, a majority of 61.81 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 23.48 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 15.91 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Besides, when customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking provides them consistent experience across all of its Digital Banking channels, a majority of 55.30 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 25.46 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither agree nor disagree. However, regarding the fees of the studied bank Digital Banking, there is a mix of opinions with the order of prevalence: 41.06 per cent did not find the studied bank Digital Banking fees reasonable, followed by 39.69 per cent agree and 19.24 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Furthermore, based on the qualitative data analysis in Chapter 6, most of the managers generally agreed that the studied bank provides a diversify of Digital Banking services/products and also a wide range of features on its Digital Banking channels (web/app). The managers think their Digital Banking service is suitable for different customer segmentation. However, it is essential to note that most of the managers stated that the current fee of its Digital Banking is currently high compared to other banks, which could not be a competitive advantage for the studied bank. This is consistent with the results in the open-ended questions of the Survey for customers: some customers commented that the studied bank needs to decrease the fee of the Digital Banking services.

In essence, the consolidation of the findings strongly suggests that the diversification of digital banking services does not play an important role on fostering the level of customer satisfaction in the studied bank. The variety of digital banking services offered, whether simple transactions like bank transfers and account management or more complicated products such as insurance and investment transactions, appears to have less influence on client satisfaction in the context of Vietnam Commercial Banks.

However, it is critical to emphasise that this does not diminish the significance of other aspects of digital banking services that may contribute to client satisfaction. Given that 41.06 per cent of the surveyed banking customers articulated their dissatisfaction with the current fee structure of the studied bank's digital banking services along with the fact that most of the interviewed banking managers stating the current fee of its Digital Banking is currently high compared to other competitors, a fruitful recommendation for the studied bank is taking into consideration a comprehensive review and restructuring of digital banking fees, aligning with customer expectation, banking standards and competitor practices. The studied bank should also prioritise the transparency and clarity regarding the fees by fully educating and communicating with its customers about all the costs and benefits related with the given digital banking

services. The studied bank could also enhance the justification for the cost by providing value-added services or features. The structure and level of digital banking fees is an important consideration for the investigated bank. Banking fees, particularly those linked with digital platforms, may be a significant factor impacting consumer satisfaction and, as such, must be carefully considered.

In essence, the research offers insightful implications, suggesting a re-evaluation of strategies related to the diversification and fee assessment of digital banking services, with the ultimate aim of achieving enhanced customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

7.2.2. Ease of Use

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship of Ease of Use and Customer Satisfaction shown by H2 (correlation = 0.805, p-value = $2.344e - 146$) is a high positive correlation. This outcome indicates that Ease of Use is a strong driver of customer satisfaction, which contradicts Yoon (2010), yet confirms several studies of Raza et al. (2020); Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba (2018a); Jun and Palacios (2016); Kassim and Abdullah (2010); Castaneda et al. (2007); Devaraj, Fan and Kohli (2002). These results imply that Ease of Use has a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction.

Based on the survey questionnaires descriptive analysis, the analysis indicates that most of the respondents (58.18 per cent) agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) found it is easy to register and log in to the studied bank Digital Banking channels. Besides, 59.09 per cent of respondents (both strongly agree and agree combined) also found it easy to navigate Digital Banking channels. Additionally, 59.70 per cent of respondents (both strongly agree and agree combined) also found it easy to process transactions on Digital Banking channels.

Overall, the finding indicates that the majority of respondents (about nearly 60 per cent) found it is easy to use Digital Banking channels, followed by about 20 per cent disagreed and 17 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Based on the qualitative data analysis generated from interviews with bank management, a consensus was detected, demonstrating that the digital banking solutions provided by the studied bank are typically user-friendly. The seamless integration of online and app interfaces, which require only a single username and password, contributes to this usability. Nevertheless, complications involved in the activation process of Smart OTP might pose difficulties and challenges for banking users in the middle-age demographic in using digital banking services, as can be realised from the shared concern among some managers, potentially affecting their satisfaction level. Furthermore, the majority of the managers feel that the bank has not yet fully implemented its communication strategies and guiding processes for consumers using digital banking services. The studied bank has not been consistent in posting instructional videos to educate clients on how to use various features of their digital banking platforms. Furthermore, communication about the release of new features has not been successfully disseminated, with the reach of these announcements being neither widespread nor in-depth.

In essence, the consolidation of the findings strongly suggests that perceptions of Ease of Use of Digital Banking exert strong effect on customer satisfaction in the studied bank. Overall, regarding customers, the finding indicates that the majority of respondents (about nearly 60 per cent) found it is easy to use Digital Banking channels. On the other hand, as are perceived by the managerial staff, the studied bank's digital banking services as user-friendly and intuitive. Conversely, concerns have been raised about the complexities of some elements, particularly activation process of Smart OTP. These characteristics represent critical areas that require attention and modification in order to improve the overall customer satisfaction in digital

banking. Simultaneously, providing comprehensive guidance and effective communication to customers is

7.2.3. Convenience

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the association of Convenience and Customer Satisfaction showed by H3 (correlation = 0.805, p-value = $5.734e - 159$) is a high positive correlation, therefore accepting the hypothesis. This finding contradicts Srinivasan et al. (2002) and Keisidou et al. (2013) yet confirms Jun and Palacios (2016). The findings show that Convenience has a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction, highlighting the need for the studied bank to intentionally increase consumer perceptions of convenience as a way to raise customer satisfaction.

Upon rigorous descriptive analysis of the surveyed banking customers, the gathered survey data exemplifies that a majority of the contributors, about 63.33 per cent affirmed their ability to utilise these banking services irrespective of time and place, appreciating the flexibility of digital banking. Correspondingly, an equal percentage of the respondents, roughly 63.33 per cent, articulated that digital banking services offers the simplicity and peace of mind for them in administering the bank account. Additionally, 65.30 per cent of respondents documented the long-term conveniences offered by digital banking which is the ability to operate their financial transactions in a cashless manner. Taken as a whole, the data reveals a striking finding: 63 to 65% of respondents, or a majority, perceived digital banking as a convenient tool. In contrast, over 20% of those surveyed disagreed with this opinion, while approximately 15% of respondents remained undecided, neither agreeing nor disagreeing. This distribution of responses demonstrates how the majority of surveyed banking customers generally perceive digital banking offered by the studied bank to be convenient.

A rigorous analysis of the in-depth interview responses showed a holistic evaluation from all the interviewed managers praising the convenience of the studied bank's digital banking services. They all agreed that Digital Banking brings many conveniences for customers such as time and cost savings and unrestricted access any time anywhere. In addition, all managers highly evaluated the convenience of a simplified authentication system 01 username and 01 password across Digital Banking channels web/app. They also endorsed the benefits a uniform transaction limit, which is easy for customers to remember. Overall, all the interviewed managers appreciated the convenience of digital banking services, highlighting the tremendous change that these platforms have made to modern banking. From the managerial perspective, these common observations highlight the tremendous potential and value of digital banking services.

In essence, the consolidation of the findings strongly suggests Convenience has a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction, highlighting the need for the studied bank to intentionally increase consumer perceptions of convenience as a way to raise customer satisfaction. Overall, regarding customers, the finding indicates that the majority of respondents (about 63 to 65 per cent) perceived digital banking as a convenient tool, which is a good sign for the studied bank in their Digital Banking implication journey. On the other hand, as are perceived by the managerial staff, all the interviewed managers appreciated the convenience of digital banking services, highlighting the tremendous change that these platforms have made to modern banking. However, the studied bank should also place greater emphasis on investigating the reasons that some customers do not perceive the convenience of Digital Banking as indicated by the fact that over 20% of those surveyed customers disagreed, while approximately 15% of respondents remained undecided when asked about the convenience of Digital Banking.

7.2.4. Usefulness

Based on the rigorous quantitative analysis delineated in Chapter 5, there exists a strong positive correlation between Usefulness and Customer Satisfaction, as indicated by the test statistic H4 (correlation = 0.836, p-value = $9.245e - 168$). These findings are congruent with the research conducted by Jun and Palacios (2016), thereby further corroborating the Usefulness and Customer Satisfaction in the domain of digital banking. Essentially, these findings point to a relationship in which increased perceived usefulness of Digital Banking leads to increased customer satisfaction.

This link is further clarified by a thorough review of the customers' perceptions on the value of Digital Banking services as shown by the descriptive analysis. Based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, taking a closer look into the Usefulness of Digital Banking services, the survey results from the customers reflected that 61.81 per cent of respondents recognised the broad array of financial services accessible via Digital Banking. Further, 63.94 per cent indicated that Digital Banking acknowledged that Digital Banking efficiently facilitates time-saving, and 52.43 per cent indicated Digital Banking allows them to achieve a cost -saving advantage. In general, the survey overall results demonstrated that a significant majority of respondents (approximately 60 per cent) appreciated the usefulness of Digital Banking while a minority group creating 20.91 per cent disagreed, and 19.09 percent remained neutral. This finding implies the need for enhanced efforts aimed at improving customers' cognizance regarding the usefulness of Digital Banking services.

From a managerial standpoint, all five interviewed banking managers strongly acclaimed the usefulness of Digital Banking for their customers. All of them stated that Digital Banking had brought many benefits to customers with diverse features allowing customers to perform financial transactions. Nonetheless, most managers believe that the analysed bank has the potential ability to optimise its digital banking services usability.

When the conclusions drawn from these data are combined, it becomes clear that, in the context of Digital Banking services, customer satisfaction is significantly boosted by the perception of usefulness. Overall, results demonstrated that a significant majority of respondents (approximately 60 per cent) appreciated the usefulness of Digital Banking while a minority group creating 20.91 per cent disagreed, and 19.09 percent remained neutral. This finding implies the need for enhanced efforts aimed at improving customers' cognizance regarding the usefulness of Digital Banking services. In light of this, banks must do all possible to raise client banking customers awareness of the useful advantages of digital banking services and products offered. This can be accomplished through thorough advertising and consultative activities, allowing clients to develop a comprehensive awareness of the benefits of using Digital Banking services.

7.2.5. Reliability

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the association of Reliability and Customer Satisfaction, shown by H5 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = 2.435e – 192), is a high positive correlation; hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Reliability was found to be another vital Digital Banking Service Quality factor driving customer satisfaction to Digital Banking. These findings propose a similar view as those of previous studies in Pakistan internet banking (Raza *et al.*, 2020), Lebanese banking sector (Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba, 2018) and e-banking (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy 2019; Liao and Cheung 2002), internet banking (Tan and Teo, 2000) or (Kettinger and Lee, 2005). Findings indicate that the more accurate and reliable the digital banking services customers perceived, the more satisfied the customers are with the banks, demonstrating by preserving reliability of the Digital banking services, banks can elevate their consumer satisfaction level.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, regarding customers' views on the Reliability of Digital Banking they have been using at the studied bank, 62.58 per cent of

respondents stated that the studied bank Digital Banking system always provides them the services exactly as promised. Besides, 49.09 per cent of respondents further said the studied bank Digital Banking provides them the services at the promised time. Additionally, 59.54 per cent stated that the Digital Banking channels are accurate, timely, and complete. Moreover, 62.27 per cent of respondents noted the fees are transparent.

However, with the statement “the studied bank Digital Banking channels rarely make mistakes”, there is an opposite trend of the order of prevalence with 39.09 disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 38.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

This is consistent with the findings from interview managers who concerned with errors in transaction of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank. Based on the qualitative data analysis in Chapter 6, based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers are generally concerned with the Reliability of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank, particularly with the errors with the instant money transfer 24/7 service. When customers use the instant money transfer 24/7 service outside the studied bank, sometimes errors can happen which makes the beneficiaries cannot receive money instantly.

These findings suggest that urgent attention needs to be paid into increasing Reliability of Digital Banking service in order to enhance users’ satisfaction level. This is because the higher level of accuracy and credibility the Digital Banking service accounts for, the greater the level of customer satisfaction in using Digital Banking. Banks should provide customers with upgraded services without transaction errors within a certain time and also make sure that the information they allocate to customers is correct and up to date in order to address customers’ worries about the reliability of Digital Banking.

7.2.6. Privacy and Security

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the association of reliability and Customer Satisfaction, shown by H6 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = $1.806e - 195$), is a high positive correlation; hence, the hypothesis is accepted. These findings confirm previous studies Yoon (2010) studying about China online banking or Jun and Palacios (2016) about in USA mobile banking, or other studies Rita, Oliveira and Farisa (2019); Blut et al. (2014); Saccani et al. (2014); Quach et al. (2016). Privacy and Security play a critical role in driving consumer satisfaction. It is undeniable that customers have different opinions about their expectations of the service and their satisfaction is determined by how successfully banks can innovate their services to satisfy those expectations. In this case, banks should offer the ability to carry out transaction procedures online and instruct their customers about how to use internet banking services safely and how to handle security issues. Customers have lots of concerns over the security of their financial payments and the privacy of their personal information when they use e-banking. As a result, banks should guarantee that customers' private information recorded in e-banking platforms should not be available to other third parties. And in order to improve the level of security in making transactions, banks should offer secure and unique identification code for each individual and always send notifications about login and transactions to verified contact numbers or email addresses. Banks should also give passwords that can be used only once to users in order for them to complete transactions, thus helping them to avoid fraud or scams. Although, in general, privacy and security are top issues for all Digital Banking customers, they tend to be prioritised by high-involved users rather than low-involved ones. As a result, banks are suggested to give an additional contribution to inform high-involved customers about their policies regarding security and privacy. For example, customers who spend more than the typical amount of time on Digital Banking can receive e-mails with clarifications of security and privacy regulations imposed by banks.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, it is evident from the table that respondents' view about the Privacy and Security of the Digital Banking services that they have been using at the studied bank is very mixed.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels ask them for additional verification if it spots a login from an unknown device, 61.21 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.28 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree) combined and 16.51 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

However, when customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking allows them to use biometric authentication to log in (fingerprint/voiceprint/facial recognition), 48.63 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.43 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 13.94 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Besides, concerning the protection of customers' account information, finding from the statistical analysis indicates that 51.51 per cent disagree that their account information is protected on the studied bank Digital Banking platform (both strongly disagree and disagree combined). In comparison, 32.58 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 15.91 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Moreover, in terms of the safety of transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels, 49.51 per cent disagree that the transactions over the studied bank Digital Banking channels are safe and secured (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) while 33.52 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 16.97 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Overall, the finding analysis implies customers of the studied banks have concerns with the privacy and security of Digital Banking services.

However, based on the analysis of the interviews in Chapter 6, most of the managers generally evaluated the Privacy and Security of Digital Banking channels as “relatively good”. They all agreed that the studied bank currently integrate many advanced security technologies to ensure the privacy and security for customer information and transaction on the Digital Banking channels web/app. However, they also stated that problems such as unauthorised banking transactions sometimes come from customers’ side when they accidentally disclose their information to scammers. Conclusions from interviews with bank managers also point out that equipping some banking customers with a sense of security is also necessary.

7.2.7. Speed

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the link of Speed and Customer Satisfaction, exhibited by H7 (correlation = 0.864, p-value = $7.535e - 192$), is a high positive correlation, thus accepting the hypothesis H5. These results are consistent with the studies carried out by several researchers (DeLone and McLean, 1992; Srinivasan, 1985, Aladwani & Palvia, 2002, Yoon, 2010). The findings show evidence that the speed at which Digital Banking services are delivered via an app or website link critically contributes to its customers’ satisfaction.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, overall, the finding indicates that about 50 per cent of respondents are happy with the Design of DB channels of the studied bank, followed by nearly 28 per cent disagree and 20 per cent neither disagree nor agree. In detail, regarding the connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...), a majority of respondents (52.73 per cent) think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.42 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.85 per cent neither disagree nor agree. Regarding the page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding also indicates that a majority of respondents (51.21 per cent) think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.17 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined)

and 20.61 per cent neither disagree nor agree. Regarding the transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding indicates that 51.06 per cent of respondents think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.03 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 20.91 per cent neither disagree nor agree.

Furthermore, based on the qualitative data analysis in Chapter 6, there are mixed messages from the bank managers regarding the Speed of Digital Banking channels. On the one hand, most of the managers agreed that, in general, the Speed of Digital Banking channels had improved significantly. The studied banks offer smooth transactions on their Digital Banking channels, only sometimes a bit slow at the end of the day because this is when the banks run end-of-day data. On the other hand, some managers are concerned that the system is often overloaded, making customers unable to access their accounts.

7.2.8. Design

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship of Design with Customer Satisfaction, represented by H8 (correlation = 0.806, p-value = $4.354e - 147$), is a high positive correlation, the hypothesis is accepted. This result verifies previous studies (Amin, 2016; Raza et al. 2020; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy 2019; Kassim & Abdullah, 2010). The findings suggest that if the design of the Digital Banking channels (web/app) becomes more well organised, user friendly and professional, customers will be more satisfied with Digital Banking. The higher the level of Design of the Digital Banking channels (web/app) will lead to the higher the increase in Customer Satisfaction.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, when customers were asked about their views of the Design of the Digital Banking channels(web/app) that they have been using at the studied bank, 60 per cent of respondents stated that the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is friendly. Besides, 61.52 per cent of respondents further noted the Design

of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is consistent across all channels (web/app). Moreover, 60.31 per cent stated the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is well-organised. Additionally, 60.91 per cent indicated the Design of the studied bank Digital Banking channels is professional.

Overall, the finding indicates that about 60 per cent of respondents are happy with the Design of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank, followed by about 20 per cent disagree and 20 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Regarding the connection speed of the studied bank Digital Banking with other devices (QR code payments, ATM withdraw...), a majority of respondents (52.73 per cent) think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.42 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.85 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Regarding the page loading speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding also indicates that a majority of respondents (51.21 per cent) think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.17 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 20.61 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Regarding the transaction processing speed of the studied bank Digital Banking channels, the finding indicates that 51.06 per cent of respondents think it is fast (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.03 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 20.91 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Overall, the finding indicates that about 50 per cent of respondents are happy with the Design of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank, followed by nearly 28 per cent disagree and 20 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Furthermore, based on the qualitative data analysis in Chapter 6, most of the managers agreed that, in general, the Design of Digital Banking channels is simple, modern, and easy to use with

the new style “dark mode”. They stated customers have good feedback with the Design and colour of the Digital Banking web/app. However, in terms of the features of the web/app, they also noted the features displayed on the screen are not concise and logical. There is an overuse of icons, requiring many manipulations with the toolbar from customers to choose. Moreover, they are concerned that putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers.

In short, consolidation of these above findings, banks should pay more attention to the development of Digital Banking channels interface design as this might impact customer satisfaction. In order to offer customers service with superior quality, banks should create Digital Banking channels that include excellent designs that are appealing to the sight, attractive contents that have appropriate information users need, the easiness of making transactions and reading texts, the availability of some promotions or discounts and also quick loading capacity.

7.2.9. Customer Service and Support

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship between Customer Service and Support and Customer Satisfaction, represented by H9 (correlation = 0.873, p-value = $1.930e - 200$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted. Although these findings contradict Kassim & Asiah Abdullah (2010), they support those from the studies of Raza et al. (2020); Hammoud et al. (2018); Jun & Palacios (2016); Amin (2016). Findings indicate that the better, swifter and more positive the Customer Service and Support customers received from the Digital Banking providers, the greater the level of increase in Customer Satisfaction. Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, the findings show a mix of messages in terms of Customer Service and Support that customers have received when using Digital Banking at the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels offer them easy access to Customer Service representatives, 43.79 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 33.94 agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 22.27 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking channels inform them what to do if their transaction is not processed, 45.31 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 35.30 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 19.39 per cent neither agree nor disagree. The finding implies there seems to be a problem with error notifications of Digital Banking provided by the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether Banking advisors are prompt in replying to their queries or requests, 42.42 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 33.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 24.09 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

When customers were asked whether their banking advisors have customers' best interests at heart, 42.73 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 35.60 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 21.67 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

However, most respondents believe that the studied bank banking advisors are knowledgeable in Digital Banking services with 60.61 per cent (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.15 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

This is consistent with the findings from the managers' interviews in which all of the five interview managers highly evaluated the quality of the bank staff in terms of Digital Banking knowledge and capability of supporting customers (presented in Chapter 6). However, based

on the qualitative data analysis in Chapter 6, all five interview managers are concerned that customers have difficulties reaching Hotline 24/7 Customer Service due to extremely high-volume calls. In contrast, they stated that the Digital Banking app/website of the studied bank has not yet allowed customers to contact online with customer service.

In short, the consolidation of the findings implies that banks should provide Digital Banking users with sufficient technical assistance and guarantee that staff is trained to have adequate professional knowledge about the Digital Banking service and eager to support customers. Furthermore, banks should have the ability to offer quick responses to platform queries and enhance customer care to low-involved users who seem to need more support than high-involved customers.

7.2.10. Digital-Emotional Connection

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship between Digital-Emotional Connection and Customer Satisfaction, represented by H10 (correlation = 0.900, p-value = $1.154e - 231$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted. It is significant to note that based on this study, the main factor that significantly influences Digital Banking Service Quality was determined to be a Digital-Emotional Connection - a newly established measure. This finding implies that customers have placed greater weight on the digital emotional connection rather than any of other Digital Banking Service Quality components. They tend to view this feature as the most significant element in deciding their satisfaction with the banks. These findings contribute to the new knowledge. This evidence shows there is a clear trend in customer needs emerging, which recognises that every customer is unique and should be treated individually through service personalisation to improve security and experience. These are crucial problems that banks should put into consideration. Staff's understanding of client requirements is critical to this success; as a result, staff should interact with consumers more to get the necessary information to construct Digital Banking that is

tailored to their users' wants and needs. According to the interviews, banks gain a better understanding of their employees' opinions about the services they provide to clients via involvement.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, the findings show a mix of messages in terms of Digital - Emotional Connection between customers and the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether they think the studied bank understands them, 48.18 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.73 percent neither agree nor disagree and 24.09 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

When customers were asked whether they think the studied bank Digital Banking offers them the most value compared to the same types of products, 48.33 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 27.12 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 24.54 percent neither agree nor disagree.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking often launches new Digital Banking features to enhance their experience, the majority of respondents with 55 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.88 percent neither agree nor disagree and 22.12 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking provides them with customised services according to their preferences, 48.64 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 28.33 percent neither agree nor disagree and 23.02 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined).

Overall, the finding indicates that about a half of respondents could feel Digital - Emotional Connection with the studied bank.

In short, the consolidation of the findings implies that although Digital - Emotional Connection exerts the strongest impact on Customer Satisfaction, in the case of the studied bank, only half of the respondents have a feeling of Digital - Emotional Connection with the studied bank. Therefore, significant attention should be paid to the studied bank to improve this connection with customers. In general, commercial banks need to define the customers they want to focus on clearly. Young people prefer to experience technology, middle-aged and elderly people have the mentality of safe bank savings, people with high incomes require convenience and quality of products and services, etc. From there, banks should develop more effective marketing measures in offering specific products in accordance with the needs of customers Relationships between customers and banks are intimate, sentimental, and feeling-based. Positive emotions foster long-lasting relationships and retain client loyalty. Positive feelings also lead to satisfaction. Customers with strong emotional ties to their brand bank will put up with short-term service quality issues and preserve a long-term engagement with their bank service providers.(Levy and Hino, 2016).

7.2.11. Trust

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship between Trust and Customer Satisfaction, represented by H11 (correlation = 0.924, p-value = $1.863e - 268$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted. The findings confirm previous studies (Liang et al., 2009; Levy and Hino (2016), suggesting that that the greater the trust Vietnamese banking customers have in Digital Banking providers, the higher the satisfaction they will gain when using Digital Banking channels.

Moreover, based on the descriptive analysis in Chapter 5, the findings show a mix of messages regarding Digital Banking Trust of customers for the studied bank.

When customers were asked whether the studied bank Digital Banking cares about users' current and future interests, 40.91 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 36.82 percent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.27 percent neither agree nor disagree.

When customers were asked whether they completely trust the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding indicates 40.60 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.27 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 22.12 percent neither agree nor disagree.

However, most of respondents believe that the studied bank has necessary experience to provide Digital Banking services with the majority of 61.36 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.45 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 18.18 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Besides, the majority of respondents think the studied bank is a leading brand in the market with 60.76 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 20.00 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 19.24 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

7.2.12. Covid-19 Risk Perceptions

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship between Covid-19 Risk Perceptions and Customer Satisfaction, represented by H12 (correlation = 0.335, p-value = $3.289e - 18$), is a low positive correlation. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that Covid-19 Risk Perceptions has a low impact on Customer Satisfaction.

In contrast to the author's expectations, the role of Covid-19 Risk Perceptions is less relevant in terms of customer satisfaction. Possible explanations for these findings can be traced back to the survey results, which indicate that the majority of respondents are the studied bank

customers for three or more years, which means most respondents can use Digital Banking even before the pandemic.

Moreover, based on quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, in terms of Covid-19 Risk Perceptions, about half of respondents agree that Covid-19 has a high fatality rate and stated a health concern for their family and themselves. It can be seen that the majority of respondents (48.03 per cent) are in the young age group of 25-34 young respondents, so Covid-19 Risk Perceptions (fear) does not affect their satisfaction level. This is possibly the reason why the factor Covid-19 Risk Perceptions has low effect on customer satisfaction.

The results might be different if the respondents' profiles are forced to use Digital Banking after the pandemic due to social distancing and lockdown, which can be seen as a future research direction.

7.2.13. Summary of key dimensions

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, in terms of the effect of Digital Banking Service Quality on customer satisfaction, based on Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient results, 12 factors of Digital Banking Service Quality can be divided into four groups based on the strength of its relationship with Customer Satisfaction in the order of importance:

- ✓ Group 1: Trust (correlation = 0.924), followed by Digital Emotional Connection (correlation = 0.900), has the most substantial impact on customer satisfaction (very high positive correlation).
- ✓ Group 2: Customer Service and Support, followed by Privacy and Security, then Reliability and Speed (same correlation = 0.864), Usefulness (correlation = 0.836), Convenience (correlation = 0.824), Design (correlation = 0.806), lastly is Ease of Use (correlation = 0.805). These Digital Banking service quality dimensions all have highly correlated with Customer Satisfaction.

- ✓ Group 3: Covid-19 risk perceptions (correlation = 0.335) presents a low positive relationship with Customer Satisfaction.
- ✓ Group 4: The last being Services Portfolio/Products (correlation = 0.261). the relationship between Services Portfolio/Products and Customer Satisfaction has a negligible correlation.

Amongst 12 Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions, Group 1 (Trust, Digital Emotional Connection) and Group 2 (Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability and Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use) mentioned above have the most significant impacts on customer satisfaction, which in turn have a strong impact on customer loyalty. However, it should be noted that, in contrast to the author's assumptions, the role of Covid-19 risk perceptions and Services Portfolio/Products is less relevant as critical drivers of customer satisfaction. The results allow managers to understand better how Digital Banking Service Quality is created and the importance of each Digital Banking Service Quality factor in ensuring customers' satisfaction, which may lead to increased customers' loyalty. Based on the findings of this study, managers can be able to increase the quality of Digital Banking service by paying more attention to the identified Group 1 and Group 2 dimensions to implement Digital Banking innovations to sustain a high level of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

7.3. Customer Satisfaction - Customer Loyalty and Trust- Customer Loyalty.

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, in terms of the effect of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty, based on Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient results, the relationship between "Customer Satisfaction" and "Customer Loyalty", represented by H13 (correlation = 0.927, p-value = $1.923e - 273$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that "Customer Satisfaction" significantly impacts "Customer Loyalty".

These findings are consistent with the view of other researches in the similar context such as Mbama and Ezepue (2018); Kassim and Abdullah (2010); Raza et al. (2020); Amin (2016); Jun and Palacios (2016; Keisidou et al. 2013), therefore, demonstrating the comparability of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty across various countries. The more satisfied and pleased the customers are with Digital Banking Services, the more loyal and dedicated they will become.

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, in terms of the effect of Trust on Customer Loyalty, based on Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient results, the relationship between "Trust" and "Customer Loyalty", represented by H14 (correlation = 0.873, p-value = 1.368e – 242), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that "Trust" significantly impacts "Customer Loyalty". These findings confirm (Kassim and Abdullah 2010; Levy & Hino, 2016). In order to build a solid foundation for a long-term relationship between customers and service providers, initial trust is regarded as a critical precondition of customer loyalty to online banking (Hong and Cho, 2011). Customers are more loyal to service suppliers when they feel trust in the banking service providers (Kassim and Asiah Abdullah, 2010; Sanchez-Franco, 2009; Butt and Aftab, 2013).

7.4. Stakeholder Perceptions about Digital Banking developments in Vietnam.

7.4.1. Customers

Based on the descriptive analysis of the survey data present in Chapter 5, the findings showed customers' perceptions about the Digital Banking applications provided by the studied bank. It is evident from the result that respondents' view of Customer Satisfaction proves a consistent pattern.

Regarding satisfaction with the Digital Banking services provided by the studied bank, the order of prevalence is 39.85 per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined),

followed by 37.87 per cent are not satisfied (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.27 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Concerning satisfaction with the transactions process via Digital Banking channels by the studied bank, the Survey reflected that 40.85 per cent of respondents are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 36.67 per cent are not happy (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

In terms of satisfaction with the experience with the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding showed that 39.70 per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 37.88 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Overall, the findings shows that about 40 per cent of sample customers are satisfied with the studied bank Digital Banking while about 37 per cent of respondents are not satisfied and about 23 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Based on the descriptive analysis of the survey data present in Chapter 5, Regarding Loyalty, there is a mix of opinions from sample Digital Banking users.

In terms of Intentions to say Positive things about the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding indicates 40.15 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 36.52 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), and 23.33 per cent are neither agree nor disagree.

In terms of Intentions to recommend Digital Banking to someone who seeks their advice, the order of prevalence is 39.39 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.64 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 2.88 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

When customers were asked whether they would encourage their friends and family to use the studied bank Digital Banking, the Survey reflected 41.09 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.09 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and then 21.82 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

However, when customers were asked whether they would consider the studied bank Digital Banking as their first choice for future transactions, 39.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed 38.40 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.12 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Besides, about their Intentions to continue using the studied bank Digital Banking, the results show a nearly a half (49.39 per cent) of respondents agree to continue using Digital Banking (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 31.67 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 18.94 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, the relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty, represented by H9 (correlation = 0.927, p-value = $1.923e - 273$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that customer satisfaction has a significant positive direct relationship with customer loyalty. The relationship between Trust and Customer Loyalty, represented by H9 (correlation = 0.873, p-value = $1.368e - 242$), is a high positive correlation; the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that trust significantly impacts customer loyalty. Findings from the research justified that both customers' satisfaction and trust have significantly contributed to loyalty which is similar to the insights of Kassim & Abdullah (2010) in their study of e-commerce settings in the context of Malaysia and Qatar. These findings imply that banks should focus on increasing customer satisfaction and customer trust to increase customer loyalty.

7.4.2. Bank managers

Based on the Template Analysis of the interview data presented in Chapter 6, the findings showed the perceptions of managers about the Digital Banking applications provided by studied bank. In conclusion, bank managers are fairly satisfied with the Digital Banking experience that they provided to their clients. However, they propose some suggestions on improving Digital Banking and customisation in order to enhance the level of customers' satisfaction, which will take a certain amount of time and investment. All of the managers acknowledged that the level of customers' satisfaction is moderate, which suggests that the study is able to indicate staffs' opinions on how satisfied customers are with the banks' Digital Banking services. It demonstrates how the experience from using Digital Banking services can help determine the satisfaction levels of staffs and customers and also identify loyalty outcomes from staffs' perspectives. The findings suggest that customers' satisfaction might increase if banks could provide high quality services which in turn bring about better experience for customers.

7.5. Challenges for Digital Banking developments in Vietnam.

7.5.1. Legal Frameworks

Based on the results of qualitative analysis obtained from bank managers' interview, one of the main challenges hindering the developments of Digital Banking in the context of Vietnam which is stated by all of the participants is the shortage of the legal framework for Digital Banking operations. They all stated that although the SBV has issued general guiding documents for digital banking implementation, however, along with the development of the market, many new relationships and products have arisen, but legal documents to regulate them have not been issued in time, which prevents the development of Digital Banking of the studied bank in particular and the Vietnam banking sector in general.

The findings align with report from the Vietnam Banks Associations, the legal corridor for electronic payment activities has not been accomplished. Particularly, the legal framework and mechanisms and policies related to services, online payment means, new and modern electronic, virtual money, virtual card, electronic money... are new and complex issues, to date has not been guided by regulatory agencies or currently is in the pilot phase (VNBA, 2022).

This problem results from a mismatch between the quick development of domestic legal regulations and the rapid advancement of digital payment technologies. As a result, commercial banks have been reluctant to adopt new technologies and provide innovative services outside of the banking system's approval, to take advantage of the opportunities provided by digital banking because they are faced with ambiguity and potential regulatory concerns when implementing new technology and services in the absence of a strong and current legal framework.

7.5.2. Information Security System

Findings gathered from the qualitative analysis presented in Chapter 6 has exposed a outstanding concern articulated by all five banking managers regarding the absence of a robust Information Security System, which poses one of the most important challenges to the development of Digital Banking in Vietnam. All interviewed banking managers shared their concerns that fraud cases related to high-tech crimes are increasingly dangerous, sophisticated and complex. Although the ability to prevent and combat fraud in digital banking transactions has always been of interest to the studied bank, it has not yet created complete peace of mind for customers. This finding aligns with the secondary data demonstrating the security risks faced by the banking sector in the context of Vietnam. According to Banking Review (2022), in Vietnam, predominant security risks such as fraud, customer fraud, cyberattacks targeting bank infrastructure and unauthorised access to user data are increasing. As concerned by

Vietnam Information Security Association (VNISA) Southern President Ngo Vi Dong, online fraud in cyberspace is becoming more and more complicated (VNISA, 2022). Meanwhile, Ngo Minh Hieu, a Vietnam National Cyber Security Monitoring Centre (NCSC) expert, issued a warning about the increasing use of deepfake video technology (NCSC, 2022). This misleading approach use artificial intelligence to blend one person's picture and voice with that of another, resulting in phone movies that can be exploited for fraudulent reasons (NCSC, 2022). This concerning tendency has resulted in financial losses for a number of people. Despite efforts to intervene and avoid similar events, new varieties of this fraudulent practice are expected to arise in the future.

Also in 2021, according to the "Security Endpoint Threat Report", Vietnam ranks second in Asia in terms of the number of ransomwares, an increase of 200% compared to 2020. Research by Viettel network company 2021 also shows that 90% of cyber-attacks are related to the financial - banking system in 2021, up to 42.4% compared to 2020 (Viettel,2021). These risks have been on the rise, as highlighted by the Banking Review (2022). This report illustrates the importance of tackling information security in the banking industry and points out the digital vulnerabilities that banks experience (VISA, 2022).

By 2022, according to Kaspersky - a Russian security software manufacturer and distributor, Vietnam is among the top 5 countries in the Asia-Pacific region in terms of the risk of cyberattacks (Kaspersky,2022).

As pointed out by The Ministry of Information and Communications (2023), online fraud cases tend to increase, most of which are fake websites of financial and banking institutions. In the first 6 months of 2023, more than 4,000 complaints were received about fraud cases sent by Vietnamese Internet users through warning systems, of which more than 95 per cent were related to fraud in the banking - finance sector (MIC,2023).

7.5.3. Capital Requirements

In additions, based on the results of qualitative analysis obtained from banking managers' interviews, one of the prominent challenges for banks in Vietnam is that the implementation of digital banking requires a substantial Capital requirement, including investments in technology, infrastructure and human resource training. The findings are consistent with the view of Dr. Nguyen Quoc Hung – Vice President and General Secretary of Vietnam Bankers Association (VNBA) “Investment costs for technology systems and development of new products and services are intensive. In addition, banks must also invest significantly and frequently in security solutions to ensure that customer information and payment transactions are not exposed; in training employees and customers on new technologies and how to navigate them safely” (VNBA,2023). According to The Economist (2021), four America's largest banks are spending a total of more than \$25 billion per year perfecting customer applications and learning how to use data smarter. Although statistics has shown that by the end of 2022, the Vietnamese banking sector has invested more than VND 15,000 billion in digital transformation activities (VNBA,2023), yet compared to other banking setting globally, the financial potential of Vietnamese commercial banks is still quite limited (VNBA,2023).

7.5.4. Human resources

According to the qualitative analysis in Chapter 6, all five bank managers agree that there are insufficient human resources in the Digital Banking service, which suggests that increases in customers' requirements cannot be fully met. As specified by all the interviewed banking managers, Banks are focusing on digital transformation and automation, which is increasing demand for positions in IT, technology, and data analytics... These vacancies particularly require high-quality human resources, which poses a significant challenge for banks in recruitment and investment owing to market competition. With existing human resource,

Digital transformation requires a change in culture and processes within the bank. This can face the difficulty of changing traditional thinking and working habits.

The results are consistent with the general opinion of the Vietnam bank's leaders which stated that the number of personnel with sufficient knowledge, vision and skills to realise digital transformation of the banking industry in Vietnam is currently limited (Banking Review, 2022). Apart from technical upgrades for the system, human resources' knowledge and proficiency are also imperative factors, accounting for running Digital Banking system effectively and smoothly. Therefore, to carry out digital transformation, commercial banks urgently need human resources capable of operating and developing digital products and services on modern technology platforms (Banking Review, 2022).

7.5.5. Competitions

Regarding Competitions, as concerned by all the interviewed banking managers, the Vietnamese digital banking landscape has been rapidly expanding, leading to an infusion of both domestic and foreign institutions into the market who are in constant race in investing cybersecurity measures and meeting customers' expectations. This can be seen as a substantial challenge for the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general in their digital transformation journey. Findings align with the secondary data, which confirms its robustness. According to SBV Survey, 95% of Vietnamese banks have been developing or planning to develop a digital transformation strategy, of which 39% have approved a digital transformation strategy or integrated in business development/information technology strategy; 42% of banks are building a digital transformation strategy (SBV, 2020). Not only Vietnamese commercial banks have to face a stiff competition among banks but also with technology companies in financial/payment services. Some global brands that have penetrated the Vietnamese market are Samsung Pay, Amazon (through an agreement to provide e-commerce services for VECOM); Alibaba (through its 83% ownership of Lazada) and JD.com (through

its \$50 million investment in Tiki) (Banking Review, 2022). Although the big technology corporations in Vietnam (FPT, Viettel, BKAV) still mainly focus on the main field of technology, but some corporations have started to approach providing financial services through the development of electronic payment tools, such as WePay, Zalo Pay, Bao Kim, Bankplus (VN Finance Magazine, 2022), intensifying the competitions in the Vietnamese digital banking landscape.

7.5.6. Cashless payments challenges

As concerned by all the interviewed banking managers, Cashless payments challenges is another challenge for the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general in their digital transformation journey. The main reason for cashless payments challenges is due to the habit of using cash ingrained in people's subconscious, the fear of accessing new payment technology, as well as concerns about security and safety when making online purchases using digital banking services. Therefore, changing people's consumption habit of using cash also poses many challenges to the digital transformation process of the studied bank in particular and the Vietnamese Commercial Banks in general.

According to SBV (2020), during the period from 2016 to 2020, the Vietnam Government and the SBV worked together to change the institutional environment and foster digital transformation in Vietnam. During this time, there has been a noteworthy shift in consumer behaviour, with a decrease in the usage of cash for payments and an increase in preference for electronic payment methods provided by financial institutions (SBV, 2020). The Cashless Payment Development Project has produced significant outcomes, as indicated by customers' decreasing reliance on cash transactions. According to a VNBA Statistics, comparing the first 5 months of 2023 with the same period in previous year 2022: Non-cash payment transactions increased by 52.35% in quantity; via Internet channel increased by 75.54% in quantity and

1.77% in value; via mobile phone channels increased by 64.26% and 7.65% respectively; via QR code method increased by 151.14% and 30.41% respectively; via POS increased by 30.35% and 27.27% respectively in value; via ATM decreased by 4.62% in quantity and 6.43% in value, reflecting the trend of shifting to electronic payment and non-cash payment (VNBA,2023).

However, despite the progress made, challenges for cashless payment in a cash-based economy such as Vietnam is still outstanding, which in turn, poses a significant challenge for digital banking development in the context of Vietnam Banking Sector. According to Mr. Pham Anh Tuan, Director of Payment Department, State Bank of Vietnam (SBV), the vast majority of Vietnamese people still have the habit of using cash in payment, especially in rural areas (SBV,2022). Limited access to banking services, inadequate technological infrastructure, and lower levels of digital literacy among the population are often the challenges these regions have to encounter in the non-cash payment journey (SBV,2022). This is in line with the view of VNBA (2023), non-cash payment methods have been increasingly popular in Vietnam's core provinces and towns, where the infrastructure for technology is well-developed, but not in remote and distant areas of the country (VNBA,2023). It is estimated that approximately 70% of the population in these areas do not have bank accounts, making them more reliant on physical cash for their financial activities (VNBA,2023). In order to promote cashless payment, a representative of the SBV said that in the coming time, the State Bank will continue to study, review and complete the legal framework, develop mechanisms and policies to promote non-cash payment on the basis of technology application and innovation (SBV,2023).

In essence, the findings from banking managers interviews are consistent with the view of different key stakeholders, mostly policymakers, revealed in authentic secondary data sources, which increases the robustness of the results.

7.6. Summary

This chapter presented a comprehensive analysis and discussion of the consolidation of findings derived from both quantitative and qualitative aspects, as presented in Chapter 5 and Chapter 6, demonstrated its connection to the extant literature and its implications in addressing the four research questions: key dimensions of Digital Banking Service Quality affecting Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty, different stakeholders' perceptions about Digital Banking developments, challenges for developments Digital Banking in Vietnam,

Throughout this chapter, we have critically analysed the results, identified key themes, and drawn connections between the different sources of information. By synthesizing these various sources, we have been able to provide a comprehensive overview of the research findings and their implications.

Firstly, Key DBSQ dimensions affecting Digital Banking customer satisfaction and customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks were discussed. Findings revealed 10 out of 12 Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability, Speed, Usefulness, Convenience Design, Ease of Use has strong impact on Customer Satisfaction with Trust (correlation = 0.924), followed by Digital Emotional Connection (correlation =0.900), has the most substantial impact on customer satisfaction. Theoretically, these ten validated attributes of Digital Banking service quality and their related items can serve as building blocks for further research in the field of digital banking and customer relationship management. Practically, Vietnamese Commercial Banks should place greater emphasis on the aforementioned ten most vital dimensions of digital banking service quality to effectively nurture customer satisfaction and ultimately foster their customer loyalty.

The findings also indicate that Trust and Customer Satisfaction has strong impact on Customer Loyalty, which are consistent with the view of other researches in the similar context such as Mbama and Ezepue (2018); Kassim and Abdullah (2010); Raza et al. (2020); Amin (2016); Jun and Palacios (2016), therefore, demonstrating the comparability of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty across various countries. Subsequently, the research discussed the perceptions of key stakeholders (banking managers and banking customers) towards the current implementation of digital banking of the studied banks along with the challenges for Digital Banking developments in the context of Vietnam Banking Sector. These discussions pave the way for the recommendations for relevant stakeholders in utilising Digital Banking as a means of enhancing customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, which will be presented in the final chapter of this study.

CHAPTER EIGHT:

CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1. Introduction

This study's last chapter is intended to summarise the entire research process and delineate how the set research questions were successfully answered. Each research question will be addressed separately in order to determine its fulfilment and the resulting outcomes.

Subsequently, the chapter analyses the research's theoretical and managerial implications, as well as acknowledges research limitations and prospective future research directions, paving the way for future scholars interested in the dynamic subject of digital banking and its applications. Building on the findings of digital banking customer satisfaction and loyalty, the chapter will proffer informed recommendations for relevant stakeholders about how to utilise Digital Banking service quality as a means to foster customer satisfaction and loyalty strategies in the context of the Vietnamese banking system. The final section of this chapter is devoted to the researcher's reflective 'End-of-Thesis Self-Reflection' as an appropriate conclusion to this intellectually exciting and satisfying academic journey.

8.2. Summary of the Research

The extensive literature review on digital banking services revealed an important yet unanswered research gap that calls for an in-depth and systematic investigation of the key dimensions of digital banking service quality and its impact on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. To fill this research gap, the research employs Pragmatism Philosophy, Abduction Approach, Case Study Strategy, Mixed-Methods Design with customers survey and banking managers interviews, Spearman Correlation Coefficient and Template Analysis respectively, facilitating a comprehension of current implementations and effects of digital

banking phenomenon in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks from various perspectives.

8.3. Main research results by Research Questions

This section concisely summarises the important empirical data that have been conscientiously gathered and assessed in answer to the research questions. These findings, informed by a rigorous methodology and extensive data analysis, serve as direct responses to the four primary research questions, which have been carefully formulated to address the critical aspects of digital banking, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in the context of the Vietnamese Banking System, allowing for an in-depth investigation of the research topic. Each of these four essential research questions served as a framework for the study, guiding data collection and analysis. The findings linked with each issue are elaborated in detail, based on the extensive empirical data acquired throughout this investigation. The below section provides a comprehensive summary of the research's outcomes by briefly summarising these main findings based on separate research question, offering a better grasp of the practical and theoretical implications of the research.

8.3.1. Research Question 1

RQ1: “Which Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions are most significantly associated with DB customer satisfaction and DB customer loyalty as perceived by banking customers in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?”

The main purpose of this research is to investigate the dimensions of digital banking service quality and their influence on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of the Vietnamese Banking System. In order to achieve this goal, the current research conducted an extensive review of relevant literature and employed a mixed-method research design including web-based self-completed surveys for digital banking users, semi-structured interviews with banking managers, and thorough analysis of secondary data.

Through the analysis of collected primary data and an extensive literature review, the research investigated how Digital Banking service quality dimensions can lead to an increase in customers' satisfaction and loyalty by determining the major dimensions of Digital Banking Service Quality affecting them in the banking sector in Vietnam. The most significant antecedents of Customer Satisfaction found in this research: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability and Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use. Additionally, customer satisfaction and trust emerge as the primary drivers of customer loyalty. The findings offer valuable insights into how Vietnam commercial banks can leverage digital banking to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty effectively. This study provides evidence of the effectiveness of utilising digital banking as a means to improve customer satisfaction and foster customer loyalty.

8.3.2. Research Question 2

RQ2: "How do the primary stakeholders (banking customers and banking managers) perceive the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks?"

The following section presents the summary of the perceptions of banking customers and banking managers about the current situation of Digital Banking implementation in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks" building upon the insights gathered from the quantitative and qualitative data collection.

Banking Customers Perceptions

Based on the descriptive analysis of the survey data present in Chapter 5, the findings showed customers' perceptions about the Digital Banking applications provided by the studied bank. It is evident from the result that respondents' view of Customer Satisfaction proves a consistent pattern.

Firstly, regarding satisfaction with the Digital Banking services provided by the studied bank, the order of prevalence is 39.85 per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 37.87 per cent are not satisfied (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.27 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Concerning satisfaction with the transactions process via Digital Banking channels by the studied bank, the Survey reflected that 40.85 per cent of respondents are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 36.67 per cent are not happy (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither agree nor disagree. In terms of satisfaction with the experience with the studied bank Digital Banking, the finding showed that 39.70 per cent are satisfied (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 37.88 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.42 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Overall, the findings shows that about 40 per cent of sample customers are satisfied with the studied bank Digital Banking while about 37 per cent of respondents are not satisfied and about 23 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Secondly, regarding Loyalty, there is a mix of opinions from sample Digital Banking users based on the descriptive analysis of the survey data present in Chapter 5. The finding indicates 40.15 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 36.52 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined), and 23.33 per cent are neither agree nor disagree that they have the intentions to say positive things about the studied bank Digital Banking. In terms of Intentions to recommend Digital Banking to someone who seeks their advice, the order of prevalence is 39.39 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.64 per cent agree (both strongly agree and agree combined) and 2.88 per cent neither agree nor disagree. When customers were asked whether they would encourage their friends and family to use the studied bank Digital Banking, the Survey reflected 41.09 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined), followed by 37.09 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined) and then 21.82 per cent neither agree

nor disagree. However, when customers were asked whether they would consider the studied bank Digital Banking as their first choice for future transactions, 39.48 per cent agreed (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed 38.40 per cent disagreed (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 22.12 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Besides, about their Intentions to continue using the studied bank Digital Banking, the results show a nearly a half (49.39 per cent) of respondents agree to continue using Digital Banking (both strongly agree and agree combined), followed by 31.67 per cent disagree (both strongly disagree and disagree combined) and 18.94 per cent neither agree nor disagree.

Moreover, based on the quantitative analysis in Chapter 5, findings from the research justified that both Customer Satisfaction and Trust have significantly contributed to Customer Loyalty which is similar to the insights of Kassim & Abdullah (2010) in their study of e-commerce settings in the context of Malaysia and Qatar. These findings imply that banks should focus on increasing Customer Satisfaction and Trust to increase Customer Loyalty.

Banking Managers Perceptions

In terms of Services portfolio/products, most of the managers generally agreed that the studied bank provides a diversify of Digital Banking services/products and also a wide range of features on its Digital Banking channels (web/app), which are suitable for different customer segmentation. However, it is essential to note that most of the managers stated that the current fee of its Digital Banking is currently high compared to other banks, which could not be a competitive advantage for the studied bank. In terms of Ease of Use, most of the managers agreed that in general, Digital Banking products offered by the studied bank is easy to use for customer with the consolidations of web/app design by 01 username and password. However, some managers are concerned that the Smart OTP activation is too complex, which might be difficult for middle-aged customers. Most managers agreed that the studied bank had not comprehensively developed communications and guidance for customers in using Digital

Banking services. The bank has not regularly uploaded video guidance to instruct/educate customers to perform all the features of the Digital Banking app/websites. Communications on each new feature launching have not been reached broadly (widely and deeply) to customers”. In terms of Convenience, all of the managers agreed that Digital Banking brings many conveniences for customers: saving time, saving cost, access service any time anywhere. All managers highly evaluated the convenience of 01 username and 01 password on both Digital Banking channels web/app and the same transaction limit across all Digital Banking channels. Addition, Usefulness is another feature that all the five managers perceived that their Digital Banking for customers highly evaluated the of. All of them stated that Digital Banking had brought many benefits to customers with diverse features allowing customers to perform financial transactions. However, most managers think the studied banks can do better.

However, Reliability of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank is one of their concerns. Most managers are concerned with the errors that sometimes happen when customers use the instant money transfer 24/7 service from the studied bank to other banks but do not receive money instantly.

Based on the analysis of the interviews, most of the managers generally evaluated the Privacy and Security of Digital Banking channels as “relatively good”. They all agreed that the studied bank currently integrate many advanced security technologies to ensure the privacy and security for customer information and transaction on the Digital Banking channels web/app. However, they also stated that problems such as unauthorised banking transactions sometimes come from customers’ side when they accidentally disclose their information to scammers.

Based on the analysis of the interviews, there is a mixed messages from the bank managers regarding the Speed of Digital Banking channels. On one hand, most of the managers agreed that in general, the Speed of Digital Banking channels have improved significantly. The studied

banks offer smooth transactions on their Digital Banking channels, only sometimes a bit slow at the end of the day because this is when the banks run end-of-day data. On the other hand, some managers are concerned that the system is often overloaded, making customers unable to access their accounts.

Based on the results of the five interviews, most of the managers agreed that in general, the Design of Digital Banking channels is simple, modern, and easy to use with the new style “dark mode”. They stated customers have good feedback with the Design and colour of the Digital Banking web/app. However, in terms of the features of the web/app, they also noted the features displayed on the screen are not concise and logical. There is an overuse of icons, requiring many manipulations with the toolbar from customers to choose. Moreover, they concerned that putting many icons on the application screen is confusing and unfriendly for middle-aged customers.

Based on the results of the interviews, all of the managers highly evaluated the quality of the bank staff in terms of Digital Banking knowledge and capability of supporting customers. They are concerned that customers have difficulties reaching Hotline 24/7 Customer Service due to extremely high-volume calls. In contrast, all of the managers stated that the Digital Banking app/website of the studied bank has not yet allowed customers to contact online with customer service. All of the managers highly evaluated the quality of the bank staff in terms of Digital Banking knowledge and capability of supporting customers. All managers stated that in their digital banking implementation, their mindset has been shifting from a rational aspect such as various performance measures to an emotional aspect such as customer and employee satisfaction, with an emphasis on building a long-term relationship between the bank and our customers”

Based on the Template Analysis of the interview data presented in Chapter 6, the findings showed the perceptions of managers about the Digital Banking applications provided by studied bank.

In conclusion, bank managers are fairly satisfied with the Digital Banking experience that they provided to their clients. However, they propose some suggestions on improving Digital Banking and customisation in order to enhance the level of customers' satisfaction, which will take a certain amount of time and investment.

All of the managers acknowledged that the level of customers' satisfaction is moderate, which suggests that the study is able to indicate staffs' opinions on how satisfied customers are with the banks' Digital Banking services. It demonstrates how the experience from using Digital Banking services can help determine the satisfaction levels of staffs and customers and also identify loyalty outcomes from staffs' perspectives. The findings suggest that customers' satisfaction might increase if banks could provide high quality services which in turn bring about better experience for customers.

8.3.3. Research Question 3

RQ3: "What are the key challenges for Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty?"

In order to answer Research Question 3, the research reviewed survey results for customers, bank managers' interviews, and different stakeholders' perspectives of current Digital Banking developments in Vietnam from secondary data.

Based on insights gathered from the research, the following section is dedicated to a comprehensive discussion about the challenges for Vietnamese Commercial Banks in using Digital Banking Services as a means of enhancing Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty.

Firstly, the legal framework that serves as the foundation for Digital Banking administration and growth does not take into account some factors. For example, there is a very fast evolution in the digital payment field by dint of advancements in technology, however, legal policies have lagged behind, disincentivising banks to adopt new services and technological advances outside the framework of the banking system permission.

Second, the recent cases of fraud related to digital payment activities are becoming more and more sophisticated and complex. The ability to prevent fraud for Digital Banking transactions has always been of interest to commercial banks but still cannot create peace of mind for customers. The Department of Cybersecurity and High-Tech Crime Prevention (Ministry of Public Security) announced that there is a continuous grow in the cybercriminals' level in sectors such as internet payment, finance, and banking. This is because the subjects use the profits benefit from promotion programs to scam individuals' money via sending messages comprising fake links, using spam sims impersonating bank staff, reporting errors to require clients to provide passwords and OTP codes, etc.

Third, the technological race in the banking industry with Digital Banking projects also contributes to many risks in security in general and insecurity of user information in particular. The capacity to secure financial information in the digital environment is still limited in Vietnam.

Fourth, users' awareness when they are not aware of the risks in online banking transactions, disregarding the security of personal information; students, employees... leasing information, creating conditions for criminals to create ghost accounts, causing difficulties in the investigation; transactions, fraud tricks are increasingly sophisticated and difficult to detect...

Fifth, in Vietnam, most people still prefer to pay using cash and non-cash payment is only common in big cities in which people are equipped with advanced technological infrastructure

conditions. While on the other hand, non-cash payment is still in the planning stage in remote regions.

8.3.4. Research Question 4

RQ4: “What recommendations can be proposed to stakeholders regarding the utilisation of digital banking channels to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnamese Banking Sector?”

The researcher's ultimate goal is to make recommendations for Digital Banking relevant stakeholders in the context of the Vietnam Banking Sector regarding the use of Digital Banking channels as a means to improve Digital Banking Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. Suggestions are put forward on the basis of the findings from a customer survey, along with bank managers' interviews and secondary data. Triangulating these results together will lead to the robustness of the recommendations which will be discussed in more detail in Section 8.5, answering the Research Question 4.

Detailed discussions of these recommendations are presented in Section 8.5 of this chapter.

8.4. Contribution to Knowledge

Providing meaningful contributing to the existing body of knowledge is the fundamental goal of this doctoral thesis. The selected research topic has been rigorously analysed and examined throughout this study. This research's contributions to knowledge will be divided into two categories: theoretical and practical implications, as presented below.

8.4.1. Theoretical implications

This DBA research has a crucial inference for the theoretical implications by offering a noteworthy contribution to literature of bank marketing and academicians by delineating how digital banking service quality dimensions are used as a predictor of DB customer satisfaction and subsequently foster DB customer loyalty in the context of an emerging economy - Vietnam.

First, in the current literature on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty with Digital Banking, the majority of this study are centred on the context of Western countries and there is also sparse research being conducted in the context of emerging economies such as Vietnam. The findings of this thesis have bridged the literature gap in Digital Banking identified in Chapter 2, which will significantly contribute to the existing body of knowledge relating to digital banking, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty with a special emphasis on bank marketing and financial services marketing. The research at hand extends the existing literature in global context (Mbama & Ezepue, 2018; Raza et al., 2020; Hussien and El Aziz, 2013; Amin, 2016, Alkhowaiter,2020, Jun & Cai, 2001; Jun & Palacios, 2016; Larsson & Viitaoja, 2017; Yoon, 2010; Shankar and Jebarajakirthy, 2019; Ayo et al., 2016; Kassim & Abdullah, 2010; Hammoud et al., 2018; Ho & Lin, 2010; Liu et al., 2008) and in Vietnam context (Chong et al.,2010; Pham et al.,2013; Nguyen et al., 2019; Trinh, Le and Nguyen, 2020, Nguyen and Huynh, 2021; Thu Nguyen et al., 2020; Duong, 2015; Hsu and Nguyen, 2016; Vu, Nguyen and Huu, 2016).

Secondly, this study is carried out in the Vietnam Banking context and provided key innovative insights by forming a research model and testing hypotheses to identify the key Digital Banking Service Quality determinants of Customer Satisfaction, which offers invaluable theoretical implications for bank marketing and future research avenues. The most significant antecedents of Customer Satisfaction found in this research are: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability and Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use, while both Customer Satisfaction and Trust immensely affect Customer Loyalty. For example, findings reveal Ease of Use is a strong driver of customer satisfaction, which contradicts Yoon (2010), yet confirms several studies of Raza et al. (2020); Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba (2018a); Jun and Palacios (2016); Kassim and Abdullah (2010); Castaneda et al. (2007); Devaraj, Fan and Kohli (2002). Finding reveals

Convenience has a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction contradicts Srinivasan et al. (2002) and Keisidou et al. (2013) yet confirms Jun and Palacios (2016). Findings reveals Convenience has a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction propose a similar view as those of previous studies in Pakistan internet banking (Raza *et al.*, 2020), Lebanese banking sector (Hammoud, Bizri and El Baba, 2018) and e-banking (Shankar and Jebarajakirthy 2019; Liao and Cheung 2002), internet banking (Tan and Teo, 2000) or (Kettinger and Lee, 2005). In genera, research findings confirms and contradicts with the extant literature, therefore, theoretically, these ten digital banking service quality dimensions developed and acknowledged in the research along with their related items can assist as a building block for future research avenues in the field of digital banking and customer relationship management.

Thirdly, a distinctive and innovative characteristic of this study that provides the most valuable contribution to future research is that it is the first study attempting to delve into the effects of Digital – Emotional Connection on Customer Satisfaction in the context of Vietnam Commercial Banks. Evidence indicates that in the context of Vietnam Banking Sector, Digital-Emotional Connection accounts for the most important element in impacting Customer Satisfaction when it comes to using Digital Banking. Since the research is the first attempt to incorporate the Digital -Emotional Connection in the conceptual framework to investigate its relationship with Customer Satisfaction in the context of Vietnam Digital Banking, this finding is a significant addition to the existing body of knowledge.

However, it should be noted that, contrary to the author's expectations, the role of Services Portfolio/Products is less relevant as key drivers of customer satisfaction. These findings imply that Services portfolio/ Products appear to have little impact on Customer Satisfaction and hence, Services Portfolio/Products appear irrelevant for Digital Banking customers. This result contradicts prior research of Jun and Cai (2001), indicating that "Banking service product

quality” exerts a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction when investigating Internet Banking in the USA. Possible explanations for these contradictories may be due to the research site- Vietnam. Since Digital Banking is a new emerging service/product in Vietnam, the range of Digital Banking services offered by different Vietnam banks is currently quite similar. Simultaneously, Digital Banking in Vietnam is also a newly developed services, customers are. This findings indicate that the portfolio, diversity, and breadth of digital banking services currently offered do not have a great impact on customer satisfaction in the context of Vietnam. These results, hence, add fresh perspectives to the existing body of knowledge.

Furthermore, it's worth mentioning that, in contrast to the researcher's initial assumptions, the significance of Covid-19 Risk Perceptions as a decisive determinant of customer satisfaction in the context of Digital Banking is not as pronounced as anticipated. A plausible explanations for these findings can be traced back to the survey results, which indicate that the majority of respondents are the studied bank customers for three or more years, indicating their familiarity with Digital Banking predates the pandemic. Additionally, a predominant proportion of survey participants - 48.03% - fall into the 25–34 age range, which is considered to be a younger demographic. Their opinions on the hazards associated with Covid-19 reportedly have little to no impact on how satisfied they are with Digital Banking Services offered by the studied bank. This demographic factor may help to explain why our findings just show a relatively minor effect of Covid-19 risk perceptions on customer satisfaction. The results might be different if the respondents’ profiles are forced to use Digital Banking after the pandemic due to social distancing and lockdown. Theoretically, this scenario presents a compelling direction for future research.

Last but not least, as articulated in Chapter 2 Literature Review, Research Methodology employed in research is another gap the researcher found in the Digital Banking literature in

the Vietnam context. Based on the discussions above of Digital Banking literature in Vietnam, most of the recent studies focus on investigating the Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions only from customers' perspectives, using Survey Questionnaires as a main data collection method and SEM as the primary data analysis technique to test hypotheses. Therefore, theoretically, this thesis has bridged the gaps by examining Digital Banking from different stakeholders' perceptions (banking managers and banking customers) by employing a mixed-method study with a survey for customers, interviews for bank managers, and secondary data for other stakeholders' groups. Methodologies of collecting data and approaches of analysing data employed in this research demonstrate the deep understanding and robustness of upgraded Digital Banking models, which will significantly contribute to the existing body of knowledge.

In summary, theoretically, the research's insightful and solid findings contribute significantly to the literature on service marketing and customer behaviour, particularly in the field bank marketing. This study is especially useful for scholars who want to grasp more knowledge about Digital Banking from different viewpoints.

8.4.2. Practical Implications

The rapid growth of digital banking, the intense competitions among banks and the constantly changing customer needs, in the context of Vietnamese commercial banks emphasises the importance of concentrating on Digital Banking and Customer Relations as a crucial factor to address when designing any digital banking strategies. This doctoral dissertation undertakes an in-depth investigation of Digital Banking service quality and its subsequent effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty, particularly in the context of Vietnam. Research findings make significant contribute to practice by yielding valuable managerial implications.

First and foremost, findings from the research reveals overall, about 40 per cent of sample customers are satisfied with the studied bank Digital Banking while about 37 per cent of respondents are not satisfied and about 23 per cent neither agree nor disagree. Consequently, enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering the loyalty of Digital Banking customers at the studied bank is deemed to be of paramount importance.

From a practical standpoint, the outcomes of the research also provide some crucial interpretations for banking practitioners by suggesting insightful strategies to enhance customers' satisfaction loyalty with Digital Banking. The data indicates that 10 out of 12 Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions in the study's model, namely: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability, Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use exert strong effect on Customer Satisfaction while at the same time Customer Satisfaction and Trust both exert a strong influence on Customer Loyalty. This offers financial institutions and professional relevant information about digital banking service quality dimensions that will promote greater customer satisfaction and foster greater customer loyalty. With this in mind, Banking managers should place Greater emphasis on these ten aforementioned validated dimensions in deploying Digital Banking strategies to gain a competitive advantage and enhance customers' satisfaction, which in turn improves customer loyalty. Comprehending these relationships enables the Digital Banking Sector in developing the marketing strategies, preserving long-term the relationship with their customers, and achieving competitive advantages in the digital banking landscape.

Unlike previous studies in Vietnamese digital banking literature, this research is the first attempt to determine Digital Emotional Connection explicitly and investigate digital banking and its perceived effects on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty from multi perspective. The findings offer the most comprehensive study from different stakeholders' groups in the

current developments of Digital Banking and its impact on to customers' satisfaction loyalty, which are of great significance for the decision-making in the Vietnamese banking industry in when it comes to facilitate the digital transformation of Vietnamese commercial banks, contributing significant managerial implications for relevant stakeholders. Findings about Stakeholder Perceptions about Digital Banking developments in Vietnam presented in Chapter 7 will assist the Digital Banking sectors in building effective marketing tactics, fostering long lasting relationships with customers and gaining the competitive edge in the market. Results can be applied to propose relevant strategies to increase customers' satisfactions with the use of Digital Banking services. More attention should be drawn to should be placed.

Furthermore, findings reveal Services portfolio/ Products appear to have little impact on Customer Satisfaction, implying that consumer satisfaction in the context of Vietnamese digital banking is not significantly influenced by the portfolio, diversity, and breadth of digital banking services currently provided by the studied bank. Hence, it is beneficial for Vietnamese commercial banks to study and integrate digital banking service portfolios or products from developed countries, leading to a potential decrease in resource allocation for Digital Banking research and development. These findings offers fresh perspectives and valuable practical implications for managerial level: Vietnamese users of digital banking may not completely appreciate the uniqueness and novelty of these goods and services. Therefore, it may be advantageous for Vietnamese commercial banks to analyse and incorporate similar digital banking service or product portfolios adopted from Western/developed nations, or other countries who successfully implemented Digital Banking, potentially reducing resources allocated for research and development.

This conclusion means that the bank must critically evaluate and comprehend the fundamental elements of convenience from the perspective of the customer, as doing so would enable the bank create policies and digital offers that are more in line with the demands and expectations

of the latter. Aspects such as ease of use, 24/7 accessibility, streamlined processes, seamless multi-channel integration, and immediate customer support could be potential areas of focus. This is consistent with the findings from interview managers who concerned with errors in transaction of Digital Banking channels of the studied bank. Findings reveal most of the banking managers are generally concerned with the Reliability of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank, particularly with the errors with the instant money transfer 24/7 service. These findings suggest that urgent attention needs to be paid into increasing Reliability of Digital Banking service in order to enhance users' satisfaction level. This is because the higher level of accuracy and credibility the Digital Banking service accounts for, the greater the level of customer satisfaction in using Digital Banking. Banks should provide customers with upgraded services without transaction errors within a certain time and also make sure that the information they allocate to customers is correct and up to date in order to address customers' worries about the reliability of Digital Banking.

While still relatively new and far from being widely accepted in Vietnam, the concept of digital banking is unquestionably in an exciting stage of development. As a result, the conclusions drawn from this study may prove to be a useful compass for Vietnamese banks as they navigate the rapidly evolving landscape of information technology. This study provides a crucial road map for service improvement by showing how Digital Banking Service Quality could be used to better foster customer satisfaction and customer loyalty of Vietnamese banking customers. Furthermore, the research conducted here could act as a stepping stone for future studies, paving the way for a deeper comprehension and analysis of the developing Vietnamese digital banking frontier.

8.5. Recommendations

With respect to Vietnamese banking industry, this research proposes a variety of practical and effective recommendations for enhancing the quality of the Digital Banking service.

8.5.1. Recommendations for the studied banks

The process of completely embracing digital technology requires significant financial investments. As a result, it becomes crucial for banks in general and the studied bank in particular to plan a wise balance in budget allocation, assuring the most efficient deployment of resources for the application of digital banking.

Results of this study make it clear that when using Digital Banking to increase customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, the studied bank needs to focus on the aspects of the Digital Banking Service Quality that exert a stronger influence on Customer Satisfaction which were identified in this thesis: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability and Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use. Therefore, Vietnam Commercial Banks needs to prioritise the 10 identified Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions in implementing Digital Banking innovations to sustain a high level of customers' satisfaction and loyalty. By focusing on those identified dimensions of a digital banking service quality that has stronger effect on customer satisfaction and the perception of customers toward digital banking service quality, bank managers may discover methods to develop appropriate strategies in fostering its customer satisfaction while ensuring an effective and efficient resources allocation.

Although Digital - Emotional Connection exerts the strongest impact on Customer Satisfaction, in the case of the studied bank, only half of the respondents have a feeling of Digital - Emotional Connection with the studied bank. Therefore, significant attention should be paid to the studied bank to improve this connection with customers. In general, the studied bank needs to realise that the key to promoting sustainable development lies in connecting with customers on an emotional level. The specific needs, wants, and emotions of customers need to be researched to come up with the most appropriate emotional connection strategy. The bank also needs to define the customer segment they want to focus on clearly and from there banks should

develop more effective marketing measures in offering specific products in accordance with the needs of customers.

Regarding the Customer Service and Support, according to the results of the qualitative data analysis based on the interviews with banking managers at the investigated banks, there is a glaring gap in the communication efforts made by the banks under study to promote and raise awareness of their new digital banking channels. Users of Digital Banking who seek to contact the 24/7 Customer Service hotline run into difficulties, mostly as a result of the consistent high call volumes that cause busy lines or overloading. Although instructional videos has made available on their website to assist customers with digital banking transactions, however, these videos do not encompass all the features of their service, resulting in some users experiencing difficulties while navigating the platform and the level of communication and guidance for customers is viewed as less than optimal. Since social media platforms have become effective means for banks to interact directly with a large customer base, the studied bank should place a lot of emphasis on managing its communications and information there. This strategic approach is essential to promptly informing their customers about the various digital banking services that the bank provides.

Regarding privacy and security, to help clients realise the value of information security, financial institutions should regularly host workshops and educational sessions, both offline and online. Customers should be educated on the many threats that could exist, how to spot them, and what steps need to be taken right away if a security breach is suspected. For digital banking, banks should proactively explain risk mitigation strategies. This can be done via a variety of media, including SMS, OTT platforms, emails, and educational videos.

Moreover, findings reveal that most of the managers are generally concerned with the Reliability of Digital Banking services offered by the studied bank, particularly with the errors

with the instant money transfer 24/7 service. When customers use the instant money transfer 24/7 service outside the studied bank, sometimes errors can happen which makes the beneficiaries cannot receive money instantly. These findings suggest that urgent attention needs to be paid into increasing Reliability of Digital Banking service in order to enhance users' satisfaction level. This is because the higher level of accuracy and credibility the Digital Banking service accounts for, the greater the level of customer satisfaction in using Digital Banking. Banks should provide customers with upgraded services without transaction errors within a certain time and also make sure that the information they allocate to customers is correct and up to date in order to address customers' worries about the reliability of Digital Banking.

Synthesising the insights derived from these findings, it becomes evident that, in the context of Digital Banking services, although customer satisfaction is significantly boosted by the perception of Ease of Use, Usefulness and Convenience but not all customers are able to perceive these dimensions in the case of the studied bank. For example, although the studied bank's digital banking services receive commendation from the managerial perspective for their ease of use, concerns have surfaced regarding the complexity of certain features, underscoring areas that need enhancements to further improve the digital banking experience. In light of this, the studied bank should place a greater emphasis on raising client banking customers awareness of the useful advantages of their digital offerings. This can be accomplished thorough advertising and consultative activities, allowing customers to develop a comprehensive awareness of the usage, benefits and convenience of using Digital Banking services.

However, it should be noted that, contrary to the author's expectations, it is evident from the hypothesis findings that the role of Services Portfolio/Products is less relevant as a key driver of customer satisfaction. The Vietnamese banking customer currently displays a tendency to

not highly appreciate the diversification and uniqueness, but focusing more on the related fees of digital banking services and products. Therefore, Vietnamese commercial banks can learn and adapt the products/services from other Digital Banking providers to save the research and development investment. Simultaneously, banking fees, particularly those linked with digital platforms, may be a significant factor impacting consumer satisfaction and, as such, must be carefully considered. The studied bank should also prioritise the transparency and clarity regarding the fees by fully educating and communicating with its customers about all the costs and benefits related with the given digital banking services. The studied bank could also enhance the justification for the cost by providing value-added services or features. The structure and level of digital banking fees should be carefully developed to be aligned with customer expectation.

In short, consolidation of these above findings, banks should pay more attention to the development of Digital Banking channels interface design as this might impact customer satisfaction. In order to offer customers service with superior quality, banks should create Digital Banking channels that include excellent designs that are appealing to the sight, attractive contents that have appropriate information users need, the easiness of making transactions and reading texts, the availability of some promotions or discounts and also quick loading capacity.

8.5.2. Recommendations for Vietnamese Commercial Banks

Decision makers in banks should focus on the main dimensions of digital banking service quality, which found to be significantly associated with customer satisfaction.

Findings Customers' trust in commercial banks is the factor that has the strongest impact on customer satisfaction, so greater emphasis is recommended to place on improving safety and information security, eliminating risks of information theft and fraud, ensuring the reputation

of commercial banks to customers in providing digital banking products and services. In terms of security and privacy, research findings reveal that Vietnamese commercial banks should place considerable emphasis on deploying synchronise solutions to protect, prevent and prevent data leakage and leakage on the entire information system; strengthen inspection and supervision of the entire process and stages with potential risks of information security (Banking Review, 2022). To tackle the challenge of huge capital investments required for Digital Banking, Cooperation with Fintech companies could be considered as the best solution banks to be equipped with more modern technologies, upgrade core banks, and strengthen cooperation between commercial banks. (Banking Review, 2022). Moreover, results of this study shed light on the problem that Vietnam commercial banks should invest in their human resource for the digital transformation. The recruitment and training of human resources for digital transformation at Vietnamese commercial banks should be based on actual human needs and existing human resources. For positions that require personnel with deep expertise in information technology that the bank cannot meet in a short time, the bank should recruit from outside; positions that need additional personnel with skills in digital skills, business acumen, and social skills, banks should choose among existing personnel, organise training to improve skills for them. In addition, in order to have a strong network of cybersecurity engineers in the future, with knowledge of Digital Banking operations and the ability to handle ever-changing risks in cyber security, helping the bank to adapt and overcome the rapid changes in the digital age, the advanced training for existing network security engineers is the optimal solution for commercial banks (Banking Review, 2022). Furthermore, in order to guarantee that both banking staff and clients are knowledgeable of potential threats and best practises for safeguarding sensitive information, it is also essential to promote a culture of cybersecurity awareness and education. Individuals can be empowered to identify and report suspicious

activity through regular training programmes and awareness campaigns, increasing the community's defence against cybercrime.

8.5.3. Recommendations for the SBV

The SBV needs to accelerate the research process on financial technology (Fintech), create a legal corridor for the application of modern technology in the financial - banking sector, and at the same time establish a Research Group on Digital Banking to assess the potential and trends of development/shift of the digital banking model in Vietnam in order to have supportive policies for commercial banks in this transition. Moreover, in order to successfully implement Digital Banking, obstacles caused by dispersed information must be removed, huge databases must be created through a high level of service integration within the financial sector.

8.5.4. Recommendations for Vietnam policymakers

Firstly, Vietnam Government needs to build a legal corridor to secure user data and information security to provide a safe and trustworthy system for digital transactions (Banking Review, 2022). Regulations regarding Digital Banking include the policy on generating an information platform and a national citizen database, the policy of authenticating e-customers, and other laws related to network security. For example, the Vietnamese Government should speed up the progress of the study and development of the Law on Electronic Transactions to replace, modify and broaden the Law on Electronic Transactions 2005 to provide a legal framework for ministries and branches to accomplish relevant legal provisions, assisting in the promotion of digitalisation and digital application, creating a favorable environment for individuals and businesses to carry out transactions via digital channels and electronic methods. At the same time, it is crucial to create an identical QR code standard for the market, develop an interbank information exchange system, advance the technology applied in electronic documents rather than paper documents and also encourage the use of electronic signatures, etc. The Government should soon introduce a Decree establishing a structure to regulate activities regarding Fintech

in the banking industry, creating favorable conditions for the cooperation between Vietnamese commercial banks and Fintech companies. (Banking Review, 2022). To ensure the most synchronised and efficient consumer identification, the government should lead the charge in improving the population's national database, which can then allow banks to authenticate their clients and enable payment solutions. Completely upgrade the national population infrastructure and establish a strategy that enables the database to be distributed and available in some industries namely telecommunications, insurance and banking to incentivise the growth of the service of Digital Banking and finance, which will promote financial universalisation for people especially the ones who lived in rural and mountainous regions. Encourage the use of technological advancements in management activities, as well as support scientific and technical research, then apply it in digitisation research to help formulate regulations and legal frameworks. It is imperative that policymakers, regulators, and relevant stakeholders work collaboratively to expedite the development of an updated legal framework that addresses the challenges and opportunities presented by Digital Banking. This proactive approach will not only benefit banks and financial institutions but also contribute to the overall growth and digital transformation of Vietnam's financial sector, ultimately benefiting businesses and consumers alike. Addressing the shortage of a comprehensive legal framework for Digital Banking operations in Vietnam is crucial for fostering a conducive environment that encourages innovation, promotes healthy competition, and ensures consumer protection. By establishing clear guidelines and regulations that align with technological advancements, financial institutions will gain the confidence to leverage new digital technologies, expand their service offerings, and deliver enhanced customer experiences. Last but not least, another recommendation for policymakers is to organise international seminars/forums on digital banking, thereby helping commercial banks learn, share, and act as a bridge for commercial

banks to cooperate with other banks/financial institutions that have implemented carefully digital banking and successfully built/transformed a digital bank.

8.5.5. Recommendations for customers

The technology race in the banking industry with Digital Banking projects also contributes to many risks in security in general and insecurity of user information in particular. Vietnam's capacity to secure financial information in the digital environment is still limited. Due to lack of awareness, customers sometimes could disregard their personal data and accidentally create conditions for criminals to create fake accounts. Fraud tricks are increasingly sophisticated and difficult to detect; therefore, to have good experience using Digital Banking applications, customers should also equip themselves with digital technology knowledge to avoid risks. Customers should regularly check their transaction history and account details for any unusual activities. Any suspicious transactions should be reported to their bank immediately.

8.6. Limitations

This Doctoral Thesis contributes profound theoretical insights and robust practical indications; however, it is believed to have certain limitations in it, which in turn, pave the way for future research avenues.

Firstly, the research concentrates on one of the Vietnamese commercial banks which can limit its generalisability to other banks globally. However, the fact that banks typically adopt common standards in bank financial management implies that the findings are potentially robust for global bank management. Replicating the study in banks in other countries will further enhance this robustness.

Secondly, in a strict sense, although the use of convenience sampling for customer survey is a common practice, it might be another potential limitation of the current research, which needs to be addressed in future research. By using a convenience sampling method for the survey,

the sample of quantitative data in this research is limited to customers who had used the Digital Banking service of the studied bank – one of the Vietnamese Commercial Banks. The survey was crafted online by Survey Monkey as a practical response to the Covid-19 pandemic restrictions, when face-to-face data collecting was impractical due to social distance regulations and health concerns. Although the online survey approach proved especially beneficial at the time, it did, however, inevitably have certain drawbacks. While significant efforts have been made to craft the survey to be accessible and user-friendly across various devices and encourage broader participation, the use of convenience sampling might mean that our sample is not fully representative of the broader population of digital banking customers, which limits the generalisability of the results. On the other hand, regarding the qualitative study, although purposive sampling was employed to select the managers from digital banking population with professional experiences to provide a rich and valuable perspective on digital banking, however, due to resource constraints, time limitations and Covid-19 pandemic, the study was only able to conduct the interviews with a relatively small number of participants, which may limit the generalisability of the findings. Hence, generalisations to a broader population should be done with cautions.

Thirdly, another limitations of this current research is from the mix-method research designs with survey for banking customers and interviews for banking managers in which the participants' responses could be shaped or limited by their willingness to reveal sensitive information (Whiting, 2008). Conducting an interview also faces an inherent risk of “social desirability bias”, meaning the participants may over-report “positive behaviour” though under-reporting “negative behaviour”. To reduce this risk, the researcher ensured the presented questions were as neutrally worded as possible and gave complete anonymity for all participants (Larsson and Viitaoja, 2017).

Moreover, this research suffers from a limitation in the complexity of the outlined conceptual framework and time constraints, this research has only tested the direct influence of each component, ignoring the possibility for moderation or mediation effects between factors. In the future, research should focus further on examine each variable's moderating effects.

Notwithstanding the aforementioned constraints, the integration of in-depth qualitative data from banking managers and broad quantitative data from banking customers offered a holistic examination of key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions, along with their importance on customer satisfaction and loyalty in Vietnam from different perspectives, which provides essential theoretical and practical implications

8.7. Future Research Directions

This thesis provides a number of fruitful directions for future research avenues which potentially contribute to the knowledge enrichment in digital banking in particular and banking marketing in general.

Firstly, replicating this study to across different cultural and economic contexts, such as Southeast Asia countries to disseminate if the findings are shared across the region could be another prospective area for future research could involve. Such comparative study might be interesting and challenging, to determine to what extent the perception on digital banking service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is shared across different nations. we propose as a future research line to evaluate our model with a sample of non-internet banking users in order to compare the results obtained or in other countries with different online banking adoption levels to evaluate the stability of our results.

Secondly, to further extend the research, longitudinal studies to explore the evolution of the relationship between digital banking service quality dimensions and its impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty through time could be a key field of research. Longitudinal studies,

which can follow the same people across time, provide a unique view on how patterns and relationships change. This type of research could contribute substantially in the field of digital banking. It could capture and explain the revolution in how banking clients perceive the digitalisation process affecting their satisfaction and loyalty as they gain more knowledge and competency with digital banking services. This could range from understanding the initial adaptation phase to the eventual integration of these services into their routine banking activities. Insights gained from such longitudinal research could also aid in revealing important touchpoints in the customer journey where strategic interventions could significantly foster customer satisfaction and, as a result, promote stronger loyalty. Furthermore, the knowledge acquired from this type of study may enable banks to anticipate variations in customer perceptions and proactively alter their digital offerings to match rapidly evolving expectations.

Moreover, in terms of the conceptual framework, integrating moderation and mediation constructs when considering the factors influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty in order to develop a more comprehensive and robust conceptual framework is also a new fruitful path for future researchers to explore. For example, it is recommended for future researches to incorporate other variables such as Initial Trust and Customer Satisfaction as mediators and Consumer Innovativeness as moderator, and reexamine this model. Future research might also investigate the relationship between customer satisfaction and trust on customer loyalty through two separate construct “Word of mouth” and “Intention” as conducted by Kassim & Abdullah (2010). Future research might seek to diversify the sampling strategies and explore hybrid (online and offline) methods of data collection as pandemic-related restrictions ease.

Covering all these directions for further research is believed to significantly add richness to this research findings and contribute to the development of a digital bank marketing theory with more robustness. Every study, every insight, and every knowledge obtained will lead to a broader, more nuanced understanding of the digital banking experience. This, in turn, will be

critical in determining the future of digital banking - a future aligning with customer needs, fostering customer satisfaction, and nurturing enduring loyalty.

8.8. Conclusions

The banking industry is an essential part of the financial services sector, in which there is intense competition between domestic and international banks all over the world. The study aimed to investigate the potential impacts of Digital Banking service on customer's satisfaction and loyalty in the context of Vietnam.

The digital banking service quality conceptual framework presented in the paper proposes a framework linking digital banking service quality determinants with Digital banking customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. On the basis of an extensive literature review, the research proposed a research model with 12 dimensions: The study followed a mixed-method research design with 660 surveys Vietnamese Digital Banking customers responses and five bank managers interviews, Spearman's Correlation Coefficient with Python and Template Analysis respectively for the data analysis investigating Digital Banking and evaluating the key Digital Banking Service Quality dimensions affecting customers' satisfaction.

According to the results of this research, Digital Banking service quality was found to have a significant impact on customer satisfaction. The results allow managers to have a better understanding of how Digital Banking Service Quality is created and also the importance of each Digital Banking Service Quality factor in ensuring customers' satisfaction, which may lead to increased customer satisfaction. In detail, the results indicate that 10 out of the 12 Digital Banking Service Quality Dimensions: Trust, Digital Emotional Connection, Customer Service and Support, Privacy and Security, Reliability and Speed, Usefulness, Convenience, Design, Ease of Use (in decreasing order of strength) all have huge impacts on customers' satisfaction. Research findings also reveal Customer Satisfaction and Trust are both strong predictors of

Customer Loyalty in the context of Vietnam Digital Banking. Therefore, Vietnam Commercial Banks needs to pay more attention to the ten aforementioned dimensions to implement Digital Banking innovations to sustain a high level of customers' satisfaction and loyalty.

As indicated in the literature evaluation, similar studies had been conducted across the world; however, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, it seems like none of them had been applied in the case of the Vietnamese banking industry. A unique and distinctive aspect of this research is the examination of customers' loyalty through several points of view rather than only through the opinion of banking clients. Besides, the undertaken thesis is unique in the sense that the researcher has adopted a newly developed research model. Moreover, the research employs Pragmatism Philosophy, Abduction Approach, Case Study Strategy, Mixed-Methods Design with customers survey and banking managers interviews, Spearman Correlation Coefficient and Template Analysis respectively, facilitating a comprehension of current implementations and effects of digital banking phenomenon in the context of Vietnamese Commercial Banks from various perspectives, ensuring the robustness of the findings.

In essence, nonetheless, this research has made substantial progress, the journey of research in digital banking and customer relationship management is not at its end, but rather, it's just the beginning, with many research questions to be answered and numerous insights to be discovered.

8.9. Personal Reflection on the DBA journey

The final section of this chapter is devoted to the researcher's reflective 'End-of-Thesis Self-Reflection' as an appropriate conclusion to this intellectually exciting and satisfying academic journey. This reflective remark captures the thesis's whole journey, identifying obstacles encountered at various stages of the research process and truthfully considering areas for

improvements. This perspective not only marks the end of this research project, but it also serves as a catalyst for future scholarly endeavours.

“It is not sufficient to have the experience to learn. Without reflecting on this experience, it may quickly be forgotten, or its learning potential lost” (Gibbs, 1988). Gibbs' Reflective Cycle, developed by Graham Gibbs in 1988, is a widely recognised framework utilised in a variety of fields, including education and management, to facilitate professional and personal development through reflective practice (Gibbs, 1988). Gibbs' Reflective Cycle offers a structured approach to this process, comprising of six major phases: Description, Feelings, Evaluation, Analysis, Conclusion, Action Plan (Gibbs, 1988).

Figure 8. 1 Gibbs' Reflective Cycle (Gibbs, 1988)

It is hard to believe that my long Doctorate journey is almost complete. Pursuing a doctoral journey has been the most challenging yet highly rewarding academic goal in my life. My DBA

stretched me intellectually and emotionally, but I encouraged myself to attain to the best of my abilities. I enjoyed much of the journey and am immensely proud of what I have achieved.

Reflecting on completing my doctoral thesis, I can honestly say it has been a challenging yet stimulating and worthwhile experience. During this time, I have made substantive progress in developing my critical thinking, research methodology, data analysis, etc. I have also gained a wide range of valuable skills and lessons for my future career. From my own experience, the most important thing contributing to the successful completion of my DBA thesis is that I was fortunate to choose an exciting topic that can sustain my interest in more than four years. My research topic is Digital Banking and Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, which arose from my interest following my previous educational background and professional experience. I obtained my Bachelor's Degree (Distinction) in Banking and Finance from Banking Academy, Vietnam 2011. Then I worked in Asia Commercial Bank of Vietnam for about two years as a Credit Analyst before coming to the UK to pursue an MBA in Finance at the University of Sunderland in 2014. I have always been interested in banking topics; therefore, my MBA dissertation is about Credit Risk Management and Financial Performance. Subsequently, for my DBA, I continued to research within the field of banking that I am genuinely passionate about. Without this love and passion for the research topic, it will be challenging for me to maintain the fire of enthusiasm during such a long way.

DBA journey has revealed my unforeseen potential of emotional and cognitive endurance. During my DBA journey, I have been through feelings of self-doubt, not sure whether I can successfully conduct good research. However, being an independent learner and finishing the thesis on my own, I realised that I need to trust my abilities more than I do.

Reflecting on my doctoral journey, I have found that one of the most challenging parts is to conduct a critical literature review. During my first year of writing my thesis, I have spent

considerable time and effort reading widely about my research topic - Digital Banking. I have found the most relevant and high-quality journal articles related to my research aims and objectives. I limited my reading to mostly only high-quality journal articles. I found Emerald Management journals and EthOS is valuable online databases sources. However, the more I read, the more I realised that I had not read deeply enough about the topic. I realised that I need not only to read widely but also to read deeply and critically. I learned it would be more helpful to employ systematic reviews for assessing research. I found that using systematic reviews saved time searching through numerous journals articles. This acknowledgment prompted me to read more research on systematic reviews of Digital Banking.

Of course, like many other doctoral candidates, my DBA journey has many challenges that pushed me out of my comfort zone. I have completed my DBA thesis in one of the most transformative periods of my life, during pregnancy with my second child, raising a young family, and living throughout the pandemic. However, in the most challenging time when I felt of self-doubt or even thought of quitting, I always remember what my grandmother often says: "The easy way is the downhill road. Whenever we feel difficult, even exhausted, it means we are going on a good path. The way out is the way through". Hardships and setbacks have allowed me to explore my true ability, determination, and resilience. I realised that I was stronger than I thought. I am now so proud of what I have achieved. I do not see my parental responsibilities as a challenge for my DBA thesis completion. Conversely, my family is the biggest motivation that keeps me strong even when things are not always going the way I planned. The dream of graduation in front of my family, especially my children, sharing achievements and joy with them, becoming a role model for my children keeps me moving forward, even in crying moments. Achievements, mistakes, and challenges along the way have made a new me today. I am more resilient and determined than I was. The roadblocks that I encountered only strengthened my resolve and encouraged me rather than discouraged me from

seeking my goal. It is also slowly building confidence in my abilities, and I am learning to trust myself.

Another lesson that I learned from my DBA journey is that “if you love a job because of its moments of success, you don't love it as much as you think; you only really love a job when you can love even the bitter, challenging moments on the way to success”.

Finally, after a long exciting, yet challenging journey of loads of intensive work, I am now putting the finishing touches on my thesis and submitting it in a few weeks. It will feel great to present it finally! Even though I do not know the result yet, I am pleased that I chose to undertake the challenge of pursuing a doctoral degree and finally get it done. I also believe that my findings would make a valuable contribution to the extant literature in Digital Banking. I have learned and grown so much after this long journey, and I confidently walk away better equipped for my future career.

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APPENDICES

1. APPENDIX A: SURVEY QUESTIONAIRES IN ENGLISH

Survey Questionnaires
in English.pdf

2. APPENDIX B: SURVEY QUESTIONAIRES IN VIETNAMESE

Survey Questionnaires
in Vietnamese.pdf

3. APPENDIX C: SURVEY SUMMARY DATA IN ENGLISH

Survey Summary Data in English.pdf

4. APPENDIX D: SURVEY SUMMARY DATA IN VIETNAMESE

Survey Data
Summary in Vietnam.

5. APPENDIX E: INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPANTS IN ENGLISH **PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET**

Dear Prospective Participants

You are invited to participate in a research study which forms part of my Doctor of Business Administration degree requirements. Before you make a decision whether or not to participate in this study, it is important that you have a clear understanding of the research being conducted and the implications of your participation. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. You can also contact the researcher for clarification or additional information. Please take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for reading this invitation.

1. Who will conduct the research?

Researcher: Phuong Thanh Nguyen

Doctor of Business Administration Candidate

University of the West of Scotland, London Campus, UK.

Email: [REDACTED]

2. What is the research about?

The main aim of this research is to investigate how do banking customers and bank managers perceive the digital banking quality dimensions, their impact on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty as well as current developments, challenges, opportunities of Digital Banking in Vietnam Banking Sector.

The methods to be used to collect information: online survey for customers and interview for banking managers/senior executives.

3. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because we value your experience and feedback in using Digital Banking as a customer (for survey) or a banking manager/senior executive (for interview) of the case bank.

4. Do I have to take part?

It is entirely up to you to decide whether or not to take part. You do not have to take part if you do not want to. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to sign a consent form. You will be given this information sheet and a signed consent form to keep.

5. What will my involvement be if I decide to take part?

Survey questionnaires

Since you are a customer using Digital Banking and decide to participate in the study, you will be invited to take part in a survey about your digital banking experience. It will take you about 10 minutes to complete the survey. The questionnaires will focus mainly on your experiences and opinions when using Digital Banking services, which is consistent with the main purpose of the research. If you would like to provide more details about your digital banking experience,

you can leave your contact information in Question 30 of the survey. Researcher will contact you to invite you to participate in a follow-up client interview (optional).

Interview

As a bank manager, if you decide to participate in the study, you will be invited to take part in an interview based on your experience and knowledge in management practice about Digital Banking. The content of the interview is consistent with the main aim of the study. The interview will be held online via Skype or Telephone and lasts approximately one hour. The purpose of the study is to learn from your banking management experience in Digital Banking to understand the current developments, challenges and opportunities of Digital Banking as well as the impact of Digital Banking on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Vietnam.

6. Will my taking part and my data be kept confidential? Will it be anonymised?

All the information that we collect from you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. All digital files, transcripts and summaries will be given codes and stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. Any hard copies of research information will be kept in locked files at all times. Only myself and my supervisor will have access to the files and any audio tapes.

Your data will be anonymised – your name will not be used in any reports or publications resulting from the study. You will not be able to be identified in any ensuing reports or publications. All information being provided will be processed and stored in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) which its details can be found through this link: <https://www.gov.uk/data-protection>.

Limits to confidentiality: confidentiality will be maintained as far as it is possible, unless your provided information implies that you or someone you mention might be in significant danger of harm and unable to act for themselves; in this case, I may have to inform the relevant agencies of this, but I would discuss this with you first.

7. How do I withdraw from the study?

You can withdraw from the study at any point up until 4 weeks after interview/survey, without having to give a reason. The interview/survey will primarily concentrate on the Digital Banking services and will not ask you for contentious and sensitive information like religion and politics. However, if any questions make you feel uncomfortable, you do not have to answer

them. Withdrawing from the study will have no effect on you. If you withdraw from the study, any personal data you have provided up to that point will be deleted unless you agree otherwise.

8. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

- Survey

The only record will be your response in the survey questionnaire. Question 30 in the survey asks whether or not if you wish to give your contact information if you want to have a follow up interview. If you decide to take part in this interview, we will ask for your permission to record your responses.

- Interview

Your responses can be recorded and stored anonymously, using password-protected software and will be used only for research purposes. No other use will be made of them without your written permission, and no one outside the project will be allowed access to the original recordings.

To note: If you do not want your participation recorded you can still take part in the study.

9. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no known disadvantages or health risks associated with this research. However, if any questions make you feel uncomfortable, you do not have to answer them.

10. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

You will not benefit financially from this study or from any possible outcome it may result in the future. Whilst there are no immediate benefits for participants of this research, it is hoped that this study will provide valuable recommendations for the developments of Digital Banking in Vietnam Banking Sector.

11. What will happen to the results of the research project?

The research results will be used for my Doctoral thesis defense. In the future, research papers might be published, but your identification will be kept strictly confidential in any publications. If you wish, you may request a copy of the results of this research study by writing to the researcher at: [REDACTED].

12. Who is organising and funding the research?

Researcher will fund the project herself.

13. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This research has been ethically approved by the University of the West of Scotland's ethics review procedure.

14. What if I have a question or complaint?

If you have any questions regarding this study, please contact the researcher or my supervisor:

Researcher:

Phuong Thanh Nguyen, University of the West of Scotland, London Campus.

Email: [REDACTED]

Supervisor: **Amare Desta** [PhD, MEd, MSc, LCGI, BSc (Hons)]

Professor of Information & Knowledge Management
Programme Manager of DBA (Doctor of Business Administration)
University of Wales Trinity Saint David (UWTSD) London
Winchester House, 11 Cranmer Rd, London SW9 6EJ

Email: [REDACTED]

If you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction, please contact University of the West of Scotland (UWS) London Campus via Phone: +44 (0)141 848 3047.

I hope you will consider contributing to this study!

If you are happy to participate in this study, please sign the consent sheet attached below.

Thank you for taking part in my research!

I agree to participate

- No
- Yes

6. APPENDIX F: INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPANTS IN VIETNAMESE
BẢNG THÔNG TIN DÀNH CHO ĐỐI TƯỢNG THAM GIA NGHIÊN CỨU

Kính gửi Quý vị,

Quý vị được mời tham gia vào một nghiên cứu nằm trong yêu cầu tốt nghiệp bằng Tiến sĩ Quản trị Kinh doanh của tôi. Trước khi Quý vị đưa ra quyết định có tham gia vào nghiên cứu này hay không, điều quan trọng là Quý vị phải hiểu rõ về nội dung nghiên cứu được thực hiện và những vấn đề liên quan đến sự tham gia của Quý vị. Xin Quý vị vui lòng dành thời gian đọc kỹ thông tin sau đây và thảo luận với những người khác nếu Quý vị muốn. Quý vị cũng có thể liên hệ với Nghiên cứu sinh để làm rõ hoặc bổ sung thông tin. Xin Quý vị vui lòng dành thời gian để quyết định xem Quý vị có muốn tham gia nghiên cứu hay không.

Cảm ơn Quý vị đã dành thời gian đọc lời mời này.

1. Ai sẽ tiến hành nghiên cứu?

Nghiên cứu sinh: Nguyễn Thanh Phương

University of the West of Scotland, London Campus, UK.

2. Nghiên cứu về đề tài gì?

Mục đích chính của nghiên cứu này là điều tra xem khách hàng và các nhà quản lý ngân hàng nhận thức như thế nào về các khía cạnh chất lượng ngân hàng số, tác động của chúng đến sự hài lòng của khách hàng và lòng trung thành của khách hàng cũng như những phát triển hiện tại, thách thức và cơ hội của Ngân hàng số trong ngành Ngân hàng Việt Nam.

Các phương pháp được sử dụng để thu thập thông tin: khảo sát trực tuyến đối với khách hàng và phỏng vấn đối với các nhà quản lý ngân hàng.

3. Tại sao tôi được chọn?

Quý vị được chọn vì chúng tôi đánh giá cao trải nghiệm và phản hồi của Quý vị trong việc sử dụng Ngân hàng số với tư cách là khách hàng (để khảo sát) hoặc các nhà quản lý ngân hàng (để phỏng vấn).

4. Tôi có phải tham gia không?

Quý vị hoàn toàn có quyền tự quyết định có tham gia hay không. Quý vị không cần phải tham gia nếu Quý vị không muốn. Nếu Quý vị quyết định tham gia, Quý vị sẽ được yêu cầu ký vào mẫu đồng ý. Quý vị sẽ được cung cấp tờ thông tin này và một mẫu đơn đồng ý có chữ ký để lưu giữ.

5. Sự tham gia của tôi sẽ như thế nào nếu tôi quyết định tham gia?

- **Bảng câu hỏi khảo sát dành cho khách hàng**

Vì Quý vị là khách hàng sử dụng Ngân hàng số của Ngân hàng đang được nghiên cứu và quyết định tham gia nghiên cứu, Quý vị sẽ được mời tham gia cuộc khảo sát về trải nghiệm sử dụng dịch vụ ngân hàng số của Quý vị. Quý vị sẽ mất khoảng 10 phút để hoàn thành khảo sát. Các bảng câu hỏi sẽ tập trung chủ yếu vào kinh nghiệm và ý kiến của Quý vị khi sử dụng dịch vụ Ngân hàng số, điều này phù hợp với mục đích chính của đề tài nghiên cứu. Nếu Quý vị muốn cung cấp thêm thông tin chi tiết về trải nghiệm ngân hàng số của mình, Quý vị có thể để lại thông tin liên hệ của mình trong Câu hỏi 30 của khảo sát. Nghiên cứu sinh sẽ liên hệ để mời Quý vị tham gia vào một cuộc phỏng vấn tiếp theo dành cho khách hàng (không bắt buộc).

- **Phỏng vấn dành cho nhà quản lý ngân hàng**

Với tư cách là nhà quản lý ngân hàng, nếu Quý vị quyết định tham gia nghiên cứu, Quý vị sẽ được mời tham gia một cuộc phỏng vấn dựa trên kinh nghiệm và kiến thức trong thực tiễn quản lý của Quý vị về Ngân hàng số. Nội dung cuộc phỏng vấn là phù hợp với mục tiêu chính của nghiên cứu. Cuộc phỏng vấn sẽ được tổ chức trực tuyến qua Skype hoặc Điện thoại và kéo dài khoảng một giờ. Mục đích của nghiên cứu là học hỏi từ kinh nghiệm quản lý ngân hàng của Quý vị trong Ngân hàng số để hiểu được sự phát triển hiện tại, thách thức và cơ hội của Ngân hàng số cũng như tác động của Ngân hàng số đối với Sự hài lòng và Lòng trung thành của Khách hàng tại Việt Nam.

6. Việc tham gia của tôi và dữ liệu của tôi có được giữ bí mật không? Thông tin sẽ được ẩn danh chứ?

Tất cả các thông tin mà chúng tôi thu thập từ Quý vị trong quá trình nghiên cứu sẽ được giữ bí mật tuyệt đối. Tất cả các tệp kỹ thuật số, bảng điểm và tóm tắt sẽ được cấp mã và được lưu trữ riêng biệt với mọi tên hoặc nhận dạng trực tiếp khác của những người tham gia. Mọi bản in ra giấy của thông tin nghiên cứu sẽ luôn được lưu giữ trong các tệp bị khóa. Chỉ bản thân Nghiên cứu sinh và Người hướng dẫn Nghiên cứu sinh mới có quyền truy cập vào các tệp và bất kỳ băng ghi âm nào.

Dữ liệu của Quý vị sẽ được ẩn danh - tên của Quý vị sẽ không được sử dụng trong bất kỳ báo cáo hoặc ấn phẩm nào là kết quả của nghiên cứu. Quý vị sẽ không thể được xác định trong bất kỳ báo cáo hoặc ấn phẩm nào tiếp theo. Tất cả thông tin được cung cấp sẽ được xử lý và lưu trữ theo Đạo luật Bảo vệ Dữ liệu (1998). Quý vị có thể tìm thấy thông tin chi tiết qua liên kết này: <https://www.gov.uk/data-protection>.

Giới hạn bảo mật: tính bảo mật sẽ được duy trì trong chừng mực có thể, trừ khi thông tin Quý vị cung cấp ngụ ý rằng Quý vị hoặc ai đó mà Quý vị đề cập có thể gặp nguy hiểm đáng kể và không thể hành động cho chính họ; trong trường hợp này, tôi có thể phải thông báo cho các cơ quan liên quan về việc này, nhưng tôi sẽ thảo luận với Quý vị về vấn đề này trước.

7. Làm cách nào để tôi rút khỏi nghiên cứu?

Quý vị có thể rút khỏi nghiên cứu bất cứ lúc nào cho đến 4 tuần sau khi phỏng vấn / khảo sát mà không cần phải đưa ra lý do. Cuộc phỏng vấn / khảo sát sẽ chủ yếu tập trung vào các dịch vụ Ngân hàng số và sẽ không yêu cầu Quý vị cung cấp thông tin nhạy cảm và gây tranh cãi như tôn giáo và chính trị. Tuy nhiên, nếu bất kỳ câu hỏi nào khiến Quý vị cảm thấy không thoải mái, Quý vị không cần phải trả lời chúng. Việc rút khỏi nghiên cứu sẽ không ảnh hưởng gì đến Quý vị. Nếu Quý vị rút khỏi nghiên cứu, mọi dữ liệu cá nhân Quý vị đã cung cấp cho đến thời điểm đó sẽ bị xóa trừ khi Quý vị đồng ý khác.

8. Tôi sẽ được ghi lại, và phương tiện được ghi sẽ được sử dụng như thế nào?

- **Sự khảo sát**

Bản ghi duy nhất sẽ là câu trả lời của Quý vị trong bảng câu hỏi khảo sát. Câu hỏi 30 trong cuộc khảo sát hỏi liệu Quý vị có muốn cung cấp thông tin liên hệ của mình nếu Quý vị muốn có một cuộc phỏng vấn tiếp theo hay không. Nếu Quý vị quyết định tham gia cuộc phỏng vấn này, chúng tôi sẽ xin phép Quý vị để ghi lại các câu trả lời của Quý vị.

- **Buổi phỏng vấn**

Các câu trả lời của Quý vị có thể được ghi lại và lưu trữ ẩn danh, sử dụng phần mềm được bảo vệ bằng mật khẩu và sẽ chỉ được sử dụng cho mục đích nghiên cứu. Chúng tôi sẽ không sử dụng chúng nếu không có sự cho phép bằng văn bản của Quý vị và không ai bên ngoài dự án nghiên cứu được phép truy cập vào các bản ghi gốc.

Cần lưu ý: Nếu Quý vị không muốn ghi lại sự tham gia của mình, Quý vị vẫn có thể tham gia nghiên cứu.

9. Những bất lợi và rủi ro có thể có khi tham gia là gì?

Không có bất lợi hoặc rủi ro sức khỏe nào được biết đến liên quan đến nghiên cứu này. Tuy nhiên, nếu bất kỳ câu hỏi nào khiến Quý vị cảm thấy không thoải mái, Quý vị không cần phải trả lời.

Email: [REDACTED]

Nếu Quý vị cảm thấy khiếu nại của mình chưa được xử lý thỏa đáng, vui lòng liên hệ với Cơ sở London của University of the West of Scotland (UWS) qua Điện thoại: +44 (0) 141 848 3047.

Tôi hy vọng Quý vị sẽ xem xét đóng góp cho nghiên cứu này!

Nếu Quý vị đồng ý tham gia vào nghiên cứu này, vui lòng ký vào bản chấp thuận đính kèm bên dưới. Cảm ơn Quý vị đã tham gia vào nghiên cứu của tôi!

Tôi đồng ý tham gia

- Không đồng ý
- Đồng ý

7. APPENDIX G: PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM IN ENGLISH

CONSENT FORM

Title of research study:

Investigating the impact of Digital Banking Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: Empirical evidence from a Vietnam Commercial Bank

Name of researcher: Phuong Thanh Nguyen

PARTICIPATION IN THIS RESEARCH STUDY IS VOLUNTARY

		Tick box
1.	I confirm that I have read and understood the Information Sheet for the above study. I have had an opportunity to consider the information and what will be expected of me. I have also had the opportunity to ask questions which have been answered to my satisfaction.	
2.	I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and understand that I can refuse to answer questions and that I can withdraw from the study at any time up until 4 weeks after interview/survey, without having to give a reason.	

3.	I understand that if I decide to withdraw, any personal data I have provided up to that point will be deleted unless I agree otherwise.	
4.	I agree to the interview being audio recorded. I consent to my interview being audio/video recorded and understand that the recordings will be stored anonymously, using password-protected software and will be used for training, quality control, audit and specific research purposes. To note: If you do not want your participation recorded you can still take part in the study.	
5.	I understand that the information I provide will be used for Phuong Thanh Nguyen Doctoral thesis and that the information will be anonymised.	
6.	I agree that my (anonymised) information can be quoted in research outputs.	
7.	I understand that any personal information that can identify me will be kept confidential and not shared with anyone other than the researcher.	
8.	I give permission for the (anonymised) information I provide to be deposited in a data archive so that it may be used for future research.	
9.	I understand that I will not benefit financially from this study or from any possible outcome it may result in in the future.	
10.	I am aware of who I should contact if I wish to lodge a complaint.	

Please retain a copy of this consent form.

Participant name:

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Interviewer _____ name:

Signature: _____ Date: _____

For information please contact:

Researcher: Phuong Thanh Nguyen

Doctorate of Business Administration Candidate

University of the West of Scotland, London Campus.

Email: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

8. APPENDIX H: PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM IN VIETNAMESE

ĐƠN CHẤP THUẬN THAM GIA NGHIÊN CỨU

Tên đề tài nghiên cứu: Đánh giá ảnh hưởng của chất lượng Dịch Vụ Ngân Hàng Số đến sự hài lòng của khách hàng và mức độ trung thành của khách hàng tại Vietcombank, Việt Nam.

Nghiên cứu sinh: Nguyễn Thanh Phương

VIỆC THAM GIA NGHIÊN CỨU NÀY LÀ TỰ NGUYỆN

		Ô đánh dấu
1.	Tôi xác nhận rằng tôi đã đọc và hiểu Bảng thông tin cho nghiên cứu trên. Tôi đã có cơ hội để xem xét thông tin và những gì sẽ được mong đợi ở tôi. Tôi cũng đã có cơ hội để hỏi các câu hỏi và đã được giải đáp thỏa đáng.	
2.	Tôi hoàn toàn tự nguyện đồng ý tham gia vào nghiên cứu này và hiểu rằng tôi có thể từ chối trả lời bất cứ câu hỏi nào và tôi có thể rút khỏi nghiên cứu bất kỳ lúc nào cho đến 4 tuần sau cuộc phỏng vấn /khảo sát mà không cần phải đưa ra lý do.	
3.	Tôi hiểu rằng nếu tôi quyết định rút khỏi nghiên cứu, mọi dữ liệu cá nhân mà tôi đã cung cấp cho đến thời điểm đó sẽ bị xóa trừ khi tôi đồng ý khác.	
4.	Tôi đồng ý để cuộc phỏng vấn được ghi âm và hiểu rằng các bản ghi âm sẽ được lưu trữ ẩn danh, sử dụng phần mềm được bảo vệ bằng mật khẩu và sẽ được sử dụng cho các mục đích đào tạo, kiểm soát chất lượng và nghiên cứu cụ thể. Cần lưu ý: Nếu bạn không muốn ghi âm lại sự tham gia của mình, bạn vẫn có thể tham gia nghiên cứu.	
5.	Tôi hiểu rằng thông tin tôi cung cấp sẽ được sử dụng cho luận văn Tiến sĩ của Nguyễn Thanh Phương và thông tin đó sẽ được ẩn danh.	

6.	Tôi đồng ý rằng thông tin (ẩn danh) của tôi có thể được trích dẫn trong kết quả nghiên cứu.	
7.	Tôi hiểu rằng bất kỳ thông tin cá nhân nào có thể nhận dạng được tôi sẽ được giữ bí mật và không được chia sẻ với bất kỳ ai khác ngoài nhà nghiên cứu.	
8.	Tôi cho phép thông tin (ẩn danh) mà tôi cung cấp được lưu trữ trong kho lưu trữ dữ liệu để nó có thể được sử dụng cho nghiên cứu trong tương lai.	
9.	Tôi hiểu rằng tôi sẽ không được lợi về mặt tài chính từ nghiên cứu này hoặc từ bất kỳ kết quả nào có thể xảy ra mà nó có thể dẫn đến trong tương lai.	
10.	Tôi biết mình nên liên hệ với ai nếu tôi muốn khiếu nại.	

Vui lòng giữ lại một bản sao của mẫu chấp thuận này.

Tên người tham gia:

Chữ ký: _____ Ngày: _____

Người _____ phòng _____ vấn:

Chữ ký: _____ Ngày: _____

Để biết thêm thông tin vui lòng liên hệ:

Nghiên cứu sinh: Nguyễn Thanh Phương

University of the West of Scotland, London Campus.

Email: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

9. APPENDIX I: INTERVIEW SCHEDULE IN ENGLISH

Interview schedule for THE STUDIED BANK managers/Senior banking executives

A. PERSONAL DEMOGRAPHICS

1. What is your Job Title?
2. What is your department?
3. How long have you been working with Vietcombank?

B. CURRENT THE STUDIED BANK DIGITAL BANKING DEVELOPMENTS

1. POSITIVE RESULTS

1.1. Could you please talk about the positive results in the current development of THE STUDIED BANK digital banking (in particular Digital Banking THE STUDIED BANK Digibank for personal customers)?

1.2. In your opinion, **how has the recent development of digital banking services** in general as well as THE STUDIED BANK Digibank in particular **benefited Vietcombank?**

2. OVERALL QUALITY

2.1. How do you assess the overall quality of Vietcombank digital banking? (Services portfolio/products, Ease of use, Convenience, Usefulness, Reliability, Privacy and Security, Speed, Design, Customer Service and Support, Digital -emotional connection)?

2.2. **Which Digital Banking Channels/ Services/ Features do you think customers value the most?**

3. COMPETITORS

In your opinion, what are the advantages and disadvantages of Vietcombank digital banking THE STUDIED BANK Digibank for personal customers compared with other competitors?

4. OVERALL CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

4.1. In your opinion, how do you think about the overall customer satisfaction when using Vietcombank digital banking?

4.2. What barriers and difficulties customers often encounter when using Vietcombank digital banking?

4.3. In your managerial practice, what feedbacks do you often receive from customers when using Vietcombank banking digital services?

5. In your opinion, what should Vietcombank do when receiving those feedbacks and then improve its customer experience in using digital banking services?

6. DIGITAL BANKING STAFFS

6.1. How do you rate the staff involved in managing and operating Vietcombank Digital Banking services?

6.2. How is the training, retraining and improvement of the quality of resources to meet the needs of digital transformation being implemented by Vietcombank, sir/madam?

7. INFORMATION SECURITY

How do you evaluate the current security and information safety of Vietcombank?

8. MAJOR INVESTMENTS AND PARTNERSHIPS

8.1. Could you please talk about the major investments and major partners in your digital banking transformation projects?

8.2. What is the reason why Vietcombank chose to cooperate with these current partners in the digital reinvention journey, sir/madam?

8.3. What benefits do these partners bring to Vietcombank in providing outstanding solutions to customers according to you?

C. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

1. Could you please tell me about the challenges and obstacles that Vietcombank is facing in the development of digital banking? (Security issues, risk control, customer information protection, human resource challenges, legal corridors...)

2. Could you please tell me about the opportunities for Vietcombank in implementing digital banking services?

D. STRATEGIES & SOLUTIONS

1. Could you please tell us about Vietcombank's action plans /major strategies to achieve the strategic goal (by 2025) to be the leading digital bank in Vietnam?

2. What recommendations do you have for the State Bank of Vietnam and the authorities in Vietnam in promoting Digital Banking in Vietnam in general, sir/madam?

Thank you for taking this interview!

10. APPENDIX K: INTERVIEW SCHEDULE IN VIETNAMESE

A. THÔNG TIN CÁ NHÂN

1. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Chức danh?

2. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Phòng/Ban?

3. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Thời gian Anh/Chị làm việc tại Vietcombank?

B. THỰC TRẠNG PHÁT TRIỂN NGÂN HÀNG SỐ VIETCOMBANK

1. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các kết quả tích cực mà VIETCOMBANK đã đạt được trong việc phát triển Ngân hàng số (cụ thể là dịch vụ Ngân hàng số THE STUDIED BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân)? Theo Anh/Chị, sự phát triển của Ngân Hàng số Vietcombank nói chung cũng như THE STUDIED BANK Digibank nói riêng đã và đang đem lại những lợi ích gì cho Vietcombank?
2. Anh Chị đánh giá thế nào về chất lượng chung của dịch vụ Ngân Hàng số THE STUDIED BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân mà Vietcombank đang triển khai (Về các mặt: Sản phẩm dịch vụ, tính dễ sử dụng, tính thuận tiện, tính hữu ích, độ tin cậy, bảo mật, tốc độ, thiết kế giao diện, dịch vụ và hỗ trợ khách hàng, kết nối cảm xúc số)? Tính năng, tiện ích nào của Ngân Hàng số Vietcombank đang được Khách hàng quan tâm đánh giá cao nhất, theo Anh/Chị?
3. Dịch vụ Ngân Hàng số THE STUDIED BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân có những ưu điểm cũng như nhược điểm nào khi so sánh với các đối thủ cạnh tranh khác, thưa Anh/Chị?
4. Anh/Chị đánh giá như thế nào về mức độ hài lòng của Khách hàng khi sử dụng Ngân hàng số THE STUDIED BANK? Các khó khăn thường gặp của khách hàng trong quá trình sử dụng dịch vụ Ngân hàng số Vietcombank? Những phản hồi/ý kiến thường gặp của khách hàng khi sử dụng dịch vụ ngân hàng số THE STUDIED BANK là gì, thưa Anh/Chị?
5. Theo Anh/Chị, Vietcombank cần làm gì trước những phản hồi đó của Khách hàng và tiếp đó là gia tăng trải nghiệm Khách hàng về dịch vụ ngân hàng số?
6. Anh chị đánh giá thế nào về đội ngũ nhân sự tham gia phụ trách, vận hành dịch vụ ngân hàng số Vietcombank? Công tác đào tạo, đào tạo lại, nâng cao chất lượng nguồn lực đáp ứng nhu cầu chuyển đổi số đang được Vietcombank triển khai như thế nào, thưa Anh/Chị?
7. Anh/Chị đánh giá như thế nào về việc đảm bảo an ninh, an toàn thông tin của Ngân Hàng số Vietcombank hiện nay?
8. Xin Anh/Chị có thể cho biết Vietcombank chú trọng đầu tư hạng mục nào trong các dự án chuyển đổi số và đối tác chiến lược của Vietcombank là những đơn vị nào? Lí do Vietcombank lựa chọn hợp tác cùng các đơn vị này trong hành trình số hóa ngân hàng là gì, thưa Anh/Chị? **Lợi ích các đối tác này mang lại cho Vietcombank trong việc cung ứng các giải pháp vượt trội cho khách hàng theo Anh/Chị?**

C. THÁCH THỨC & CƠ HỘI

1. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các thách thức mà Vietcombank đang đối diện trong thực tiễn phát triển Ngân hàng số? (vấn đề bảo mật, kiểm soát rủi ro, bảo vệ thông tin khách hàng, thách thức về mặt nhân sự, hành lang pháp lý...)

2. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các cơ hội dành cho Vietcombank trong thực tiễn triển khai dịch vụ Ngân hàng số?

D. CHIẾN LƯỢC & GIẢI PHÁP

1. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết những kế hoạch hành động của Vietcombank nhằm đạt được mục tiêu chiến lược (đến năm 2025) Đứng đầu về Ngân hàng số tại Việt Nam?

2. Anh/Chị có kiến nghị gì đối với NHNN Việt Nam và các cơ quan chức năng ở Việt Nam trong việc thúc đẩy Ngân hàng số tại Việt Nam nói chung không, thưa Anh/Chị?

Em xin chân thành cảm ơn Anh/Chị đã dành thời gian cho buổi phỏng vấn này!

11. APPENDIX L: INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT SAMPLE IN ENGLISH
INTERVIEW 3 (CB)

A. PERSONAL DEMOGRAPHICS

1. What is your Job Title? Manager
2. What is your department? Customer Service Department - Branch
3. How long have you been working with Bank? I have been working in Bank for 12 years.

B. CURRENT DEVELOPMENTS OF BANK DIGITAL BANKING

1. Could you please talk about the positive results in the current development of Bank digital banking (in particular Digital Banking BANK Digital Banking for personal customers)? In your opinion, how has the recent development of digital banking services in general as well as BANK Digital Banking in particular benefited Bank?

1.1. Could you please talk about the positive results in the current development of Bank digital banking (in particular Digital Banking BANK Digital Banking for personal customers)?

Answer:

Personalized the service to make it suitable for all of the needs of individual customers. Digital Banking is the first multi-channel banking model of BANK.

1.2. In your opinion, how has the recent development of digital banking services in general as well as BANK Digital Banking in particular benefited Bank?

Answer:

Developed new personal customer base, maintain the market share of current personal customer base in the market.

2.1. How do you assess the overall quality of Bank digital banking? (Services portfolio/products, Ease of use, Convenience, Usefulness, Reliability, Privacy and Security, Speed, Design, Customer Service and Support, Digital -emotional connection)?

Answer:

Uhm, well, basically, Digital Banking has met the quality of the service, but the system is often overloaded, leading to the problem that customers sometimes could not be able to access to their accounts. Moreover, the feature of Instant money transfer 24/7 outside Bank usually faces a timeout error, making beneficiaries unable to receive their money immediately.

2.2. Which Digital Banking Channels/ Services/ Features do you think customers value the most?

Answer:

Account Packages. Customers who register for account packages will have free transferring fee.

3. **In your opinion, what are the advantages and disadvantages of Bank digital banking BANK Digital Banking for personal customers compared with other competitors?**

Answer:

Advantages:

The service is suitable for all the needs of using science and technology of every individuals.

Disadvantages:

The services fee is relatively high compared to competitors in the banking sector.

4. **In your opinion, how do you think about the overall customer satisfaction when using Bank digital banking? What barriers and difficulties customers often encounter when using Bank digital banking? In your managerial practice, what feedbacks do you often receive from customers when using Bank banking digital services?**

4.1. **In your opinion, how do you think about the overall customer satisfaction when using Bank digital banking?**

Answer:

Customers who usually make transactions tend to have a higher level of satisfaction than customers who rarely use the services.

4.2. **What barriers and difficulties customers often encounter when using Bank digital banking?**

Answer:

Customers faces difficulties in increasing money transfer limit, activating Smart OTP transaction authentication method.

4.3. In your managerial practice, what feedbacks do you often receive from customers when using Bank banking digital services?

Answer:

Errors in 24/7 money transfer, difficulty in activating Smart OTP transaction authentication method.

5. In your opinion, what should Bank do when receiving those feedbacks and then improve its customers' experience in using digital banking services?

Answer:

Enhancing communications and guidance for customers on how to activate Smart OTP through update more regularly and comprehensively instruction clips.

6. How do you assess the quality of Bank staffs involving in digital banking operations? How has the training programs for human resources for digital transformations in Bank developed?

6.1. How do you assess the quality of Bank staffs involving in digital banking operations?

There are too many departments related to Digital Banking in terms of policies and operations. Moreover, the operation department is divided in terms of each functionality, which makes branches facing difficulties in contacting head office for support and guidance.

6.2. How has the training programs for human resources for digital transformations in Bank developed?

Regular training is needed when new facilities are available and employees are trained relatively fully and regularly.

7. How do you assess the current information security in Bank digital banking?

Answer:

Relatively good

BANK Digital Banking inherits the security methods that had been applied to customers on those former online services including login security, transaction security and especially Smart OTP. Furthermore, BANK Digital Banking is improved in terms of security with the addition of a new login authentication technology – Push Authentication.

However, the fact that scammers/hackers take advantage of customers' lack of digital understanding and knowledge to steal the money in customers' bank account is a very common problem, despite many warnings for risk prevention and transaction security regularly sent by Bank through many media means such as social networks, texts, email, media communications.

8. Could you please talk about the major investments and major partners in your digital banking transformation projects? What are the reasons for selecting the current partners to collaborate with Bank in digital reinvention journey? What are the benefits these partners bring to Bank in developing innovative solutions for customers?

8.1. Could you please talk about the major investments and major partners in your digital banking transformation projects?

Answer:

To the best of my knowledge, currently Bank focus primarily on some main categories regarding safety and security problems in digital transformation projects. Also, FPT is one of Bank's strategic partners.

8.2. What are the reasons for selecting the current partners to collaborate with Bank in digital reinvention journey?

Answer:

The reasons for developing the partnership with FPT is FPT is a large, reputable organization and also it has a high-qualified human resources.

8.3. What are the benefits these partners bring to Bank in developing innovative solutions for customers?

Answer:

Ensuring safety and security for BANK and customers, while at the same time, fixing arising errors promptly as well as supplementing more utilities and features for customers.

C. CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES

1. What are the challenges and obstacles that Bank has to face in its journey of developing digital banking?

Answer:

The biggest obstacle that Bank is facing is that BANK's brand image and reputation is negatively affected by "dirty communications" (distortion, speculation). Moreover, the fact that scammers/hackers take advantage of customers' lack of digital understanding and knowledge to steal the money in customers' bank account is a very common problem, despite many warnings for risk prevention and transaction security regularly sent by Bank through many media means such as social networks, texts, email, media communications.

2. What are the opportunities that Bank has in developing digital banking?

Answer:

Bank has a huge customer base with a wide network of over 600 branches and office locations throughout Vietnam, however, the current coverage of customers using digital banking is not high as expected, the number of digital transactions is still limited.

Brand image and leading position in the Vietnam banking sector.

These are opportunities for Bank digital banking developments.

D. STRATEGIES & SOLUTIONS

1. Could you please talk about the major strategies that Bank has been following with the aim of achieving a leading bank in Digital Banking in Vietnam in 2025?

I think the most important strategies of Bank in developing digital banking is to improve customer experience: catalog customer journeys, implement initiatives to help improve customer experience to achieve the goal of being the top bank in terms of customer service, enables integration of the customer journey with the partner ecosystem.

2. What would you like to recommend the State Bank of Vietnam and Vietnam Government in terms of promoting Digital Banking Transformation for Vietnam Banking Industry?

Answer:

Policy makers should improve mechanisms and policies on digital banking, making it more suitable for the current practical situation. They should also build a more complete legal framework to prevent and tackle those mentioned offences.

Thank you for taking this interview!

12. APPENDIX M: INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPT SAMPLE IN VIETNAMESE

Kính chào các Anh/Chị!

Em là Thanh Phương- hiện em đang là nghiên cứu sinh Tiến sĩ Quản trị Kinh doanh tại University of the West of Scotland London Campus. Em đang thực hiện một đề tài nghiên cứu để tìm hiểu **“Các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến sự hài lòng và lòng trung thành của Khách hàng về chất lượng dịch vụ của Ngân hàng số BANK”**.

Ngoài khảo sát dành cho Khách hàng mà em đã thực hiện, nghiên cứu của em sẽ trở nên toàn diện hơn nếu may mắn nhận được ý kiến đóng góp từ phía các Lãnh Đạo của BANK về thực tiễn triển khai Ngân hàng số tại BANK, cụ thể là dịch vụ Ngân hàng số BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân. Vì vậy em rất mong muốn được lắng nghe quan điểm của các Anh/Chị. Mọi ý kiến đánh giá của các Anh/Chị đều vô cùng quý giá và đóng có vai trò quan trọng then chốt trong thành công của đề tài nghiên cứu của em.

Xin Anh/Chị hoàn toàn yên tâm rằng ý kiến của Anh/Chị chắc chắn sẽ chỉ được sử dụng cho mục đích nghiên cứu và sẽ luôn được giữ ẩn danh và bí mật.

Em kính mong nhận được sự trợ giúp của các Anh/Chị!

Em xin chân thành cảm ơn!

Trân trọng

Em Phương

Em xin phép kính gửi các Anh/Chị danh sách các câu hỏi phỏng vấn ạ!

D. THÔNG TIN CÁ NHÂN

4. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Chức danh: Phó trưởng phòng
5. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Phòng/Ban: Phòng Dịch vụ khách hàng – Chi nhánh
6. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết Thời gian Anh/Chị làm việc tại BANK: 12 năm

E. THỰC TRẠNG PHÁT TRIỂN NGÂN HÀNG SỐ BANK

9. **Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các kết quả tích cực mà BANK đã đạt được trong việc phát triển Ngân hàng số (cụ thể là dịch vụ Ngân hàng số BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân):**

Cá nhân hóa dịch vụ, phù hợp với mọi nhu cầu của khách hàng cá nhân, phát triển digibank là mô hình ngân hàng hợp kênh đầu tiên của BANK.

Theo Anh/Chị, sự phát triển của Ngân Hàng số BANK nói chung cũng như BANK Digibank nói riêng đã và đang đem lại những lợi ích nào cho BANK:

Phát triển KHCN mới, giữ vững thị phần KHCN trên thị trường.

10. **Anh/Chị đánh giá thế nào về chất lượng chung của dịch vụ Ngân Hàng số BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân mà BANK đang triển khai? (Về các mặt: Sản phẩm dịch vụ, tính dễ sử dụng, tính thuận tiện, tính hữu ích, độ tin cậy, bảo mật, tốc độ, thiết kế giao diện, dịch vụ và hỗ trợ khách hàng, kết nối cảm xúc số):**
Về cơ bản, Digibank đã đáp ứng được chất lượng dịch vụ tuy nhiên hệ thống vẫn thường xuyên bị quá tải dẫn đến KH không truy cập được và giao dịch chuyển tiền nhanh liên ngân hàng 24/7 hay gặp lỗi timeout, người hưởng không nhận được tiền ngay.

Tính năng, tiện ích nào của Ngân Hàng số BANK đang được Khách hàng quan tâm đánh giá cao nhất:

Tính năng Đăng ký gói tài khoản

11. **Theo quan điểm của Anh/Chị, dịch vụ Ngân Hàng số BANK Digibank dành cho khách hàng cá nhân có những ưu điểm cũng như nhược điểm nào khi so sánh với các đối thủ cạnh tranh khác, thưa Anh/Chị:**

Ưu điểm: Phù hợp với mọi nhu cầu sử dụng của KHCCN và phù hợp mọi đối tượng KHCCN.

Nhược điểm: Phí dịch vụ tương đối cao so với các đối thủ cạnh tranh.

12. **Anh/Chị đánh giá thế nào về mức độ hài lòng của Khách hàng khi sử dụng Ngân hàng số BANK:**

Với khách hàng giao dịch nhiều sẽ có mức độ hài lòng cao hơn so với các KH ít sử dụng dịch vụ.

Các rào cản và khó khăn thường gặp của khách hàng trong quá trình sử dụng dịch vụ Ngân hàng số BANK là gì, thưa Anh/Chị: Nâng hạn mức chuyển tiền, kích hoạt phương thức xác thực giao dịch Smart OTP.

Trong thực tiễn quản lý của mình, những phản hồi/ý kiến thường gặp của khách hàng khi sử dụng dịch vụ ngân hàng số BANK là gì, thưa Anh/Chị: Chuyển tiền 24/7 bị lỗi, khó kích hoạt phương thức xác thực giao dịch Smart OTP.

13. **Theo Anh/Chị, BANK cần làm gì trước những phản hồi đó của Khách hàng và tiếp đó là gia tăng trải nghiệm Khách hàng về dịch vụ Ngân hàng số:**

Truyền thông sâu rộng tới khách hàng về hướng dẫn khách hàng kích hoạt Smartt OTP thông qua clip hướng dẫn KH.

14. **Anh/Chị đánh giá thế nào về đội ngũ nhân sự tham gia phụ trách, vận hành dịch vụ Ngân hàng số BANK:**

Quá nhiều đầu mối liên quan đến Digibank bao gồm về mặt chính sách, khối vận hành lại chia theo từng tiện ích dẫn đến chi nhánh khó khăn khi cần liên hệ.

Công tác đào tạo, đào tạo lại, nâng cao chất lượng nguồn lực đáp ứng nhu cầu chuyển đổi số đang được BANK triển khai như thế nào, thưa Anh/Chị: Thường xuyên đào tạo khi có tiện ích mới, cán bộ được đào tạo tương đối đầy đủ và thường xuyên.

15. Anh/Chị đánh giá như thế nào về việc đảm bảo an ninh, an toàn thông tin của Ngân hàng số BANK hiện nay: Tương đối tốt

16. Xin Anh/Chị có thể cho biết BANK chú trọng đầu tư hạng mục nào trong các dự án chuyển đổi số và đối tác chiến lược của BANK là những đơn vị nào:

Với hiểu biết của bản thân, hiện BANK chú trọng vài hạng mục an toàn, bảo mật trong các dự án chuyển đổi số và FPT là một trong những đối tác chiến lược của BANK. Việc lựa chọn hợp tác cùng FPT do đây là tập đoàn công nghệ lớn, uy tín, có đội ngũ lao động có trình độ cao.

Lợi ích các đối tác này mang lại cho BANK trong việc cung ứng các giải pháp vượt trội cho khách hàng theo Anh/Chị:

Đảm bảo an toàn, bảo mật cho BANK và KH đồng thời khắc phục, sửa chữa lỗi phát sinh kịp thời cũng như bổ sung tiện ích, tính năng được nhanh nhất

F. THÁCH THỨC & CƠ HỘI

3. Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các thách thức mà BANK đang đối diện trong thực tiễn phát triển Ngân hàng số? (vấn đề bảo mật, kiểm soát rủi ro, bảo vệ thông tin khách hàng, thách thức về mặt nhân sự, hành lang pháp lý...):

Thách thức BANK gặp phải lớn nhất là truyền thông bản ảnh hưởng tới uy tín thương hiệu BANK. Việc các đối tượng lợi dụng sự thiếu hiểu biết của KH để lừa đảo chiếm đoạt tiền trong TK khách hàng cũng là vấn đề thường xuyên gặp phải dù BANK thường xuyên gửi cảnh báo tới KH thông qua nhiều phương tiện như mạng xã hội, tin nhắn, email, trên các phương tiện truyền thông.

Xin Anh/Chị cho biết các cơ hội dành cho BANK trong thực tiễn triển khai dịch vụ Ngân hàng số: Data khách hàng lớn, độ phủ sóng khách hàng sử dụng digibank chưa cao và giao dịch trên digibank chưa nhiều. Thương hiệu và vị thế dẫn đầu trong hệ thống ngân hàng Việt Nam.

G. CHIẾN LƯỢC & GIẢI PHÁP

3. **Xin Anh/Chị cho biết những kế hoạch hành động của BANK nhằm đạt được mục tiêu chiến lược (đến năm 2025) đứng đầu về Ngân hàng số tại Việt Nam:**
4. **Anh/Chị có kiến nghị gì đối với Ngân hàng Nhà nước Việt Nam và các cơ quan chức năng ở Việt Nam trong việc thúc đẩy Ngân hàng số tại Việt Nam nói chung, thưa Anh/Chị:**
Hoàn thiện cơ chế, chính sách về ngân hàng số để phù hợp hơn với tình hình thực tế hiện nay; Xây dựng hành lang pháp lý đầy đủ hơn để ngăn chặn và xử lý kịp thời các hành vi vi phạm pháp luật.

Em xin chân thành cảm ơn Anh/Chị đã dành thời gian cho buổi phỏng vấn này!

13. APPENDIX N: PYTHON CRONBACH ALPHA ANALYSIS

**Python cronbach
alpha.pdf**

14. APPENDIX O: PYTHON SPEARMAN CORRELATION ANALYSIS

PythonAnalysis.pdf